

**Exploring Teacher Leadership in the Algerian Context:
Middle School English as a Foreign Language (EFL)
Teachers' Perspectives**

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Declaration

Banner Number: B00376428

I hereby declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, this thesis is the result of my own work. I also certify that the thesis has not been previously and is not being currently submitted for any other degree at the University of West of Scotland and or any other institutions either in United Kingdom or out of it.

Name: Imene MESSALEM

Date: 08 December 2023

Dedication

I wholeheartedly dedicate this work to the most important people in my life, my strongest support network, my parents: Ahmed Messalem and Naima (Khamsa) Boussahel. I am forever thankful to you both for always believing in me and for supporting and encouraging me to travel far, alone, to pursue my academic endeavours despite this being emotionally tough for you. Thank you, mom and dad, for your endless prayers; your profound love; and for constantly reminding me that my dream is yours too.

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To my stepsisters: Amel and Chaima; my lovely nephew Adam and niece Layan; and my dear cousins Abir and Mouna.

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Abstract

This qualitative exploratory study investigates teacher leadership in the underrepresented Algerian context. It specifically looks at teachers' perceptions and reported practices of teacher leadership, supports and hindrances of teacher leadership within their context as well as their perceptions of the role of engaging in informal collaborative practices within teachers' communities in enhancing their professional learning and growth as teacher leaders. The study draws particularly on perspectives of a sample of 18 middle school EFL teachers. Data was obtained from the selected sample using individual semi-structured interviews, written reflections, and online focus group discussions, and was analysed thematically. Findings revealed that while the term 'teacher leadership' was not necessarily a familiar term for most participants, their responses indicated an understanding of what constitutes teacher leadership. Interestingly, teachers' perceptions were specifically centred on non-positional teacher leadership, viewing the concept in terms of influence rather than a designated position or authority. Such influence is exerted, according to them, through teachers' practices within their classrooms, their practices beyond their classrooms, their participation in decision-making processes as well as the set of traits which they demonstrate. Their reported practices of teacher leadership were largely consistent with their perceptions of the concept as they were primarily self-initiated, involving practices both within their classrooms and beyond. Some discrepancy was, however, noted between their perceptions and their reported practices, specifically in light of notable scarcity of any reported school-wide or community-based practices of teacher leadership. Findings highlighted myriad factors that might have led to such discrepancy. In this sense, the study found that while teachers often referred to some desired supports, which they believe could enhance their leadership practices, they spoke at length about hindrances that currently limit such practices. These factors broadly related to teachers' personal characteristics; school-based factors; system-based factors; and sociocultural factors. Interestingly though, despite these hindrances, participant teachers still managed to practise teacher leadership within their schools at some level. Findings equally indicated that participant teachers held positive perceptions of the role of engaging in informal collaborative practices within teachers' communities within their schools and beyond in enhancing their professional learning and growth as teacher leaders. The study draws on concepts from Communities of Practices, specifically on Campbell et al. (2019) Communities of Practice for Teacher Leadership Model and Wenger's (1998) modes of belonging to holistically interpret and discuss the emerging findings and subsequently provides a more detailed discussion of these

findings with reference to the research questions. Based on these findings, the study concludes by providing recommendations for policy and practice to support and promote teacher leadership enactment in Algerian public middle schools as well as suggestions for future research.

Key words: teacher leadership, supports, barriers, EFL, Algeria

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

BERA: British Educational Research Association

CAPEM: Certificate of Aptitude for Middle School Teaching (translated from French: Certificat d' Aptitude Professionnelle a l' Enseignement Moyenne)

CBA: Competency Based Approach

CNRSE: National Commission of Educational System Reform

CoP: Communities of Practice

CoPTLM: Communities of Practice for Teacher Leadership Model

EFL: English as a Foreign Language

ENS: Teachers' College (translated from French Ecole Normale Superieure)

KSA: Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

MoNE: Ministry of National Education

MHESR: Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research

PhD: Doctor of Philosophy

TEFL: Teaching English as a Foreign Language

UAE: United Arab Emirates

UK: United Kingdom

USA: United States of America

Chapter One: General Introduction

1.1. Background of the study and Statement of the Problem

Algeria underwent a period of over 130 years of colonial French rule, during which Algerians endured immense hardship as many people died and massive changes were imposed on the country's cultural heritage, local governance, and educational system. Under the French rule, Algerians were prevented access to education as all Koranic schools across the country were closed (Mami, 2020) and the teaching of Arabic and Islamic history as well as Algerian geography was banned (Djabri, 1981). Towards the end of this era in the country's history, the level of education among Algerians sharply deteriorated, which was evidenced by the alarming levels of illiteracy.

As Algeria declared its independence in 1962, it started its thorough reconstruction process, which covered all sectors including education. Arguably, establishing a stable educational system in Algeria became a major priority since the early stages of the post-independence era, leading the government to engage in an extensive series of educational reforms. The reform agenda was mainly centred on enhancing literacy among Algerians; retrieving the Arab and Islamic identity; adjusting the structure of the schooling system; and introducing changes and improvements to textbooks and curricula in all subjects (Mami, 2013) (see section 2.3 for more details). Official reports indicate that these reform efforts resulted in significant quantitative improvements. Expenditure on the educational sector remarkably increased, access to education became significantly higher than ever before and illiteracy rates dropped noticeably, with more schools being established across the country.

In spite of the substantial achievements in terms of expenditure, access to education and increased levels of literacy, fewer achievements have been noted in terms of the quality of education in Algeria, which has often received major criticism from researchers and practitioners in the field. This was particularly evident as the initiated reforms were often resisted and were equally viewed to have yielded mixed results (Gherzouli, 2019). While it could be argued that, as in the case of many other contexts, the problems of Algeria's educational system could be attributed to multiple factors, Gherzouli (2019) argues that the main shortcoming of the system is its highly centralised nature that led to marginalising teachers and to perceiving them as mere decision implementors rather than active change agents, and stresses that such marginalisation of teachers is likely to lead to a lack of sense of ownership in their profession. In a similar way, Messekher and Miliani (2017) stress that within the Algerian context, 'the whole exercise of reforming national education seems to bump into a centralized and vertical system that creates problems more than it actually solves' (p. 308).

These arguments make a great deal of sense as Algerian public-school teachers are required to comply with strict guidelines that regulate their day-to-day work to ensure the implementation of policies, programmes and reforms set by the Ministry of National Education (MoNE hereafter). Working within such a highly centralised system, Algerian teachers, including English as a Foreign Language (EFL hereafter) teachers, seem have no voice in decision-making processes that directly relate to their teaching practice and to their students' learning. To exemplify, Gherzouli (2019) explains that this was the case for the 2003 curriculum reform that did not encourage teachers' involvement or seek their support but was rather initiated and implemented in a top-down fashion. The author described this as an 'imbalanced power relation between the government and teachers with the former controlling and dictating curriculum and excluding teachers from the whole developmental process' (p. 01). If, as part of future educational reforms, Algerian public-school teachers' roles continue to be restricted to passively receiving and merely implementing top-down policies and decisions, rather than being actively engaged in leadership processes and activities, it is likely that the outcomes of these reforms might not differ greatly from past initiatives. Indeed, over a decade ago in the USA context, Herterbran (2010) stressed that 'If it can be agreed upon that the spate of recent reform efforts has been largely ineffective, maintaining a culture where 'just a teacher' states of mind prevail is a terrible waste of expertise, energy, and influence in the school community' (p.365). This view is equally relevant to the status quo in Algeria where teachers' agency and potential seem to be highly undervalued, and their roles are largely restricted, with leadership confined to those at the apex of the system's hierarchical structure.

Given these shortcomings, a shift to a less centralised educational system that distributes leadership among different stakeholders is likely to attain more desired outcomes in terms of the quality of teaching and learning in Algeria. In this sense, distributed leadership was introduced in other contexts, particularly Western, as a less leader-centric, more relational, and more organisationally relevant and participative approach to leadership research and practice (Bolden, 2011; Spillane, Halverson and Diamond, 2004). As Spillane (2006) maintains, when leadership is dispersed, all school members, including classroom teachers, could demonstrate and engage in leadership work. A shift to a less centralised and more distributed approach to leadership within the Algerian educational system would, therefore, imply empowering different stakeholders, and primarily teachers, and extending their roles beyond mere implementation of predetermined top-down guidelines and policies that govern their work to include participation in leadership and decision-making processes. This view is to some extent supported by Messekher and Meliani (2017) who emphasise that Algerian teachers should be more involved in the conception rather than mere implementation of reforms and that future educational reforms in the country should be primarily

informed by ‘recommendations stemming from teachers to researchers and on to top decision makers’ (p.309). To tap into teachers’ potential to initiate and lead change and to effectively contribute to school and system improvement, the concept of teacher leadership has been introduced as an important subset of more distributed and less hierarchical approaches to leadership (Harris, 2005; McMahon, 2011; Muijs, Chapman and Armstrong, 2013; Poekert, 2012). Teacher leadership has long been advocated in many Western contexts, primarily in the United States of America (USA), United Kingdom (UK), Canada and Australia and is more recently gaining currency in non-Western countries, including the Arab World.

The concept of teacher leadership has indeed become an integral part of the international literature on school leadership and management and educational reform, and teacher leadership as both an academic and a research field has grown considerably in the last few decades (Nguyen, Harris and Ng, 2019; Schott, van, Roekel and Tummers, 2020; Wenner and Campbell, 2017). The perception of teachers as educational leaders and active change agents has gained ground globally as many researchers and practitioners around the world stress teachers’ agency and professional influence as key variables contributing to improved learner outcomes and overall improvements at both school and system level (Harris and Jones, 2019; Muijs and Harris, 2006). Confidence in teacher leadership stems primarily from the belief that teachers are the closest individuals to classrooms and learners and are accordingly better positioned than other leaders to initiate changes that positively contribute to their students’ learning (Ghamrawi, 2013; Hargreaves and Fink, 2006). Harris and Jones (2019) maintain that it is crucial that teachers are considered not only as implementors, but also as creators and instigators of educational change. The authors argue that more positive and empowering educational outcomes are likely to be attained in contexts where teachers are placed at the front line of change and reform initiatives, while less promising outcomes would be noted in contexts where teachers are considered as passive recipients and implementors of top-down policies. Arguably, Campbell (2020) maintains that as teachers work purposefully and collaboratively on important matters, they can influence both policy and practice in multiple ways. Overall, the available evidence suggests that teacher leadership is significant for: sustaining student learning (Nguyen, Harris and Ng, 2019); supporting innovation and creativity (Frost, 2012; Hargreaves and Fullan, 2020); increasing schools’ capacity to cope with the complexities of this century (Acquaro, 2019; Webber et al., 2023a); and enhancing teachers’ sense of ownership and feelings of involvement, self-efficacy and self-worth that would eventually lead to enhanced job satisfaction and teacher retention (Harris and Muijs, 2004). All these reasons together support the need to nurture and encourage teacher leadership practice as a catalyst of change within schools. Teacher leadership, could, therefore, be considered a new,

seemingly promising, approach to cope with the challenges currently faced by the education system in the Algerian context. This is a view that the current study endorses.

This thesis, therefore, supports the argument that teachers should be at the very heart of educational change and improvement efforts and that empowering Algerian teachers, building their capacity, and extending their roles should be an integral part of future reform initiatives in Algerian public education. This, as discussed earlier in this section, would require a shift to a less centralised approach to leadership and management in which teachers are encouraged and supported to engage in leadership practices within and beyond their schools. In this sense, the present study challenges the currently held perception in Algeria, and perhaps other similar contexts, that leadership in education must be centred on those at the top of a hierarchy either at school or system level and brings to the fore the idea of teacher leadership as an invaluable source for student success and school improvements. An empirical study of Algerian public school teachers' perceptions and practices of teacher leadership as well as the available supports, hindrances and professional development and learning opportunities is required to inform, facilitate, and support such a shift. These are the main foci for the current study. In the following section, I illustrate my initial interest in investigating teacher leadership in the Algerian context and how it developed into an empirical study.

1.2. Rationale and Personal Motivation

The decision to conduct this research was in the first place inspired by my personal motivation and subsequently by considerations of theoretical needs to explore teacher leadership within the Algerian context, a context in which scarcity of research in this field is noticeably evident. Conducting this research was, therefore, initially inspired by my personal encounters with some Algerian middle school teachers, though the focus at that early stage was not on 'teacher leadership' per se. As I was completing my master's degree in TEFL (Teaching English as a Foreign Language) in my home university in Algeria, and seeing myself as a prospective EFL teacher, I constantly engaged in discussions with my relatives, friends and some colleagues who were already public-school teachers at that time. On multiple occasions, they expressed how they began their careers with high levels of motivation and enthusiasm but were faced with various obstacles that often limited their professional autonomy and their potential to practise their agency. Moreover, most of them seemed to be dissatisfied with the status quo regarding the limited voice that they have within the educational system and with certain reforms and policies that they were required to implement, though they did not fully agree with. These were among the major concerns that I continuously reflected on as I tried to consider ways to overcome these challenges when I begin teaching. When I completed my masters' degree, I was granted a scholarship by the Algerian government to pursue my doctoral studies in the UK as part of the government's continuous efforts to introduce improvements to the educational

system in the country (mainly in terms of EFL teaching). At that stage, issues of teachers' participation in decision making processes, teachers' agency and professional autonomy were initially considered as a core focus of my proposed PhD research. Throughout the period that I spent completing a pre-session course at Canterbury Christ Church University, I engaged in extensive readings on these particular issues, and it was only at that stage that I, myself, came across the term 'teacher leadership'. The concept of teacher leadership attracted me as it represented an umbrella term that covers all of the aspects that I was initially interested in researching in the Algerian context in addition to many other aspects that were so appealing to me. Beyond that, it represented a promising approach towards teacher empowerment within the Algerian context. Teacher leadership, therefore, became the main focus of my PhD research.

In terms of the theoretical needs, the lack of empirically based research investigating teacher leadership in the Algerian context further motivated me to embark on this study. While research on teacher leadership within Western contexts has increased noticeably since the 1980s and more significantly since the publication of York-Barr and Duke's (2004) seminal work, knowledge about the nature of teacher leadership in non-Western contexts remains remarkably limited. Hallinger and Kovacevic (2021) noted that scholars from western contexts, namely the USA, are more actively engaged in the fields of teacher leadership and educational leadership and management than researchers from other contexts and cautioned that such predominance of the USA depicts more specifically the uneven development of this research field. Indeed, many recent systematic reviews of teacher leadership research highlight this gap in the research field (Nguyen, Harris and Ng, 2019; Pan, Wiens and Moyal, 2022; Schott, van Roekel and Tummers, 2020; Webber et al., 2023; Wenner and Campbell, 2017). Likewise, review studies conducted with a particular focus on the Arab World further stress the scarcity of such educational leadership and management research within the Arab World, with no theoretical or empirical evidence provided from the Algerian context (Ahmed, 2020; Hallinger and Hammad, 2019). While researchers in many Arab contexts addressed this knowledge gap by conducting empirical research that provided insights into teacher leadership in different parts of the Middle East and North Africa (MENA region hereafter) (Alsalahi, 2016; Altae, 2022; Emira, 2010; Hammad et al., 2023; Idelcadi et al., 2023; Sawalhi, 2019), the Algerian perspective is still -to date- missing. This study, therefore, explores the phenomenon of teacher leadership within an under-represented context in the existing international knowledge base.

It was, therefore, through my interactions with some teachers, my personal reflections, and my initial readings of relevant research that I developed the idea of conducting an empirical study focused on teachers' understandings of teacher leadership. The broader aim is primarily to introduce teacher

leadership to the Algerian context as an emerging approach to leadership that is likely to empower Algerian teachers to take the lead and to exert influence.

1.3. Rationale for the Focus on Middle School EFL Teachers' Perspectives

In Algeria, English language receives considerable attention by the Algerian government, being perceived as a vital tool to keep up with the globalised world (Abdat, 2023). Rezig (2011) argues that teaching English in Algeria has been notably advancing. While Algerians' attitudes toward English as opposed the French language in the past might seem paradoxical, given that Britain, too, represents another imperial power, Algerians do not associate the English language with colonialism (Abdat, 2023). Algeria's educational system has, accordingly, witnessed significant changes in recent years, in which most of the efforts were directed towards promoting TEFL in the country (more details in section 2.6). This is evident in the governments' most recent reform initiatives implemented by both the MoNE and the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research (MHESR hereafter), which particularly target improvements in the teaching and learning of English language in the country. Belmihoub (2018) maintains that the Algerian government has made great efforts to promote English and English language learning in the country mainly in light of the political and economic relations with the UK and the USA. British institutions were, for instance, very active in promoting English learning in Algeria (*ibid*), and as part of the Algerian-British cooperation, an agreement was made between the Algerian government and that of the UK in 2014 to train 5 cohorts of Algerian PhD students (a total of 500 students) from different Algerian university English departments in UK universities, with the aim of providing research-based evidence to inform future educational policies and reforms directed to enhancing EFL teaching and learning in the country (British Council, Algeria, nd). The present research is sponsored by the Algerian government under this plan.

Therefore, while I acknowledge many researchers' observations of the paucity of teacher leadership research in foreign language teaching contexts, and particularly in the EFL context (Alsalahi, 2016; Nguyen, Huynh and Tran, 2022; Whitehead and Greenier, 2019), my focus on EFL teachers' perspectives in the present study was primarily informed by the practical considerations discussed above. It is, therefore, important to note that the sample of EFL teachers selected for participation in this study is primarily instrumental in exploring and understanding teacher leadership in the Algerian context. That is, the present study does not assume that the context of EFL teaching necessarily represents a unique context for teacher leadership enactment that would be significantly different from the contexts of teaching other subjects. Rather, the aforementioned practical considerations, in particular, necessitated a focus on the views and perspectives of EFL teachers with the aim that their perspectives would provide deep insights into the phenomenon of teacher leadership within the under-represented Algerian context.

Although in Algeria, EFL is taught at both middle and secondary school levels, the context of teaching in general, including EFL teaching, at those levels differ (see section 2.5) and my choice to focus on middle school rather than secondary school level stems from two fundamental considerations. First, basic education, involving primary and middle school education, represents the core of the educational system in the country. This could partially be reflected by the fact that the two cycles that constitute basic education in the country (primary and middle school education) are compulsory for all Algerians, following the government's directives. Second, most of the recent reforms and policies launched by the Algerian MoNE target improvements at these two cycles. This might imply that basic education is currently at the core of the government's reform agenda and that this type of schooling is likely to be influenced by government's future initiatives. Thus, research focused on basic education is needed to provide empirical evidence to inform future reform efforts. Given that at the time of the fieldwork for the present research, EFL was only introduced at the second cycle of compulsory education (middle school level) further narrowed the scope of the present study to middle school EFL teachers.

1.4. Significance of the Study

This research is significant in particularly two main ways. First, given the preceding discussion in section 1.2, this is -to the best of my knowledge- the first empirical research to investigate teacher leadership within the Algerian context. This study, therefore, comes as a response to the surge of recent calls for additional research on teacher leadership beyond Western contexts (Nguyen, Harris and Ng, 2019; Pan, Wiens and Moyal, 2022; Schott, van Roekel and Tummers, 2020; Webber et al., 2023; Wenner and Campbell, 2017). To this end, the study is undertaken as part of the efforts to enrich and diversify the existing international knowledge base on teacher leadership by unearthing particular perspectives, practices, insights, and impediments in a non-Western setting. Conducting such research within the Algerian context is particularly significant given that the cultural, social, and perhaps even educational structures in Algeria differ, by and large, from those in Western contexts from which most of the currently available knowledge on teacher leadership is drawn. Considerations of such contextual differences are underscored by Hallinger's (2018) argument that all types of leadership should be explored with reference to community, institutional, political, economic, cultural, and school improvement contexts. More particularly, investigating teacher leadership within specific contexts, as in Algeria in the case of this research, is crucial as 'Insufficient consideration of context can result in inappropriate cross-cultural borrowing of educational constructs and lead to the failure of teacher leadership to enhance localized educational practices' (Webber et al., 2023, p. 11). Schott, van Roekel and Tummers (2020) equally stress the importance of exploring teacher leadership in context for strengthening understandings of antecedents that facilitate teacher leadership enactment and

influence, which would eventually lead to more informed implementation of the construct within the research context. This is the case for the present research that sets as one of its main aims exploring potential supports, hindrances, and professional learning opportunities within the specific Algerian context. Being the first empirical research examining teacher leadership in Algeria, it is hoped that this study would serve as impetus for more research on teacher leadership and on educational leadership and management in this largely under-represented context.

More practically, this research is significant as it provides a sample of Algerian public-school EFL teachers at middle school level with a platform to share their views and perspectives regarding teacher leadership with a particular reference to the context in which they work. This focus on teachers' perspectives is important given the argument that teacher leadership could best be explored when teachers are addressed for insights about the phenomenon (Slater, 2008). Arguably, the current research is based on the view that understanding Algerian public-school teachers' perspectives on teacher leadership could be significantly valuable for informing future directions for teacher leadership policy and practice in Algeria. Indeed, this study provides valuable insights into teacher leadership, mainly as it delineates current hinderances and desired supports for teacher leadership in the research context. Such findings inform important implications and recommendations for future educational reforms launched by the Algerian MoNE and MHESR particularly for nurturing teacher leadership enactment in Algerian public schools as well as for developing teacher leadership knowledge and skills among pre-service and in-service public-school teachers. Being sponsored by the MHESR as part of the governments' plan to introduce improvements to the educational system in Algeria, particularly in the field of TEFL, a copy of this thesis will be shared with the MoNE and the MHESR, thus allowing authorities and educational policymakers to access this contemporary, research-based evidence. Although the current study's findings may be limited to participant teachers, it could be argued that these could be transferable to the wider Algerian context. Given the highly centralised nature of the educational system in Algeria and a management structure that implies high degrees of 'sameness' across schools (Hanson, 1990, cited in Hammad, 2008), findings of the present research are likely to be transferable and relevant to other public-school teachers across the country.

1.5. Aims and Research Questions

In light of the issues outlined in sections 1.1, 1.2 and 1.4 and given the evident scarcity of teacher leadership research in Algeria, this qualitative study seeks to explore teacher leadership within the Algerian public middle school context, thus providing contemporary evidence of the nature of teacher leadership within this under-represented context. Being the first study to investigate teacher

leadership in Algeria, it was deemed important that this exploratory research addresses some basic, yet central, aims and research questions outlined below:

RQ1). What perceptions do middle school EFL teachers hold regarding teacher leadership?

This question aims to explore Algerian middle school EFL teachers' perceptions of teacher leadership. Given the novelty of the research topic in the Algerian context, it is important to look at teachers' perceptions of teacher leadership and to determine whether and how Algerian middle school teachers understand what is meant by this concept. This is particularly important as King (2017) noted that the way in which teacher leadership is conceptualised arguably impacts its enactment in practice.

RQ2). What are middle school EFL teachers' reported practices of and experiences with teacher leadership?

Through this question, the aim is to get insights into the realities of teacher leadership enactment in the Algerian middle school context as reported by participant teachers. Answers to this research question also enabled me to highlight existing consistencies or discrepancies between participant teachers' perceptions of teacher leadership and their reported practices.

RQ3). What factors reportedly hinder/ foster their practice of leadership?

This question aims to explore the available supports and current hindrances of teacher leadership enactment in the Algerian context. Answers to this research question are likely to provide explanations for any noted discrepancies between participant teachers' perceptions of teacher leadership and their reported practices by highlighting impediments to teacher leadership enactment within their work environment.

RQ4). How do teachers view collaboration with each other within their school community as contributing to their professional development as teacher leaders?

Given the scarcity of research investigating teacher leaders' professional development and learning in addition to the lack of formal teacher leadership preparation programs within the Algerian context, it was deemed important to look at the potential role of job embedded professional learning opportunities that are part of teachers' day-to-day work in enhancing their professional growth as teacher leaders. More specifically, through this question, I seek to get insights into teachers' perceptions of the potential of teachers' informal collaboration with peers within their school community to serve as an informal, job-embedded professional learning experience through which teachers could learn and grow professionally as teacher leaders.

To address these questions, I relied on teacher's perceptions of the issues under investigation. Thus, within a qualitative research design adhering to the interpretive paradigm, I utilised individual semi-structured interviews, written reflections, and online focus group discussions to explore 18 middle school EFL teachers' perceptions and reported practices of teacher leadership as well as the

available supports or current hindrances of teacher leadership practice within the study context. Moreover, I examined participant teachers' perceptions of the potential role of collaboration with peers in enhancing their professional learning and growth as teacher leaders.

1.6. Defining Key Terms

This section provides brief definition of recurring concepts that are key to the present research. These are: agency, empowerment, and globalisation.

Agency: Agency is commonly broadly defined as an intentional act whose key feature is 'the power to originate actions for given purposes' (Bandura, 2001, p. 6), thus integrating elements of purposeful actions, self-regulation, and self-reflections aiming at continued individual and collective improvements (Bandura, 2006). Goller and Paloniemi (2017) stress that usually, agency is associated "with individuals who, in a given situation, make decisions, take initiatives, act proactively rather than reactively, deliberately strive and function creatively and innovatively" (p. 1). As part of their conceptualisation of agency, Ukkonen-Mikkola and Varpanen (2020) postulate four main characteristics of this concept, which are: 1) the capacity to act, 2) intentionality or a sense of purpose, 3) the exertion of a causal power in the social environment, and 4) the sense of being the initiator of one's actions. Etelapelto et al. (2013) specifically stressed intentionality as a key feature of agency explaining that an action is only considered agentive when it is an intentional act rather than a mere responsive reaction to an emerging event. Teacher agency, more specifically, refers to teachers' ability to take decisions and to make choices related to their work, drawing on their professional knowledge, their beliefs, and their values, which in turn empowers them to efficiently address their learners' needs to contribute to educational policies (Sang, 2020) and encompasses teachers' capacity to autonomously and collaboratively act on topics of interest (Teng, 2019).

Empowerment: Broadly, empowerment refers to 'a process whereby employees develop the competence to take charge of their own growth and resolve their own problems' (Short, 1994, p. 488). While consensus on a definition of teacher empowerment is still missing, this concept often relates to teachers as autonomous professionals who are willing to perform their best at work when they feel intrinsically motivated (Wan, 2005) and to control critical decisions about teaching and learning conditions (Sweetland and Hoy, 2000). Such a definition of the concept is based on a psychological perspective focused on an individual's psychological state which, according to Spreitzer (1995; 1996), is manifested in four cognitions: (1) meaning, which refers to a match between the needs of an individuals' work from the one hand and their values, beliefs and behaviours from the other hand; (2) competence, which entails individuals' self-efficacy in relation to their work and their capability to effectively perform that work; (3) autonomy, which refers to a sense of choice in initiating and regulating one's actions; and (4) impact, which refers to the extent to which one can influence work-

related administrative, strategic or operating outcomes. In addition to the psychological perspective, some scholars equally stress the social structural perspective of the concept, which accounts for the influence of certain environmental factors and work conditions on teachers' roles and tasks (Sweetland and Hoy, 2000). Studies adopting this latter perspective often perceive empowerment as an act of school principals or senior management teams, who grant teachers more power and autonomy in their work (Sagnak, 2012; Vecchio, Justin and Pearce, 2010). To provide a clearer definition of teacher empowerment, Short and Rinehart (1992) outlined six dimensions of the concept, which are: (1) teachers' participation in decisions that directly affect their work; (2) professional recognition and respect from colleagues; (3) teachers' impact and influence at the school level; (4) professional development opportunities; (5) teachers' professional autonomy; and (6) teachers' self-efficacy.

Globalisation: Globalisation represents one of the most complex and highly contested concepts (Guillen, 2001; Zajda, 2018b). Kumaravadivelu (2006) maintains that the term 'globalisation' may mean different things to different people and in different contexts, which necessitates handling and using it with caution. Zajda (2018a, p. 2) elaborates on this view, stressing that globalisation is 'a multi-dimensional cultural construct, reflecting the necessary interdependence and connections of all core facets of culture: the economy, politics, ideology, languages, education, consumer goods, travel, modes of communication, technology, and the people around the world'. One of the definitions proposed for this construct by Giddens (1990, p.64) is that it refers to 'the intensification of worldwide social relations which link distant localities in such a way that local happenings are shaped by events occurring many miles away and vice-versa'. Accordingly, globalisation has created a situation in which societies have increasingly become involved in global processes and embroiled in each other (Delanty, 2006). Given its multifaceted and contested nature, Fairclough (2006) cautions against the misuse of the term 'globalisation', as this could result in the misrepresentation of what it actually is. This is particularly important because, in some cases, this term might be used by some as a cover to the continuation of a (neo)colonialist Western domination over the world (Kumaravadivelu, 2006a) especially as the West is the driving force for globalisation. This has, therefore, often led to the perception of globalisation as a process of Americanisation Westernisation, with the West aiming to maintain control over former colonies (Coupland, 2011).

1.7. Structure of the Thesis

This thesis is organised into seven chapters. This first chapter provided an introduction to the study, presenting the background and narrowing the scope for the study. The rationale and personal motivation for conducting this research, the research significance as well as the research questions and aims were also addressed.

Chapter 2 provides an overview of the study context. It begins with a brief background on Algeria as well as an overview of the reform initiatives introduced by the Algerian government post to the country's independence. The chapter further outlines the current organisational and management structure of the educational system and the place of teacher leadership within it. It also provides a brief overview of the place of English language and English language teaching within the Algerian context. Providing such an overview of the research context would enable the reader to construct a conceptual image of the background surrounding the present research findings.

Chapter 3, the literature review, positions this study within the existing body of research conducted on teacher leadership. It provides a detailed review of relevant literature in the field. The chapter is broadly organised in line with the study's research questions and as such the review covers aspects such as conceptualisations and definitions of teacher leadership, conditions that either support or hinder teacher leadership enactment as well as the professional development and learning for teacher leaders. An overview and discussion of empirical research with similar foci as the present study in Arab contexts is also provided. The final section delineates the conceptual framework that underpins this study, providing a discussion of important concepts connected to the findings that emerged from the current research.

Chapter 4 presents the methodology and research design adopted to address the research questions and to achieve the aims of this research. It begins by explaining the philosophical stance of the study, justifying why the interpretivist paradigm, associated with the qualitative exploratory design, was deemed most appropriate for the study. Subsequently, the chapter addresses participants' selection procedures and provides a detailed account of the data collection methods and data analysis procedures employed in the present research. The chapter further highlights my positionality and role in this research and outlines measures taken to enhance the research trustworthiness and to address ethical concerns.

Chapter 5 presents the findings of this study. In this chapter, the four research questions guiding this study provided a framework for presenting the research findings. The chapter is, accordingly, structured into four main sections, each presenting findings related to one of the four research questions.

Chapter 6 begins by broadly discussing the emerging findings in light of the conceptual framework, and subsequently discusses these findings in more detail in relation to previous empirical research conducted in the field of teacher leadership (presented in chapter 3). The chapter equally interprets the findings in light of features of the current educational context in Algeria (presented in chapter 2).

Chapter 7 briefly summarises the research findings with reference to the research questions and highlights the study's contribution to the existing knowledge base on teacher leadership. The chapter also addresses the implications and practical recommendations of the study alongside its limitations and suggestions for future research. This final chapter ends with my personal reflection on the journey of conducting this research.

Chapter Two: Context of the Study

2.1. Introduction

The current research was conducted in Algeria, where data were obtained from a sample of Algerian middle school teachers of English (EFL teachers hereafter). This chapter, thus, sets to provide an overview of the research context. The aim is to familiarise the readers with the context in which participant teachers work, and therefore to enable them to build a conceptual image of the background surrounding the research findings. The chapter begins with a brief background on Algeria (section 2.2), and then moves to focus on the Algerian educational system. To this end, the chapter first outlines the various reform initiatives undertaken by the Algerian Ministry of National Education (MoNE hereafter) to stabilise and advance education across the country (section 2.3). This is followed by a discussion of the current structure and management of the educational system, and the place of teacher leadership within it in section 2.4. Section 2.5, then, provides an overview of English language and English language teaching in Algeria given that the present study draws on data obtained from a sample of Algerian EFL teachers. The final section (section 2.6) provides a summary of the chapter.

2.2. A Brief Background on Algeria

Algeria, officially assigned as the People's Democratic Republic of Algeria, with Algiers as its capital, is a North African country and part of the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region (Benrabah, 2005). Algeria is bounded by the Mediterranean Sea to the north (with a 1200 kilometres coastline), Mauritania and Mali to the southwest, Niger to the southeast, Tunisia to the northeast, Libya to the east, and Morocco to the west (see map in figure 2.1 below). Spanning across 2,381,741 square kilometres, Algeria is the tenth largest country in the world, and the largest in Africa and in the Arab World. The Sahara Desert covers more than four-fifths of the Algerian territory. The country is composed of fifty-eight provinces, with Algiers, the capital, being the most densely populated province.

Figure 2.1. Map of Algeria showing its position in Africa (World Factbook, 2020).

Algeria is a nation characterized by cultural and linguistic diversity (Belmihoub, 2018). As of November 2022, Algeria’s population was estimated to exceed 45 million inhabitants (Worldometer, 2022), belonging primarily to one of the two major ethnic groups in the country, Arabs and Berbers. The vast majority of Algerians (99% of the population) are Arabo-Berber, while the remaining 1% are non-Arabo-Berber, mainly French, with some Italian, Maltese, Spanish, and Corsican minorities. Berbers are made up of four main groups: the Tuaregs (living mainly in the southern parts of Algeria), the Mozabites (living in Gharda’ia province and in some regions in the Sahara), the Chaouias (living in the Aures Mountains, further east, south of Constantine province), and the Kabylis (Benrabah, 2005). The official language is Standard Arabic, with French used in business and Amazigh spoken in a number of regions. While Standard Arabic is taught in schools and used in administrations, Algerians use the colloquial language known as ‘Darija’, which is a blend of Standard Arabic, Amazigh, Turkish and French, in their day-to-day life. In some regions, Berber is spoken almost exclusively. As for religion, Sunni Islam is the state religion, and Muslims constitute 99% of the population. The remaining 1% of the population are mainly Christians, with a very small minority of Jews.

2.3. An Overview of Educational Reforms in Algeria

When Algeria declared its independence in 1962, after 132 years of French colonial rule, the country’s illiteracy rates were alarming, as at that time 85% of the population were illiterate (Messekher and Meliani, 2017). This situation urged the Algerian government to establish a stable educational system as education was perceived as key for rebuilding the nation. To this end, the

government engaged in a series of reforms which, since the earliest stages, stressed education as a free and guaranteed right for all Algerians. Mami (2013) asserts that educational reforms in Algeria were particularly centred on enhancing the teaching quality, adapting curricula or reorganising the school setting. Accordingly, the history of the educational reforms in Algeria can be divided into three main stages discussed below.

Stage 1: 1962-1970

The severe circumstances that the country suffered from at this stage were clearly reflected in different sectors, and education was no exception. As early as September 15, 1962, the National Commission for Educational Reform, appointed by President Ahmed Ben Bella, held an urgent meeting to highlight the main reform measures that must be undertaken. Arabisation of the school system both in terms of contents and in terms of instruction was seen to be the main priority, aiming to eliminate all traces of the coloniser (Rezig, 2012). In October 1962, President Ben Bella declared that standard Arabic was to be introduced to schools (Benrabah, 2007). Standard Arabic was proclaimed the language of instruction for all school subjects except for medicine and science university courses. Arabisation of education was in itself challenging due to the shortage of Algerian workforce qualified to teach standard Arabic as well as the lack of textbooks and teaching materials at that time. This pushed the government to recruit almost a thousand Egyptian, Iraqi and Syrian teachers starting from 1964 (Mami, 2013; Sharkey, 2012). As for educational materials, all materials in French were gradually abandoned and replaced by materials in Arabic which were primarily imported from Egypt. Besides Arabisation, the Algerian Government was also concerned with reinforcing Islamic principles as a core aspect of Algerian citizens' national identity. Accordingly, Islamic education was introduced as a compulsory subject, substituting sociology, philosophy and French literature both in secondary and in higher education (Mami, 2013). In terms of its structure, the educational system was organised at this stage into three independent levels: six years for primary school education, four years for middle school education and three years for secondary school education. By the end of each level, pupils had to pass an exam that qualified them to move to the following level. Centralised reforms initiated at this stage were, thus, primarily meant to reduce the illiteracy rates and retrieve the Algerian national identity.

Stage 2: 1970-1999

During the 1970s, and under the presidency of Houari Boumediene, various reforms were initiated. On April 16, 1976, the MoNE passed legislation, emphasising the compulsory nature of education. To reinforce this, the school system was reconstructed introducing the 'fundamental school', a new school body that combines primary and middle school education (Cherif and Salmi, 2018). Fundamental education starts at the age of six and lasts for a compulsory period of nine years

divided into three cycles, each lasting for three years. Thus, the exam that qualifies pupils to progress from primary to middle school education was cancelled, allowing all students who finish grade six of fundamental education (cycle 2) to move to grade seven of fundamental education (cycle 3). This new structure of the educational system was generalised across the country and officially applied starting from the school year 1980-1981 (Bouchaala, 2017). Some other changes in the structure of secondary school education were introduced, organising it into three streams in the first grade, leading to 15 branches in the second grade of secondary education. By the late 1980s, approximately 3.8 million pupils were enrolled in primary education and around 2.1 million pupils in secondary education (Mami, 2013). During this stage, all teaching material and course books were designed and printed in Algeria (Bouchaala, 2017). The 1976 Ordinance also asserted that education is a state monopoly, and that the Algerian government is the only entity responsible for the organization and supervision of the country's educational system (Cherif and Salmi, 2018). One of the main foci of the 1970s reforms was, thus, the abolishment of all private education. Standard Arabic, at this stage, became the medium of instruction for all subjects including scientific ones, except for foreign languages. Despite the perceived and measured outcomes of the reform initiatives introduced at this stage, Gherzouli (2019) explains that fundamental education faced various efficiency and quality problems, particularly in terms of the lack of facilities and qualified teachers, limited teaching materials, overcrowded classrooms, and varying educational perspectives and philosophies. By the end of this stage, Algeria witnessed the end of a drastic period in its history, 'the Black Decade'; a civil war that lasted for ten years, affecting the country at so many levels. At the level of education, educational reforms were frozen starting 1992 because of this civil war.

Stage 3: 2000-Present

By the beginning of this stage, Algeria was emerging from a ten-year bloody civil war known in Algeria's history as "la décennie noire" or 'The Black Decade' (Mami, 2013). In 2000, realising the urgent need for reforming the educational system which was then described by president Abdelaziz Bouteflika as being 'doomed' (Gherzouli, 2019), the Algerian president appointed 170 educators, specifically educational inspectors and curriculum specialists, and politicians to form the 'National Commission for the Reform of the Educational System' (La Commission Nationale de Réforme du Système Educatif, or CNRSE) in order to evaluate the educational system and to provide some recommendations on the necessary reforms (Bouchaala, 2017). The commission was set up on May, 13, 2000, and handed its report to the Algerian president in 2001. On August 13, 2003, the government passed an executive decree that amended the 1976 reforms and introduced changes to the educational system based on the commission's recommendations, which stressed the need for a shift in teaching methods, introduction and implementation of new syllabuses and textbooks and initiation of teacher

training programmes. The 2003 reform was primarily marked by the shift from teacher-centred to learner-centred teaching and learning processes by introducing the Competency Based Approach (CBA) for all subjects and across all school levels. Bader and Hamada (2015) maintain that the main reason for implementing the CBA as part of the 2003 reform is 'to cope with the demands of the globalized world' (p. 8). The adoption of this new approach implied a change in the role of both teachers and learners (Tawil, 2005). Under this approach, teachers were expected to become planners of what is referred to as 'a situation of integration' and facilitators of knowledge construction instead of being knowledge providers. In the same way, students were expected to become more involved in active learning and problem solving to construct knowledge. Apart from implementing the CBA approach, the 2003 reform shifted the structure of the school system from a 6-3-3 structure (primary-middle-secondary) to a 5-4-3 structure (Ordinance N° 03-09 of August 13, 2003; Law N° 08-04 of January 23, 2008). The state monopoly nature of education was relaxed, and the government allowed the establishment of private educational institutions under defined regulations and guidelines set by the MoNE. As part of the most recent reform initiatives, the MoNE launched new textbooks and curricula for both primary and middle school levels starting from September 2016 to further enhance implementation of the CBA in basic education. Similarly, starting from September 2022, English was introduced to primary school pupils starting from grade 3.

The preceding discussion proves that establishing a stable educational system has always been one of the major concerns of the Algerian government as huge efforts and funds were invested towards this aim. However, over half a century after the country's independence and despite the extensive series of educational reforms launched by the Algerian government as discussed in the above, education in Algeria still suffers from various dysfunctions and drawbacks (Messekher and Miliani, 2017). Though the measures undertaken to address some of the major quantitative concerns that emerged immediately after the country's independence represent an undeniable achievement benefiting all Algerians, it is fundamental that these quantitative achievements are complemented by further measures to enhance the quality of education in the country. Although the introduction of new teaching approaches and methods and the implementation of new curricula came as an attempt from educational policymakers to enhance the quality of education in Algeria, these centralised initiatives that were planned and implemented in a top-down fashion often faced resistance from teachers whose views were not considered. Indeed, Messekher and Miliani (2017) stress that 'the whole exercise of reforming national education seems to bump into a centralized and vertical system that creates problems more than it actually solves' (p. 308) and that for reforms to be successful and well-targeted, they should alternatively be organic and participatory, involving all actors within the educational system. The authors, accordingly, emphasise that future educational reforms in Algeria should be

planned in a less centralised fashion in which recommendations from teachers serve as the basis for informing these reform initiatives. The following section provides an overview of the current educational system in Algeria based on the most recent reforms implemented by the MoNE.

2.4. An Overview of Algeria's Pre-university Educational System

The Algerian educational system guarantees free-of-charge education for all Algerians from kindergarten until higher education. Education in Algeria is managed by two separate ministries: The MoNE and the MHESR. The former is responsible for basic and secondary education while the latter is in charge of the tertiary sector. To provide an overview of the pre-university educational system, I first outline its current organisational structure that is based on the 2003 reforms (section 2.4.1). Then, I discuss issues related to the management of the educational system and the role(s) of teachers within it. Given the scarcity of research on teacher leadership and educational leadership and management in the Algerian context, this section draws largely on my own review of the publicly available policy documents detailing school regulations and regulations of the broader educational system in terms of roles of each of the stakeholders and the nature of teachers' initial and in-service professional training, as well as the content of EFL teachers' pre-service programmes in the form of coursework provided for EFL student teachers at public universities and teacher colleges. Thus, I first look broadly at the organisational structure of education management in Algeria (section 2.4.2), then I narrow down my focus to consider teachers' roles and the content of pre-service and in-service training that they receive with respect to teacher leadership, the focus of this study (section 2.4.3). Moreover, it is important to note that while these sub-sections aim to provide more insights into the study context, it was deemed important to look at the Algerian educational context in comparison with other Western and Arab contexts to draw relevant comparisons. These comparisons would enable readers to judge the potential transferability of findings that emerge from this research to other similar educational contexts.

2.4.1. Current Structure of the Educational System

As discussed in section 2.3, one of the main foci of educational reforms in Algeria was the restructuring and reorganisation of the system in terms of the schooling levels. The current structure of the schooling system is based on the 2003 reform, remodelling the years of schooling on a 5-4-3 basis (five years primary school level, four years middle school level and three years secondary school level) with the introduction of kindergarten education for children aged 4 to 5 years old. The first two stages (primary and middle school levels), usually referred to as 'Fundamental' or 'Basic', constitute the compulsory education in the country and have very high attendance, whereas kindergarten and secondary education are optional and have lower enrolment levels (Gherzouli, 2019). At the age of four or five, children join kindergarten classes that aim mainly to develop their social skills and to

teach them the basics of Islam, Arabic language and mathematics, thus serving as a base for their future education. At the age of six, they enrol in primary schools for a period of five years leading to a national examination called ‘Primary School Examination’. Those who pass the examination then move to middle schools (Law N° 08-04 of January 23, 2008). Middle school level encompasses four years by the end of which students undergo another national examination called ‘Middle School Examination’. Holders of middle school certificates move to secondary schools whereas those who do not pass this examination or who do not wish to complete their secondary school education can choose to pursue distance learning managed by the National Office for Education and Distance Learning (l’Office National d’Enseignement et de la Formation à Distance, or ONEFD), join vocational training centres or seek employment once they reach the age of sixteen (Law No. 08-04 of January 23, 2008). Secondary education is non-compulsory and it comprises three years. It begins with a foundation year supporting two further years of study. Course content in the first year is organised into two main branches: Science and technology, and Letters, which unfold into various sub-branches starting from the second year. The branches offered for science and technology pupils include mathematics, experiential sciences, management and economy, and technical mathematics. As for Letters, two branches are offered: Letters and Philosophy and Foreign Languages. By the end of the third year, secondary school pupils sit a final national examination, the Baccalaureate (BAC) which qualifies them to access universities or teacher colleges (see appendix A for structure of the Algerian educational system).

2.4.2. Management of the Educational System

The Algerian educational system is highly centralised and operates in a strict hierarchical, top-down fashion (Gherzouli, 2019; Messekher and Miliani, 2017). Overall, the educational system in Algeria is managed at three levels: the national, the regional and the local. At the national level, the MoNE, located in the capital, Algiers, is found at the top of the organisational management structure, being considered the centre of all decision-making processes. In this sense, the MoNE represents the primary body responsible for designing curricula and textbooks, selecting instruction and assessment approaches, allocating financial resources as well as issuing laws and regulations for recruiting and promoting staff and providing in-service teacher training (Gherzouli, 2018; Zarzour, 2022). These highly centralised measures and processes ensure unified school structures as well as teacher recruitment, supervision and promotion regulations within all public schools across the country. Different consultancy boards are established under the auspices of the MoNE to assist the Minister in planning and formulating educational policies. Examples of these bodies include the General Secretary, the Head of Cabinet, the General Inspectorate and the General Inspectorate of Pedagogy (Executive Decree No. 09-318 of October 6, 2009).

At the regional level, Directorates of Education have been established across the 58 provinces in the country; one directorate in each province except for the capital, Algiers, in which three directorates have been established due to the population density and large numbers of schools. Directorates of education are responsible for governing all educational matters at the level of the respective provinces following the regulations and guidelines set by the MoNE. Their primary task is, therefore, to interpret policies from the MoNE and facilitate their implementation within schools in the respective provinces. Overall, the directorates of education assume various responsibilities including: evaluating and ensuring the implementation of programmes, curricula and policies; assuring the availability of the required work conditions within all schools and supervising the construction and equipment of new schools across the respective province; allocating teachers to schools; and providing in-service professional training for teachers and staff across all schools within the respective province (Gherzouli, 2018). Each directorate is directed by a director of education (ibid). Other members working at the level of regional directorates of education are school and subject inspectors, who are assigned by the director of education to supervise schools and teachers in specific districts within the province. The role of school inspectors, on the one hand, is to ensure that schools under their supervision fully implement the guidelines, procedures and policies set up by the MoNE and that students within these schools are well-prepared for national examinations (Executive Decree No. 08-315 of October 11, 2008). Subject inspectors' role, on the other hand, is more specifically related with teachers of a particular subject, EFL for instance, within the schools under their supervision. They are, therefore, responsible for: ensuring the implementation of national curricula; mentoring and instructing subject teachers and checking their overall progress through scheduled and unscheduled visits to schools; designing and implementing initial teacher training; and evaluating novice teachers who have completed their internship and accordingly taking decisions regarding their permanent recruitment following the MoNE guidelines (Executive Decree No. 08-315 of October 11, 2008).

At the local level, schools represent spaces where the policies and reforms decided by the MoNE are implemented with the school principals being responsible for ensuring effective implementation of the directives and policies of the MoNE coming through the regional education directorates under the supervision of school inspectors. Algerian public schools are therefore headed by a school principal who collaboratively works with a director of studies, a bursar, an education advisor and other administrative staff (Executive Decree N° 10-230 of October 2, 2010; Executive Decree N° 12-240 of May 29, 2012). This implies that a pyramidal management structure is also prevalent within individual public schools in which school principals, based on the MoNE directives, retain most authority. However, it is important to note that despite the level of authority that school

principals might hold within schools, they themselves seem to be mainly viewed as reform and policy implementers rather than active participants in policy design and formulation within the Algerian context. In regulating their schools, all public-school principals must strictly adhere to the top-down policies, regulations and guidelines set by the MoNE.

Algerian public-school teachers, including EFL teachers, are found at the bottom of the hierarchical structure, where their roles are restricted and their participation in decision-making processes seems to be remarkably limited. Public-school teachers fulfil their responsibilities under the supervision of school principals and subject inspectors, whose role is to ensure that teachers teach in accordance with the directives of the MoNE. Overall, the highly centralised nature of the educational system implies that control ultimately remains with the MoNE even when responsibilities seem to shift to regional levels (Directorates of education) or local levels (public schools).

Characterised by notably high levels of centralisation, the organisational structure of education management in Algeria shares similar characteristics with that in other Arab countries like Jordan, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA), Iraq, Oman, Qatar, and Morocco (Al-Zboon, 2013; Alnasser, 2022; Alsalahi, 2016; Altae, 2022; Amghar, 2019; Hammad et al., 2023; Ramahi, 2019). Oplatka and Arar (2017) confirm this in their review of research on educational leadership and management in the Arab World, concluding that the hierarchical top-down approach to leadership dominates most schools in this region. Such dominance is perceived by some as ‘characteristic of collectivist cultures’ that value group cohesion and loyalty and consider seniority and rank as critical organisational values, resulting in centralised leadership approaches and decision-making processes (Hammad et al., 2023, p. 5).

2.4.3. The Place of Teacher Leadership in Policy Discourse and in Teachers’ Professional Training Programmes in Algeria

In Algeria, teachers’ roles as outlined in the school regulations documents implemented by the MoNE seem to be largely associated with the general and basic functions of classroom teachers, including responsibilities such as preparing and delivering lessons to their pupils, marking exams, and keeping records of their learners’ progress (Executive Decree N° 12- 240 of May 29, 2012, completing and modifying Executive Decree N° 08-315 of October 11, 2008). The terms ‘teacher leadership’ or ‘teacher leaders’ are not explicitly mentioned in any of these policy documents. However, some responsibilities expected to be accomplished by public-school teachers as well as some positions to which they could be promoted seem to be relevant to teacher leaders’ roles and formal positions highlighted in the existing literature (see section 3.3.2). In this regard, primarily based on seniority in teaching, public school teachers could seek promotion to the positions of principal teachers, teacher mentors, school or subject inspectors, and curriculum specialists (see section 2.4.3.1 for more details). Likewise, public school teachers in Algeria are encouraged to engage in continuous professional

development opportunities by participating in in-service training; to participate in management councils within their schools; and to contribute to organising extracurricular activities (Executive Decree No. 12- 240 of May 29, 2012, completing and modifying Executive Decree N° 08-315 of October 11, 2008). School management councils are established in all public schools following the MoNE guidelines and are meant to provide different stakeholders, including teachers, within public schools with a space to share their opinions regarding important school matters. These activities have all been cited in the existing teacher leadership literature as examples of non-positional teacher leadership practices (see section 3.3.2).

Such indirect references to teacher leadership roles were equally noted by researchers in other Arab contexts such as KSA (Alnasser, 2022), Morocco (Amghar, 2019; Idelcadi, Rguibi and Bouziane, 2023) and Iraq (Altae, 2022). Webber, Conway and van der Vyver (2023) similarly reported indirect indications to teacher leadership attributes in other non-Arab contexts such as the UK, Canada, the Netherlands, and Mali. In some other contexts, however, more explicit references to teacher leadership are made. Perhaps the most explicit of which is in the context of the USA, where the Teacher Leader Model Standards were developed by the Teacher Leadership Exploratory Consortium (2011), explicitly detailing teacher leadership dimensions, domains and functions and recognising both formal and informal roles of teacher leaders in the USA.

In terms of teachers' training and preparation in Algeria, the discussion provided subsequently in this section is based on a review of the content of the pre-service preparation and training programmes provided for prospective EFL teachers as well as the initial and in-service professional development programmes provided to public-school teachers, including middle school EFL teachers.

While in-service training for Algerian public-school teachers is designed and implemented following guidelines set by the MoNE, EFL student teachers receive pre-service training in the form of university coursework at public universities and teacher colleges that are governed by the MHESR. Arguably, the higher education system in Algeria is a relatively centralised system as higher education institutions are regulated following the policies, reforms and decisions issued by the MHESR (Souleh, 2017). A review of the content of prospective EFL teachers' coursework at teachers' college revealed that EFL student teachers receive extensive training in areas of teaching methods and student assessment, classroom management and the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), though such training is highly theoretical. Throughout their first and second year of training at the teachers' college, EFL student teachers are mainly trained on the use of ICTs (particularly the use of Microsoft Excel and PowerPoint) in addition to receiving input related primarily to the English language skills and components (written expression, oral expression, grammar, phonetics, linguistics,

etc.). The main objective is to enhance student teachers' English language mastery and competence. Starting from the third year of their course, the Teaching English as a Foreign Language (TEFL) module is introduced, the objective of which is to introduce student teachers to the 'basic concepts in TEFL' and to provide them with 'tools that would help them in their future careers'. The content of the TEFL module includes an introduction to the teaching methods, approaches and materials, lesson planning and presentation as well as input related to testing, student assessment and classroom management. The content that EFL prospective teachers receive at public universities is to a great extent similar to the content implemented for EFL student teachers in teacher colleges. What is clearly noted, then, is that prospective EFL teachers (both public university and teacher college graduates) seem to receive no input on issues related to educational leadership overall, and to teacher leadership in particular. Such university coursework seems to be more centred on developing student teachers' pedagogical and subject knowledge.

In terms of initial and in-service teacher training, this is provided to public school teachers following guidelines set by the MoNE in the ministerial executive decree No. 14-28 of February 2014. The initial teacher training programme is standardised across subjects and school levels and is designed and implemented by subject inspectors with the assistance of teacher mentors at the level of each directorate of education. All public-school teachers, including EFL teachers, are required to attend these training sessions which, according to the MoNE's guidelines, take place during school holidays for a total duration of seven weeks (190 hours in total). As per its content, it involves both theoretical and practical aspects, particularly revolving around ten modules broadly related to pedagogical and subject knowledge and school legislation. Notably, most of these modules seem to directly relate to and support teachers' role within their classrooms (educational psychology, classroom management, pedagogical assessment and evaluation, TEFL and teaching methods, and ICTs). The modules 'school legislation' and 'the Algerian educational system' are meant to familiarise teachers with the general guidelines set by the MoNE to regulate their day-to-day work, specifying their roles and the roles of other members within Algerian public schools. Time allocated to each of these modules differ. It is noted, however, that overall, modules that are tightly related to teachers' classroom practices account for a total of 120 out of 190 hours devoted for in-service teachers' professional training. As per teachers' in-service training and formal Continuous Professional Development (CPD hereafter) sessions, the MoNE entitles public school teachers, including middle school EFL teachers, to six sessions of formal CPD per year (Ouarzeddine, Gomas and Ravanis, 2020). Many studies conducted within the Algerian context, however, reported that EFL teachers stressed the inadequacy of these training sessions, which were reported by most teachers to be reduced to one session per year (Abdat, 2023). Findings of these studies confirm Haouam's (2015) observation

that teachers' in-service training in Algeria were often reduced to ad-hoc sessions delivered in a top-down fashion by subject inspectors.

The preceding discussion may, therefore, indicate that Algerian middle school EFL teachers are not prepared in the field of educational leadership and teacher leadership, given that these concepts are currently not part of their preparation and training programmes, which alternatively seem to have a clear focus on developing teachers' pedagogical and subject knowledge and skills. While this conclusion is not meant to belittle the importance of the pedagogical and subject-related side of teachers' training, such restricted focus on these aspects implies overlooking teachers' capabilities and potentials for leadership, particularly beyond their classrooms, which is likely to result in teachers' restricted and narrowed perceptions of their roles, thus representing a possible barrier to developing teachers as teacher leaders.

It is important to note, however, that such scarcity in teacher leadership professional preparation and training programmes is not exclusive to the Algerian context or to other Arab contexts. In Spain, for instance, Gratacós, de Guevara and Rodriguez (2021) maintain that although some Spanish academics continuously advocate the need to train teachers in aspects related to teacher leadership, these dimensions are not taken into consideration by Spanish legislation and initial teacher education and professional development programmes implemented for pre-service teachers in the country. Even in contexts where teacher leadership is now well-established both as a field of research and as an essential aspect of teachers' practice and professionalism (such as the USA, UK, Canada and Australia), focus on the professional training and preparation programmes remains limited. Teacher leadership preparation and training programmes have only recently begun to emerge and to receive considerable attention in Western contexts that dominate the field of teacher leadership (see section 3.5.1 for more details).

2.4.3.1. Teachers' Recruitment and Promotion in Algerian Public Middle Schools

Following the above discussion and given the centralised nature of the educational system in Algeria, the MoNE strictly sets the conditions and modalities for recruiting and promoting teachers, including EFL teachers, across all public schools in the country. Priority of recruitment is for graduates of 'Ecoles Nationales Supérieures des Enseignants (ENS)', or teacher colleges. After recruiting graduates of teacher colleges, and in order to cover the remaining vacant positions, the regional directorates of education, following guidelines set by the MoNE, organise recruitment examinations for public university graduates with a bachelor's or master's degree in specific subject areas such as TEFL. This involves both a written and an oral examination. The written part consists of the speciality exam (EFL in this case), an Arabic language exam, culture exam and ICTs exam. Those who pass the

written part, then move to sit the oral exam, and those who pass this latter are then assigned a position as middle school teachers by the regional directorate of education at the chosen public middle school.

In their first-year teaching, both public university graduates who pass the recruitment examination and ENS graduates spend a one-year probationary period during which they receive a minimum of 15 hours mentoring at their schools or at a school within the same district by principal teachers or teacher mentors (Bellalem, 2008). Moreover, trainees at this stage are supposed to attend a preparatory pedagogical training. The content and duration of this pedagogical training are specified by the MoNE (as described in section 2.4.3). Throughout this period, subject inspectors regularly visit the trainees and attend some of their classes (Ouarzeddine, Gomatos and Ravanis, 2020), and by the end of it, trainees are evaluated by the subject inspector assigned to their schools, to be awarded a Qualified Teacher Status.

Teachers who obtain a Qualified Teacher Status are permanently recruited and could, then, seek promotion to positions, some of which are consistent with some positional teacher leadership roles outlined in previous research (see section 3.3.2). Within the Algerian context, two of the central positions that teachers could be promoted to, while maintaining their classroom teaching practices, are the position of a principal teacher and the position of a teacher mentor. Based on the responsibilities and roles that come with these positions, they are similar to the positional teacher leadership roles of team leaders and teacher mentors, respectively. Other positions that Algerian public-school teachers can be promoted to are subject inspector, school inspector, school principal and curriculum specialist. The latter is equally stressed in the existing literature as a positional teacher leadership role. In Algeria, promotion to these roles is primarily based on teachers' seniority and their length of teaching experience, following the MoNE's directives. Teachers promoted to the roles of a principal teacher, or a teacher mentor, have a lighter teaching load and receive additional remuneration. Those promoted to the positions of school or subject inspectors or curriculum specialists also receive additional remuneration; however, they have to move away from their classrooms to fulfil their roles. As the focus in this study is on teachers who maintain their classroom responsibilities, the sample included principal teachers and teacher mentors in addition to teachers who do not have a formal teacher leadership position. Guidelines set by the MoNE and implemented at the level of regional Directorates of Education for teachers' promotion to these positions and the additional responsibilities attached to them are outlined in more details below.

a. Position of a principal teacher:

Based on the description of responsibilities that come with this position, this is equivalent to the positional teacher leadership roles of a team leader and a teacher mentor. The ministerial executive

decree No. 08-315 of October 11, 2008 outlines the conditions for promotion to the position of a principal teacher based on seniority and on examination as follows:

- Middle school teachers who have ten years' experience teaching in middle schools are automatically promoted to the position of a principal teacher.
- Middle school teachers who have five years' experience teaching in middle schools are allowed to participate in the promotion examination. Those who pass the examination and selection process are promoted to the position of a principal teacher.

In addition to their responsibilities inside their classrooms, principal teachers, based on the executive decree No. 177 of March 02, 1991, must fulfil the following roles:

- Coordinate the work of teachers who teach all subjects in the same class.
- Follow up the behaviour, work and results of students in the same class in accordance with other teachers and regularly present that information to the school principal.
- Activate collective thinking among teachers within the same class to solve problems encountered by students or teachers themselves.
- Regularly organize meetings with all teachers of the class to discuss professional issues.
- Principal teachers of all classes of the same level must organize coordination and consultation meetings twice per semester.
- Participate in the disciplinary board of students belonging to the class they supervise.
- May be invited to participate, when necessary, in the meetings of the Administrative Coordination Council.
- If the number of teachers who meet the criteria of promotion to the position of middle school principal teacher is less than the number of classes in the institution, then one principal teacher will be assigned this position in one or two additional classes.
- Principal teachers working in schools that have no teacher mentors, or in cases when teacher mentors are on leave, are required to assume themselves the role of supervising and mentoring ENS students and novice teachers.

b. Position of a teacher mentor:

Within the existing knowledge base on teacher leadership, mentoring is explicitly referred to as a positional teacher leadership role by many researchers (Dozier, 2007; Gul, Demir and Criswell, 2019; Nguyen, Harris, and Ng, 2019; Wenner and Campbell, 2017; York-Barr and Duke, 2004). Dozier (2007) explains that mentoring is considered one of the positional teacher leadership roles as it entails providing professional support for peers and supporting less experienced teachers to transform their practices. Within the Algerian middle school context, the ministerial executive decree No. 08-315 of

October 11, 2008 sets the conditions for promotion to the position of a teacher mentor, based on seniority or on examination as follows:

- Middle school principal teachers possessing ten years of experience in the position of principal teachers are automatically promoted to the position of a teacher mentor.
- Middle school principal teachers possessing 5 years of experience as principal teachers are allowed to sit the promotion examination for the position of a teacher mentor.

In addition to their responsibilities as classroom teachers, middle school teacher mentors are required to:

- Supervise ENS students and novice teachers during their internship.
- Participate in framing, organising and evaluating in-service training programmes and their outcomes.
- Guarantee completion of support and make up activities for students.
- Coordinate with subject inspectors to plan, organise and deliver educational seminars and conferences for teachers.

2.5. The Place of English Language and English Language Teaching in Algeria

As it has been explained earlier in this chapter, Algeria is particularly characterised by its linguistic diversity, with French and English being the main two foreign languages in the country. Given the Algerian government's determination to erase traces of the French coloniser and to cope with the globalised world, several attempts have been made to eliminate the French language from the Algerian educational system, and English was seen as the most appropriate alternative. English language, then, gradually gained ground in Algeria.

When English was first introduced into Algerian schools, it was taught starting from grade 8 to pupils aged 13 years old. Some educators, however, insisted that studying English at such an advanced age would not be advantageous as learners may face difficulties to attain mastery of the language (Rezig, 2012), and therefore, suggested that English language should be integrated starting from the primary school level. Accordingly, and in an attempt to make a gradual transition from French to English, primary school pupils were permitted to choose between French and English as a mandatory foreign language in grade 4. However, this plan was unsuccessful as the majority of pupils' parents preferred French and obliged their children to choose it (ibid). According to Rezig (2012) the reason for this might be either because at that time English was still a new foreign language for parents, who believed that children would never use it in their social life within the Algerian context; or because the traces of the French language were still present and as such it seemed to be the only language to be used in future as it was the main foreign language already used at that time. At the

early stages of introducing English to Algerian schools, both national and foreign teachers were employed to teach English. The number of foreign teachers, however, remarkably decreased by 1986 after the oil crisis. Today, all the teaching staff, including EFL teachers, are Algerians (Bouhadiba, 2006).

More recently, following globalisation and in order for the country to stay on track with the developed countries, English secured a significant place as a foreign language in Algeria (Benadla, 2013). As per the educational system, promoting EFL teaching and learning in Algeria has become one of the core aspects of the most recent educational reforms. Alongside the increasing interest of Algerian people in the English language due to globalisation, the Algerian government has equally made great efforts to promote English and English language learning in the country mainly in light of the economic and political relations with the USA and the UK (Belmihoub, 2018). British institutions were, for instance, very active in promoting English learning in Algeria (ibid), and as part of the Algerian-British cooperation, an agreement was made between the Algerian government and that of the United Kingdom in 2014 to train 5 cohorts of Algerian PhD students (a total of 500 students) from different Algerian university English departments in UK universities (British Council, Algeria, nd), with the aim of providing research-based evidence to inform future educational policies and reforms directed to enhancing EFL teaching and learning in the country. The present research is sponsored by the Algerian government under this plan. More recently, in 2019, another agreement was signed with the University of Limerick, Ireland, to train another group of 400 PhD students. According to the Irish Times, the Algerian government's aim was 'to move from French to English as the official language of teaching and learning' (O'Brien, 2020, para. 2). Moreover, one of the most recent reform initiatives launched by the Algerian MoNE is centred on the introduction of English language at the primary school level starting from the third grade by the beginning of the school year 2023-2024. Although a similar preceding attempt to introduce English at primary school level was deemed unsuccessful as discussed earlier in this section, this most recent attempt seems to be more promising given the great reciprocity of English language among Algerians in recent years as compared to the immediate post-independence era.

Starting from the school year 2022-2023, English was introduced for third grade pupils across all public primary schools, although some nurseries and private schools often teach it to children at an even younger age. At middle school level, English is taught from grade 1 to grade 4 in which pupils aged 11 to 15 study English three times per week. At this level, pupils are required to learn the basics of the English language. The secondary school level represents a relatively different context than the middle school context in terms of teaching English. Within public secondary schools, the number of classes usually based on the stream the students are enrolled in. Students who opt for 'foreign

languages' stream, for instance, study English more extensively compared to those enrolled in experimental sciences, accounting, and mathematics. Learners at this level are introduced to the four language skills and to more detailed input related to grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, and phonology. By the end of secondary school level, pupils who obtain their Baccalaureate degree can choose English as a university major and study it for at least three years or can alternatively join teacher colleges to become EFL teachers at middle schools or secondary schools or lecturers at English Language Departments or teacher colleges depending on their university degree and available job opportunities.

2.6. Chapter Summary

This chapter provided an overview of the context in which the present research has been conducted, beginning broadly with a brief overview on Algeria, then narrowing the focus to discuss issues related to the Algerian educational system. The Algerian educational system has been subject to many reforms during the post-independence era. The series of reforms that the Algerian government constantly introduced to the educational system prove that this latter has always been 'at the core of the country's policy making efforts' (Gherzouli, 2019, p. 3). The initiated centralised reforms at each stage were indeed timely, addressing the country's particular and urgent needs at that given stage. Despite the significant improvements that these reforms brought mainly in terms of access to education, expenditure on education and restoring the Algerian national identity, fewer improvements have been noted in terms of the quality of the educational service in Algeria, a limitation that many researchers attributed to the marginalisation of teachers from decision-making processes and the perception of teachers as mere decision implementors. Indeed, Gherzouli (2019) and Messekher and Miliani (2017) argue that the main shortcoming of the educational system in the country is its centralisation and the marginalisation and exclusion of teachers from decision-making processes. The discussion in sections 2.4.2 and 2.4.3 in relation to the management structure of the Algerian educational system and the notably limited recognition of teachers' potential as leaders further support these arguments. This thesis, therefore, argues for a shift to a less centralised educational system that empowers teachers and provides them with more opportunities to practise their agency, participate in decision-making processes and contribute to leadership work. Examining teachers' own perspectives on teacher leadership, and exploring its potential barriers and supports within the Algerian context is required to facilitate such a shift. This constitutes the main focus of the current study, which aims to investigate teacher leadership within the Algerian context from the perspective of Algerian middle school EFL teachers, and eventually to contribute to the empowerment and recognition of teachers as change agents and as educational leaders rather than mere implementors of top-down decisions and policies within the study context. The following chapter provides a foundation for understanding the

concept of teacher leadership by reviewing relevant theoretical and empirical literature against which findings of the present study will be discussed.

Chapter Three: Review of the Literature

3.1. Introduction

While the previous chapter provided an overview of the research context, this chapter aims to situate the current study within the existing knowledge base on teacher leadership. To consult and review related research in the field, I used search engines from University of the West of Scotland (UWS) Library as well as Google Scholar, SAGE, Taylor & Francis, and ProQuest. I also searched in particular journals focused on research on educational leadership and management and teacher leadership such as: *International Journal of Teacher Leadership*, *Journal of Educational Management Administration and Leadership*, *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, and *Journal of School Leadership and Management*. In searching for relevant publications, I used key words or phrases including, but not exclusive to, ‘teacher leadership’, ‘teacher leader’, ‘change agents’ as well as country’s names particularly to search for relevant research in the Arab World. In searching for research conducted within the Algerian context, I consulted the archive for theses published by all Algerian universities. Following Nguyen, Harris and Ng’s (2019, p. 72) reference to what they termed ‘hidden literature’, that is literature produced in languages other than English, I also searched for any research published in Arabic, mainly within the Algerian context where no research published in English could have been identified, except for one study, Gherzouli (2019), which focused on one particular aspect relevant to teacher leadership. It was also useful to consult relevant references cited in each source I read. It is important to note that although for practical considerations, this study examines teacher leadership within the Algerian context, drawing on data obtained particularly from a sample of middle school EFL teachers, it does not assume that the field of TEFL represents a unique context that differs from contexts of other subjects when it comes to teacher leadership enactment. Therefore, this chapter provides a review of teacher leadership research at pre-university level, regardless of the teaching subject.

As for its structure, the chapter is organised into six broad sections, each involving further sub-sections, in addition to an introduction and a chapter summary. Section 3.2 provides an overview of the emergence and evolution of teacher leadership and its value. Section 3.3 conceptualises teacher leadership based on the review of existing theoretical and empirical research. Subsequently, section 3.4 addresses the factors that either support or hinder teacher leadership practice. This is followed by a discussion related to teacher leaders’ professional development, preparation and learning in section 3.5. Then section 3.6 provides a review and discussion of empirical research conducted within the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region with similar foci and aims as the present study, thus situating this study more specifically within the emerging field of teacher leadership research in the Arab World. Section 3.7 presents and discusses the conceptual framework that underpins this study.

The final section, section 3.8, summarises key aspects discussed throughout the chapter and highlights the knowledge gaps addressed by the present research.

3.2. Emergence of Teacher Leadership

This section seeks to explore the contexts in which teacher leadership has emerged, and as such it situates teacher leadership within broader discourses of ‘educational leadership’ (section 3.2.1) and ‘distributed leadership’ (section 3.2.2); and delineates the chronological stages of teacher leadership evolution (section 3.2.3).

3.2.1. Educational leadership

Educational leadership has attracted the attention of scholars and become a field of research and practice in its own right. Bush (2007) suggest that interest in educational leadership research has increased notably in the early part of the 21st century. Such an increased interest is mainly due to the common belief that the quality of school leadership is a significant factor that contributes to both students’ and schools’ outcomes. Regarding its impact on students’ learning, leadership is seen to be second only to classroom teaching given that almost all documented cases of schools provided evidence that proved the correlation between improved students’ achievement and talented school leadership (Leithwood, Harris and Hopkins, 2008). Revisiting and revising this claim over a decade later, Leithwood, Harris and Hopkins (2020) maintain that ‘school leadership has significant effects on features of the school organisation which positively influences the quality of teaching and learning. While moderate in size, this leadership effect is vital to the success of most school improvement efforts’ (p. 6).

Looking more broadly at the concept of ‘leadership’ and despite the increased interest in leadership research, consensus on a definition of this concept is still missing. The term leadership is often employed in both academic and common discourse (Gronn, 2003). Historically, other terms close in meaning included ‘power, authority, influence, manipulation, coercion, force and persuasion, still, leadership has always been the offspring among these terms due to the positive connotation it has’ (Gronn, 2003, p. 274). One of the clearest distinctions between management and leadership was provided by Cuban (1988) in which he relates leadership to change and management to stability or maintenance:

By leadership, I mean influencing others’ actions in achieving desirable ends. Leaders are people who shape the goals, motivations, and actions of others. Frequently they initiate change to reach existing and new goals... Leadership... takes... much ingenuity, energy and skill. Managing is maintaining efficiently and effectively current organisational arrangements. While managing well often exhibits leadership skills, the overall function is toward maintenance rather than change. I prize both managing and leading and attach no special value to either since different settings and times call for varied responses (p. 21)

Greenberg and Baron (1993) defined leadership as ‘the process whereby one person influences individual or group members towards goal setting and goal achievement with no force or coercion’ (p. 444). This definition seems to imply the existence of a leader-follower relationship. More recently, many scholars challenged this view arguing that leadership does not necessarily entail status or official authority and is not an entitlement of only one individual. Goddard (2003), for instance, argues that leadership is the act of collaborating with other individuals to accomplish shared goals. His view of leadership entails that no individual authority is required for such work and that decisions are made after listening to individuals with the most appropriate ideas, not necessarily with the highest official status. Such a view gave rise to a leadership style known as distributed leadership. In educational settings, distributed leadership challenged the traditionally held assumption that school principals are the sole leaders within schools (Oppi, Eisenschmidt and Stingu, 2023; Sheppard, Wolfinger and Talbert, 2021). Distributed leadership, in this sense, decentred school leadership from the one-leader perspective to a more participative and distributed leadership style (Bush and Glover, 2014), inviting all individuals working within schools to think of themselves as leaders (Harris, 2005; Hartley, 2010).

3.2.2. Distributed Leadership

As noted above, distributed leadership insinuated a re-conceptualisation of leadership as practice, challenging the widely held view that restricted leadership to specific roles or positions (Harris, Jones and Ismail, 2022). Bush (2013) stresses that ‘an important starting point for understanding [distributed leadership] is to uncouple it from positional authority. Leadership may arise anywhere in the organisation and is not confined to formal leaders’ (p. 543). Based on expanding leadership roles in educational institutions beyond those in formally designated positions, distributed leadership is one of the most influential ideas within the field of educational leadership (Harris, 2011). This new approach to leadership gained great popularity and attracted the attention of educational leadership scholars over time. Harris and Spillane (2008) attribute the increased interest in distributed leadership to three main reasons. First, distributed leadership has ‘a normative power; it reflects current changes in leadership practice in schools’ (ibid, p. 31). In order to cope with the expansion of leadership tasks within schools, leadership came to be distributed between different members of the school community. Second, the concept of distributed leadership also possesses a ‘representational power’ as it represents the ‘alternative approaches to leadership that have arisen because of increased external demands and pressures on schools’ (ibid). Distributed leadership seems to be better suited to the increasingly complex field of education as the traditional organisational structures are believed to be unable to meet the requirements of learning in recent times (ibid). Finally, distributed leadership has an ‘empirical power’. Research supports the significant effect of distributed leadership on both school organisation and students’ learning (Harris et al., 2007).

Harris (2013, p 12) stated that distributed leadership, by definition, refers to 'leadership that is shared within, between and across organisations'. However, as it is the case for any newly emerging concept or theory, different interpretations and definitions of distributed leadership exist resulting in various conceptual confusions (Torrance, 2013), yet certain criteria often differentiate it from other leadership approaches (Harris and DeFlaminis, 2016). First, distributed leadership puts great emphasis on leadership as a practice rather than a designated position or role (Spillane and Diamond, 2007). In this sense, it is first and foremost concerned with leadership practice rather than leaders' roles and characteristics (Spillane, 2006). Second, it gives greater importance to interaction rather than to individual actions (Harris and DeFlaminis, 2016). From a distributed leadership perspective, any staff member of the educational system is able and has the right to practise leadership. Decision-making is the result of interaction between all those individuals, and it is this interaction process that matters for distributed leadership. Notably, while Hartley (2010, p. 27) argues that 'its popularity may be pragmatic' given that it relieves the burden of overworked school principals, Bush (2013, p. 543) maintains that its merit goes beyond such 'instrumental motive', being an approach that recognises the value of utilising all the available expertise within an organisation.

Despite its popularity, distributed leadership has been accompanied by critique and controversy. Harris and DeFlaminis (2016) argued that 'As with any new idea, it was both enthusiastically greeted by some and soundly dismissed by others' (p. 141). One area of criticism was the lack of consensus on a definition of this concept. Despite this being a limitation, the lack of one clear definition of distributed leadership has not actually hindered research in this area or negatively affected interest in it. Additionally, although distributed leadership may have positive effects, it can also underestimate and obscure institutions' power dynamics by neglecting the importance of competition while stressing collaboration and partnership (Bolden, 2011). Harris (2013) cautions that as with any other leadership approach, distributed leadership might also have 'a dark side' in case power, authority or influence are misused.

Another concern was raised by Torrance (2013) whose study stressed the discrepancies between theoretical and policy-based assumptions of distributed leadership and its actual practice within schools. Data collected from school principals and staff provided evidence that, according to the author, challenged five generally held assumptions of distributed leadership. First and second are the assumptions that every individual within an institution is able to lead or wishes to lead. The third assumption is that leadership roles of other staff members are legitimised simply by school principals' endorsement. The fourth assumption is that a distributed approach to leadership occurs naturally. The final generally held assumption is that a distributed approach is not problematic. Findings from Torrance's (2013) research indicate that distributed leadership across the three schools that she studied

did not occur naturally, rather it was carefully and purposefully planned by the three school headteachers, taking over two years to be effectively implemented. Likewise, certain issues and tensions emerged when a distributed approach was implemented within the three schools. These included feelings of anxiety; friction between school staff; and attitudes of resistance from the part of some school staff to either take on leadership roles or to accept leadership roles of other members. One school principal in her study equally raised a concern regarding the balance between her own control and staff autonomy. In this sense, Harris (2013) stresses the importance of maintaining a balance of control to ensure that formal leaders' efforts to make improvements are not disrupted or undermined by another individual or another group within the organisation. Another issue is that distributed leadership research usually focusses more on formal leaders and less on interaction between individuals and relations both within and outside organisations (Bolden, 2011).

Despite those critiques, distributed leadership remains an influential approach within educational leadership research and practice (Harris and DeFlaminis, 2016), as well as a resilient and practical concept (Harris 2013). Harris and Jones (2020) argue that distributed leadership, unlike many other leadership theories or styles, has proved its effectiveness and has arguably witnessed a renaissance during the Covid-19 era, when leadership practice become largely remote, virtual, and inevitably distributed. More importantly, many researchers stress that it is through distributed leadership that teachers' potential to assume leadership responsibilities was accentuated. In this sense, Hallinger and Heck (2009) explain that the concept of distributed leadership is particularly attractive to policymakers who seek to involve the teaching staff in school leadership regardless of their formal positions. Similarly, both Harris (2005) and Poekert (2012) stress that literature on distributed leadership enlightens and supports what is known about teacher leadership.

3.2.3. Evolution of Teacher Leadership

The history of teacher leadership can be traced back to 1903 as it first appeared (though implicitly) in John Dewey's writing, in which he argued that it is crucial that every teacher has 'some regular and representative way to register judgement upon matters of educational importance, with assurance that this judgement would somehow affect the school system' (p. 195, cited in Danielson, 2006, p. 16). Danielson (2006) explains that an important aspect of Dewey's advocacy of democratic societies was manifested in his advocacy of democratic schools. That is, in addition to teachers' role in enhancing student learning, Dewey insisted on democratising schools in a way that enables teachers to engage in leadership work that would contribute to increasing school capacity and efficacy.

Although the evolution of the concept cannot be viewed in terms of a strict chronological timeline, Silva, Gimbert and Nolan (2000) argue that it continued to evolve through three main waves. These three waves provide a clearer understanding into the way in which the concept and its practice

have developed, suggesting a continuum from formal to informal teacher leadership. Indeed, Pounder (2006) maintains that the three waves that delineate teacher leadership development gradually delinked this concept from the formal hierarchical structures within educational institutions.

In more recent times, the concept emerged as part of the educational reforms implemented in the United States of America in the 1980s in response to the several top-down reforms in the 1960s and 1970s, representing a means for decentralisation and school improvement (Smylie, Conley and Marks, 2002). This first wave of teacher leadership development, beginning in the early 1980s, restricted the practice of teacher leadership to managerial and formal roles and positions such as master teachers, department heads, and union representatives (Silva, Gimbert and Nolan, 2000). Within this first phase, teachers assumed formal leadership positions as they were promoted from their teaching position to the position of a department head, for instance (Harris, 2005) and were removed from their classrooms to fulfil these formal roles. The main criticism of this first wave was that it implied top-down structures and promoted a hierarchical and bureaucratic school culture, leading to the separation between promoted leaders and teachers. Teacher leaders were given the right to control the work of other teachers who were viewed as mere implementers of the imposed decisions and policies. In this sense, teachers promoted to leadership positions were perceived as only an extension of traditional administrative staff whose major role was to maintain change and ensure its efficacy, rather than actually initiate it. Arguably, Harris and Muijs (2004) report that teacher leaders at this stage were ‘representatives of change rather than leaders who enact or initiate change’ (p. 16).

The restricted roles of teachers in the first wave paved the way for the emergence of the second wave of teacher leadership, which acknowledged the fundamental role of teachers as pedagogical and instructional leaders (Silva Gimbert and Nolan, 2000). Teachers were formally promoted to assume instructional leadership positions based on their pedagogical knowledge and expertise (Harris, 2005). Thus, teacher leaders moved from exclusively functioning in managerial roles towards more participative instructional roles. These instructional leadership roles, similar to the managerial roles in the first wave, remained formal in nature including positions such as team leaders, professional development specialists, curriculum designers, and teacher mentors (Silva, Gimbert and Nolan, 2000). Teacher leadership practice within this wave was also subject to criticism, mainly at two levels. First, the school culture at this stage remained hierarchical. Control was in the hands of instructional leaders who often created ‘pre-packaged materials’ that classroom teachers had to implement (Pounder, 2006, p. 534). Second, such an approach to leadership was centred on pedagogical and instructional positions that were ‘apart from’ rather than ‘a part of’ teachers’ daily work (Silva, Gimbert and Nolan, 2000, p. 780).

The third wave began in the mid-1990s and is considered the emerging form of teacher leadership (Wilson, 2016; York-Barr and Duke, 2004). At this stage, the notions of teaching and leadership were integrated, and the concept of teacher leadership was transformed from formal appointed positions into informal activities of teachers regardless of their positions and based on their professionalism and collegiality (Silva, Gimbert and Nolan, 2000; Pounder, 2006). Contrary to the two preceding waves, teacher leadership in this wave is perceived to be part of teachers' daily work mainly with the aim of improving the teaching practice and contributing to educational reforms. In this third phase, teachers are viewed as central to the process of initiating and leading change based on their instructional and collaborative skills and expertise regardless of their positions (Harris, 2005). Teachers are, therefore, supposed to exchange knowledge and expertise, collaborate with each other, and assist colleagues with professional development activities and to develop an environment of trust and support within the institution (Silva, Gimbert and Nolan, 2000). Thus, the basis for this new approach to teacher leadership is collective and collaborative tasks carried out by teachers rather than the roles that they individually perform of the positions to which they are promoted. Despite the positive effects of such collaborative school cultures, complete implementation of this approach was not always possible, as the distribution of leadership power remains top-down. Silva, Gimbert and Nolan (2000) argue, however, that despite being frequently disempowered through top-down policies, teachers, in this wave, could lead from within their classrooms through informal teacher leadership practices.

Pounder (2006) identified a fourth wave, which he termed 'transformational classroom leadership'. This fourth wave highlights the professional and intellectual perspectives of leadership within the classroom and emphasises their crucial effect on students' learning. It suggests that as a means towards teachers' empowerment, teachers should be given space to practise leadership within their classrooms regardless of their formal position. Transformational teacher leadership views teachers as leaders who lead by example. Being exemplary professionals within their classrooms, teachers inspire their students and can positively influence them, resulting in enhanced learning, innovation and creativity, and installing ethical behaviour (Pounder, 2006). This fourth wave, however, focused on the role of teachers as leaders within their classrooms, yet neglected their role beyond their classroom context as well as the importance of developing a culture of professional collegiality and collaboration between teachers and with other members of the educational institution.

3.3. What is Teacher Leadership?

The review of the existing literature indicates a lack of consensus as to how teacher leadership is defined as various definitions have surfaced in existing research. To this end, an overview of these competing and overlapping definitions of the construct is provided in section 3.3.1, followed by a

discussion of positional and non-positional teacher leadership roles; teacher leaders' traits and skills; and the impact of teacher leadership practice in sections 3.3.2, 3.3.3 and 3.3.4 respectively.

3.3.1. Overlapping and Competing Definitions of Teacher Leadership

Despite the growing interest in teacher leadership, a clear and agreed-upon definition of the concept is still to date missing (Schott, van Roekel and Tummers, 2020; Wenner and Campbell, 2017). Indeed, several authors have proposed various definitions of the concept (Muijs and Harris, 2003). York-Barr and Duke (2004) attribute such variation and confusion to 'the expansive territory encompassed under the umbrella term 'teacher leadership'' (p. 260). They explain that teacher leadership involves a variety of work with different members of the school community, and that it operates at different levels: the organisational, the instructional and the professional. Similarly, this concept is further complicated because teacher leaders often do not hold identical titles, or any titles at all, across schools and often perform different roles depending on the school context (Cooper et al., 2016). Thus, what further complicates conceptualisations of teacher leadership is that teacher leaders may function in different roles and hold different positions. Despite such variations, a review of the various interpretations and definitions of teacher leadership can still provide better insights into the concept and enhance our understanding of it.

One of the most widely cited definitions of teacher leadership is that of York-Barr and Duke (2004). Based on a meta-analysis of teacher leadership research conducted between 1980 and 2004, York-Barr and Duke provided an integrated definition of the concept, stating that:

Teacher leadership is the process by which teachers, individually or collectively, influence their colleagues, principals and other members of school communities to improve teaching and learning practices with the aim of increased student learning and achievement. (p. 287-288)

This definition foregrounds four important features of the concept. First, the practice of teacher leadership influence can be either individual or collective, though the latter approach seems to be more relevant to the emerging form of teacher leadership advocated throughout recent years. Teacher leadership is, therefore, collaborative in the sense that teacher leaders work together with their peers and with other members in the educational system for the sake of achieving goals; addressing challenges and problems; and improving instructional practices (Hunzicker, 2022). Second, teacher leadership is a process of influence. In a more recent review of teacher leadership research conducted between 2003 and 2017, Nguyen, Harris and Ng (2019) further supported this view, stressing that most definitions explained teacher leadership in terms of influence rather than a formal role or position. Thus, teacher leadership is perceived as a process of change and teachers as change agents (ibid). Indeed, most of the conceptualisations of teacher leadership found in the literature refer to teacher leadership in terms of reciprocal and mutual influence and collegiality rather than imposition and authority. For instance, Bangs and MacBeath (2012) emphasise that teacher leadership commonly

relates mainly to teachers' 'collegial influence with colleagues, with curriculum development and policymaking within or across schools' (p. 331). Similarly, Murphy (2005) maintains that teacher leadership is particularly a matter of collegial influence that aims at improving professional practices. Likewise, Anderson (2004) suggests that teacher leadership is a process of interaction between leaders and followers, with mutual influence between the two in which followers and leaders may at times blend or change roles. Third, the collaborative practice of teacher leadership occurs within a community, namely the educational setting. Harris (2007) asserts that the community aspect of teacher leadership is one of the most recurrent themes in much of the existing literature. Fourth, the main goal of teacher leadership practice, based on York-Barr and Duke's (2004) definition, is to enhance students' learning and achievement. This view is reiterated by Hunzicker (2022) who argues that a key feature of teacher leadership is that it is student-centred as teacher leaders work particularly towards enhancing students' learning and ensuring their well-being. The review of the international literature on teacher leadership conducted by Wenner and Campbell (2017) equally revealed that most definitions of the concept refer to the goal of teacher leadership. Specifically, the authors explain that apart from increasing student learning, most definitions emphasise that teacher leadership targets improvements of educational practice and schools as a whole. Nguyen, Harris and Ng (2019) similarly assert that within the studies that they reviewed, teacher leadership was most commonly defined in terms of its impact and outcomes. The authors reported that the outcomes of teacher leadership related to improved instructional practices (Smith, Hayes and Lyons, 2017; Taylor et al., 2011); enhanced school efficacy (Angelle and Teague, 2014; Chew and Andrews, 2010); and improved student learning (Eckert, Ulmer, Khachatryan and Ledesma, 2016). Further details on the impact of teacher leadership are provided in section 3.3.4.

Another important aspect emanating from the literature is that the practice of teacher leadership is not restricted to the classroom context. Defining teacher leadership, Katzenmeyer and Moller (2001, p. 17) suggest that 'teachers who are leaders lead within and beyond the classroom, identify with and contribute to a community of teacher learners and leaders, and influence others toward improved educational practice'. Cooper et al. (2016) contend that despite the varied conceptualisations of teacher leadership, most scholars agree that teacher leadership can take place both within and outside classrooms to influence schools' instructional practice. Similarly, Margolis (2012) presents the notion of a 'hybrid teacher leader', which he explained as 'a teacher whose official schedule includes both teaching K-12 students and leading teachers in some capacity' (p. 292). Resonating with all these views, Öqvist and Malmström (2018) assert that teacher leadership behaviour is 'a mobilisation of the available attributes of teachers to influence students at the ground level during their daily activities at school, within and outside of the classroom, and beyond' (p. 5).

Participation in decision-making is yet another aspect relevant to the conceptualisation of teacher leadership within the existing literature. Muijs and Harris (2007) conducted a study that aims to investigate the various ways in which teacher leadership is manifested within schools in the United Kingdom (UK). To this end, they operationalised teacher leadership as ‘increased teacher participation in decision-making, and opportunities for teachers to take initiative and lead school improvement’ (p. 113). Likewise, Muijs and Harris (2003) conducted a review of the literature on teacher leadership in which they stressed that central to the concept of teacher leadership are the two concepts of ‘empowerment’ and ‘agency’. Defining teacher leadership with reference to teacher empowerment is highly frequent in the literature (Lieberman and Friedrich, 2010). Teacher empowerment entails a shift from a centralised to a decentralised school culture through distributing power between all members of the school community including teachers. As for agency, Harris and Muijs (2004) explained teacher leadership as agency that empowers teachers to assume leadership work with other members of the school community. In a similar vein, Bangs and MacBeath (2012, p. 331) maintained that teacher leadership, most typically, ‘refers to teachers’ individual agency, often with reference to classroom management and pedagogy’. Lai and Cheung (2015) suggest that two main examples of teachers’ agency are decision-making and initiating activities. These two examples relate directly to Muijs and Harris’ (2007) definition of teacher leadership discussed earlier in this section. An important issue worth reflecting on in relation to such definitions that relate teacher leadership to decision-making is the extent of decision-making power that teacher leaders possess as participation in decision-making may not necessarily imply actually possessing decision-making power. Based on analysis of policy documents across three countries (Colombia, Mexico and Spain) with the aim of exploring conceptualisations of teamwork as an essential aspect of teacher leadership, one of the main findings reported by Pineda-Báez, Fierro-Evans and Gratacós (2023), for instance, was that although teachers across the three settings were invited to share their opinions when implementing plans, their participation seemed to remain peripheral as it did not necessarily imply possessing decision-making power in relation to important school matters, with the exception of pedagogical matters.

The range of definitions of teacher leadership that emerged from the reviewed literature indicate that it is a multi-faceted and situational construct. As it has been shown, some of the core aspects that most definitions of this construct often refer to are the roles of teacher leaders, their characteristics and skills and teacher leaders’ ultimate goals or impact within their schools and beyond. Each of these aspects will be subsequently addressed in more details in sections 3.3.2, 3.3.3, and 3.3.4. Notably, most of the existing and widely recognised definitions and conceptualisations of teacher leadership emerge particularly from Western contexts, specifically from the USA and the UK. Perspectives from non-western contexts remain notably limited. It is, therefore, important to highlight

that while the current review has provided insights into the various conceptualisations of teacher leadership as found in previous related research, this study, while acknowledging that teacher leadership should not be restricted to the classroom context nor to formal positions of authority, does not adopt any one specific definition, but rather seeks to arrive at a conceptualisation of teacher leadership that is context-specific and relevant to the Algerian context through investigating the various perceptions of teacher leadership from the perspectives of a sample of Algerian middle school EFL teachers.

3.3.2. Positional and Non-Positional Teacher Leadership

The Teacher Leadership Exploratory Consortium (2008) defines a teacher leader as ‘a teacher who assumes, formally or informally, one or more of a wide array of leadership roles to support school and student success’ (p. 37). This definition implies that teacher leadership falls into two main broad categories, namely formal and informal teacher leadership. Referring to the preceding discussion in relation to the evolution of teacher leadership (section 3.2.3), it could be noted that the three waves of teacher leadership evolution represent a continuum from formal to more informal teacher leadership. While within the first two waves, teacher leadership was perceived in terms of formal administrative and instructional positions, it is within the third wave that understanding of the concept shifted in a way that incorporates practices that are more informal.

Formal teacher leadership is generally conceptualised as role-based (Murphy, 2005). That is, formal teacher leaders gain legitimacy and power due to their designated position of authority. In order for teachers to take on a formal leadership position, they often go through a selection and promotion process, and once they are selected or promoted, they usually receive training to be able to assume their leadership role (Danielson, 2007). The selected teachers usually possess the necessary professional qualifications, and in some cases receive additional remuneration for their leadership role (King, 2017). Formal teacher leaders may take on a variety of roles, depending on the various situational educational needs (Taylor et al., 2011). In general, formal teacher leaders assume pedagogical and managerial responsibilities (Muijs, Chapman and Armstrong, 2013). More specifically, they can function as department heads (Leithwood and Jantzi, 2000; York-Barr and Duke, 2004), union representatives (Leithwood and Jantzi, 2000), master teachers (Carver and Meier, 2013), curriculum specialists and team leaders (Harrison and Killion, 2007; York-Barr and Duke, 2004), and mentors (Gul, Demir, and Criswell, 2019; Nguyen, Harris and Ng, 2019; Wenner and Campbell, 2017). Formal teacher leaders often move away from the classroom to assume their roles as full-time leaders but might also undertake part-time duties along with a lighter teaching load.

According to York-Barr and Duke (2004), exclusive focus on formal teacher leadership may contradict the egalitarian relations between peers, creating hierarchies between the teaching staff,

which in turn may result in conflict and distance between formal teacher leaders and their colleagues. They further suggest that teacher leaders perform better and are more capable of influencing their peers when they are not seen as formal leaders within a given hierarchy. Similarly, most of the existing literature on distributed leadership (Harris, 2003; Spillane and Diamond, 2007) shows that teachers who are not assigned a formal leadership position carry out a substantial proportion of school leadership activities. Teachers often perceive themselves as leaders particularly when leadership is defined as a participatory and collaborative process, rather than a formal position (Lambert, 2003). Von Dohlen and Karvonen (2018) similarly assert that teacher leaders often evolve through informal leadership practices. Informal teacher leadership is, accordingly, a community-based concept, and an emergent and collaborative activity that focuses primarily on improving teaching and learning (Murphy, 2005). It implies conceptualising teacher leadership ‘as a professional stance that all teachers can draw upon’ (Carver and Meier, 2013, p. 175). This view aligns well with Frost (2017) who suggests that:

[All] educational practitioners can exercise leadership as a dimension of their professionalism rather than by virtue of a designated formal role in their schools provided that they have the right kind of support. (p.1)

Teachers, therefore, engage in informal leadership practices regardless of their position, but rather based on their collegiality and professionalism. Rather than being officially selected to be leaders, informal teacher leaders emerge spontaneously and often deliberately take the initiative to enact change (Frost and Durrant, 2003; Danielson, 2007). Their influence emanates from their collegial relationships with their peers and from the trust, respect, and credibility that they gain due to their expertise (Murphy, 2005, Danielson, 2007). In this regard, Katzenmeyer and Moller (2009) assert that:

drawing from their expertise and passion for teaching, [informal teacher leaders] influence other teachers...through having casual conversations, sharing materials, facilitating professional development, or simply extending an invitation for other teachers to visit their classrooms (p. 7).

While it might be feasible to delineate a list of teachers’ formal teacher leadership roles, it could be rather difficult to provide a similar list of all the self-initiated work that teachers undertake as part of informal teacher leadership. Overall, informal teacher leadership is not necessarily limited to the classroom context as it often involves practices beyond classrooms. Findings from previous research suggested that within the classrooms, informal teacher leadership is often manifested in activities such as planning, communicating, and achieving goals and objectives; organising and regulating activities; supervising learners and evaluating their performance; and creating and maintaining a suitable learning environment (Greenier and Whitehead, 2016; Tahir et al., 2021). Chien (2020) conducted an exploratory study of ten Taiwanese elementary school English teachers’ perceptions of teacher leaders and leadership. Drawing on data obtained through document analysis,

interviews and questionnaires, findings suggested that participant teachers perceived teacher leadership in terms of instruction and the teaching profession rather than teachers' formal position. Participants, in this sense, particularly stressed classroom-based practices such as innovative teaching, observing learners and providing feedback as essential teacher leadership practices within the classroom context. Another study in the Vietnamese context by Nguyen, Huynh and Tran (2022) more specifically related teacher leadership inside the classroom to pedagogical innovation, reporting that participant EFL teachers enacted leadership within their classrooms by creating a suitable learning environment for their learners; adapting textbooks to meet learners' characteristics; and engaging their learners in diverse classroom activities. A recent review of teacher leadership research by Achach-Sonda and Cisneros-Cohernour (2023) reiterated and expanded these findings. The authors reviewed empirical teacher leadership research to understand the ways in which teacher leaders enhance students' learning and outcomes, and concluded that within their classrooms, teacher leaders attend to their learners' needs and interests by designing and implementing innovative and attractive teaching strategies; adopting differentiated instructional approaches; and providing personalised assistance for learners.

Findings from previous studies equally highlight various activities that teacher leaders could engage in beyond their classrooms, regardless of their positions. Oppi, Eisenschmidt and Stingu (2023), for instance, explored teacher leadership understanding and manifestation among a group of 16 teachers and five principals from five schools in Estonia. Data obtained through semi-structured interviews revealed that participants acknowledge both formal and informal teacher leadership. Findings specifically highlighted informal teacher leadership practices beyond the classroom including working with peers to improve their instructional practices; taking initiative to promote professional development ideas; functioning as role models for colleagues; sharing knowledge and experiences with peers; and engaging in professional discussions to generate innovative ideas and to offer solutions to problems raised by the school management team. Some participants in Chien's (2020) study shared similar views as they perceived modelling instructional innovation sharing and discussing classroom practices with peers as an important aspect of informal teacher leadership work beyond the classroom context. For those teachers, such practices were perceived not only to support colleagues' professional growth but also to enhance students' academic outcomes. Other practices highlighted in previous research include encouraging others (Greenier and Whitehead, 2016) and encouraging parents and community involvement (Oracion, 2014).

Apart from attempts in distinguishing between formal and informal teacher leadership, some authors raised an issue of terminology. Frost and Durrant (2003), in particular, criticised the use of the term 'informal' to refer to teachers practising leadership without having a formal position. They

suggest that the term ‘informal’ may be understood to mean a lack of legitimacy in practising leadership, while in fact, it merely implies the absence of an appointed leadership position and not of leadership practice. Frost (2014), accordingly, suggests referring to leadership by non-appointed teachers as ‘non-positional teacher leadership’. The terms ‘positional’ and ‘non-positional’ were proposed to distinguish between formally designated teacher leaders and self-directed teachers who take initiative to affect change at the personal, professional, and organisational levels (Frost, 2012; Frost and Durrant, 2003). According to Frost (2014), the non-positional approach to leadership challenges traditional schools’ hierarchies and perceives leadership as practice rather than a designated formal position.

Central to the non-positional understanding of teacher leadership is the perception of leadership as an opportunity available for all teachers regardless of their formal delegation (Bangs and Frost, 2016). This does not necessarily imply that all teachers must take on leadership responsibilities, but that leadership practice must be facilitated for all teachers who are willing to undertake it (Qanay et al., 2019). It is, accordingly, a deliberate, systematic, self-willed, and values-based activity that requires collaboration between all school members within a conducive environment, aiming to impact teaching and learning at the immediate classroom level, and broadly at the school and system levels (Bangs and Frost, 2016). It also depends greatly on teachers’ moral purpose, commitment, and agency (Frost, 2018). Indeed, Frost (2012) defines non-positional teacher leadership by relating it directly to the development of teachers’ agency:

[Non-positional teacher leadership is] the process whereby teachers can clarify their values, develop a personal vision of improved practice and then act strategically to set in motion a process where colleagues are drawn into activities such as self-evaluation and innovation. This is truly about the enhancing of human agency and the development of a culture of shared responsibility for reforms and the outcomes for all students. (p. 211).

As for the current research, the terms ‘positional’ and ‘non-positional’ are respectively used to refer to appointed and non-appointed teacher leaders. The sample for this research consists of both positional teacher leaders and teachers who do not hold a positional teacher leadership role. Positional teacher leaders, selected for participation in this study, are teachers who are promoted to undertake leadership roles along with their roles and responsibilities as classroom teachers.

3.3.3. Traits and Skills of Teacher Leaders

While teacher leaders can be defined with reference to the roles that they assume within and beyond their schools as discussed in the previous section, they are also usually described in the existing literature in terms of their qualities and the set of skills that they possess. This section provides a synthesis of the most recurrent qualities and skills of teacher leaders that surfaced in the reviewed literature.

In terms of characteristics, some authors argue that most of the qualities of effective classroom teachers are also fundamental qualities for teacher leaders. These may, for instance, involve being knowledgeable about students and subject matter, being dedicated, possessing teamwork abilities, and being good communicators (The Institute for Educational Leadership, Inc, 2011). More specifically, Katzenmeyer and Moller (2011) stress three main qualities of teacher leaders: competence, credibility, and approachability. This view resonates to some extent with Von Dohlen and Karvonen (2018) and Oracion (2014) who found that teacher leaders were perceived as excellent teachers who are respected by their colleagues. Teacher leaders' competence is generally reflected in their classroom practices, their pedagogical knowledge and expertise and classroom management skills. Teacher leaders' competence, expertise and effectiveness are what gain them credibility, recognition, and respect among their peers (Oracion, 2014; York-Barr and Duke, 2004), yet only teachers who are approachable are able to pass on their experiences and knowledge to their colleagues and thus can influence them towards improved instructional practices (Katzenmeyer and Moller, 2011). Notably, given the emphasis on teachers' expertise, teacher leadership has long been associated with experienced teachers. Many studies, however, advocate novice teachers' potential to exercise leadership. Levenson (2014), for instance, maintains that when novice teachers begin their careers, they demonstrate high levels of passion, ambition, and desire to contribute to educational improvements both within and beyond their classrooms. Muijs, Chapman and Armstrong (2013) equally noted that novice teachers are keen to engage in teacher leadership both in its positional and non-positional forms. These views resulted in increased interest in preparing prospective teachers for teacher leadership roles as part of their pre-service teacher education programmes (more details in section 3.5.1).

Teacher leaders are also described as self-driven, learning-oriented individuals who take initiative and assume responsibility for their own learning and professional growth (Oracion, 2014; van der Heijden, 2015; York-Barr and Duke, 2004). As part of their life-long learning, teachers reflect on their teaching practices and lived experiences and constantly search for information and ideas to improve and refine their practice (York-Barr and Duke, 2004).

Furthermore, effective teacher leaders are teachers who have a strong sense of purpose and sense of self (Lambert, 2003). Maintaining a strong sense of purpose implies teachers being aware of their purpose and roles as leaders within their schools, and thus are inquisitive in their practices, assume responsibility for students' learning and possess a strong sense of self (Lambert, 2003). Teachers with a strong sense of self, in turn, recognise their value and do not feel intimidated by other people's inactions (ibid). Dozier (2007) additionally argues that teacher leaders are confident teachers who actively seek to engage in leadership activities.

Another important trait of teacher leaders emerging from the literature is collaboration (van Der Heijden et al., 2015; Oppi, Eisenschmidt and Stingu, 2023). Pantic and Florian (2015) argue that teachers who are advocates of change both within and beyond their classrooms are required to develop their relational agency. Teacher leaders are, thus, ‘effective communicators with strong interpersonal skills, and have a collaborative orientation toward working with others’ (York-Barr and Duke, 2004, p. 15). Teachers’ motivation, resilience, passion, sense of commitment, sense of empowerment, and desire for change and improvement have also been identified in previous research as central qualities of teacher leaders (Oppi, Eisenschmidt and Stingu, 2023; Oracion, 2014; van der Heijden et al., 2015). Further characteristics of teacher leaders are identified by many researchers. Teacher leaders are, accordingly, reliable, trustworthy, and have a sense of humour (Bond, 2011), as well as being empathic and considerate (Oppi, Eisenschmidt and Stingu, 2023).

Jackson, Burrus, Bassett and Roberts (2010) highlighted the key personal skills of teacher leaders by synthesising findings from previous studies on teacher leadership. This enabled them to identify teacher leaders’ personal skills, and accordingly developed a framework that organises the emergent skills into eight categories. These categories are work ethic, openness, teamwork, leadership, vision, risk-taking, positive affect, and teaching-related skills.

3.3.4. Impact of Teacher Leadership

According to York-Barr and Duke (2004), various claims regarding the desired and possible outcomes of teacher leadership exist in the literature; however, evidence that support such claims remains to date relatively limited. Overall, the review of the literature reveals that teacher leadership has effects on teacher leaders themselves, school principal and fellow teachers, student learning, and the school culture, organisational capacity and reforms as a whole.

Research suggests that teacher leadership has particularly remarkable effects on those who practise it. Arguably, York-Barr and Duke (2004) posit that ‘the strongest effects of teacher leadership have been on teacher leaders themselves’ (p. 282). Participation in school leadership is reported to provide chances for ongoing learning, particularly as teachers engage in coaching, instructional leadership, and curriculum development (Harrison and Killion, 2007). Barth (2001) supports this view stating that teachers’ participation in school leadership and decision-making processes is a valuable learning opportunity, and that teachers engage more actively in learning in schools where they work as leaders. Furthermore, more recent research suggests that as teachers engage in leadership work, they feel less isolated, more personally and professionally satisfied, with an increased sense of instrumentality and membership in their school communities, as well as increased knowledge about change processes, about schools and about themselves, which positively affect their classroom practice (Barth, 2001). Engaging teachers in leadership work and providing them with opportunities

to lead change and to engage in decision-making within their schools were equally perceived by teachers in different studies to significantly enhance their job satisfaction (Chew and Andrews, 2010; Oppi, Eisenschmidt and Stingu, 2023; Wang and Ho, 2020). Improvements in teachers' self-esteem and job satisfaction were, in turn, perceived to result in higher retention rates in the teaching profession (Wang and Ho, 2020). Moreover, teacher leadership positively affects teachers' sense of agency, which is described by Frost (2006) as the capacity to make a difference. As teachers engage in leadership work, their leadership knowledge and skills improve (Wenner and Campbell, 2017), and they feel more committed, confident, and empowered (Oppi, Eisenschmidt and Stingu, 2023).

Research suggests, however, that assuming leadership roles may also negatively influence teacher leaders. Some teachers in Baecher's (2012) study, for instance, reported feeling overwhelmed, uncomfortable, and stressed when leading peers for change and professional growth. Additionally, Wenner and Campbell (2017) emphasise that teacher leaders may feel pressures, trying to balance between their leadership responsibilities and their classroom teaching. Such feelings may result from certain internal and external factors. As for the internal factors, teachers may face difficulties in balancing between the leader role and the teacher role, and they may be uncertain about the nature of their leadership roles or insufficiently prepared for leadership work (Baecher, 2012). As for the external factors, they relate to fellow teachers' attitudes and the shift in the nature of teacher leaders' relationships with their colleagues (Margolis, 2012).

Through teacher leadership practice, teachers could equally influence other members of the school community, namely school principals and fellow teachers. The main premise of teacher leadership is that schools are too complex to be managed by a school principal, thus, it is necessary to incorporate teachers in school leadership work. This view resonates with findings from Muijs and Harris (2006) that teacher leadership is essential for school improvement as 'it was seen to harness teacher creativity and devolve work and responsibility from the head' (p. 965). Similarly, Barth (2001) maintains that teacher leadership extends headteacher capacity by reducing their workload.

Teacher leaders could similarly influence their colleagues in multiple ways. First, research has shown that one of the primary roles of teacher leaders is promoting the professional development and learning of their peers. A study by Pan and Chen (2021) in the Taiwanese context examined the relationship between teacher and principal leadership and teachers' professional learning. Data collected from 1340 teachers indicated that teacher leadership directly affected teachers' learning as teacher leaders with extended expertise in subject area and instruction often share knowledge, exchange ideas with peers and establish learning communities. Teacher leadership in this study was found to exhibit a greater direct effect on teachers' learning than did principal leadership. In the USA,

Supovitz (2018), drawing on data obtained through interviews with 48 leadership team members across eight schools, equally reported that teacher leaders were perceived to enhance instructional practices of their peers by employing various ‘soft strategies’. Those teachers supported their peers to grow professionally and to enhance their instructional practices through leading by example; collaborating with colleagues and encouraging them; and being available as a resource to fellow teachers. Additionally, Angelle and Teague (2014) argue that a significant correlation exists between teacher leadership and teachers’ collective efficacy. Collective efficacy refers to ‘the perceptions of teachers in a school that the faculty as a whole can organize and execute the courses of action required to have a positive effect on students’ (Goddard and Goddard, 2001, p. 809). In a quantitative study examining the relationship between teacher leadership and collective teacher efficacy in Chinese upper secondary schools, Liu (2020) reported positive effects of teacher leadership on collective teacher efficacy. More specifically, autonomy, collegiality, development focus, positive environment, and open communication were the main teacher leadership dimensions found to enhance collective teacher efficacy (ibid).

Teacher leaders can also exert influence at the school’s organisational level (Nguan, Harris and Ng, 2019) and may even extend their influence beyond their schools and into the whole district (Danielson, 2007). Harris (2003), for instance, explains that teacher leadership can support a more democratic school environment. Moreover, teacher leadership may promote a more positive culture and school environment (Beachum and Dentith, 2004). Teacher leaders can contribute to their schools’ overall leadership capacity both formally by taking on leadership tasks allocated to them by the principal, or informally by sharing expertise with fellow teachers, and going beyond their classrooms to contribute to the school organisation in a variety of practices (Angelle and Teague, 2014). Lai and Cheung (2015) also referred to teachers’ roles in supporting reform efforts and guiding their colleagues towards the implementation of new practices.

Particularly stressed in teacher leadership literature is that improving instructional quality and hence student learning is at the heart of teacher leaders’ work (Fairman and Mackenzie, 2012; York-Barr and Duke, 2004). Teachers lead primarily within their classrooms (Hunzicker, 2017) as they carefully consider their students’ emotional, cognitive, and social needs as well as the various ways in which their students learn and accordingly provide relevant academic and social-emotional support (MacBeath et al., 2018; Öqvist and Malmström, 2018). As discussed in section 3.3.2, most of the practices that non-positional teacher leaders engage in within their classrooms specifically target improvements in students’ learning through implementing differentiated and innovated instructional practices; providing individualised support for learners and establishing a suitable learning

environment (Achach-Sonda and Cisneros-Cohernour, 2023; Chien, 2020; Greenier and Whitehead, 2016; Nguyen, Huynh and Tran, 2022; Tahir et al., 2021).

Schools in which teacher leadership is enacted mainly in the form of classroom decisions regarding pedagogical matters often have fewer issues with students' outcomes and behaviour. Evidence from more current studies on the relationship between teacher leadership and student learning and behaviour support these views. Shen and colleagues (2020), for instance, conducted a meta-analysis to synthesise findings from quantitative research on the relationship between teacher leadership and student achievement. Their study specifically examined the relation between seven key teacher leadership dimensions identified from reviewing relevant literature. The seven teacher leadership dimensions that they addressed were: promoting a shared school vision, mission, and goals of student learning; facilitating improvements in curriculum, instruction and assessment; coordinating and managing beyond the classroom; participating in policy and decision-making; fostering a collaborative culture in schools; promoting teachers' professional development; and improving collaboration with families and communities. The authors conclude that teacher leadership -to some degree- positively relates to student achievement. Although the seven dimensions were all found to be positively associated with enhanced student achievement, facilitating improvements in curriculum, instruction and assessment had the strongest association (ibid). In another study, Ingersoll, Sirinides and Dougherty (2017) investigated the relationship between teacher decision-making and school performance. Their findings suggest that schools in which the greatest levels of instructional leadership are exercised by teachers scored better in mathematics and English language arts compared to schools in which teachers have lower levels of participation in decision-making. These findings support York-Barr and Duke's (2004) argument that 'teacher leadership work that is focused on the classroom level of practice is likely to show student effects more readily than work focused on the organizational level' (p. 288).

Although empirical research regarding the direct impact of teacher leadership on students is still -to some extent- limited (Schott, van Roekel and Tummers, 2020; Shen et al., 2020), studies of the indirect effects could provide valuable insights. This involves investigating the ways in which teacher leadership correlates with other school variables that may be more directly related to student learning, representing mediating variables between teacher leadership and student learning. Teacher leadership may, for instance, enhance student learning indirectly through its impact on fellow teachers. To illustrate, teacher leadership, as it has been discussed earlier, is reported to enhance teachers' collective efficacy, which is, in turn, reported to have a positive effect on students' performance (Goddard and Goddard, 2001). While this section outlined the multi-levels on which teacher leaders

could exert influence, such influence could only be exerted when teachers are supported to engage in leadership practices. The following section provides more insights into the factors that could either support or hinder teacher leadership practice.

3.4. Factors that Influence Teacher Leadership Practice

Effectiveness of both formal and informal teacher leadership requires creating appropriate conditions and providing sufficient support for teacher leaders. The review of the existing knowledge base revealed that teacher leadership enactment can be affected by teachers' own characteristics and beliefs, school culture and structures, school principals, and peers. Each of these factors will be discussed in more detail in the following sub-sections.

3.4.1. Teachers' Characteristics and Beliefs

Teachers' beliefs and personal characteristics have been identified by many researchers as having a great influence on teacher leaders' work. Muijs and Harris (2007), for instance, believe that teachers' lack of confidence and experience discourages them from participating in leadership work. Some teachers are reluctant to participate in leadership work because they obey the traditional hierarchical school structure, or do not feel comfortable being perceived as the boss (Brosky, 2011). Teachers' lack of confidence as well as their reluctance to practise leadership have equally been identified by Tahir and colleagues (2021) as the main obstacles of teacher leadership enactment in the Malaysian context. Teachers' perceptions of themselves as legitimate professionals with a sense of professional agency is a strong predictor of leadership practice (van der Heijden et al., 2015). Such perceptions encourage them either to assume leadership responsibilities, or to only position themselves as classroom teachers (Anderson, 2004; Muijs and Harris, 2006). Many researchers have additionally reported that teachers' awareness, self-initiation, and willingness to practise leadership are among the main antecedents of teacher leadership enactment and development within schools (Wand and Ho, 2020).

Several studies have equally examined the potential impact that certain demographic variables such as a teacher's degree, position, nationality, gender, and school level might have on teacher leadership perceptions or practice (eg. Aliakbari and Sadeghi, 2014; Angelle and DeHart, 2011; Hammad et al., 2023; Sawalhi and Chaaban, 2021; Sawalhi and Sellami, 2019). These studies adopted a quantitative approach, employing either Katzenmeyer and Moller's (2009) Teacher Leadership School Survey or Angelle and DeHart's (2011) Teacher Leadership Inventory. These empirical studies, however, yielded mixed and inconsistent results. For instance, while Angelle and DeHart's (2011) research in the USA context and Aliakbari and Sadeghi's (2014) study in the Iranian context indicated significant differences in teachers' perceptions of teacher leadership practice in relation with

their educational degree and the level that they taught, Sawalhi's (2019) research in Qatar reported no significant differences with reference to school level. Likewise, Aliakbari and Sadeghi (2014) reported no significant relationship between teachers' leadership roles and gender. Findings from Hammad et al. (2023), however, highlighted teachers' gender as a significant variable affecting teachers' perceptions of teacher leadership practice. In the Qatari public-school context, Sawalhi and Sellami (2021) found that teachers' nationality significantly shapes their perceptions of teacher leadership roles. The authors explained that within the Qatari context, nationals are prioritised over expatriates when selecting staff for leadership roles.

These inconsistent results point out that empirical evidence on the relationship between these demographic factors and teacher leadership remains inconclusive and might be further influenced by broader contextual variables. Indeed, Hammad and colleagues (2023) stress that when examining these demographic factors, researchers should carefully consider the social, economic, cultural, and political context in which their research is being conducted.

3.4.2. Impact of the broader context

As it has been noted in the previous section, the broader context could have an impact on both teacher leadership conceptualizations and enactment. Indeed, many researchers in the field have recently stressed the need to address teacher leadership in light of the broader context in which it is researched or practised. Hallinger (2018), for instance, argues that all types of leadership should be explored with reference to community, institutional, political, economic, cultural, and school improvement contexts. Similarly, Boyce and Bowers (2018) stress that teacher leadership must always be thought of as a culturally sensitive concept.

Despite these calls by researchers to account for the impact of such broader contextual variables on teacher leadership conceptualization and enactment, the existing knowledge base on teacher leadership provides little evidence on such impact. Of the few studies that reported on the impact of the broader historical context in particular was a study conducted by Van der Vyver, Fuller and Khumalo (2020) with the aim of exploring teacher leadership conceptualisation and manifestation in the South African context. Based on their analysis of official documents directed for teachers and educational institutions, those researchers found that in light of the socioeconomic, political, and historical context of South Africa, almost half of the analysed documents were specifically focused on issues of equality, non-discrimination, democracy, and the protection of human rights for everyone. In an earlier study conducted by Ali (2014) in Pakistan, the researcher stressed that it is fundamental to thoroughly explore teacher leadership in the Pakistani context in which becoming a school leader

or broadly a leader in society is likely to be largely dependent on individuals' gender, kinship, race and so forth rather than their qualifications.

As far as the institutional or school context is concerned, and as it has been discussed in section 3.4.4, educational settings that adopt a distributed approach to leadership are more conducive to teacher leadership enactment compared to contexts in which educational leadership and management are more hierarchical in nature (Harris, 2013; Torrance, 2013). This view was supported by findings from previous research which reported that teachers perceived hierarchical and top-down management and leadership approaches as a major hindrance for teacher leadership enactment. This was, for instance, the case for teachers in the Saudi context (Alsalahi, 2016), the UAE (Al-Teneiji and Ibrahim, 2017), and the Moroccan context (Idelcadi et al., 2023). Given the similarities between the Algerian context and the aforementioned contexts in terms of the hierarchical approaches to school management and to educational leadership (as discussed in section 2.4.2), it could be inferred that such a management approach is likely to represent an important factor limiting teacher leadership enactment in Algerian middle schools. However, as in the case of the Saudi, Moroccan and UAE contexts, teachers could challenge such a hindrance posed by the centralised educational system and be able to practise teacher leadership and exert influence at some level based on their own initiatives, professionalism, innovation and collaborative practices.

3.4.3. School Culture and Structures

Muijs and Harris (2006) suggest that teacher leadership requires 'favourable cultural conditions...created through certain structural arrangements' (p. 967). In a similar way, Munroe and Driskill (2014) and Frost (2017) stress that non-positional teacher leaders, in particular, possess a great potential to contribute to school development; however, their influence can only be exerted when they function within appropriate school structures and supportive cultures.

School culture, on the one hand, is a recurrent theme in much teacher leadership research, representing one of the main conditions that could support teacher leadership enactment (Angelle and DeHart, 2011; Cooper et al, 2016). Barth (2002) defines school culture as a set of beliefs, norms, attitudes, and behaviours that represent the core of the organisation and that have the potential to shape individuals' thinking and actions. Hargreaves and Fullan (2012) agree with this view, noting that the school culture is powerful because it determines norms of thinking and shapes teachers' behaviours. Findings from previous research suggest that school cultures that support teacher leadership are mainly characterised by collaboration, collegiality, and trust (Visone, 2020; Wang and Ho, 2020). Such collaborative cultures enhance relationships and trust between teachers and the whole school community. Trust between teachers is crucial for promoting teacher leadership (Mitchell and Sackney, 2011) as it leads to legitimising teacher leadership practice (Frost and Harris, 2003). Empirical

evidence from a quantitative study by Kılınç, Bellibas and Bektas (2021) with 618 teachers in the Turkish context suggests that successful teacher leadership enactment is contingent on the degree of trust between teacher leaders and their peers. The authors report that when trusting relations are established and sustained, teacher leaders are more likely to collaborate with colleagues, sustain their peers' professional learning and support instructional improvements.

Establishing positive relationships with the school leadership team is equally important because, as such, teachers would feel secure to be involved in leadership practice and to take risks in a non-blame culture (Visone, 2020). Supportive school cultures are also reported to be marked by a shared sense of purpose; a shared vision; and commitment to student learning and teacher empowerment (Cooper et al., 2016; Pineda-Baez, Bauman and Andrews, 2019, Visone, 2020). Such cultures give teachers opportunities to engage in life-long learning and participate in decision-making (Chukowry, 2018). Acton (2022) maintains that enacting teacher leadership within non-supportive school cultures is evidently challenging given the outright opposition that teacher leaders might face from peers. Highly bureaucratic and hierarchical school cultures seem to represent a major hindrance for teacher leadership as they impede collaboration and learning (Murphy, 2007).

School structures, on the other hand, are often described in terms of allocating time, space and resources that support teacher leadership enactment (Katzenmeyer and Moller, 2009). A quantitative study conducted by Galland (2008) on the relationship between effective teacher leaders who lead from within their classrooms and school structures revealed that three types of school structures are particularly significant in supporting teacher leadership: role clarity; organisational structures (scheduling time, teams, school policies); and physical structures (school layout and spaces for collaboration). Teacher leadership is reported to be facilitated and promoted when the school leadership teams provides the necessary support including resources and physical facilities, rewards, sufficient time, and partnerships with other schools (Oppi, Eisenschmidt and Stingu, 2023). Essentially, as collaboration is proved to be an important enabler of teacher leadership, it is equally important that schools allocate communal spaces for teachers' meetings and collaborative activities (Galland, 2008; Muijs and Harris, 2006). These spaces should be conveniently located within schools to facilitate access (Easton, 2008). Silva, Gimbert and Nolan (2000) stresses that schools that do not provide such facilities are not providing the necessary support for teachers' professional work and engagement.

Many studies reported that shortage of time, coupled with work overload discouraged teachers from participating in leadership work within their schools. As leaders, teachers have more responsibilities added to their daily work including engaging with students' parents, supervising

school activities and regularly attending professional development sessions (Barth, 2001, p. 445). Gerrard (2004) suggests that the additional tasks that teachers are supposed to accomplish may affect their professional efficacy and engagement. School leadership teams are, thus, encouraged to allocate the necessary time for teachers to collaborate and lead change (Harris and Muijs, 2004). Finally, recognising and rewarding teachers' leadership initiatives is crucial for enhancing teacher leadership. Recognising teachers' work could enhance teacher leadership development and self-directed leadership and learning. Harris (2003) emphasises the importance of reward stating that:

While it could be argued that teacher leadership brings its own reward through enhanced effectiveness, a sense of collegiality, improved teaching practices, etc, it would remain a marginal activity within schools unless forms of remuneration are put in place to actively encourage teachers to engage in leadership tasks (p. 319-320).

3.4.4. School Principals

Most of the existing research maintains that school principals have a great potential for either supporting or impeding teacher leadership within their schools. Findings from such research suggest that school principals can support teacher leadership within their schools through sharing leadership; establishing positive teacher leader-principal relationships; and ensuring the availability of resources that support teacher leaders' work.

Distributed leadership by school principals has been highlighted by many researchers as the preferred leadership approach to support and nurture teacher leadership enactment (Muijs and Harris, 2003). In this sense, Harris (2013) stresses the need for a shift from the traditional hierarchical ways in which principals interact with teachers to a model in which control is more relinquished, giving other school members more authority and opportunities to lead. School principals could, accordingly, support teacher leadership by adopting a more distributed leadership style, and minimising the influence of hierarchical school structures, which could restrict teachers' participation in leadership work and decision-making processes. Based on data generated through document analysis and interviews with twenty novice teachers in Hong Kong, Cheng and Szeto (2016) similarly concluded that principals need to know when to provide teachers with more space and opportunities to promote and facilitate their participation in decision-making processes.

Cheng and Szeto (2016) equally stress the importance of interpersonal relationships and interactions between principals and teachers in establishing an environment where teacher leadership could thrive. Drawing on data obtained from documentary evidence and interviews with 20 beginning teachers, Szeto and Cheng (2018) examined the role of principal-teachers' interactions in the leadership development of participant teachers. Findings highlighted three principal-teacher interactions patterns which contributed to developing teacher leadership: inspirational, empowering

and allowing. The first type, inspirational, implies school principals sharing visions for school improvement; acting as role models; and setting high expectations. Empowering interactions involved school principals setting up conditions that support teacher leadership; facilitating teachers' professional learning; and encouraging their participation in decision-making processes. School principals, in this sense, trusted teachers' potentials and enhanced their confidence to advocate and stand for their teaching approaches and their professional learning. The final interaction pattern, described as allowing, entails principals adopting a 'laissez-faire' approach, providing highly motivated teachers with higher levels of autonomy and sufficient margins of freedom to develop a shared sense of responsibility to meet school directions and goals.

Moreover, principals are more likely to support teacher leadership when they fully understand teacher leaders' roles and responsibilities and reward teachers for accomplishing these roles (Wenner and Campbell, 2017). Teachers often stress the importance of feeling valued and receiving verbal recognition, praise, and encouragement from their school principals (Cheng and Szeto, 2016; Szeto and Cheng, 2018). Pineda-Báez et al. (2020) maintain that the recognition and praise that teachers receive from their school principals enhance their intrinsic motivation to engage in more leadership practices within their schools. Besides recognition and praise, findings from previous research equally stressed that principals can support teacher leadership by providing the necessary classroom resources and materials (Hoy and Hoy, 2009); allocating sufficient time and communal spaces for collaboration (Chew and Andrews, 2010); or adapting schedules (Wenner and Campbell, 2017).

In their review study, Wenner and Campbell (2017) concluded that unsupportive principals constrain teacher leaders' work as: a) they do not provide the necessary resources to enable teacher leadership, b) they limit teachers' autonomy, c) they do not recognise or value teacher leaders' contributions, or d) the wider faculty does not recognise the necessity to deal with teacher leaders' work.

3.4.5. Colleagues

Relationships between teacher leaders and their peers are fundamental to teacher leadership enactment in schools. Margolis (2012) notes that teachers feel more motivated and willing to take on leadership roles when they obtain collegial support from their peers. This is particularly because teachers may develop professionally through reflecting on their own experiences and sharing knowledge with their peers within their professional community (Johnson and Donaldson, 2007). Similarly, role acceptance by peers is an essential enabler of teacher leadership (Galland, 2008). Therefore, poor relationships with colleagues may hinder teacher leadership (Wenner and Campbell, 2017). Resistance and resentment by colleagues, according to Wenner and Campbell (2017),

constrains teacher leadership as working with colleagues is the core of teacher leaders' work. Brosky (2011) further explains the obstacles that teacher leaders face because of resentful colleagues. Resistance may occur when teacher leaders are perceived to take on leadership roles for personal profit, or when they are perceived to use 'undue influence over the principal' (Brosky, 2011, p. 6). This is also stressed by Anderson (2004) who explains that formal teacher leaders, for instance, may encounter resistance from their colleagues if they behave as typical leaders and exclude others from participation in decision-making. Teacher leaders also highlighted the existence of alliances among colleagues as a factor that impedes teacher leadership by blocking its progress and advancement (ibid). Campbell et al. (2019) argue that gaining peers' support might be more challenging for informal teacher leaders who do not possess a formal position of authority and may often not consider themselves as school leaders.

Enacting teacher leadership within schools is, therefore, contingent on various conditions, ranging from teachers own traits and beliefs, to schools' structure and culture, and to relationships with staff, namely principals and colleagues. Teachers' empowerment, as suggested by Mitchell and Sackney (2011), requires a different perception schools as professional communities or an organisations. While teachers' competence, sense of self, sense of purpose, willingness and confidence seem to encourage them to engage in leadership practices, support and collaboration from the school principal and fellow teachers remain fundamental. Allocating time and communal spaces for teachers to meet and interact are also central for nurturing teachers' leadership capacities and potential within a school culture marked by collegiality, trust, and distribution of authority. The current research sets as one of its aims investigating the available supports and current hindrances of teacher leadership enactment within the Algerian context from the perspectives of participant teachers.

3.5. Teacher Leaders' Professional Learning and Development

As it has been noted in the previous section, teachers' lack of knowledge and insufficient training and preparation represent one of the main barriers to teacher leadership enactment. Over two decades ago, particularly in the USA, Katzenmeyer and Moller (2001) argued that teachers are often expected to take on leadership roles without being prepared to assume them, primarily due to the assumption that teachers 'appear to intuitively know how to work with their colleagues' (p. 47). While this claim might be currently irrelevant for many Western contexts such as the USA, UK and Canada in which formal preparation and training programmes for teacher leaders are gaining considerable attention, the review of teachers' preparation and training programmes in Algeria (section 2.4.3) indicated that teachers in Algeria receive no leadership-related input as part of their pre-service or in-service professional training and therefore are indeed not prepared to assume leadership roles within their schools and beyond.

Many researchers stress that a strong link exists between teacher leadership and teachers' professional development. In this sense, Poekert (2012) explains that 'professional development is both a cause and an outcome of teacher leadership' (p. 170). On the one hand, one of the major outcomes of teacher leadership enactment is creating opportunities for and promoting the professional development of peers within the school context (as discussed in section 3.3.4). Apart from contributing to the professional development of their peers, teacher leaders themselves continuously learn and develop through the practice of teacher leadership. Hence, teacher leadership enactment results in the professional learning and development of peers and of teacher leaders themselves. On the other hand, teacher leadership is more than a means for teachers' professional learning; it could equally be an outcome of professional development. Professional development, in this sense, is fundamental for preparing, training and developing teachers as leaders. Murphy (2005) argues that when teachers' professional development is effectively planned and administered, it is likely to serve as an impetus for professionalising teaching and for developing teachers' leadership skills towards influencing their peers and improving their practices. In short, thus, teacher leadership can both result from and contribute to teachers' professional development, a view that is parallel with Baecher (2012) who asserts that teacher leaders should be considered as both deliverers and recipients of professional development and argues that teacher leaders should receive professional development in the preservice stage, in induction and on an ongoing basis. Sufficient and relevant training is, therefore, necessary as it familiarises teachers with the various formal and informal roles and responsibilities of teacher leaders (Lowery-Moore, Latimer and Villate, 2016). York-Barr and Duke (2004), suggest that both formal training including teacher education and professional development programmes, and job-embedded support such as mentoring, coaching, and collaborative practices are crucial for teacher leaders' professional development.

An important point to address at this point is the difference between the concept of 'professional development' and that of 'professional learning' as the difference between the two often surpasses the semantic level. Professional development, on the one hand, is generally associated with top-down approaches, focusing primarily on single events like workshops, seminars or lectures mostly led by external experts to guide teachers into ways to improve their work and enhance their mastery of specific competencies and skills (Bergmark, 2023). Such an approach reinforces a hierarchical pedagogy in which teachers are regarded as passive recipients instead of being actively involved in or responsible for their own learning (Easton, 2008). According to Frost (2017), 'continuous professional development' is mainly an extension of this view, as teachers are regarded as requiring fixing. Professional learning, on the other hand, stands in contrast to the event-based, top-down professional development (Timperley, 2011). Teachers are, accordingly, more empowered to assume responsibility

for their own professional improvement (Martin et al., 2014). Teachers' professional learning is context-specific, collaborative, and embedded in activities that are part of teachers' daily work (Opfer and Pedder, 2011); generally representing a teacher-driven practice directed towards improved student learning (Lloyd and Davis, 2018). Put briefly, Prestridge and Main (2018) explain: 'Essentially, professional learning is a 'growth in practice' model that values active engagement, teacher voice, creation and collaboration, inquiry and reflection' (p. 436).

3.5.1. Formal Training and Professional Development of Teacher Leaders

York-Barr and Duke (2004) maintain that formal professional development of teacher leaders can take various forms ranging from graduate university coursework and locally based professional development programmes to workshops and in-service training, all of which are likely to enhance teachers' leadership skills. King, McMahon, Nguyen and Roulston (2019) stress that effective training of future teacher leaders requires introducing leadership learning as a core aspect of prospective teachers' education programmes. Recently, universities across countries like Canada, Australia, Scotland, England, USA and China were reported to engage in an emerging and notably extensive approach towards pre-service preparation of prospective teacher leaders (Acquaro and Gurr, 2022b; Webber, 2021a; Webber and Nickel, 2021). Acquaro and Gurr (2022a) maintain that as an essential part of teacher training, countries like the USA, Canada, Hong Kong, England, Australia, and Singapore are developing and implementing teacher education programmes that aim to introduce leadership theory and skills through leadership-based subjects. The importance of such training and preparation lies in expanding prospective and beginning teachers' vision of the profession and enhancing their understanding and awareness of school leadership as well as their potential to initiate and lead change through teacher leadership (Moral-Santaella and Sánchez-Lamolda, 2023; Sheppard, Wolfinger and Talbert, 2021).

Such formal professional development programmes are believed to be more likely beneficial for teacher leaders when they focus on the development of certain types of knowledge and skills that are required for their leadership roles and practices. Sato, Hyler and Monte-Sano (2014), for instance, suggest that teacher leaders' professional development should focus on enhancing teachers' knowledge of school culture, school organisational improvement and professional collaboration models. As for the skill set, Katzenmeyer and Moller (2001) argue that in order for teachers to be well prepared for their leadership roles, professional development programmes need to be designed around skills such as managing groups and workshops and conducting action research. Furthermore, such professional development programmes must consider enhancing teachers' confidence, their desire to leave their comfort zone as well as their willingness to inform and influence school reform

(Helterbran, 2010; Uribe-Flórez, Al-Rawashdeh and Morales, 2014). Muijs and Harris (2003) assert that enhancing teachers' self-confidence to assume leadership responsibilities within their schools is amongst the most important aspects for teacher leaders' capacity building.

It is worth noting, however, that formal teacher professional development programmes overall have been subject to criticism by some researchers and practitioners for various reasons. First, most of these programmes are often designed following a behaviourist approach to learning (Pitsoe and Maila, 2012) which entails a one-way, top-down approach to learning. Second, Kedian, Giles, Morrison and Fletcher (2015) argue that leadership professional development workshops neglect contextual variables and thus 'show minimal concern for the situational and contextual realities of the leader' (p.2). Notably, though, existing literature suggests an increased interest in establishing professional learning communities (PLCs) within schools to support teachers' professional learning. Within PLCs, teachers could engage in collaborative practices and professional dialogue within their schools, leading to enhanced teachers' professional learning and hence improved student achievement (Kruse and Johnson, 2017). Chen and colleagues (2020) maintain that two types of PLCs could be established within schools, namely institutionalised, and voluntary or loosely organised PLCs. While institutionalised PLCs are reported to promote regular collaborative learning and interdisciplinary dialogue between teachers, they are often criticised as contrived collegiality that seems to be imposed on teachers (Wang, 2015). Wang (2015), accordingly, proposed developing and promoting genuine collegiality through shared commitment, reciprocal responsibility and mutual trust. Such collaborative and job-embedded learning is discussed in detail in the following section.

3.5.2. Collaborative Job-embedded Professional Learning

Given the limitations of decontextualised top-down professional development, a paradigm shift towards more contextualised and job-embedded teacher professional learning has been advocated by many researchers and practitioners (Morris and Hiebert, 2011). Hence, teacher professional learning began to adopt a more social-constructivist approach in which teachers are perceived to grow professionally as they collaborate and work together on issues of practice.

Professional learning is most commonly described as a process of social interaction rather than an isolated experience (Darling-Hammond and Richardson, 2009). A common theme in the literature relates to the significant impact of collaboration on teachers' professional learning. Teachers are, in this sense, perceived to learn collaboratively within communities and networks (Lieberman, 2000) in which they jointly construct knowledge to transform and improve teaching and learning. Teachers' knowledge and skills could, accordingly, be enhanced as teachers participate in collaborative activities that involve elements of peer-mentoring and coaching (Bowe and Gore, 2017). Cherkowski and

Schnellert (2017) explain that collaboration provides an opportunity for providing feedback, exchanging and testing out new ideas, and for increased dialogue.

The usefulness of such informal collaborative practices is that they are often embedded in and constitute an element of teachers' day-to-day work. Mawhinney (2010) explains that a common context within schools in which these collaborative practices are likely to occur is in the teachers' lounge. This argument is supported by findings from a two-year ethnographic study conducted by Mawhinney (2010) based on interviews with teachers and observations of their interactions in the staffroom during lunch breaks. Findings indicated that informal discussions and interactions between teachers in staffrooms served as a support mechanism, both holistically through offering social and emotional support and enhancing peers' self-confidence, and professionally through developing teaching capacities and sharing knowledge and advice. Based on these findings, the author argues for recognising these spaces as sites in which professional interactions and discussions and teachers' professional learning and development occur.

Discussions of collaboration in the educational field often refer to the notion of Professional Learning Communities (PLC). Stoll et al. (2006) defined a PLC as 'a group of people sharing and critically interrogating their practice in an ongoing, reflective, collaborative, inclusive, learning-oriented, growth-promoting way' (p. 223). Many researchers have accordingly argued that PLCs are based on five aspects: collaborative activity, shared values and goals, reflective dialogue, collective focus on student learning, and deprivatised practice (Vangrieken et al., 2017). There appears to be common agreement among most researchers that PLCs promote community-based and job-embedded sharing, collaboration and reflection toward teacher professional learning and overall school improvement (Wang, 2015). Within such communities, teachers can experience risk-taking as they experiment with practice, be more open about their own practice, and engage in collaborative development activities (Frost, 2012). Reason and Reason (2007) posit that 'creating a PLC encourages teams of teacher leaders to help one another grow and evolve as leaders and learners' (p. 39).

The emergence of teacher leadership as a result of teachers' collaborative work to improve their practice in response to reform efforts is a recurrent theme within the existing literature (Smylie, Conley and Marks, 2002, Muijs and Harris 2003, Trabona et al., 2019; York-Barr and Duke, 2004). Nicolaidou (2010) maintains that teachers often implicitly progress to be teacher leaders as part of 'an ongoing process integrated in the normal working day' (p. 232). Teachers are, therefore, likely to be empowered as leaders when they have opportunities to reflect on their own practices and to own their professional learning (Katzenmeyer and Moller, 2001). Lieberman and Friedrich (2007) point out that participation in collaborative practices provides teachers with an opportunity to practise small-scale leadership in addition to recognising peers' areas of expertise, establishing trust, and collectively

engaging in solving problems and completing tasks. This view is echoed by Muijs (2010) who maintains that through collaborative practices, teachers are encouraged to exercise leadership skills by providing support and sharing expertise, experiences and knowledge.

Findings from an ethnographic study conducted by Higgins (2013) which explored teacher leadership and teacher leaders' professional learning further stressed the usefulness of collaborative job-embedded opportunities for the professional learning of teacher leaders. Data obtained through observations, document analysis and interviews with five teachers of mathematics at a high school in Florida, USA, indicated that within their school, teacher leaders learnt from one another through the opportunities that their school environment provided for them to informally share their expertise. Participants in this study were also reported to engage in leadership practices beyond their department through leading professional development seminars and modelling instructional practices. Based on these findings, the author stressed, that within the context of this study, both formal and informal workshops that teachers collaboratively engaged in represented the key source for their professional learning. These findings further establish the potential effectiveness of informal and collaborative forms of leadership practices in enhancing teacher leaders' professional development.

Findings from another empirical study by Fairman and Mackenzie (2015) further stressed the usefulness of collaboration in teacher leadership development and school improvement. Employing a qualitative case study design of seven Maine schools in the USA, Fairman and Mackenzie examined ways in which teachers engaged in tasks with their peers to improve teaching and learning and to enhance their understanding of their work as leaders. Data obtained through 24 interviews with teachers in both elementary and high schools revealed that participant teachers considered informal collaboration and professional relationships based on trust and collegiality as fundamental for supporting teacher leadership development and overall school improvement. These findings support the argument that collegiality and informal collaboration could represent effective strategies for teacher leaders' professional growth regardless of the context and setting in which teachers work.

To sum up, and in light of the above discussion, it could be argued that formal professional development alone -such as university programmes, workshops, and conferences- might not be sufficient for the professional development of teacher leaders. Therefore, more informal, and job-embedded professional learning opportunities are required to develop teachers as teacher leaders. The combination of collaborative experiences and job-embedded professional learning seems to represent the most effective way for preparing teacher leaders (Hunzicker, 2012). Empirical research that supports this argument in the field of teacher leadership, however, remains notably limited. One of the aims of the present study is, therefore, to examine, from a sample of Algerian middle school EFL teachers' perspective, the usefulness of engaging in informal collaborative practices in enhancing

teachers professional learning and growth as teacher leaders. For this purpose, teacher leadership learning is defined in the present study as developing skills, qualities and dispositions that would empower teachers to engage in leadership work within their schools.

3.6. Teacher Leadership Research in the MENA Region

Teacher leadership is an emerging field in the Arab World and the majority of recent empirical studies conducted in Arab contexts seem to come as a response to a surge of calls by researchers for teacher leadership research that provides insights into this phenomenon in non-Western contexts (Nguyen, Harris and Ng, 2019; Wenner and Campbell, 2017; Schott, van Roekel and Tummers, 2020; Webber et al., 2023). It was interesting to note from the review of the existing knowledge base that teacher leadership began to gain ground as an important research area in the MENA region. Most of the relevant studies were conducted in the Middle East, particularly in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA), United Arab Emirates (UAE), Qatar, and Egypt (Alsalahi, 2016; Al-Teneiji and Ibrahim, 2017; Emira, 2010; Sawalhi, 2019). Research on teacher leadership in Arab countries in North Africa, however, remains remarkably limited with only one relevant empirical study conducted in Morocco (Idelcadi et al., 2023). Although a few studies were conducted at the higher education level, this section only considers empirical research conducted at the pre-university level, and as such it provides an overview of these studies and their findings.

One of the earliest studies conducted in the MENA region is a study in the Egyptian context by Emira (2010), reporting on findings from his doctoral research that investigated English language teachers' and senior teachers' views of teacher leadership and whether their views were affected by their length of teaching experience. One further aim was to explore participants' perceptions regarding the relationship between teacher leadership and decision-making. The researcher administered open-ended questionnaires to twenty English language teachers and conducted follow-up interviews with six teachers, whose length of teaching experience ranged between 2 and 13 years. Findings revealed that their definitions of teacher leadership varied but were essentially related to teacher leaders' characteristics, styles of leadership, and roles inside and outside classrooms. Findings equally indicated that almost all participants stressed a link between teacher leadership and decision-making, and that the length of teaching experience did not have a significant impact on their views. Participant teachers in his study further stressed their desire to be more involved in decision-making processes which, within their context, remain top-down and hierarchical in nature.

In the context of KSA, Alsalahi's (2016) doctoral research that was based on a qualitative exploratory design examined Saudi English language teachers' understandings of the concept of teacher leadership and their perceptions of themselves as teacher leaders. The study further explored conditions that either support or hinder teacher leadership enactment in the Saudi context. The sample

involved nine English language teachers employed in five intermediate and secondary schools and data was collected using focus group discussions, reflective essays, and individual semi-structured interviews. Findings revealed that although teacher leadership did not seem to be a common topic in the Saudi context, participants perceived themselves as teacher leaders whose roles extend beyond their classrooms and that teacher leadership was particularly related to teachers' professionalism and knowledge. However, lack of a description of teacher leadership roles, inadequate pre-service and in-service teacher training and lack of empowerment and support within highly hierarchical educational structure represented major barriers to teacher leadership practice in the study context. Findings equally indicated that despite these barriers, participants were willing to engage in leadership practices given the perceived benefits that these practices could have for peers, school principals, curricula, students and for teachers themselves.

In the UAE, Al-Teneiji and Ibrahim (2017) conducted a mixed methods study employing questionnaires with 937 teachers followed by interviews with ten teachers, with the aim of investigating teachers' perceptions of their leadership practices and examining the personal and contextual factors that either deter or support them to become teacher leaders. Findings from the quantitative data revealed that while certain leadership roles were often practised by participant teachers particularly in terms of providing professional support for peers and establishing relationships with learners, other practices such as participating in professional groups or leading action research were rather infrequent. Qualitative data indicated that personal factors including teachers' beliefs about teacher leadership and their willingness to assume leadership roles as well as school contextual factors including time constraints, language barriers and unsupportive leadership styles represented the main impediments to adequate realisation of teacher leadership potential and benefits in UAE schools.

In the context of Qatar, Sawalhi's doctoral research (2019) investigated perceptions of teacher leadership among Qatari public-school teachers and the factors that influence their perceptions, with a particular focus on teachers' gender, age, school level, qualifications, school size, years of experience and leadership position. A mixed methods approach was employed, using questionnaires with 2969 teachers and individual interviews with 96 teachers. The study employed Angelle and DeHart (2011) Teacher Leadership Inventory and adopted York-Barr and Duke's (2004) Teacher leadership for student learning framework. Findings revealed that Qatari teachers defined teacher leadership with a particular reference to positional leadership roles and titles, yet they practised various non-positional roles through which they professionally and socially supported their peers. The interviewees' responses similarly indicated that within the Qatari context, the main support for teacher leadership is the support from school and family members while factors that were reported to inhibit

teacher leadership varied including limited team support, dealing with difficult people, culture and language differences, and continuous reforms implemented by the Qatari ministry of education.

The most recent study was conducted by Idelcadi, Rguibi and Bouziane (2023), reporting quantitative findings from a larger multi-stage mixed-methods study of teacher leadership perceptions and practices among 112 Moroccan teachers of English language. Quantitative data indicated that while some participant teachers acknowledged their leadership, many others still hesitate to refer to themselves as leaders. Moreover, the results pointed at the complexity and diversity of teacher leadership practices within the Moroccan context where teachers reported leadership practices at the classroom level as well as within and beyond their schools. Most of these practices were informal in nature and were self-initiated by participant teachers. Examples of these informal practices included: introducing innovative ideas within classrooms; leading projects both within and beyond their classrooms; establishing positive relationships with school staff; and coaching colleagues. These practices were, however, highly dependent on opportunities and space provided for teachers to engage in professional learning and leadership. Moreover, while teachers in this study reported possessing relatively more professional autonomy in terms of their teaching practices, they stressed that their participation in decision-making processes at a broader level was notably limited given the centralised nature of the educational system in the Moroccan context.

It is worth noting that although Arab countries share common features such as religion, language and history, some differences could be noted in terms of their social, cultural, and economic characteristics (Rauch and Kostyshak, 2009). This holds true for the educational systems across these countries. At the level of educational systems, perhaps the main common characteristic is the highly centralised nature of educational systems across Arab countries as highlighted in section 2.4.2. Yet, one possible difference that might be noted between educational contexts in the Arab world, for instance, is the segregation of schools based on gender (both for students and for staff) in the Middle Eastern countries as opposed to mixed-gender schools in North African countries like Algeria and Morocco.

3.6.1. Research in the Algerian Context

While teacher leadership research is gaining considerable attention in non-western contexts, and particularly in the Arab World, the Algerian context remains underrepresented in the current teacher leadership literature. The only study that focused on an issue that is relevant to teacher leadership, though not explicitly referring to the concept or using the term teacher leadership, is a mixed-methods study conducted by Gherzouli (2019) to explore secondary school EFL teachers and subject inspectors' perceptions of the 2003 curriculum reform and its implementation. The study reports on the barriers to teachers' professional autonomy and their participation in the process of

curriculum development. To meet these aims, questionnaires were completed by 156 secondary school EFL teachers, while interviews were conducted with five secondary school subject inspectors. Findings revealed that teachers' attitudes towards textbooks and curriculum were mostly negative. More specifically, teachers stressed that the curriculum was unsuitable for their students' needs and that their professional autonomy and participation in decision-making is highly restricted. Subject inspectors, however, held contradicting views to those shared by teachers particularly as they stressed the suitability and contextual relevance of the textbooks and curriculum. Findings highlighted various factors that resulted in teachers' resistance to the curriculum reform including instructional, institutional, organisational, and curriculum-related factors. The most salient finding, though, was the power imbalance between policymakers and teachers as the former strictly controls and dictates the curriculum without consulting teachers or engaging them in the curriculum development process. Based on these findings, the author argues for the need to consider a more democratic model of curriculum development in Algerian context. She explains that such model should involve teachers in this development process, thus combining top-down government standards and policies with bottom-up teacher creativities.

Despite the valuable insights that Gherzouli's (2019) study provides, it differs from the current research in that it only focusses on one aspect of teacher leadership (teachers' involvement in curriculum design) and is marked with the absence of any explicit mention of terms like 'educational leadership' or 'teacher leadership'. Moreover, Gherzouli's research was particularly focused on EFL teachers and subject inspectors at secondary school level, while the present study draws on data obtained from a sample of Algerian middle school EFL teachers to gain deep insights into the phenomenon of teacher leadership within the Algerian context. The current study is, therefore, the first to introduce the term teacher leadership to the Algerian context and to empirically investigate this phenomenon in this notably under-represented context, to the best of my knowledge.

3.7. Conceptual Framework

In their review of teacher leadership research, Wenner and Campbell (2017) noted that in 33 empirical studies, 26 different theoretical frameworks were adopted. This implies that the field of teacher leadership still lacks consensus on a theoretical grounding of related research. Campbell and colleagues (2019) further stress that none of the previously adopted frameworks was specific to teacher leadership as they often informed particular aspects of this phenomenon yet did not encompass its essence. To theorise findings that emerged from the present research, the study broadly draws on Wenger's (1998) concept of Communities of Practice (CoPs hereafter), and more specifically on the Communities of Practice for Teacher Leadership Model (CoPTLM hereafter) developed by Campbell and colleagues (2019) as well as Wenger's (1998) description of the three modes of belonging.

The choice of these two frameworks was particularly informed by the study's aims as well as my intensive engagement with and reflection on findings that emerged from the present research. This study sets as its overarching aim the exploration of teacher leadership within the Algeria context. This involves exploring perceptions, reported practices as well as supports or hindrances of teacher leadership enactment within the research context. Campbell and colleagues' (2019) CoPTLM provided a useful lens to better understand and broadly contextualise findings that emerged from participants' accounts as to which CoPs or social settings their leadership practices contribute to, what types of recognition are associated with different leadership practices within the study context as well as the role of the identified structures in either supporting or impeding teacher leadership enactment within different communities. Moreover, one further aim of this research is investigating teachers' perceptions of the role of engaging in informal collaborative practices with their peers in enhancing their professional learning and growth as teacher leaders. The focus on informal collaborative practices entails a perception of teachers' professional learning as a process that is situated in teachers' daily practices, resulting from their social interactions and professional connections. Such a view of professional learning is largely consistent with Wenger's (1998) CoPs and particularly with their description of the three modes of belonging. Campbell and colleagues' (2019) CoPTLM and Wenger's (1998) modes of belonging are discussed in more details in sections 3.7.1 and 3.7.2 below.

3.7.1. Campbell and colleagues' (2019) Communities of Practice for Teacher Leadership Model

Acknowledging that teacher leadership research remains partially atheoretical (Wenner and Campbell, 2017), and that previous research in the field drew on theoretical and conceptual frameworks that were not specific to teacher leadership, Campbell et al. (2019) attempted to answer the question Wenner and Campbell raised in their widely cited review of teacher leadership research: 'Can a theory of teacher leadership be developed to capture the essence of this unique form of leadership?' (2017, p. 165). Rooted in previous researchers' acknowledgement of teacher leadership as going beyond the 'dynamic leader' perspective (Katzenmeyer and Moller, 2009; Spillane, 2006), and drawing on concepts from identity work and social learning theory, Campbell and colleagues (2019) developed a model that depicts teacher leadership as practice within different communities. To iterate and refine their proposed model, the authors applied it to a study of teacher leadership in the context of local schools.

Campbell and colleagues (2019) posit that 'using social practice -especially the notion of CoP as a conceptualisation of group level practice- points to the need to understand not only the practices of teacher leaders..., but as important, which CoP or social contexts the identified practices are central to' (p. 175). That is, teacher leadership practices should be understood in terms of which social contexts or communities these practices contribute to. This is particularly relevant as teacher leaders

are reported in the existing literature to contribute to different communities both within their schools and beyond.

Beyond locating teacher leaders' work within CoPs and social contexts, the authors recognised the necessity to consider the ways in which teacher leaders' identity authoring is negotiated in such social practices. To assist understanding of teacher leaders' identities within different social contexts, Campbell et al. (2019) drew on Carlone and Johnson's (2007) tripartite framework to teacher leader identity, which posits that identity could be understood in terms of three empirically accessible dimensions: competence, performance, and recognition. These three dimensions imply that in order for individuals to enact a given identity that is perceived to be credible by others, they need to draw on relevant competences and practices that would meet the community's needs in a given context.

Campbell and colleagues (2019) argue that teacher leadership practice takes place across multiple CoPs and that existing structures within these communities play a central role in either supporting or hindering teacher leaders' work. In light of their application of the initial CoPTLM to data obtained from six teachers, the authors revised the initial model in order to account for important features that were not initially considered (see figure 3.1).

The first issue that the revised model accounts for is 'the entanglement of competences and performances' (Campbell et al., 2019, p. 190). This was particularly because the authors found it challenging to differentiate between participants' statements related to teacher leaders' competences and their performances as these two aspects appeared to be tightly related. They explained, for instance, that when looking at teachers' ability to effectively listen to their peers and engage in meaningful discussions with them, the authors could not disentangle the knowledge and skills that teachers drew upon for effective communication (competences) from their actual engagement in conversations and discussions with fellow teachers (performance). The authors, therefore, found it more appropriate to acknowledge these tight connections rather than attempt to disentangle the 'inextricably linked dimensions' of competence and performance.

The second issue concerns the linkages between internal and external recognition. It was accordingly important to consider both external validation from others and teachers' internal recognition of themselves and their practices. In their revised model, Campbell and colleagues referred to these aspects as external recognition (E-R) and internal recognition (I-R), respectively. The authors maintain that while teachers may often hold a 'hazy picture of what their possible selves' (Cleaves, 2005, cited in Campbell et al., 2019, p. 191) as teacher leaders could be, the external recognition that they receive, primarily from their peers helps them see themselves as teacher leaders and their work as teacher leadership practice. Campbell et al. (2019), accordingly, revised their initial CoPTLM in a way that highlights the ways in which teacher leaders' perceptions of themselves were 'teacher

leaders' accounts of themselves were closely connected to 'what seemed to be a more pronounced interacting relationship between personal and social recognition' (p. 191).

The third issue that the revised model accounts for is the overlap between the different communities in which teacher leaders' work takes place. In this sense, Campbell and colleagues (2019) argue that common competences, performances, and recognition are often valuable across multiple social settings in which teacher leadership practice takes place. This argument highlights the potential of boundary crossing as an essential aspect of teacher leaders' work (Wenger, 1998) in which teacher leaders could navigate the space between multiple communities to which they belong and could contribute. Teacher leaders, accordingly, engage in practices across different communities within systems drawing on common competences and performances across these communities (ibid).

The fourth and final feature stressed in the revised model relates to the ways in which teachers' lens, dispositions, and existing structures all together shape teacher leaders' work (Campbell et al., 2019, p. 190). Teachers' lens was found to be central to the practices of teacher leaders, who often reported that as they engaged in leadership practices, they often had students' benefits in mind, maintaining that students are their first priority and that they do what is necessary for their success. Such emphasis on their work being primarily directed to their students' benefits, the authors explain, is consistent with Fullan's (2002) description of teachers' moral purpose, which similarly denotes teachers' role in making a difference in their pupils' lives. In this sense, teacher leaders' classroom-based teaching responsibilities and their proximity to students' learning influence and shape their commitments and perspectives to engage in leadership work that directly impacts learners within their classrooms, while at the same time they negotiate a form of leadership that ultimately connects their practices within other communities with their classroom practice and perspectives.

Apart from teachers' lens, the CoPTLM equally stresses the ways in which teachers' dispositions influenced their teacher leadership work. In this model, dispositions refer to 'dimensions of human personality that have a consistency about them and are characterized, exemplified, or typified in behavior patterns' (Mullin, 2003, p. 5, cited in Campbell et al., 2019, p.191). Examples of teachers' dispositions involve, among other aspects, teachers' ability to collaborate with others as well as their interpersonal skills. These represent aspects of teachers' personality that seemed to be conducive to teacher leadership enactment, but that did not necessarily fall under the categories of competence or performance. Teacher leaders' collaborative and interpersonal skills, for instance, were found to be central to practices that supported peers' professional learning including activities such as co-planning and co-teaching (Campbell et al., 2019).

The final element depicted in the CoPTLM as shaping teacher leaders' work refers to structures, which Campbell and colleagues (2019, p. 192) described as 'the canvas on which teacher

leadership practice was constituted’. The authors, more specifically, acknowledge the ways in which structures (policies, historical and cultural norms) could influence actors (teacher leaders in this case) and shape their practice and at the same time the ways in which actors, too, can influence structures through constant negotiation of their practices over time.

Figure 3.1. Campbell et al. (2019) CoPTLM (Adopted from Campbell et al., 2019, p. 190).

3.7.2. Wenger’s (1998) Modes of belonging

In studying teacher leaders’ professional learning, many researchers have drawn on Lave and Wenger’s (1991) and Wenger’s (1998) theories of social learning within what they labelled ‘Communities of Practice’ (eg. Huggins, Lesseig and Rhodes, 2017; Lieberman and Friedrich, 2010). Within the sociocultural perspective of learning, CoPs which was first coined by Lave and Wenger (1991) and was later developed by Wenger (1998). CoPs’ perspective to learning shares similar characteristics with Vygotsky’s (1978) sociocultural theory of learning as both consider social interaction as a fundamental aspect of learning. Hara (2009) argues that CoPs provide an informal learning environment for both novice and experienced members of the community given the opportunities that all members have to interact with each other, share their experiences and learn from each other. This is a view that the present study endorses. Given that learning is a continuing process, CoPs are likely to provide learning opportunities for both novice and experienced teachers.

An important contribution of Wenger’s (1998) work is the perception of learning and identity construction as inseparable. Wenger (1998) made a clear claim that ‘[b]ecause learning transforms who we are and what we can do, it is an experience of identity. It is not just an accumulation of skills and information, but a process of becoming -to become a certain person’ (p. 215). Smith (2006)

maintains that ‘the most salient feature of Wenger’s theory in terms of learning and identity construction is his description of three modes of belonging’ (p. 619). In this sense, Lieberman and Friedrich (2010) maintain that professional learning according to Wenger (1998) is deeply rooted in individuals’ need to feel a sense of belonging and to contribute to a community. Essentially, teachers’ learning is more likely to thrive when teachers have a sense of belonging and contribute to a community (Trabona et al., 2019). Wenger (1998) conceptualises learning and identity construction in terms of belonging as he highlights three modes of belonging to a CoP, namely engagement, imagination, and alignment. These three modes of belonging are not linear or mutually exclusive, but rather occur through inter processes (Huggins, 2017).

Engagement, as defined in a later paper by Wenger (2000), is about ‘doing things together, talking and producing artefacts (eg. Helping a colleague with a problem or participating in a meeting)’ (p. 227). Individuals accordingly engage with practice and share experiences with co-practitioners, which provides them with opportunities to negotiate meanings and to develop a shared repertoire as they work towards achieving common goals (Biza, Jaworski and Hemmi, 2014; Huggins, Lesseig and Rhodes, 2017). As practitioners, teachers engage in shared practices such as designing curriculum and materials; creating student-centred learning environments; using summative and formative assessment (Goodnough, 2010), jointly planning lessons and teaching classes; discussing ideas; or providing feedback for each other (Nguyen and Loughland, 2018). Such shared activities that teachers participate in within their schools develop their relationships and create mutual engagement.

Imagination is conceptualised by Wenger (1998) as ‘a process of expanding our self by transcending our time and space and creating new images of the world and of ourselves’ (p. 176). Imagination is, in this sense, related to individuals’ ability to re-create the images of themselves and of the world through different perspectives. In this sense, Huggins, Lesseig and Rhodes (2017) explain that imagination transcends engagement and occurs when community members look beyond the immediate practice to envision new possibilities. Imagination, therefore, necessitates self-awareness and active reflection on one’s engagement in order to explore new ways of doing things and to incorporate other perspectives into one’s identity and practice. Imagination enables teachers to ‘view themselves in new ways and their profession in new ways; teachers critically examine their practices and the teachers they would like to become’ (Goodnough, 2010, p. 169). Through imagination, teachers could envision how to change classroom practices as they consider implementing new teaching and assessment strategies or using technology to advance student learning (ibid). Findings from Nguyen and Loughland’s (2018) study provided an example of how participation in a paired placement based on observing other teachers enabled one teacher to imagine a calmer teacher identity as opposed to her assertive and severe identity and to modify her teaching accordingly. Imagination,

in this sense, requires creativity and flexibility that would permit members to create opportunities for novel learning and to reinvent practices of a given community (Goodnough, 2010).

The third mode of belonging, alignment, results from ‘coordinating our energy and activities in order to fit within broader structures and contribute to broader enterprises’ (Wenger, 1998, p. 174). Alignment, thus, entails sharing objectives and principles with other group or community members, enabling individuals to position their own practices within broader communities. Biza, Jaworski and Hemmi (2014) explains that alignment as a mode of belonging describes the ways in which community members line up with the expectations and norms that are central to their community. It implies establishing a broad common vision and coordinating and directing energies and efforts to achieve shared goals (Goodnough, 2010). An example of this could be teachers coordinating and directing their efforts to enhance students’ learning, which in this case represents the common goal within a teachers’ community (ibid).

Of the three modes of belonging, alignment seems to receive more critics. The argument for most of those critics is that alignment as a mode of belonging might have some negative implications as it might imply control and disempowerment for community members. Goodnough (2010) and Filstad, Traavik and Gorli (2019), for instance, argue that alignment could be disempowering and binding as members of the community may feel obliged to adhere to the practices of a given community without meaningful engagement. In the context of teacher learning, Goodnough (2010, p. 169-170) further maintains that ‘teachers may feel powerless if asked to implement the ideas of others or if they have not had input into decisions that affect their schools and classrooms’, which may in turn hinder collaboration and enactment of new practices and ideas. Alignment with traditional practices that might be the norm in certain CoPs, for instance, could leave something to be desired as per teachers’ instructional practices. It might limit teachers’ potential to innovate or to challenge the status quo as well as efforts to initiate change, all of which are essential aspects of teacher leadership practice. Interestingly, Biza, Jaworski and Hemmi (2014) explained that while alignment with broader goals of a community is often necessary, it does not have to be uncritical. In this sense, the authors maintain that a ‘critical alignment would imply a questioning of the status quo’. For instance, teachers who observe that learners do not seem to benefit from traditional instructional approaches, could seek to modify their practice to better support their learners.

Figure 3.2. Wenger’s (1998) Modes of belonging (developped by the researcher)

Nguyen and Loughland (2018) argue that CoPs theory was central to shaping an extensive body of research, challenging the perspective of learning as knowledge transmission and situating learning within individuals’ day-to day work environments. It acknowledges learning as a result of social interaction between co-practitioners (teachers in the case of this study). This perspective to learning is consistent with the aim of examining teachers’ professional learning through engaging in informal collaborative practices within teachers’ communities. Within the present study, discussing the emerging findings in light of Wenger’s (1998) modes of belonging further enhanced understanding of and strengthened the argument for the usefulness of informal collaborative experiences as spaces for teachers’ situated learning, highlighting the ways in which teachers in the present research, as part of informal collaboration within teachers’ communities, *engaged* in joint practices, *aligned/ critically* their practices with the principles and goals of these communities and *imagined* new ways to refine and improve their practices.

3.8. Chapter Summary

To situate the present research in the existing knowledge base on teacher leadership, this chapter provided a review of existing research in the field. The chapter began by briefly discussing broader contexts of educational leadership and distributed leadership and looking at the evolution of teacher leadership. This was followed by a discussion of the various conceptualisations and proposed definitions of teacher leadership including positional and non-positional teacher leadership, teacher leaders’ traits and skills and the impact of teacher leadership. The chapter further addressed the conditions that either support or hinder teacher leadership enactment within schools. Professional

development and learning opportunities for teacher leaders were equally discussed with reference to both formal professional development in the form of university coursework, workshops, or seminars; and informal, job-embedded opportunities particularly in the form of informal collaborative practices with fellow teachers. This chapter equally provided a discussion of studies with similar foci as the present research conducted in Arab contexts, indicating that although teacher leadership represents an emerging research area that is gaining ground in Arab countries like the KSA, UAE, Egypt, Qatar or Morocco, the Algerian context remains -to date- underrepresented. Subsequently, a discussion of the conceptual framework which in turn provided a relevant grounding to broadly look at the findings that emerged from the present research was provided.

To address the aforementioned gap and as a response to the surge of calls from researchers to investigate teacher leadership beyond Western contexts, the present study, being -to the best of my knowledge- the first study in the Algerian context, broadly contributes to the global teacher leadership knowledge base and particularly to the emerging field of teacher leadership research in the Arab World by exploring teacher leadership within the Algerian context, drawing on data obtained from a sample of Algerian EFL public-school teachers at middle school level. The following chapter outlines the methodology employed to meet the study's aims.

Chapter Four: Research Methodology

4.1. Introduction

This chapter discusses and justifies the research methodology employed in the current study. The chapter begins by addressing the philosophical underpinnings of this study (section 4.2) and explaining the rationale for adopting a qualitative exploratory design (section 4.3). It then provides a discussion of the procedures followed for selecting participants (section 4.4) and the three data collection methods used in this research (section 4.5). Section 4.6, then delineates and justifies the procedures deployed for data analysis. This is followed by a discussion of my role and positionality in this research (section 4.7); strategies to enhance the research trustworthiness (section 4.8); and an overview of ethical considerations (section 4.9). A summary of the chapter is then provided in section 4.10.

This research was designed to investigate teacher leadership within the Algerian context, drawing on perspectives of a sample of middle school EFL teachers, and is guided by the following four research questions:

1. What perceptions do middle school EFL teachers hold regarding teacher leadership?
2. What are middle school EFL teachers' reported practices of and experiences with teacher leadership?
3. What factors reportedly hinder/ foster their practice of leadership?
4. How do teachers view collaboration with each other as contributing to their professional growth as teacher leaders?

4.2. Paradigmatic Assumptions

Creswell and Poth (2018, p. 15) assert that 'Whether we are aware of it or not, we always bring certain beliefs and philosophical assumptions to our research'. These assumptions shape and guide the entirety of the research from the choice of the research topic to the meanings that researchers make of the collected data (Grix, 2018; Mason, 2018) and are often referred to as paradigms (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018) or worldview (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). According to Guba and Lincoln (1994), 'a paradigm is a basic belief system or worldview that guides the investigator, not only in choices of method but in ontologically and epistemologically fundamental ways' (p. 105). More specifically, a research paradigm is a theoretical perspective that informs the way in which the investigator intends to approach the research, and as such, it affects the research design, data collection, analysis, and discussion (Grix, 2018; Creswell, 2014). Many researchers have highlighted the importance of understanding and adopting a research paradigm, although in a way it is always present even implicitly. Hussain, Elyas and Nasseef (2013), for instance, assert that as researchers adopt a paradigm for their studies, their position towards their research phenomenon becomes more

clearly established. Similarly, Gray (2014) argues that research in general and more specifically the choice of research methods is, explicitly or implicitly, the outcome of underpinning ontological and epistemological beliefs. Overall, a definition of a research paradigm implies a discussion of four elements, namely ontology, epistemology, methodology and method(s). These four elements are argued to be interrelated in the sense that the ontological assumptions inform the epistemological assumptions, which in turn affect the design of research methodology as well as the selection of appropriate data collection method(s). Scotland (2012) explains that every paradigm has its own epistemological and ontological underpinnings, which are reflected in the design of methodology and the choice of methods. While ontology is concerned with ‘the very nature or essence of the social phenomena being investigated’, epistemology is concerned with ‘the very bases of knowledge – its nature and forms, how it can be acquired and how communicated to human beings’ (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p. 5). Epistemological assumptions delineate the nature and essence of knowledge and the ways in which knowledge can be created, acquired, and communicated. Hence, researchers need to take a position regarding their perceptions of reality and knowledge. This section, accordingly, provides an overview of the existing debate between two major research paradigms, namely the positivist and the interpretivist paradigm, considering each paradigm’s perspective to reality and knowledge and concluding with my own philosophical assumptions in this study.

Interpretivism is a philosophy based on the belief that humans construct knowledge based on interpretations of their lived experiences in the social world, as opposed to the objectivist notion of the positivists, which assumes that knowledge is simply out there to be identified, observed, and collected (Pascale, 2011). That is, while positivists claim that ‘everyone experiences the world in the same way’ (Neuman, 2011, p. 103), interpretivists maintain that humans understand, interpret, and construct the world differently and as such multiple realities exist (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). It is this latter view that the present research adheres to.

Interpretivism adopts a relativist ontology. It designates a belief that any object’s existence depends on people’s perceptions of it (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018), and that a single phenomenon can be interpreted in a variety of ways, and thus multiple realities exist. For interpretivists, there are no absolute facts in the social world, but only socially and experientially constructed interpretations (Bryman, 2016; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). This view echoes Guba and Lincoln (1994) who argue that multiple realities exist, and that both the form and content of these realities depend on the persons or groups who construct them. Reality is, accordingly, abstract, multifaceted, context-bound and intangible. Crotty (1998) explains that this approach ‘looks for culturally derived and historically situated interpretations of the social life world’ (p. 67). Humans construct, interpret and understand reality based on their cultural and ideological positions. This view

stands in contrast to the ontological stance of positivism, which is based on the belief that objects exist independently of the knower (ibid). Positivists assume the existence of only one reality that is ‘out there’ in the social world and that it is controlled by permanent natural laws (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). Proponents of this paradigm argue that only observable or measurable experiences of the world are accepted as reality. Positivism is, therefore, mostly based on the scientific method, considering the social world as value-free and subject to objective observation (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). As positivist researchers assume that the social world is physical, existing independently of human being’s minds, they argue that it can be studied in the same way as any other scientific discipline (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Grix, 2018). The current research adheres to the interpretive paradigm’s relativist ontology, maintaining that teacher leadership is perceived in terms of multiple realities that are socially and experientially constructed by participant teachers and is not independent from their consciousness. Their perceptions of teacher leadership constitute its multi-realities as understood and experienced by them.

The epistemological stance of the interpretive paradigm is subjectivism. From an interpretivist point of view, knowledge is unique and personal. Therefore, this approach often prioritises the individual over the group, seeking to understand how individuals interpret, understand, and construct their social world (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Robson, 2011). Within this paradigm, research participants are considered as helping to construct realities with the researcher (Robson, 2011). Thus, to understand a given issue or situation, researchers rely on interaction with individuals and examination of their views regarding it. This stands in contrast to the positivist realism that assumes an objectivist and dualist epistemology, in which the researcher detaches himself/herself from the researched. In such a context, the role of the researcher is to objectively observe the research phenomenon, without any interference in the research procedure (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). From a positivist perspective, tools such as observations and experiments can be used to measure reality and knowledge. In doing so, positivist research seeks mainly to facilitate replication, to draw generalisations, and to objectively validate or refute hypotheses based on controlled variables (Punch, 2014). Within the present research, participant teachers’ knowledge of teacher leadership is considered to be subjective and personal, and to be best attained through my own interaction with them and my interpretation of their views, which aligns with the subjective epistemology of the interpretive approach.

To conclude, the present study is aligned with the interpretive paradigm, perceiving reality as multifaceted and context dependent. Indeed, as discussed in the previous chapter (section 3.3.1), the existing knowledge base on teacher leadership stresses its multi-faceted and multi-dimensional nature. Knowledge about teacher leadership is attained in this study through both the interpretation of

participants' views and accounts and the interpretation of my positionality as a researcher. By aligning my research with the interpretive paradigm, I understand that any reality reported in the study's findings is a reality constructed by participant teachers' perceptions and experiences and my own interpretation of their contributions.

4.3. Research Design

This study adopts a qualitative exploratory research design. This section aims to discuss the design of this study, providing an overview of qualitative and exploratory research.

4.3.1. Qualitative Research

Broadly, based on their research aims, researchers can opt for a quantitative research approach, a qualitative research approach or a combination of both in the ultimate quest to address the research questions (Harwell, 2011). The nature of each of these methods relates primarily to the research purpose, the nature of data collection instruments, the nature of the collected data and the way this data is analysed. Punch (2009) asserts that the main difference between the quantitative approach and the qualitative approach is in the way data is presented; the former relies on numbers whereas the latter relies on words, aiming to discern 'patterns, trends, and relationships between key variables' (Grix, 2018, p. 121). Qualitative research usually seeks in-depth investigation of research phenomena and interpretation of collected data in which researchers investigate cases, often limited in number, within their particular social and cultural setting throughout a specified period of time (Grix, 2018). Thus, unlike quantitative research in which researchers aim to detach themselves from the object of their study, qualitative researchers positively interact with it to unfold its realities (ibid). Qualitative researchers believe that detailed data offers greater understanding of research contexts. Such details enable researchers to produce thick descriptions of the research social setting, individuals as well as events (Bryman, 2016). Likewise, Denzin and Lincoln (2000) argue that promoting an understanding of individuals and their contexts is at the core of qualitative research:

Qualitative researchers study things in their natural settings, attempting to make sense of, or to interpret, phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to their lives. (p.3)

For the case of this study, in light of the underpinning interpretive paradigm and given that its primary aim is to gain a detailed understanding of the concept of teacher leadership among Algerian middle school EFL teachers, qualitative research was deemed appropriate as it enabled me to conduct a detailed exploration of teacher leadership with a focus on the 'subjective opinions, experiences and feelings of individuals' (Dörnyei 2007, p.38). As HesseBiber and Leavy (2004, p. 3) put it:

If you want to understand the meaning of a particular subject, if you want to listen to the subjective experience of others and somehow make sense of them, you may want to consider a qualitative methodology for your research.

In line with the quote above, I believe that a detailed and adequate understanding of teacher leadership within the research context could effectively be reached through an in-depth analysis and interpretation of teachers' views and perceptions of it.

4.3.2. Exploratory Research

This study is situated within an exploratory research design, which 'tends to tackle new problems on which little or no previous research has been done' (Brown, 2006, p. 43). Exploratory research merely aims to identify a research problem and explore research questions to better understand the phenomenon under investigation (Dudovskiy, 2018). Creswell (2014) maintains that within exploratory research, 'the researcher seeks to listen to participants and build an understanding based on what is heard' (p. 61). The present research is rooted within an exploratory research design, as it aims to investigate the phenomenon of teacher leadership within an under-represented context. This study is -to the best of my knowledge- the first study that investigates teacher leadership within the Algerian context. In this study, I explore and provide a comprehensively detailed and rich account of this phenomenon within the Algerian context, drawing on perspectives and experiences of a sample of Algerian middle school EFL teachers.

Initially, a single case study of one middle school was considered for this research. However, given the practical considerations that necessitated focus on EFL teachers, EFL teachers working in five middle schools were ultimately included in the study. The intent here was to cast the net more widely. It was recognised that to get a broader understanding of teacher leadership in the Algerian middle school context, qualitative evidence from EFL teachers across five selected middle schools would be more compelling, adding richness and variation and increasing the robustness of the study. Data obtained from teachers across the five schools was useful for noting commonalities and any differences between these settings. Further details on the selection of the schools and teachers are provided in the following section.

4.4. Research Setting and Selecting Participants

Sampling is the process or techniques of selecting a unit or a subset from a predefined research population. It is a strategy that permits researchers to arrive at more accurate findings (Denscombe, 2010) from a limited part of the entire population. Researchers outline multiple strategies that could be employed to recruit research participants ranging from random or probability sampling to non-random or non-probability sampling (Bryman, 2016), with each of the two types being sub-divided into further sampling techniques. Although there is a variety of non-random sampling techniques, both convenience and purposive sampling seemed to be most appropriate for the current research. Purposive sampling, also called judgemental sampling, is based on the deliberate and intentional selection of participants based on some 'predetermined criteria' that they possess (Dornyei, 2007, p.

128). Although a purposive sample may not be expected to be representative of the whole population, the deliberately selected sample is generally believed to possess the necessary sufficient information and knowledge about the research topic (Fraenkel and Wallen, 2007). Convenience sampling, on the other hand, is one of the most commonly used non-probability sampling strategies, which entails the selection of participants based on their accessibility and willingness to participate. Dornyei (2007) acknowledges that by opting for convenience sampling, researchers select their research sites and participants based on some practical criteria. These criteria usually but not exclusively include geographical proximity, availability and easy accessibility at a given time and individuals' willingness to participate.

4.4.1. Selecting Schools

The present research was carried out in a single directorate of education in Setif province. This province was chosen purposively as it is the place where I live, which made it easier to access schools and participants. The five middle schools in which participant teachers work were purposively selected with the aim of ensuring that the selected schools share as many common features as possible. In this sense, the five middle schools were public schools located within the same district in the southern part of the province and were supervised by the same school inspector. Similarly, all EFL teachers within these schools work under the supervision of the same subject inspector. The five schools were equally comparable in terms of school size, number of staff and students, and students' academic achievements (as evidenced by students' results in the national middle school exit exam). Apart from the aforementioned commonalities, it is plausible to assume that these schools share similar physical and organisational structures. This assumption is supported by the fact that the Algerian educational system is highly centralised in nature, which promotes 'sameness' as a feature of the whole educational system (Hanson, 1990, cited in Hammad, 2008). As discussed in section 2.4.2, following directives and standards set by the MoNE, regional directorates of education in Algeria supervise the construction; equipment and staff recruitment; training and promotion in all schools within the respective provinces to ensure that the same physical and organisational structures are shared across all public schools. Permission from school principals was required to access the selected schools and approach teachers. More details on negotiating access to the selected schools are provided in section 4.9.1.

4.4.2. Selecting Participants

Following the qualitative nature of the current study, participants were purposefully selected (Bryman, 2016; Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). Participants' selection was guided by a predetermined set of selection criteria (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). Participants in this study are, accordingly: (1) EFL teachers; (2) teaching in the chosen public middle schools; (3) possess a positional teacher

leadership role; or (4) do not possess a positional teacher leadership role. The last two criteria ensured recruiting a heterogeneous sample. While potential participants were purposively approached following these selection criteria, their participation in the current study remained subject to their willingness and availability to take part in the research. As for the sample size within qualitative research designs, Flick (2014) asserts that there are no fixed rules for the number of participants, and that it is up to the researcher to decide the number of respondents, taking into consideration certain factors such as time, research purpose, resources, and depth of the study. Although it may be evident that a larger sample would increase the validity of the research findings, opting for a large sample within the current research was not possible. This is in part due to the limited time in which the current research was completed. More importantly, as the current research is qualitative in nature, it was expected that very rich and thorough data will be collected, and the larger the sample is, the more data will be gathered. Analysing and interpreting such voluminous data within the scope of this study would have been even more challenging and time-consuming.

That being said, the sample for the current study involves 18 out of 20 Algerian middle school EFL teachers working in the five selected middle schools. All participant teachers were recruited and assigned to their schools and some of them were promoted following the guidelines set by the MoNE and implemented at the level of the directorate of education at Setif province. Teaching in schools within the same district, all participant teachers work under the supervision of the same subject inspector. Of the 18 teachers, seven are promoted teachers and the remaining eleven are non-promoted. Participants' teaching experience ranges between 1 year and 26 years. My aim was initially to recruit a sample of 15 middle school EFL teachers who would all contribute to the three data sets (participate in individual semi-structured interviews, provide written reflections, and participate in the focus group discussions). However, as I first approached participants, all of them expressed their willingness and interest in participating in this research but many were concerned that given their overwhelming workloads and personal commitments, they might not be able to contribute to the three data sets. As insisting on their participation in the three data sets might have put pressure on them and might have resulted in their reluctance to take part in this research, teachers were initially requested to contribute to the three data sets, but I had to remain flexible in case some of them were only available to contribute to only one or two data sets due to their work overload and personal commitments. Overall, 13 teachers contributed to at least two data sets, while only two teachers were just individually interviewed and only 3 others just participated in the focus group discussions. Table 4.1 below outlines the participant teachers' biographical information. The pseudonyms used are chosen by the participants themselves to protect their identities.

Schools	Participant	Position	Gender	Years of experience	Method(s)
A	Heba	Teacher mentor	Female	26 years	Int, Ref
	Amira	Teacher	Female	2 years	FG2
	Amine	Teacher	Male	2 years	Int
	Halima	Principal Teacher	Female	7 years	Ref, FG3
B	Melina	Principal teacher	Female	10 years	Int, Ref
	Sarah	Teacher	Female	4 years	Int, Ref, FG2
	Maria	Teacher	Female	1 year	Int, Ref, FG1
	Nawel	Principal teacher	Female	13 years	Int, Ref, FG2
C	Chahine	Teacher	Female	6 years	Int, FG3
	Kenza	Principal teacher	Female	14 years	Int
	Abdou	Teacher	Male	5 years	Int, Ref
	Nour	Teacher	Female	7 years	Int, Ref, FG2
D	Rokia	Teacher	Female	1 year	Int, FG1
	Sandra	Teacher	Female	3 years	FG3
	Ibtissem	Teacher Mentor	Female	22 years	Int, Ref
E	Serine	Principal Teacher	Female	11 years	Int, FG1
	Keltoum	Teacher	Female	4 years	FG1
	Marwa	Teacher	Female	6 years	Ref, FG3

Table 4.1. Research Participants (Int: Interviews, Ref: written reflections, FG: focus groups)

4.5. Data Collection Methods

This study draws on data obtained from a sample of Algerian middle school EFL teachers using individual semi-structured interviews, written reflections and focus group discussions. The rationale for selecting these data collection methods as well as the procedures of collecting data using these methods are discussed in more details in this section.

4.5.1. Individual Semi-structured Interviews

The use of interviews as a data collection method aligns with the ontological and epistemological assumptions of the study as well as with its qualitative approach. Interviews are commonly used as a data collection method when a researcher's epistemological belief suggests that the most appropriate way to collect data regarding individuals' views, knowledge and experiences is by interacting with them and listening to them (Mason, 2018). Schwandt (2001) explains that interviews seek to report and describe people's experience 'as it is lived, felt, undergone, made sense

of and accomplished' by them. Interviews are, accordingly, the most commonly used method of data collection in qualitative research (Bryman, 2016) particularly when researchers are mainly interested in understanding individuals' beliefs, values, intentions and meaning of ideas.

The usefulness of interviews lies partially in their practicality as individuals may prefer talking about their views and lived experiences to completing a questionnaire (Gray, 2014). Furthermore, when conducted appropriately, interviews can provide high return rates and yield rich and detailed data. Using interviews, researchers can get insights into certain research areas that may otherwise remain inaccessible, including people's views and attitudes and personal experiences, and can also clarify issues on the spot and elicit more data as they interact with interviewees (ibid).

Based on their structure, Robson (2011) differentiates between three types of interviews: fully structured, semi-structured and unstructured interviews. Unstructured interviews can be completely informal as the interviewer introduces a general area of interest and permits the conversation to freely develop surrounding this area without having any list of pre-established questions. Fully structured interviews have a set of predetermined questions, using a fixed wording, often in a pre-determined order. Similar to fully structured interviews, semi-structured interviews also have a predetermined list of questions and topics to be covered. However, the order and wording of questions can be modified, and explanations can be provided whenever necessary or appropriate. Within semi-structured interviews, certain questions that do not seem appropriate or relevant to some interviewees can be omitted, while other questions can be added depending on the flow of the interview. They are generally consistent in terms of the questions to be asked for each participant, while at the same time rely on probes and follow-up questions to elicit more detailed responses from the interviewees (as required) regarding a specific topic. Not only do semi-structured interviews allow researchers to prompt interviewees, but also give the interviewees themselves opportunities to ask for clarifications whenever necessary (Creswell, 2009).

Following the above explanation, it was deemed more appropriate to employ semi-structured interviews for the current study given the flexibility that they offer as regards the questions' sequence (Denscombe, 2010) and in allowing further questions to emerge throughout the course of each interview. An interview guide was, thus, developed in light of the research questions that guide this study and my readings of relevant teacher leadership literature (see appendix B). According to Bryman (2016), the interview guide serves as a 'brief list of memory prompts' (p. 442), which aims to list the questions and topics to be covered during the interview (Patton, 2015). More flexible interview guides are characterised by using 'probes', which are 'follow-up responses [to] elicit greater detail from participants' (Cassell and Symon, 2004, p. 15). The interview schedule for a semi-structured interview, in particular, usually includes introductory comments, a list of topic headings and key

questions to be covered under each heading, a set of related prompts, and closing comments (Robson, 2011). The individual semi-structured interview schedule in this study was designed following Robson's (2011) guidance, starting with general introductory comments and questions to break the ice, then moving to the main interview questions. The set of related prompts, however, often differed following each participant's responses. The closing comments mainly involved requesting teachers for any additional remarks that they wished to add and thanking them for devoting time to take part in this research.

Individual semi-structured interviews in this study were conducted with 13 participant teachers. One issue that required consideration prior to starting the fieldwork was the language used to collect data. To ensure yielding rich data, and although participants in this research are EFL teachers who are proficient in English, they were given the freedom to respond in any language they felt comfortable using to fully convey their thoughts. As for the questions, I initially asked them in English as I was concerned that translating some of the key terms to Arabic might affect their meaning. I, however, had to make sure that I was ready to rephrase certain questions or to ask them in Arabic upon participants' requests. To this end, I relied on my own background knowledge and skills which I gained through the translation course that I had for two years as part of my BA studies to translate key terms from English to Arabic. To further ensure accuracy and validity of the translated terms in this research, I requested a certified translator, who used to be a lecturer in my home university in Algeria to translate key terms that were part of the interview schedule. The translator further confirmed the accuracy of the Arabic terms as no significant differences were found between the two translations. The same approach was adopted for the written reflections' instruction and the focus group topics and questions.

By the beginning of each interview session, I provided an overview of the aims of my research and briefly discussed issues related to ethical considerations although these were fully addressed in the information sheets handed to all participant teachers. Accordingly, I explained that any identifying information will be removed when transcribing the interviews to ensure their confidentiality and I reassured them that the data that they provide will only be used for the purpose of this research and will be reported using the pseudonyms which they provided. As explained earlier in this section, I explicitly encouraged the interviewees to respond in any language they prefer. Being EFL teachers, most of them preferred using English, but occasionally shifted to Arabic (Standard or Algerian dialect) or French while others responded primarily in Arabic (standard or the Algerian dialect). As I conducted all the interviews by myself and as I share the same linguistic background as the interviewees, the shifts between the different languages did not represent a barrier. With the interviewees' consent, the interviews and focus group discussions were audio-recorded to be

subsequently transcribed. This was crucial for ensuring that no important data is lost. Individual interviews were conducted face to face and interviewees were invited to choose the time and venue in which they preferred to be interviewed. Interviews were, accordingly, conducted in vacant classrooms. Overall, the individual interviews lasted for an average of half an hour.

Throughout the entire duration of the fieldwork, and even after it ended, I maintained good relationships with participant teachers, which resulted in mutual respect and trust (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018), leading the participants to open up and provide richer responses. Data obtained through individual semi-structured interviews primarily addressed the first and third research questions, revealing participant teachers' perceptions of teacher leadership and the factors which they believe either support or hinder teacher leadership enactment within their context, but also provided evidence that supported findings related to the second and fourth research questions.

4.5.2. Written Reflections

Deciding on how to get insights into teachers' practices of teacher leadership was not straightforward. Initially, the aim was to focus on teachers' actual practices using data obtained through observations. This was, however, not feasible for various reasons. First, given the multifaceted nature of teacher leadership and the various roles and practices that fall under this concept, it was difficult to decide what it is that should be the focus for the observations. That is, observing teachers within their classrooms, for instance, would limit the scope of the study as it would not account for teacher leadership practices beyond classrooms or even broadly beyond the school context. Moreover, even when I considered focusing on observing teachers' practices both within and beyond their classrooms (observing meetings, for instance), issues of access and sensitivity emerged. Based on my knowledge of the research context, I was aware that I might not be allowed to attend and observe these meetings given that I am not a staff member. The restrictions that followed the spread of Covid-19 further hindered conducting observations. More importantly, I gradually realised that observing teachers' practices would have shifted the study's focus from examining participant teachers' perceptions of their own leadership practices to observing and evaluating their practices, which would not be consistent with the study's overall aim to give voice to participant teachers.

Given the above limitations, I decided to shift my focus from teachers' actual (observed) practices to their self-reported practices of teacher leadership, which I decided to address using written reflections to complement the individual semi-structured interviews. Unlike interviews, written reflections are more likely to provide participant teachers with more time and a comfortable space to reflect on their own practices and experiences and to decide on any incident in which they believe they practised teacher leadership and report it in an elaborated written form. Notably, reflective writing is being acknowledged as a mainstream data collection instrument in qualitative research

(Jasper, 2005). Through reflective writing, research participants can provide narrative reflections on the research issue. Therefore, it can be said that reflective writing is a representation of participants' internal dialogue with themselves (Smith, 1999). According to Jasper (2005), researchers can collect primary data in relation to participants' reflections using autobiographies, reflective reviews, journals and vlogs or critical incidents. Within the current research, teachers were not requested to keep diaries, but were rather requested and were given time to think through their previous experiences with or practices of teacher leadership, and to write down their reflections in the form of an essay. The use of reflective writing in this study is hence consistent with Jasper's (2005) description of critical incidents. Instruction for written reflections involved only one statement in which participant teachers were requested to write a reflective essay describing a previous incident, an experience with or practice of teacher leadership. The length of the essay was determined as no more than 400 words to keep their writing more focused (see appendix C). At this phase, too, participants were encouraged to write in any language that they preferred. Data obtained from teachers' written reflections essentially addressed the second research question.

One issue with the use of reflective writing is that of individual bias, which may affect credibility of the data (Jasper, 2005). The current study addresses this issue by triangulating findings of written reflections with findings of individual interviews and focus groups. Interestingly, themes that emerged from teachers' written reflections were largely consistent with findings emerging from individual interviews as explained in section 5.3.

4.5.3. Focus Group Discussions

A focus group is an interview with a group of people 'who have a common interest or characteristic, assembled by a moderator, who uses the group and its interaction as a way to gain information about a particular issue' (William and Katz, 2001, p.46). Focus groups provide a comfortable space in which participants can socially share their views, experiences, and attitudes regarding the research subject (Krueger and Casey, 2015). In the field of education, Williams and Katz (2001) highlight the relevance and usefulness of group interviews in investigating views of a particular group of stakeholders regarding a specific issue. Krueger and Casey (2015) outline five main components of a focus group: '(1) a small group of people, who (2) possess certain characteristics, (3) provide qualitative data (4) in a focused discussion (5) to help understand the topic of interest' (p. 6). This study endorses this description of focus group discussions. Focus groups are, thus, more than a random gathering of individuals but rather a group that is characterised by its own purpose, size, procedures, and composition.

The decision to use focus groups in the present study is attributed to two main reasons. First, using focus groups to address the fourth research question is deemed appropriate given that my aim

is to examine the range of perceptions and perspectives of teachers regarding the role of collaboration within teachers' communities on enhancing their professional growth as teacher leaders. This is in line with Krueger and Casey's (2015) suggestion that researchers should consider employing focus groups if the aim is to examine the range of perceptions, feelings or ideas that people hold regarding a specific issue, practice, behaviour, programme or policy; to investigate the range of perceptions, feelings or ideas that people hold regarding a specific issue; or to understand the various perspectives through which different groups of people perceive a certain issue. Second, focus groups could create an interactive social space in which participant teachers could complement and build up on each other's responses, leading to a more extended and complete record of participants' views, and as such they are more likely to gain insights into the research issue that would otherwise remain untold (Robinson, 2012). Group interviews are more likely to 'stimulate the respondents and support them in remembering events' and 'can lead beyond the answers of the single interviewee' (Flick, 2014, p. 243). Krueger and Casey (2015) contend that when interacting with people who share common characteristics or similar attitudes towards a phenomenon, group members tend to open up more given their sense of validation.

Within the present study, I conducted three online focus groups (see Appendix D for the focus group questions). My aim was initially to conduct face-to-face focus groups. However, arranging for face-to-face focus groups at a time and setting that were convenient for all teachers was not possible. Teachers had different timetables and most of them stressed that due to their personal commitments, they could not join the face-to-face focus groups during weekends. Under the Covid-19 restrictions, conducting face-to-face focus groups became even more challenging. Therefore, after spending much time pursuing this, I decided to shift to online focus groups.

Online focus groups are particularly distinguished from face-to-face focus groups in that the discussion takes place in a network computer environment. Online focus groups, in the present study, were conducted via Zoom, being the preferred choice for all participants who stressed their familiarity with it. I conducted three online heterogeneous focus groups, each consisting of four participant teachers. The groups were heterogeneous in the sense that each group involved at least one positional teacher leader. Heterogeneous focus groups are useful in that they can stimulate the discussion and may lead other members within the group to consider the topic from a different perspective (Brown, 1999, cited in Robson, 2011). However, they can be affected by power imbalances and could be dominated by one participant. Therefore, I had to carefully moderate the focus group discussions to ensure that all participants are equally involved, and that no teacher is being left out. The fact that participants in each group were in most cases not peers working within the same school and that the

focus groups were conducted online via Zoom with teachers choosing to turn off their cameras might have provided them with a more comfortable space to express their viewpoints freely and openly. As part of my preparation to conduct the online focus groups, my supervisors put me in touch with another PhD student at UWS, who had already conducted online focus groups for his research. In light of the insightful guidelines and remarks that he provided, I arranged an online focus group session with three Algerian PhD candidates (one from UWS and two from my home university in Algeria) for further practice on moderating the session.

As for the three main focus group discussions conducted as part of this research, each session began by explaining ground rules, ensuring participant teachers, for instance, that all information they provide is useful to the research and all views are valid, that they have the right to withdraw at any time or to not respond to any questions, that anonymity and privacy are fundamental, and that the discussions will be audio-recorded upon their consent (Gray, 2014). By the beginning of each session, teachers were also reminded and encouraged to respond in any language(s) that they prefer. My role was mainly to ‘orchestrate’ each of the three sessions and to ensure that the discussion remained focused on relevant topics (Gray, 2014, p. 474), yet at the same time I had to remain open to what emerged from participants’ responses and to follow their lines of thought. With teachers consent, the discussions were audio-recorded via Zoom and a personal recording device. Each session lasted for around an hour and fifty minutes. Most participant teachers praised the use of focus groups and expressed their willingness to take part in any future focus group discussions. Some stressed that participating in the focus group discussion was a learning experience for them while others urged me to keep in touch with them and to organise other focus groups to which they would invite other colleagues to discuss various matters related to the teaching of English and to teachers’ roles in Algeria overall.

Following the discussion in sections 4.2, 4.3, 4.4 and 4.5, table 4.2 summarises the relativist ontological and epistemological underpinnings as well as the methodology adopted and methods employed in the present study.

Research Paradigm	Ontology (The nature of reality)	Epistemology (The nature of knowledge)	Research Methodology (Approach to enquiry)	Research Methods
Interpretive paradigm	Relativist ontology Multiple realities of teacher leadership, which is seen as multifaceted, intangible and context-bound.	Subjectivist epistemology Knowledge about teacher leadership in this study is considered to be subjective and personal and is obtained through interaction with a group of Algerian middle school EFL teachers and interpretation of their subjective views.	Qualitative exploratory research This study adopts an exploratory qualitative research approach which is interested in listening to the subjective views and experiences of a group of Algerian middle school EFL teachers.	Knowledge about teacher leadership is obtained through interaction with a group of EFL middle school teachers, using: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual semi-structured interviews • Written reflections • Focus group discussions

Table 4.2. Summary of the Study’s Research Paradigm

4.6. Data Analysis

Data analysis represents a fundamental part of any research, as without it, ‘little sense can be made of a huge collection of data’ (Walliman, 2005, p. 301). That is, only when researchers analyse the collected data can the bigger picture be understood by their readers. Bloomberg and Volpe (2023) explain that analysing data involves ‘reducing raw data, identifying what is significant and constructing a framework for communicating the essence of what the data reveal’ (p. 9). Data analysis is therefore meant to make data more comprehensible and logical in relation with the participants’ responses regarding the issue being investigated. Research methodology literature suggests various techniques for analysing qualitative data as the way data is approached depends largely on the research purposes (Punch, 2009). Creswell (2013) asserts that when analysing qualitative data, researchers may follow differing directions in listening to the collected data, understanding it, and conceptualising

themes from it. Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) corroborate this view, maintaining that in qualitative research, ‘there is no one single or correct way to analyse and present qualitative data; how one does it should abide by fitness for purpose’ (p. 643).

Since the present research is an attempt to gain deep insights into teachers’ views and perspectives about teacher leadership, the collected data from the three data sets was analysed using thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is one of the most recognised and widely used methods for analysing qualitative data that is based on the identifications of patterns and themes related to the research questions (Braun and Clarke, 2019). Particularly, I adopted a reflexive thematic analysis approach, which ‘emphasises the importance of the researcher’s subjectivity as analytic source, and their reflexive engagement with theory, data and interpretation’ (Braun and Clarke, 2021, p. 330). Apart from the fact that thematic analysis is compatible with the aims of the current research, the choice of this approach to data analysis also relates to its flexibility as a method as it allows researchers to choose to approach their data either inductively (starting the analysis without any set of pre-identified themes, and deriving themes from the collected data itself), or deductively (analysing and coding data based on ideas and concepts that the researcher brings to the analysis and using data for illustrating those themes). Reflexive thematic analysis enabled me to better understand my findings while acknowledging and reflecting on connections between my emergent findings and existing concepts and theories (Braun and Clarke, 2022), which in turn helped me to make sense of and better interpret my findings.

The current study, thus, follows the six phases for thematic analysis proposed by Braun and Clarke (2006; 2012; 2019; 2021). It is important to note, however, that data analysis should not be viewed as a purely linear or sequential process, but rather a more recursive and cyclic one (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Therefore, although I present the data analysis through six main stages, the process was rather recursive as I constantly moved forward and backward between the different data sets and the analysis stages. The six phases suggested by Braun and Clarke (2006), thus, served as a systematic, yet flexible guide for analysing qualitative data as follows:

Phase 1. Familiarising oneself with the data:

This initial phase of data analysis requires researchers to immerse themselves in the collected data. This was done by repeatedly listening to the audio recordings and then transcribing the interviews and focus group discussions and typing teachers’ written reflections in word documents (see appendices E, F, G). Given that the analysis is carried out on the transcripts rather than the audio-recordings, it is fundamental to ensure the quality and accuracy of the transcripts (Clarke and Braun, 2013). Therefore, at this stage, I strived to accurately and correctly transcribe the data. This is mainly why I decided to manually transcribe all the individual interviews and focus group discussions rather

than using voice recognition programmes as these could affect the reliability of the transcription (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018). Manual transcription was equally more appropriate as the interviews and focus groups were mixed of different languages. I transcribed each interview and focus group discussion directly after conducting it following Gillham's (2000) suggestion that when researchers transcribe interviews directly after conducting them, their memory would help them 'in hearing what is on the tape' (p. 71). An issue that required consideration during transcription of the individual and group interviews was the language. As explained earlier in section 4.5.1, participants in this study were encouraged to respond in any language they prefer. Participant teachers, accordingly, shifted between English, the Algerian dialect, standard Arabic and to a lesser degree French, which required me to translate parts that were not in English. To increase the reliability of my translation and ensure that it captured the exact meanings that my participants conveyed in the original language, I requested two of my PhD colleagues who share the same cultural and linguistic backgrounds with both the researcher and participant teachers to translate the parts that were in languages other than English and then compared their translations with my own to check for accuracy. No major differences between the three translated versions were found. It is worth noting that transcripts were only shared with my two colleagues after I requested and obtained permission from participant teachers. Moreover, for extracts that were somewhat challenging to translate, I also referred back to some participants to check whether the meanings that they intended to convey were still represented. After I finished the transcription (and when relevant, the translation) of each session, I replayed the audio-recordings multiple times as I read through the final transcripts to re-check their accuracy. Finally, to ensure confidentiality, all transcripts were anonymised using the pseudonyms chosen by the participants and were kept in my password-protected computer. I then engaged in reading and rereading the transcripts to obtain a general sense of my data as suggested by Creswell (2013). Although manually transcribing and reading such voluminous data was overwhelming and time-consuming, it was an essential initial step that enabled me to intensively engage with the data and allowed me to note down some initial thoughts.

Phase 2: Generating initial codes:

After several readings of the data and taking initial notes, I started coding participants' responses (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Coding entails identifying segments and aspects within the data set that are relevant and responsive to the research questions (Braun and Clarke, 2006, Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). Watling et al. (2012) specify that within research, codes can be either pre-specified or emergent from the collected data. In the case of this study, I approached the data and completed the coding process inductively. Following Seidman's (2013, p. 120) advice, my aim was to allow the transcripts to 'breathe and speak' for themselves, instead of categorising participants' responses into

a set of pre-determined categories. With all that said, it is worth highlighting that coding can be a relatively challenging and complex process, particularly for novice or beginning qualitative researchers. One possible way to facilitate the coding process is what Gibbs (2007) refer to as ‘intensive reading’, which entails precise and careful reading of a given text to determine what it is about.

It is important to note that data in the present study was coded manually. Although manual coding might be both messy and time consuming, it further enhanced my familiarity with the data (McLafferty and Farley 2006). I, accordingly, printed all transcripts and left a double space between each line of participants’ responses to write the codes below. I used a collection of highlighters and colour pens and started reading each transcript, I highlighted words, phrases, or sentences which I considered helpful and relevant for understanding participants’ accounts regarding the research topic and for answering the research questions and assigned codes for each meaningful segment of data (see appendix H for an example). This process was repeated with every transcript.

Phase 3: Searching for themes:

This stage entails organising and sorting the codes into broader themes; putting relevant codes under appropriate themes and removing any irrelevant or unwanted codes. According to Braun and Clarke (2006, p. 82), a theme ‘captures something important about the data in relation to the research question and represents some level of patterned response or meaning within the data set’. Themes should be developed during coding as the analyst is supposed to decide ‘what seems to go with what’. Initially, a small set of themes should be identified. Then, these can be edited, further chunks can be added throughout the analysis process, and themes can be organized based on their importance and relevance. By the end, less themes will be left ‘as various runners are disconfirmed by the data’ (Robson, 2011, p. 475).

I accordingly grouped similar codes into units with a common concept or idea as I searched for connections that link the initial codes together. In doing this, I had to remind myself that grouping certain codes together was ‘not just because they were exactly alike or very much alike, but because they might also have something in common – even if, paradoxically, that commonality consists of differences’ (Saldaña, 2009, p. 6). Codes referring to support from peers, for instance, had both positive and negative references in the interviewees’ responses; however, they have a common subject.

Phases 4 and 5: Reviewing and Defining themes:

At this stage, I re-examined themes from the previous phase by reviewing the coded extracts and ensuring that they fit to the themes under which they are classified. This stage also involved re-checking relationships between the identified themes and codes and ensuring that they actually reflect

the meaning of the data and to merge some themes if needed. Such revisions may lead to combining some themes together or splitting some themes into more themes. Auerbach and Silverstein (2003) perceive it as a ‘positive step, because it means that you are learning about your participants’ subjective experience in a more nuanced way’ (p. 62). After finding all the themes that are relevant to the research questions, I had to label each theme. In doing so, I tried to choose titles that best reflected the essence of each theme and most importantly involved participant teachers’ voices (Howitt and Cramer, 2011, p. 340). At this stage, I developed a map outlining the emergent themes and their subthemes which I then checked with reference to the research questions as suggested by Saldaña (2009). Despite the importance of coding and re-examining themes, Braun and Clarke (2007) insist that researchers should know when this process is supposed to end. Particularly, they emphasise that this phase should end when the researcher realises that the refinements he/ she is making are no longer adding anything significant.

Phase 6: Producing a report:

In this final phase, researchers are supposed to produce a report, presenting the data in a coherent and interesting way. For Braun and Clarke (2006), researchers, at this stage, get to ‘tell the complicated story’ of the data that they collected in a simplified way that would persuade the readers of the significance and validity of their analysis (p. 87). When reporting the data, researchers must ‘provide excerpts from their data to give the reader a real sense of how what was learned played out in the actual settings examined’ (Hatch, 2002, p. 225). Accordingly, I first selected relevant extracts that support each theme or sub-theme and then added my interpretations of the extracts. The four research questions that guided this study provided the framework within which I presented the findings in chapter five. The findings were then discussed in relation to the underpinning conceptual framework and the reviewed literature in chapter six. In presenting the findings, and given that the aim of this research is to provide a collective and holistic understanding of teacher leadership in the Algerian middle school context, data obtained from teachers from the five middle schools was triangulated. In doing so, care was given to highlight any divergence noted between responses of promoted and non-promoted teachers or between teachers from different schools. As for describing participants and sources of the extracts in chapter five, I used participants’ pseudonyms followed by abbreviations for their positions and letters referring to the schools they teach in as well as the source of the extract and line numbers. I, thus, abbreviated ‘**Teacher**’ to ‘**T**’, ‘**Principal Teacher**’ to ‘**PT**’, ‘**Teacher Mentor**’ to ‘**TM**’, ‘**interview**’ to ‘**Int**’, ‘**written reflections**’ to ‘**Ref**’ and ‘**focus groups**’ to ‘**FG1**’, ‘**FG2**’ and ‘**FG3**’. For example, an extract from Abdou, a teacher from school C, interview, lines 7-8 is noted as (**Abdou, T, C, Int 7-8**).

It is important to stress at this point that throughout the research process, including the data collection and analysis phases, I had to carefully consider my positionality and role as a researcher. This is discussed in more detail in the following section.

4.7. Researcher's Positionality

One of the crucial aspects that researchers need to clarify and discuss is their role and positionality within the research that they conduct. In this regard, Hammond and Wellington (2013) assert that it is essential for researchers to address the issue of positionality particularly when their research requires 'a greater asymmetry between the researcher and the researched' (p. 118). Creswell (2013) similarly argues that in any qualitative research, the distance between the researcher and the researched can have its own influence on bias within the enquiry. The importance of a researcher's role is in that it may, and often does, serve as an instrument for data collection and analysis in interpretive studies (Koshy, 2005). It is thus necessary for researchers both to understand and explain their position within their research and to acknowledge the potential advantages and disadvantages it may have for the research process and its findings.

Although it is generally claimed that research within social sciences is supposed to maintain a neutral position, many social sciences researchers have recently argued that maintaining such a position may not be possible. According to Berg (2004), 'research is seldom, if ever, really value neutral' (p. 155). Researchers often have a particular rationale behind the choice of their research topics, which are usually inspired by their social and professional background or by their personal interests and motivations. Hammond and Wellington (2013), for instance, explain that educational researchers who have previously been pupils or students within the research context may be affected by their own beliefs and background. In such situations, the researcher's positionality can represent a sensitive issue as it may trigger certain subjective interpretations.

As for the current research, my role as a researcher has been shifting between the position of an insider and that of an outsider. This dual role is discussed in more details in this section with reference to its implications for the current research and to the advantages and disadvantages of each of the two roles.

As defined by Merton (1972, cited in Greene, 2014), an insider researcher is a researcher who has knowledge and understanding of the context, resulting from his or her experience within the community. As per my case, I was born in Algeria where I spent my entire life and received my education for 18 years. That is, I was raised and educated within a similar context in which this research is conducted, which positions me as an insider to the research context, resulting in both advantages and disadvantages. One of the main advantages of being an insider researcher is the possibility of providing a detailed description of the research context (Miles and Huberman, 1994).

As argued by Mercer (2007), my position as an insider researcher also facilitated my access to the research sites and participants and enabled me to build and maintain stronger rapport and trust which encouraged my participants, for the most part, to openly share their views and comfortably address various issues, resulting in the collection of in-depth and rich data. Likewise, being an Algerian researcher, I share the same social, cultural and linguistic background with my participants. The shared linguistic background in particular allowed my research participants to switch between different languages to better convey their ideas and equally allowed me to effectively communicate with them regardless of the language used. Despite these advantages, my insider position also had some shortcomings that might have affected certain aspects of data collection and analysis. For instance, when conducting interviews, participant teachers sometimes left some statements unfinished assuming that, being an Algerian, I already knew everything, which required me to follow up and request further clarifications to ensure that I do not misinterpret their answers. Likewise, Hellowell (2006) argues that research might be less objective when the researcher is highly familiar with the research participants. It could, thus, be the case that when analysing data, insider researchers might miss some aspects or details which they believe to be natural; issues that an outsider researcher may perceive as important to examine. I sought to minimise such risks in this research as I frequently shared and discussed sections from my research findings chapter with my supervisors and other PhD colleagues who are outsiders to the Algerian context.

On some occasions, I considered myself an outsider and I might also have been considered so by my participants, particularly at the early stages of the fieldwork. Despite my familiarity with the Algerian broader context and the overall structure of the educational system, I have no prior teaching experience, and as such I had limited understanding and awareness of school dynamics and teachers' roles as practiced within their workplace. Similarly, being an international student at UWS highly influenced my attitude and identity as a researcher as I became immersed in the UK research culture that is characterised by greater levels of formality with which I initially approached participant teachers. This might have led them to perceive me as an outsider. Such perceptions might have been further reinforced when I requested them to sign the consent forms and to permit me to record the interview and focus group sessions; something that teachers in Algeria are not familiar with. However, as I explained earlier, I gradually gained my participants' trust, which led them to provide richer and more detailed responses.

Balancing between those two roles was necessary to limit my subjective influence on the research process and outcomes as much as possible. Certain measures were further taken to limit any

impacts of my subjectivity and to increase the study's trustworthiness as discussed in the following section.

4.8. Research Trustworthiness

While within quantitative research, the value of any research is determined by its validity and reliability, the quality of a qualitative study can be evaluated by the degree of its trustworthiness. The term 'trustworthiness' was first introduced by Lincoln and Guba (1985) who emphasise that it represents the quality criteria for the constructivist paradigm. As defined by Bryman (2008, p. 700), trustworthiness is 'a set of criteria advocated by some writers for assessing the quality of qualitative research'. It is concerned with the way in which the investigator can persuade the readers of the value of the research findings. Although establishing trustworthiness when conducting qualitative research can mostly be more strived for than proven (Lincoln and Guba, 1989), scholars suggest some tools and guidelines that can help researchers to conduct more trustworthy qualitative studies (Nowell, Norris, White, and Moules, 2017). Essentially, researchers can enhance trustworthiness within their studies by thoroughly explaining their research procedures, considering four key criteria. These are credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Bryman, 2008; Given, 2008). Each of these criteria is discussed in this section, followed by an explanation of measures that were followed to enhance trustworthiness within the current research.

A. Credibility

Credibility refers to 'the methodological procedures and sources used to establish a high level of harmony between the participants' expressions and the researcher's interpretations of them' (Given, 2008, p. 138). Flick (2014, p. 257) further explains that credibility can be defined in terms of the extent to which research data are 'free from error or distortion'. This concept may be synonymous with the concept of internal validity within qualitative research in that it is concerned with how accurately the study describes the phenomenon that it aimed to examine (Shenton, 2004). Within qualitative research, researchers obtain results that are derived from the respondents' multiple realities; therefore, they should ensure that interpretations of these realities match their informants' views (Robson, 2011).

B. Transferability

Transferability is a notion consistent with the positivists' notion of generalisability. Bryman (2008) suggests that qualitative research is more concerned with depth rather than breadth, thus, it is more concerned with providing thick descriptions (Denscombe, 2010), and investigating and reporting 'slice-of-life' accounts (Denzin and Lincoln, 2000, p. 10). Therefore, generalisability of the findings cannot be assured and it is often not an aim in itself for qualitative researchers, which is the case for the current research. Instead of generalisability, qualitative researchers should follow certain measures to increase the potential transferability of their research findings. Briefly explained by Given (2008),

transferability refers to the researcher's awareness that the research findings could be similar and applicable to other contexts. Likewise, Lincoln and Guba (1985) suggest that appropriate transferability implies recognising 'the degree of similarity between the original situation and the situation to which it is transferred' (p. 8).

C. Dependability

Dependability refers to the process and procedures that aim to ensure that the enquiry process is logical, well documented and traceable (Schwandt, 2001). Lincoln and Guba (1985) and Merriam (2009) maintain that credibility and dependability are tightly related in that a 'demonstration of the former goes some distance in ensuring the latter' (Lincoln and Guba, cited in Shenton, 2004, p.71).

D. Confirmability

The fourth aspect to consider in relation to trustworthiness is *confirmability*, which indicates the researcher's attempt to ensure that his or her interpretations match the collected data rather than his or her views or interests (Given, 2008, Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Thus, to assure confirmability, researchers should not make any claims that cannot be confirmed or supported by the data.

A number of guidelines have been proposed by various methodologists and qualitative researchers to assess and enhance the quality of qualitative research. Rallis and Rossman (2009), for instance, propose five strategies: 'being there' (or 'prolonged engagement'); 'participant validation'; 'triangulation', 'using a critical friend' and 'using [one's] community of practice' (p. 269). Creswell and Creswell (2018) outline twelve criteria: member checking, triangulation, thick descriptions, reference to contradictory evidence, peer debriefing, reflexivity, external auditor, prolonged fieldwork time, transcript checking, and consistency of codes and themes. Guidelines provided by those authors overlap at different levels, and overall provide valuable strategies to enhance quality and rigour in qualitative research. In the present study, a combination of strategies proposed by Rallis and Rossman (2009) and Creswell and Creswell (2018) have been employed to ascertain research trustworthiness:

- **Being there (or prolonged engagement):** Patton (2015, p. 685) asserts that 'time is a major factor in the acquisition of trustworthy data'. This strategy is particularly useful for enhancing credibility of qualitative research. For the present study, I spent a period of almost eight months going back and forth between data collection and data analysis. Despite the challenges faced at the initial stage of the fieldwork in terms of recruiting participants, arranging for face-to-face focus group discussions, and eventually having to shift to online focus group discussions, I tried -to the best of my ability- to use this period as effectively as I could. Thus, the days when I had no interview scheduled, I ensured I was working on transcribing previously conducted interviews and completing any necessary translation. After I finished collecting the

data, I remained in contact with most participants via social media. The time spent with the participants enabled me to establish rapport and build trust and I believe was sufficient to understand participants' views and perspectives and to ensure that I 'have more than a snapshot view of the phenomenon' (Rallis and Rossman, 2009, p. 269).

- **Member checking:** This, according to Lincoln and Guba (1985), is considered 'the most critical technique for establishing credibility' (p. 314). Member checking is the process of seeking research participants' approval and validation of the transcribed interviews and feedback on early data analysis. Given that I conducted individual semi-structured interviews face-to-face during my stay in Algeria, I ensured that I transcribe interviews immediately after the interview session ends so that I could take back the transcripts to participants when I returned to their schools to conduct interviews with their peers. I accordingly requested their feedback on both the transcription and my translation of some of their responses. All individual interview transcripts were validated by teachers and returned with no suggested corrections. As explained earlier, upon my return to the UK, I remained in contact with most participants even after I finished data collection (mainly via Facebook Messenger, Instagram, and WhatsApp). It is important to note that these social media platforms were only used to keep in contact with my participants for the sake of member checking and were not used to collect any data. Given that I returned to the UK after completing the individual face-to-face interviews and collected teachers' written reflections, these social media platforms were the most preferred means for my participants to remain in contact with the researcher. That being said, I contacted some participant teachers whenever I needed to check what they exactly meant in some of their responses to validate my interpretations. Only on one occasion, one female participant, Nawel, provided more elaborations that clarified her response and enabled me to reconsider and revise my interpretation. As I approached participants for member checking, I was aware that due to their overwhelming workloads, it would be difficult for all participant teachers to devote more time to read the transcriptions, translations, and my initial interpretations. This justifies why it was not possible to follow this procedure for focus group discussions given teachers' personal commitments and the length of focus group transcripts compared to individual interviews.
- **Triangulation:** Data triangulation (Creswell and Creswell, 2018), also known as overlapping methods (Brown, 2014), was employed to enhance the study's credibility. As previously discussed in section 4.5.4, data for this research was collected using three data collection methods: individual semi-structured interviews, written reflections, and focus group discussions. The use of multiple data collection tools is likely to increase the research quality.

In the current research, on multiple occasions, data from the three tools yielded consistent and similar findings, which enhances the credibility of the study. The use of method triangulation can equally enhance the researcher's confidence in the research findings and therefore provides greater chances of transferability to other similar settings and situations (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Likewise, another kind of triangulation was undertaken across different locations. As discussed in section 4.4, participant teachers in this study were selected from five middle schools within the same district. Accordingly, views shared by teachers from these schools were triangulated, giving me a chance to explore the research phenomenon in different sites and to note convergences and divergences (if any).

- **External audit:** On multiple occasions, I seized opportunities to present and discuss my work in various conferences, seminars, and events (eg. International Professional Development Association Conference 2022, European Educational Research Association Emerging Researchers' Conference 2023, UWS TESOL 2023, UWS Festival 2023, and seminars organised by UWS and by my home university and other universities in Algeria). These were spaces where I discussed my research with academics who are not familiar with it, which allowed me to consider some aspects and perspectives. This was particularly useful as most of the feedback received and questions posed within such events were from outsiders' perspectives.
- **Thick descriptions:** These are 'deep, dense, detailed accounts' (Denzin, 1989, p.83) that aim to provide readers with 'an element of a shared experience' (Creswell, 2009, p.193). Within the current research, I aimed to provide as many detailed descriptions of the research context and participants as possible as well as detailed documentation of all the procedures and stages followed in conducting the research (Chapter 2 and sections 4.4 and 4.5). This also involved providing direct quotes from participants to support emerging themes and reporting difficulties that I encounter while conducting this research in Algerian public middle schools. Such thick descriptions are useful for enhancing the research dependability and transferability as they could both validate the findings and enable readers and researchers to judge the potential transferability of the present research findings to other contexts and situations (Merriam 2009). Within the present research, it might be plausible to assume transferability of the research findings to other public schools within the Algerian context given the highly centralised nature of the educational system which implies high levels of 'sameness' across public educational institutions. However, it remains up to the readers to judge transferability of the research findings to other contexts or situations in Algeria or beyond.

- **Peer debriefer/ critical friends:** Throughout the research process, face-to-face and virtual and meetings were regularly held with my supervisors to discuss the findings. Moreover, drafts of the research findings were regularly sent to my supervisors for feedback and comments. Other ‘critical friends’ that I had were fellow researchers at UWS and in Algeria whose research involved individuals who shared a similar social, linguistic and cultural background.

Taking all the above into consideration, I believe, would increase the trustworthiness of the current qualitative enquiry. A final issue that equally required careful consideration was adhering to the social sciences research ethics. This constitutes the discussion of the following section.

4.9. Ethical Considerations

Ethics in social sciences are defined as a system of codes and principles that guide the research process (Wellington, 2000; Wiles, 2013) and ‘regulate the relations of researchers to the people and fields they intend to study’ (Flick, 2014, p. 36). Accounting for ethical concerns is particularly important when conducting qualitative research as Punch (2014, p. 281) stresses that:

While all social research intrudes to some extent in people’s lives, qualitative research often intrudes more. Some qualitative research deals with the most sensitive, intimate and innermost matters in people’s lives, and ethical issues inevitably accompany the collection of such information.

Likewise, Wellington (2000) emphasises that ethical considerations must be ‘at the forefront of any research project and should continue through the write up and dissemination stages’ (p. 3). Research ethics, thus, deal particularly with the impacts that a given research may have on people who participate in it.

Within the present research and prior to starting the fieldwork, I applied for and obtained ethical approval from the University of the West of Scotland’s Ethics Committee. The application form provided details about the aims of the research, data collection methods, and procedures for selecting participants. After receiving the approval letter, I returned to Algeria and started the data collection process. Ethical concerns were equally carefully observed throughout the processes of data collection, data analysis, writing up of the thesis and dissemination of the research findings. To this end, as suggested by Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018), an important initial step was obtaining access to the research context upon gatekeepers’ consent. Moreover, and in accordance with BERA (2018), further measures undertaken in the present research included: obtaining participants’ consent and assuring transparency; ensuring privacy, confidentiality and anonymity of schools and participants; and minimising harm. These measures were carefully considered in this study as discussed below.

4.9.1. Gatekeepers and Negotiating Access

Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018, p. 310) maintain that managing entry to the research context begins with 'identifying the gatekeepers who facilitate entry and access to the group being investigated'. Gatekeepers in the case of the present research were the directors of the five selected schools. The five headmasters accepted and welcomed my presence in their schools. Initially, all of them stressed that in the case where my research involves accessing classrooms to observe lessons or interacting with students, I needed to obtain approval from the directorate of education at Setif province and accordingly provide a formal letter signed by the head of the directorate. However, as I explained the aims of my research and its focus on interaction with EFL teachers, all principals confirmed that no formal letter from the directorate is required. Apart from explaining the research aims and objectives, I also provided each school principal with a copy of a formal letter by my former supervisor, confirming my enrolment as a PhD student at UWS and the need to access schools for data collection purposes (see Appendix I). The five school principals not only welcomed my presence in their schools but also expressed their interest in the research topic. Two of them even engaged in insightful informal discussions with me and provided me with some policy documents that provided deeper insights into issues discussed in chapter two.

4.9.2. Informed Consent

Within research, the targeted participants need to take a decision as to whether they wish to take part in the study or not, and it is mandatory that sufficient information is provided to guide their decision. Israel and Hay (2006) emphasise that consent must be both informed and voluntary. The term 'informed' implies the necessity of adequately informing potential participants regarding the study that they are requested to take part in. While an informed consent can be either verbal or written, Bryman (2008) prefers written consent forms for they provide clear information about the research and role of participants. Therefore, in accordance with BERA (2018) and UWS Code of Ethics (University Ethics Committee, 2020), an important first step undertaken at the outset of the fieldwork for the current research was providing participants with necessary details about the research and seeking their consent to be involved in it.

That being said, information sheets were handed to all participants prior to data collection and their consent was only sought once they had read and fully understood the information provided (see appendices J and K). Although the information sheets provided all the necessary details about the research aims, data collection procedures and issues of confidentiality and anonymity, I ensured that I met the participants either individually or in groups within their schools so that we can go through the information sheet together and I invited them to ask any questions or raise any concerns. When meeting the participants, I explained that the present research is sponsored by the Algerian Ministry

of Higher Education and Scientific Research under the government's plan to enhance the status of EFL teaching and learning in Algeria. This was equally highlighted to the readers in this thesis. Following BERA (2018), this was essential for ensuring both transparency and acknowledgement. Participants were equally informed that interviews and focus group discussions would be recorded and that some of their responses from the three data sets would be quoted when reporting and discussing the research findings. One particular concern that some participants raised related to the need to record the interview and focus group sessions as they initially felt uncomfortable being recorded. I, therefore, had to stress the necessity for using the recorder while assuring them that it was particularly meant to ensure that none of the insights that they provide would be lost; that this would facilitate transcribing the data; and that no one would have access to the recordings apart from the researcher. Although they understood the reason for recording the interview and focus group sessions and initially agreed to be recorded, permission to record interviews and focus group discussions was again requested at the beginning of each interview or focus group session. Participants' consent was also voluntary in the sense that no pressure was put on the potential participants to accept being involved in the research. Participants in the current research were not coerced in any way and they were assured that even after accepting to participate, they still have the right to withdraw their consent at any time and for any reason (BERA, 2018). In case of withdrawal, they were assured that they should not feel the need to provide any justification or explanation.

4.9.3. Privacy, Confidentiality and Anonymity

BERA (2018) maintains that 'researchers should recognise the entitlement of both institutions and individual participants to privacy, and should accord them their rights to confidentiality and anonymity' (p.21). This issue is particularly relevant to the present research given that privacy of schools, anonymity of participants and confidentiality of the information they shared had to be carefully considered. For this reason, names of the selected schools were not mentioned, and the schools were rather referred to using letters A to E. Although more details concerning the schools' size, numbers of teachers and students as well as percentage of students' success in the middle school exit exam were obtained and constituted the criteria upon which the five schools were selected, a decision was made to conceal such information for it might cause these institutions to be identified.

Apart from the above, great care was given to preserve participants' identities and confidentiality of the data that they provided. The information sheets handed to each participant teacher covered issues of anonymity and confidentiality of both participants and their responses. Assuring confidentiality and anonymity is crucial, as it enabled participant teachers to express themselves in the most truthful way possible. To do so, pseudonyms selected by the participants were used to refer to them and identifying details were removed. When conducting individual interviews

and focus group discussions, I ensured that I did not refer to the interviewees with their real names. Equally, when transcribing interviews and focus groups, I ensured that any names of individuals or schools and any identifying information was removed. Anonymity was also carefully considered throughout the writing up phase and when making presentations in relation to the current research by avoiding disclosure of any details that would facilitate identifying the participants.

Within the present research, personal equipment was used to record all the interviews and focus group discussions. In terms of data storage, and to ensure confidentiality of the participants' responses, data in all forms was kept in a safe place prior to its transcription and was only accessed by the researcher. After transcription, the Microsoft Word files were similarly labelled under the participants' chosen pseudonyms. These were safely stored in my password-protected computer and the collected data was only used for the purpose of the study. Assuring confidentiality can often be more challenging due to the possibility of having participants disclose the discussion content to others (Hennink, 2014). This could particularly be the case for focus group discussions. Thus, to minimise threats of informants' disclosure, I had to constantly remind the research participants that all content must remain confidential and that they should not divulge it outside the group. Data collected for the present research will be disposed 6 months after the completion of my doctoral studies.

4.9.4. Avoiding Harm

The final element that was taken into consideration is avoiding harm, which can take the form of physical, social, psychological or economic harm. Assuring confidentiality and avoiding deception are amongst the main strategies to minimise any potential harm to the participants. Deception relates to the researcher's attempt to represent their work differently from what it actually is (Bryman, 2008). Avoiding deception is fundamental as this latter affects informants' cooperation in research and avoiding it can enhance their active participation (Singer and Frankle, 1982). Within the present research, participants were adequately informed about the research aims and transparency was assured by informing them that the present research is sponsored by the Algerian MHESR under the government's plan to promote English language teaching and learning in the country. According to BERA (2018, p. 19), 'ethical research design and execution aim to both put participants at ease and avoid making excessive demands on them'. This was an issue that I had to carefully consider. As explained in section 4.4.2, when I first approached the research participants, I initially invited them to contribute to the three data sets employed within the present research. While some participants agreed on that, others stressed their interest and willingness to participate but expressed their concerns as to whether or not they could participate in the three data sets given their overwhelming workloads and their personal commitments. As insisting on their participation in the three data sets might have put them under pressure and might have resulted in their reluctance to take part in the research, I had to

be more flexible as to what data set each participant is capable and available to contribute to. Similarly, I showed flexibility as to the time that teachers found suitable for the individual interviews and focus group discussions so that their participation in the research does not interrupt their working schedules. During each individual interview or focus group session, I tried to break the ice to put the participants at ease and to avoid any discomfort or distress. Moreover, considering the possibility that participants might be afraid of being judged, and thus feel stressed during the interviews or focus groups or when reflecting on their own practices, I had to ensure them that my aim was to explore their perspectives and not to evaluate their knowledge. By the beginning of each individual interview or focus group session and when requesting them to provide their written reflections, I reminded the participants that there were no right or wrong answers, rather all their views, accounts and experiences matter and are crucial for the present research.

4.10. Chapter Summary

In this chapter, I provided a detailed account of the current study's design. In doing so, I began by explaining how the interpretive paradigm informed the research design, and justifying the appropriateness of adopting a qualitative exploratory approach to address the research aims and questions. The chapter equally highlighted the procedures for selecting participants and outlined the data collection methods employed in this qualitative exploratory research. Subsequently, a discussion of the data analysis procedures employed in this study as well as issues related to my positionality within the present research and strategies adopted to enhance the research trustworthiness was provided. To conclude the chapter, measures undertaken with reference to ethical considerations within the present research were outlined. The following chapter presents findings that emerged from the analysis of teachers' individual semi-structured interviews, written reflections and the three online focus group discussions.

Chapter Five: Research Findings

5.1. Introduction

This chapter presents findings obtained through individual semi-structured interviews, written reflections, and focus group discussions. The findings are organised into four broad sections based on the study's aims and main research questions outlined below.

1. What perceptions do middle school EFL teachers hold regarding teacher leadership?
2. What are middle school EFL teachers' reported practices of and experiences with teacher leadership?
3. What factors reportedly hinder/ foster their practice of leadership?
4. How do teachers view collaboration with each other as contributing to their professional development as teacher leaders?

The first section, thus, considers participants' perceptions of the concept of teacher leadership, establishing a detailed and holistic understanding of the nature of teacher leadership as perceived by a sample of Algerian middle school EFL teachers. Section two, then, addresses participants' reported teacher leadership practices. The third section uncovers supports and hindrances of teacher leadership in the participants' context. Finally, section four presents participants' perceptions of the role of informal collaboration within teachers' communities in enhancing their professional learning and growth as teacher leaders.

As this chapter seeks to provide detailed accounts of Algerian middle school EFL teachers' views, extracts from the interviews, reflective essays and focus group discussions have been used to report findings in participants' own words and to support emergent themes. From here on, teachers, in this chapter, will be identified as **T**, principal teachers as **PT**, and teacher mentors as **TM**. Similarly, data from interviews will be identified as **Int**, from written reflections as **Ref**, and from focus groups as **FG1**, **FG2** and **FG3**, followed by the extracts' line number(s) from the respective transcripts. For example, **Nawel [PT, B, FG2 15-17]** refers to Nawel's contribution from the second focus group, lines 15 to 17 in the transcript, as a principal teacher from school B. Further details regarding the participants, mainly in terms of their gender and years of experience, were presented in table 4.1 in the methodology chapter.

5.2. Conceptualising teacher leadership: Algerian middle school EFL teachers' perspectives

This section considers participants' perceptions of the concept of teacher leadership. Findings presented in this section emerged primarily from individual semi-structured interviews conducted with thirteen EFL middle school teachers. However, data from teachers' written reflections and focus group discussions is equally presented when relevant. Overall, the collected data revealed that while teacher leadership was not a term that participant teachers were familiar with, they articulated perceptions of the concept which indicated that they possessed some awareness and understanding of

what constitutes ‘teacher leadership’. Despite it being a new term for them, all interviewees across the five schools stressed its value and emphasised that the practice of leadership cannot be restricted to only one individual. In this regard, Sarah [T, B, Int 229-230], for instance, maintained ‘there is no teacher who is a leader and one who is not’.

Inductive analysis of teachers’ responses to the question ‘How would you define teacher leadership?’ led to the emergence of four major themes that related to practices within the classroom; practices beyond the classroom; a profile of teacher leaders and decision-making as an aspect of teacher leadership. Subsequently throughout the interviews, participants provided responses and examples that supported and expanded on those themes and equally highlighted their limited awareness of the available positional teacher leadership roles within their school contexts. Thus, the five themes presented subsequently in sections 5.2.1 to 5.2.5 provide a detailed and holistic understanding of teacher leadership from the participant teachers’ perspectives.

It is important to highlight at this stage that when sharing their perceptions of teacher leadership, it was noted that some participants referred to aspects that seemed to generally define an effective and competent classroom teacher rather than a teacher leader. This was particularly noted in sections 5.2.1 in which some participants referred to the role of a teacher within the classroom following the Competency Based Approach (CBA henceforth), and in section 5.2.4 as most participants referred to traits that could be seen as traits of effective and competent classroom teachers. It was important to present and highlight this for two main reasons. On the one hand, this might suggest that while some interviewees were to some extent aware of what constitutes teacher leadership but found the term unfamiliar, others might be less familiar with the concept of teacher leadership itself. On the other hand, their responses may alternatively suggest that, for some teachers, effectiveness as a classroom teacher constitutes a fundamental requirement for teachers to be teacher leaders. Based on the findings, it was equally interesting to note that all the examples that the interviewees provided in relation with teacher leadership practices within and beyond classrooms were non-positional in nature. Indeed, none of the interviewees defined teacher leadership in relation to teachers’ designated positions. Participants’ perceptions of teacher leadership as related to the five aforementioned themes are detailed in sections 5.2.1 to 5.2.5.

5.2.1. ‘Every teacher is a leader in his class’: Classrooms as the primary space for teacher leadership enactment

Defining teacher leadership in terms of teachers’ roles and practices within the classroom was the most recurrent theme in the data. Serine [PT, E, Int 75] emphasised that, for her, ‘every teacher is a leader in his class’. The interviewees’ responses in this regard centred on three main areas:

providing quality teaching; classroom management and maintaining a comfortable learning environment; and relationship with learners.

Many interviewees associated teacher leadership with *providing quality teaching for learners*. Abdou [T, C, Int 16-17], for instance, explained that teachers can be non-positional leaders within their classrooms by striving to provide their learners with the best teaching quality. Most participants equally stressed this, acknowledging that in order for teachers to fulfil this role, they must master their subject and possess extended pedagogical knowledge. In this sense, Heba [TM, A, Int 49] and Rokia [T, D, Int 61-62] stressed the importance of subject mastery, with Rokia viewing it as ‘the first requirement of being a leader in the classroom’. Apart from subject mastery, Ibtissem [TM, D, Int 12-13] explained that teacher leaders must be ‘directed towards achieving the learning objectives and must be completely aware of their role within the classroom’. To be more specific, many participants related teacher leadership practice within classrooms to the effective implementation of the Competency Based Approach (CBA), a learner-centred approach that is implemented in Algerian middle schools. Both Melina [PT, B, Int 39-42] and Sarah [T, B, Int 27-30] reported that according to CBA guidelines, teachers’ role is primarily to guide learners towards constructing knowledge and developing their competencies. Following the CBA guidelines, participants pointed out that a teacher leader is a teacher who can initiate activities and effectively elicit knowledge and information from the learners.

As a leader in your class, you should know your role. We teach according to the CBA. So, we just facilitate knowledge to the learner...we guide them and let them arrive to that knowledge by themselves [Heba, TM, A, Int 16-20]

The CBA is learner-centred and not teacher-centred. So, you should know this and know how to teach according to this approach to be the leader in your classroom with your pupils [Amine, T, A, Int 10-12]

A teacher leader just guides and supports the learners so that they themselves construct knowledge rather than sitting passively and receiving information. This is according to the CBA [Nour, T, C, Int 8-10]

As part of teacher leaders’ role in providing quality teaching, many interviewees shared the view that teacher leaders are teachers who design and implement creative teaching strategies to enhance their learning. In doing so, teacher leaders seek to accommodate their students’ needs and learning preferences. Melina [PT, B, Int 57-60], for instance, maintained:

A teacher leader does not stay the same way, presenting the lesson the same way...he creates new strategies according to the learners’ needs and capacities.

This view was echoed by Nawel [PT, B, Int 15-17], Nour [T, C, Int 47-48] and Maria [T, B, Int 32-33] who, respectively, stressed the importance of creativity in planning and delivering lessons

as an essential aspect of teacher leadership that, for them, would significantly enhance students' engagement and achievements as well as earn teachers recognition and respect among their peers.

He must always remember that the classroom is diverse. You have students who learn differently. So, you must plan your lessons according to their needs [PT, B, Int 15-17]

Teacher leaders are innovative in planning lessons that would meet the needs and learning styles of their students [T, C, Int 47-48]

Creativity in teaching is important...the teacher leader delivers the lesson in creative ways to support all the learners [T, B, Int 32-33]

Such a link between teacher leadership and teachers' innovative and differentiated instructional practices was equally noted in participants' written reflections. In this sense, Abdou [T, C, Ref 8-11], Sarah [T, B, Ref 9-13] and Nour [T, C, Ref 5-8] highlighted their innovative instructional practices as teacher leadership practices. These will be discussed in more detail in section 5.3.

Establishing and maintaining a suitable learning environment is yet another important aspect of teacher leadership inside the classroom as perceived by some participants. In this regard, Abdou [T, C, Int 62-63] shared the viewpoint that teacher leaders are teachers who are capable of establishing an appropriate learning atmosphere for their learners as he explained: 'a teacher leader is a teacher who can provide the right healthy atmosphere to the class'. Echoing this view, Maria [T, B, Int 30-31] stressed that teacher leadership entails creating a positive learning environment for all learners, which necessitates effectiveness in terms of classroom management to maintain discipline within their classrooms:

Inside the classroom, they are responsible of maintaining discipline of their students so that the classroom has a suitable learning atmosphere.

Other participants reiterated these views while providing more concrete examples of strategies deployed to maintain discipline. In this sense, Nour [T, C, Int 50-53] and Serine [PT, E, Int 25-26] maintained that teacher leaders are teachers who set a classroom code of conduct from the beginning, detailing the rules that should be followed and the behaviours that are expected from the pupils and consistently applying them:

The teacher must set the class rules from the very beginning. The teacher must clarify what is required from the learners. I used to print those rules and give copies to my pupils to sign them. It's like a contract, and believe me when they sign the document; they feel responsible and follow the rules the whole time. [Nour, T, C, Int 50-53]

Make sure that the rules are understood by the whole class and that they become part of the class routine [Serine, PT, E, Int 25-26]

The above quotes demonstrate, according to Serine and Nour, the ways in which teacher leaders could maintain discipline within their classroom, and as a result ensure creating and maintaining an optimal learning environment for all learners.

The third area in relation to practices within the classroom related to *maintaining a good rapport and establishing positive relationships with the learners*. Data revealed that for some teachers, teacher leadership entails establishing and maintaining a good relationship with their learners, based on mutual respect, tolerance, understanding and patience. Rokia [T, D, Int], for instance, considered teacher leadership to go beyond transmitting knowledge to learners. For her, teacher leaders are teachers who can make their learners love their subject by building and maintaining a good relationship with them based on understanding, tolerance, and empathy.

A teacher leader is somebody who is willing to give their learners more than just the knowledge that they have to receive in the classroom. Their job is to lead, to guide, to help, to be sometimes a psychologist, a parent, or a caring friend [Rokia, T, D, Int 37-40]

She further emphasised that a teacher leader is the one who would go beyond the immediate lesson objectives, aiming at a greater goal that is instilling in the learners ‘a life-lasting appreciation for knowledge, for transcendence, and for curiosity’ to learn more. Teacher leaders were also perceived as teachers who are capable of motivating their learners and enhancing their self-confidence and ambition. This view was corroborated by Nour [T, C, Int 110-116] as she explained:

I used to display my pupils’ project in a room in our school and this really motivated them and enhanced their self-confidence and made them love me as a teacher and love my subject too. Also, I sometimes choose the best project and prepare a video and send it to the school administration to share it in the school’s Facebook page. This way, students become very motivated and try to give their best.

What was noted among all interviewees was their emphasis on the perception of teacher leaders as a symbol or a role model for their learners. Most participants maintained that role modelling is the primary means through which teacher leaders could influence their learners. Amine [T, A, Int 99] noted how pupils would consider teacher leaders as symbols and ‘even choose to become teachers because of them’. A similar view was shared by Rokia [T, D, Int 182-186] as she reflected on her experience as she was a pupil, perceiving some of her former teachers as teacher leaders who influenced her through role modelling. She stated:

I remember from my time as a student that a lot of teachers influenced me; the way they behaved with us, the way they managed their classroom and I think that was the get go for me to, to possess some of their traits, and implement them in my classes as well. I was myself really moved by some of my teachers, and that really just made me love the subject and the profession itself.

Apart from motivating their learners as in the examples provided above, most participants stressed that through their relationships with their learners, teacher leaders play a fundamental role in instilling ethics and values in their learners. Nawel [PT, B, Int 19-22] emphasised that teacher leaders' responsibility inside the classroom extends beyond their teaching practices, to preparing learners to become 'good citizens in their society'. She, then, emphasised that for this, it is mandatory that each lesson is given 'a civic dimension' with teachers being role models who aim to instil values, ethics, and desired behaviours in their learners. For her, learners would look up to their teachers and 'try to imitate them'.

Abdou [T, C, Int 17-19], Amine [T, A, Int 52-53] and Nour [T, C, Int 97-99] also stressed that as role models, teacher leaders can either intentionally or unintentionally instil morals and values in their learners. They, respectively, explained:

[a teacher leader] can give his students the moral things, not only education. We can give them morals because the teacher is the ideal of the students.

We are here raising them with morals and good manners.

As a teacher leader, you can influence your learners with your manners; the way you behave and treat others. A teacher leader is then a role model who aims to instil values in his learners.

Findings presented in this section indicate that for almost all participant teachers, classrooms represented the primary space within which teachers could practise leadership. Although some of the examples that some teachers provided in this regard seemed to be somewhat narrow in the sense that they appear to reflect practices and roles that might relate to roles of teachers in general rather than those of teacher leaders (particularly when they referred to the implementation of the CBA approach), the focus on classroom practices might suggest that for teachers in this study, learners are the main target of teacher leaders' influence. As such, these findings suggest that relying on their enhanced pedagogical and subject knowledge and innovation; their care and affection towards their learners; and their relationship-building skills, teacher leaders provide their learners with quality and innovative teaching; establish and maintain a positive learning environment; and lead by example as they model ethical behaviour. These practices were perceived to result in enhanced students' achievements and motivation as well as improved discipline and ethical behaviour. Notably, however, teachers perceived the classroom as the primary yet not the only space for teacher leadership enactment as for all of them teacher leadership practice and teacher leaders' influence expand beyond the classroom boundaries as will be discussed in the following section.

5.2.2. Teacher leadership extending beyond the classroom context

Interestingly, most interviewees stressed that teacher leadership is not confined to the classroom context. Rather, teacher leadership was perceived by most of them to involve a variety of practices beyond classrooms. The interviewees' examples in this regard related mainly to *collaboration with peers and motivating them; functioning as mediators between school senior management from the one side and learners and fellow teachers from the other side, and engaging with learners' parents.*

In her definition of teacher leadership, Sarah [T, B, Int 16-17] stated:

Participation and collaboration with colleagues. This is teacher leadership for me.

In the above quote, Sarah referred to an important aspect of teacher leadership practice beyond the classroom, namely *collaboration with peers*. Nawel [PT, B, Int 27-28], Rokia [T, D, Int 116], Abdou [T, C, Int 29-30] and Maria [T, B, Int 9] stressed this aspect too. Rokia even explained that 'leadership is about collaboration' and that 'one leader is not really going to do much'. Likewise, Serine's [PT, E, Int 11-13] definition of teacher leadership was mainly focussed on teachers sharing knowledge, expertise and experience with other teachers, stating that as part of teacher leadership, teachers are supposed to 'meet and exchange ideas, guide each other, share expertise and provide constructive feedback and encouragement for each other'. In that sense, collaborative work within the school represents an opportunity for those teachers to express and exchange viewpoints and to learn from one another.

An example of these collaborative practices was attending each other's classes and exchanging knowledge and innovative ideas and providing constructive feedback. This was highlighted by Maria [T, B, Int 126-128] and Nawel [PT, B, Int 127-131], for example, who mentioned that within their school, teachers regularly attend each other's sessions at least twice a month, and that by the end of each session that they attend, they engage in professional discussions in which they exchange constructive feedback, which would eventually enable them all to improve their instructional practices.

Each month we prepare to attend with our colleagues. After attending that lesson, we give our feedback. If the lesson was good, we ask our colleagues and they ask us if we need somethings to add [Maria, T, B, Int 126-128]

Teachers should attend sessions with different teachers, especially the principal teacher or trainer teachers in order to learn from their experience. They can be involved in this leadership through meetings, exchanging feedback, sharing responsibilities and experiences with the trainer teachers or the principal teachers. I do this with my colleagues. When teachers exchange ideas, I'm sure that they can be involved in this leadership [Nawel, PT, B, Int 127-131]

Most interviewees perceived establishing such collaborative and collegial relationships as a fundamental means through which teacher leaders could influence their peers. Collaboration with fellow teachers, in this sense, represented an opportunity for teachers to engage in professional discussions and exchange ideas related to their daily work and teaching practices within an environment in which teachers ‘respect each other’s viewpoints’ and ‘accept constructive feedback’ [Ibtissem, TM, D, Int 57-58]. Kenza [PT, C, Int 83-84] supported this view, insisting that through collaboration and being ‘an active part in a team’, teacher leaders can influence their peers into improved instructional practices. As explained by Chahine [T, C, Int 89-93], collaboration with peers represents a learning experience and an opportunity for professional growth for all teachers regardless of their positions or years of experience, mainly when teachers attend each other’s sessions:

For any teacher’s professional development, the teacher must attend classroom sessions with as many teachers as possible, not exclusively principal teachers, but even novice teachers can provide new ideas. Teachers can learn a lot from each other when they collaborate and attend each other’s lessons.

Moreover, some participants maintained that teacher leaders could motivate their peers outside the classroom and influence them towards improved instructional practices. Interestingly, such influence was often indirect. Several interviewees provided examples of how some teachers who they perceived as teacher leaders were role models who indirectly motivated them, or how they themselves indirectly motivated their peers. Reflecting on her lived experience, for instance, Sarah [T, B, Int 46-57] stated:

Teacher leaders can motivate even their colleagues and it happened for me once with my colleagues. So, I have once organised a planting campaign inside my school with one of my classrooms. It was within the unit that we are teaching. It was about the nature, the environment, and helping to preserve their environment. We went outside and the headmaster was with us. We planted trees, we cleaned the school, and I explained the lesson...the pupils got really motivated that the lesson was outside...This had impact on my colleagues...one of my colleagues, a teacher of geography, saw me from the window of the classroom and said: ‘oh, Sarah, I liked your lesson outside, I will do the same’ and she and other teachers really did. So, in here I participated as a leader unconsciously and other teachers get inspired.

The above quote by Sarah provided an example in which she ‘unconsciously’ motivated her colleagues. Although her innovative practice was directed to motivating her learners and improving their learning, given that this practice was visible to her peers, it had an indirect impact on them. Her peers were very impressed with the idea, which motivated them to organise activities for their pupils outside the classroom too. For her, in this incident in particular, she felt that she ‘unconsciously’ participated in leadership through the indirect influence she had on her colleagues.

Supporting this view of the indirect impact that teacher leaders can have on their peers beyond their classrooms, Rokia [T, D, Int 157-162] provided an example of a teacher who was filling a

vacancy within her school. She reported that although that teacher was not a permanent teacher, ‘every single day, she was trying to give her learners the best that she can’. Rokia’s impression of that teacher was that she was very ‘motivated to speak up’ and to drive change. She explained:

She did not receive support to take her students outside, but then there was a small hall inside the school that was really deserted and needed to be cleaned. So, this is a very small trait of leadership. She went there, despite the fact that she was not granted access to other areas. She brought a wheelbarrow, and she had two students with her, she cleaned it and it became a perfect area for having classes outside the classroom.

Rokia [T, D, Int 168] expressed that what that teacher did ‘marked’ her and will mark her ‘for the rest of her teaching career’.

Another example shared by Abdou [T, C, Int 107-108] showed how, for him, one of the main roles of teacher leaders beyond their classrooms is motivating and supporting colleagues through exchanging teaching-related knowledge and materials with peers and helping them to solve issues that they face. To illustrate, Abdou [T, C, Int 110-114] described one of his colleagues who is a computer science teacher and who never hesitates to help other teachers in matters related to the subject he teaches. In describing his colleague, Abdou stated:

I think he has the features of a leader, a leader teacher because he does good things for instance in exams he offers to help in supervising exams, and the days when we as teachers are supposed to fill and upload the pupils’ grades in a software, he offers to help those teachers who are not very accustomed to using technological software. He cares so much about his colleagues...he is always there to help.

Abdou was very impressed by his colleague, who he believes ‘possesses qualities of a teacher leader’ as he takes initiative in helping and supporting his peers both with issues that relate to his area of expertise and with issues related to supervising exams. He went further to admit that he often feels ‘jealous of him’ and explained how this teacher influenced him to manifest similar traits and ‘to become as supportive and collaborative’ as that teacher.

It could be clearly noted from the data, thus, that across the five schools, both positional teacher leaders and teachers who do not hold a positional leadership role perceived collaboration with peers as an essential aspect of teacher leadership. Interestingly, novice teachers, in particular, stressed that teacher leaders have a great potential to motivate their peers towards improved instructional practices.

Another aspect that was highlighted in relation with roles beyond the classroom was *the mediating role* that teachers can play within their schools. To illustrate, Ibtissem [TM, D, Int 48-56], and Nawel [PT, B, Int 35-39] referred to reports that teachers usually prepare and present at different meetings with the school senior management. As part of those meetings, teachers communicate to the school leadership teams issues related to students’ needs, achievements, and behaviours as well as

teachers' expectations and professional requirements. In so doing, they maintain, teachers function as a link between their students and peers and the school senior management and as collaborators with the school leadership team as they highlight, discuss, and evaluate issues that might intervene in the success of the teaching and learning process and could further contribute by suggesting possible solutions to such issues.

He (a teacher leader) also leads through sharing useful information with the administration about the situation inside the classroom. As teachers, for example, we can inform the headmaster about the achievements and requirements of our learners and about any problems we face or our colleagues face [Nawel, PT, B, Int 47-50]

Teachers are the main link between the classroom and the administration. We are the ones who inform the administration about the social and educational circumstances of our learners [Ibtissem, TM, D, Int 54-56]

Ibtissem [TM, D, Int 56] further stressed that through this mediating role, teacher leaders could significantly support their school principals as they represent the main source from which school principals and the administrative team as a whole can get detailed information about the learners' progress, achievements, and behaviour. Additionally, as mediators between classrooms and school management, teacher leaders not only communicated concerns or problems but can also assist school principals in solving various problems within the school by providing possible solutions as they attend meetings. In this regard, Amine [T, A, Int 108-112] and Nour [T, C, Int 121-123] explained that by communicating such concerns and taking part in solving various problems that the school faces, teachers would ease the burden of overworked school principals.

Interestingly, Maria [T, B, Int 135-138] was the only interviewee who identified *engagement with learners' parents* and keeping them informed about their children's scores and behaviour as an important aspect of teacher leadership that non-positional teacher leaders, like herself, can engage in. She explained:

The teacher leader always tries to be in contact with learners' parents. The teacher tries to let them be part of the learning process of their children. This can be very important for pupils' success. When you tell them about any problems with their children's scores or behaviour, you can work together to solve it.

Findings presented in this section reveal that for participant teachers, teacher leadership is not confined to the classroom, but rather extends beyond the classroom boundaries. Based on their competence, effectiveness, collaborative skills, and the relationships that teacher leaders establish with their peers, they can influence fellow teachers towards improved instructional practices as they collaborate with peers and provide professional support, and model innovative and effective instructional practices. These practices gain those teachers respect and recognition among their peers.

Beyond that, teachers' knowledge of the classrooms (including knowledge of learners' needs and potentials and peers' requirements) qualify them to function as mediators between the classrooms and the schools' senior management. Remarkably less frequent in the data was the role that teacher leaders play in terms of engaging parents. Another important aspect highlighted by teachers as relevant to teacher leadership is teachers' participation in decision-making as discussed in the following section.

5.2.3. Decision-making as an aspect of teacher leadership

In her definition of teacher leadership, an interesting point that Maria [T, B, Int 13-16] shared was participation in decision-making which she believed is an essential aspect of teacher leadership. When asked about the types of decisions that teachers could take, she explained that decision-making can take place both at the classroom level mainly in terms of lesson planning and delivery, teaching materials and pupils' seating arrangement; and outside the classroom as teachers collectively decide for the time and content of tests and exams.

In the classroom, he can decide how he arranges his students' seating. He can also decide about his lessons; how he will present them, through technology, using realia and so on. Outside the classroom, he can make decisions concerning the time of the tests and he decides with his colleagues on the content of the exams and tests.

Maria's view was echoed by her colleague Sarah [T, B, Int 152-155] who explained that participation in decision-making beyond the classroom is an important aspect of teacher leadership and maintained that within her school, it is mainly collective in nature as teachers often meet and discuss issues with their colleagues with each teacher expressing his or her own viewpoint before agreeing on a final collective decision. Such collective decision-making processes, for her, provide an opportunity for both promoted and non-promoted teachers to share their views and feel valued. Sarah explained:

So, in here, decision-making is not limited to one teacher who is, for instance, the principal teacher...We sit together, we negotiate, we share our ideas, then we choose the best idea that supports our pupils' levels.

While Maria and Sarah's views of teachers' participation in decision-making were particularly restricted to the school setting and more specifically to decisions that directly relate to their classroom practices, other interviewees looked at decision-making more broadly beyond their immediate school context. In this sense, they stressed the importance of teachers' participation in decision-making in areas related to textbook design and curriculum development as an important aspect of teacher leadership. For them, classroom teachers are uniquely positioned to contribute to decisions related to textbook and curriculum development because they possess a better understanding of their students' needs and the challenges faced in their immediate teaching and learning context. The following quotes

by Chahine [T, C, Int 83-85], Melina [PT, B, Int 31-33] and Ibtissem [TM, D, Int 128-132], respectively, corroborate this view:

Teacher involvement in the decisions related to curriculum development is important to align content of the curriculum with the students' needs in the classroom.

We know the pupils better than the inspectors, the headmasters and even the ministry of education. So, we have to share our ideas and viewpoints and participate in decisions.

They (teachers) know better about the reality of their classes and learners... The teacher is the one who is directly involved in the teaching process so teachers must provide their viewpoints regarding the curriculum and share ideas regarding it.

In stressing the importance of teachers' participation in decision making, Rokia [T, D, Int 82-84] explained that it empowers teachers to initiate and lead change within their schools. Rokia held the view that driving change is at the core of teacher leadership practice and that having voice in decision-making processes is essential for that. For teachers to be leaders, she explains, it is essential that they have a strong desire and willingness to initiate and drive positive change, and that this necessitates their participation in decision-making:

Leadership is about driving change. It's the core of it. So, whenever you are given that space to take part in decision-making to drive positive change, this is a role for you to be a teacher leader.

Findings presented in this section indicate that for many participant teachers, both promoted and non-promoted, participation in decision making processes at multiple levels represents a fundamental aspect of teacher leadership. Overall, participants stress that teachers' knowledge of their learners' potentials and expectations and of classroom realities position them in the best place to inform educational policies and reforms including the design and implementation of new curricula, syllabi, and textbooks. Beyond this, analysis of participants' definitions of teacher leadership similarly revealed their tendency to define the concept by outlining qualities of teacher leaders as discussed in the following section.

5.2.4. A Profile of teacher leaders

Defining teacher leadership or teacher leaders by describing and outlining teacher leaders' traits was another recurring theme. Throughout the interviews, participants highlighted various characteristics of teacher leaders. For them, these traits gain teachers recognition particularly among their peers who would accordingly perceive them as role models.

5.2.4.1. Teacher leaders' traits

The most recurrent trait that the interviewees associated with teacher leadership was competence. Competence, from their perspective, involves proficiency in the subject matter and pedagogical knowledge.

The teacher leader must be competent because he faces a lot of questions from his students, from his teachers, from his supervisors, from his inspectors. So, he is going to face a lot of questions. So, the teacher must be competent [Abdou, T, C, Int 96-98]

The teacher should be competent; he should know what he is doing. He should know everything about the module he is teaching [Sarah, T, B, Int 33-35]

The above quotes by Abdou and Sarah revealed that competence and mastery of subject matter are mandatory for teacher leaders, as they would enable them to adequately and effectively fulfil their teaching responsibilities and respond to any questions that they receive in relation to their work. The interviewees, however, viewed competence from various perspectives. While Heba [TM, A, Int 106-108] and Maria [T, B, Int 57-58], for instance, perceived it in terms of knowledge of the curriculum and lesson planning capacities, Melina [PT, B, Int 68] perceived it to be more related to 'subject knowledge and mastery'.

Motivation was another trait that many interviewees associated with teacher leadership. Several participants pointed out that teacher leaders must be both motivated and motivating. That is, they should have intrinsic motivation towards their work, aiming to constantly improve the teaching and learning conditions within their classrooms [Amine, T, A, Int 90-92]. Melina [PT, B, Int 65] and Rokia [T, D, Int 89] also stressed that teacher leaders are a source of motivation and inspiration for their learners. While Melina [PT, B, Int 66] viewed motivation in terms of rewards given to learners, Rokia [T, D, Int 91-97] looked at it differently as she reflected on her own lived experience:

When I went to the place where I currently work, I noticed that most of the learners are not really aware that a world exists beyond their village. Most of the girls were like, this this is it, I'm studying, maybe I'm going to quit halfway, and I'm just getting married because why would I really bother doing anything else? The guys, when you ask them, what is your dream? They all want to be soldiers. So, one of the things that I really thought I needed to do before focusing on anything else was to try to erase this view from their minds. I always try to broaden their visions and to motivate them to think beyond their immediate restrictive environment.

The above quote shows how Rokia tried to motivate her pupils to learn English by convincing them that it could eventually provide them with better employment opportunities. She further explained that in doing so, her aim was mainly to broaden their horizon and to motivate them to consider and think of matters beyond their school.

Many teachers equally viewed teacher leaders as life-long independent learners. Ibtissem [TM, D, Int 64], for example, stated that for teachers to be leaders, they ‘must continue to study, to research and to renew each new academic year’. For Kenza [PT, C, Int 58], teacher leaders are driven by a sense of ‘cognitive curiosity’ that would lead them to search and to learn more regarding ‘disciplinary, pedagogical, and educational issues’. Maria [T, B, Int 45-46] similarly stressed that teacher leaders are teachers who would ‘always seek any opportunity to learn something new and to develop professionally’. She added that in pursuit of continuous professional growth, teacher leaders ‘learn from their own experiences, from their colleagues and even from their own learners’. Rokia [T, D, Int 104] equally highlighted the importance of teachers’ ‘willingness to keep being a learner’ and to keep updating themselves on issues related to their field. For her, when teachers engage in life-long learning, they can ‘reach terrains in their classrooms and profession that otherwise they cannot reach’.

Another important trait that was highlighted by some interviewees was self-confidence. Sarah [T, B, Int 99-109] explained that self-confidence is a trait that would enable teachers to effectively address problems both inside and outside their classrooms. Self-confidence, for her, would enable teachers to earn their students’ respect from the one side, and their colleagues’ and school principal’s respect and recognition from the other side. When dealing with colleagues, she further elaborates, teacher leaders recognise their value and always view themselves as equal to their peers regardless of position or years of experience:

Self-confidence also with your colleagues and with the workers of the school...I am a teacher and I have my position; you are like me. We respect each other, we have the same level, and we pass through the same stages [Sarah, T, B, Int 110-113].

Maria [T, B, Int 99-100] held a similar view, stressing that confident teachers could be exemplary teachers for their peers as she stated:

Normally when the leader teacher is confident, the other teachers would like to be like him.

Rokia [T, D, Int 165-166] added that, for her, teacher leaders are good communicators who appropriately express their viewpoints and effectively listen to other individuals’ opinions and at the same time are teachers who have a vision that goes beyond their immediate role as she maintained that they ‘really should be part of a goal that transcends their immediate gains’.

Interestingly, Serine [PT, E, Int 13] was the only teacher who referred to teacher leaders as teachers who are experienced in their field, which she believes gains them respect and credibility among both their pupils and their colleagues.

5.2.4.2. An effective classroom teacher or a teacher leader?

As data indicated that participants repeatedly emphasised teachers’ competence and

effectiveness as classroom teachers as defining criterion for teacher leaders and their work (as in section 5.2.4.1) and on multiple occasions referred to practices that seemed to be practices of effective teachers in general (as in section 5.2.1), understanding the distinction between ‘an effective classroom teacher’ and ‘a teacher leader’ from the participants’ perspective proved to be important. This was addressed in the focus groups as participants were requested to explain, from their own viewpoints, the difference between the two.

Some participants like Chahine [T, C, FG3] and Marwa [T, E, FG3] insisted that being an effective and competent classroom teacher represents a prerequisite for teacher leadership. They both agreed that for teachers to be teacher leaders and to influence their peers, they must first be recognised as competent and effective teachers.

I think that a leader teacher should be an effective teacher because if he was not an effective teacher, he won't be able to lead the others [Chahine, T, C, FG3 618-619]

If he or she is not good in teaching inside her classroom, I'm not going to follow her as a leader [Marwa, T, E, FG3 625-626]

Conversely, Rokia [T, D, FG1 688] initially explained that being a teacher leader implies being an effective teacher and vice versa. Therefore, for her, the two terms are synonymous and can be ‘interchangeable’. Then before Keltoum [T, E, FG1 691] interrupted her, Rokia [T, D, FG1 692-695] shifted to a different view stating that the main difference, for her, is that effective teachers are teachers who ‘give their best’ within their classrooms but may often be more isolated and ‘do not have a tendency to collaborate outside the classroom’. Keltoum agreed with that, explaining that it was the idea that she was trying to raise by interrupting Rokia. For Keltoum [T, E, FG1 700-702], some teachers may be ‘effective with their learners, when they are doing their job appropriately, but they do not have this sense of collaboration. They do not give and take with others’, and this is what distinguishes a teacher leader from an effective teacher, for her. A similar view was held by Nour [T, C, FG2 672-675] and Halima [PT, A, FG3 633-637]. Halima explained that effective teachers have great potentials in planning and delivering lessons and in managing their classrooms; however, this does not necessarily make them teacher leaders in case they ‘turn out to be introvert individuals’, who do not actively engage in professional discussions and conversations with colleagues within their schools. Sandra [T, D, FG3 641-642] similarly stated:

A teacher leader is one who would help and collaborate with his colleagues, exchange ideas, but an effective or competent teacher, I think is a part of a leader teacher.

The above quotes indicate that for the participants, being an effective teacher within the classroom does not necessarily make of a teacher a teacher leader, but it represents a major requirement for teachers to be leaders. These views seem to go in line with some of the data related

to teachers' reported practices of teacher leadership. In most of their written reflections, teachers referred to initiatives that they undertook to enhance their instructional practices and to their innovative practices as part of teacher leadership, but also emphasised the positive impact that those practices had on their fellow teachers (more details in section 5.2).

Data provided in relation to the difference between the two concepts, thus, reveals that while most participants emphasised that the two concepts are not synonymous, it was evident that, for them, being an effective classroom teacher is a prerequisite for being a teacher leader. Such effectiveness would enable teachers to gain respect and recognition from their peers who would then perceive them as role models and as teacher leaders. However, those effective classroom teachers can only, directly or indirectly, exert influence on their peers when they collaboratively work and interact with them outside their classrooms, thus making their effective practices visible and shared with their fellow teachers.

5.2.5. An incomplete understanding of positional teacher leadership roles

Given that none of the interviewees defined teacher leadership with reference to teachers' positional and designated roles, it was deemed important to examine their awareness of the available positional teacher leadership roles within their school context.

Data obtained in this regard revealed that when participants spoke about the available positional roles, they all referred to teachers' promotion system, which could indicate their awareness that positional teacher leaders go through a selection and promotion process. Furthermore, they perceived it as a hierarchical structure as they described it using expressions such as 'rank', 'a higher rank or position', 'highest', 'stages', and 'a hierarchy of roles'.

Overall, data revealed that across the five schools, positional teacher leaders were more knowledgeable of these roles than novice, non-promoted teachers. Participants' responses indicated their awareness that the promotion system in Algerian middle schools strictly follows regulations and guidelines set by the MoNE and that it is primarily based on teachers' years of work in their current positions and on the official national contest results. To be more specific, most promoted teachers explained that based on seniority, teachers could be automatically promoted to a 'higher position' after working in their current position for a period of ten years. They were equally aware that teachers can also be promoted to such position after only five years by passing an official competition organised by the MoNE. The following extracts from promoted teachers across different schools demonstrate their understanding of the promotion procedures:

The teacher gradually moves to these positions. They either work in their current positions for ten years to be promoted or they participate in the national contest after five years working in their current positions and in case they pass the exam, they get promoted [Kenza, PT, C, Int 18-20]

Algerian schools depend on competitions for promotion...the teacher starts as a trainee, then move on to principal teacher position through competition after five years in working of course, and after that to a trainer after another five years also [Serine, PT, E, Int 46-49]

Teachers can be promoted to a principal teacher after a long experience of teaching, five years through the contest or ten years automatically. [Ibtissem, TM, D, Int 20-21]

Similarly, promoted teachers demonstrated a better understanding of the responsibilities that come with these roles compared to novice teachers. In describing some of the responsibilities that principal teachers assume, Kenza [PT, C, Int 25-26], for instance, maintained that a principal teacher is responsible for coordination between all teachers of a given class to promote professional discussions and to solve any pedagogical issues. Melina [PT, B, Int 104-106] and Heba [TM, A, Ref 4] also respectively commented:

As principal teachers, we have to guide new teachers. We have to give them let's say new ideas for how to manage their classrooms, how to deal with learners, how to plan their lessons, how to plan a test or an exam.

As a teacher mentor, so my main role is to support and guide novice teachers.

Supervising novice teachers involves providing guidelines on lesson planning and delivery [Ibtissem, TM, D, Int 28-30] and checking and evaluating exams for relevance and appropriateness to pupils' level [Kenza, PT, C, Int 33-34]. Nour [T, C, Int 22-32] provided a more detailed description of the role of teacher mentors and principal teachers in supervising novice teachers. She explained that those promoted teachers invite novice teachers to attend some of their sessions to observe the way the lesson is delivered and the way the teacher manages the classroom. After that, she explained, teacher mentors attend lessons delivered by novice teachers and provide feedback. Reflecting on her own experience with her teacher mentor, Keltoum [T, E, FG1 653-655] described the process in a similar way:

She (the teacher mentor) explained to me how to plan and deliver a lesson. She then asked me to attend a session with her. Then, as the third step, she asked me to plan a lesson and she attended with me and gave me feedback.

Interestingly, although Chahine [T, C, Int 34] perceived principal teachers' and teacher mentors' role particularly in terms of supervising and supporting novice teachers, she stressed that she believes some promoted teachers often fail to fulfil this role. Unlike Keltoum [T, E, FG1], Chahine [T, C, Int] explained that when she first joined her school as a novice teacher, she did not receive adequate support from promoted teachers, which led her to either depend on self-directed learning strategies or seek guidance from principal teachers or teacher mentors from other schools within the district. She noted:

When I began teaching and as a novice teacher, I did not receive the needed guidance and support. I had to work and learn all by myself. I had to seek the needed supervision from another principal teacher working in another middle school in our district [Chahine, C, Int 36-40]

This view is somehow similar to Abdou's [T, C, Int 91] view that there is not a huge difference between principal teachers and teacher mentors and other teachers. He maintained that although they may have some additional roles as they are supposed to guide novice teachers, he believes that 'in reality', the main difference is that 'they get more salary'. These views might hint at some promoted teachers' ineffectiveness in fulfilling their roles. Attempting to justify this perceived ineffectiveness, Rokia [T, D, Int 205-206] attributed it to the lack of training that would prepare promoted teachers to effectively fulfil these additional responsibilities. In this sense, she stressed that while 'Trainers of Trainers' or what she referred to as 'TOT' often exist in other contexts globally, they remain absent in the Algerian context. For her, teacher mentors and principal teachers should, themselves, receive training to be able to effectively assume their responsibilities in supervising and guiding novice teachers.

It was interesting to note from the interviewees' responses that although teachers who are promoted to the positions of principal teachers or teacher mentors are required to fulfil numerous responsibilities as outlined in the section 2.4.3.1 of the context chapter, participants' responses in this regard were merely centred on supervision of novice teachers and to a notably lesser degree on coordination between teachers. This might further indicate teachers' limited awareness of the various responsibilities that come with these formal positions.

To sum up, data presented in sections 5.2.1 to 5.2.5 supports the multifaceted nature of teacher leadership as it revealed that participants viewed it from various perspectives covering a wide array of roles assumed both within and beyond classrooms. Interestingly, it was noted that across the five schools, participants' perceptions of the concept indicated a clear focus on non-positional teacher leadership roles and self-initiated practices rather than positional ones. Indeed, none of the participants across those schools defined teacher leadership with reference to teachers' designated positions. Teachers perceived teacher leadership in terms of practices that teachers deliberately engage in within and beyond their classrooms, teachers' participation in decision-making as well as the qualities that teacher leaders manifest, all of which serving as means through which teacher leaders could exert influence at multiple levels. Such influence was particularly exerted through instructional innovation, collaboration, providing professional support, and modelling effective instructional practices and ethical behaviour.

5.3. Teachers' reported practices of teacher leadership

Overall, analysis of teachers' written reflections revealed that although most of them were hesitant to acknowledge their practices as part of teacher leadership, they emphasised that those practices gained them recognition, credibility and praise and had an influence either on their learners or on their colleagues. While some teachers explicitly expressed such hesitation in their written reflections, many others did not express this in their writing, yet communicated these concerns with the researcher when they handed or sent the written reflections. Some explicit expressions from participants' reflections involved:

I am not sure if this is leadership, but it was successful in improving my pupils' learning and even my colleagues benefited from it [Abdou, T, C, Ref 22-24]
This may be simply part of my role and not leadership [Heba, TM, A, Ref 18-19]

Maybe others may not see this as leadership, but I think it is related to it because I encouraged her (her colleague) to move out of her comfort zone. [Nawel, PT, B, Ref 20-21]

Furthermore, and consistent with their perceptions of teacher leadership, participants' reported practices across the five schools were mainly self-initiated and related primarily to practices within the classroom. Data obtained from the teachers' written reflections was analysed inductively, generating two broad themes: practices within the classroom and practices beyond the classroom. Each participant's reported practice is first presented separately, then by the end of each of the sections 5.3.1 and 5.3.2, a summary of the reported practices both within the classroom and beyond it is provided.

5.3.1. Reported practices within the classroom

Teachers' reported practices within the classroom related particularly to their *innovative teaching practices and classroom management strategies* and their *relationship with their learners*.

In terms of their teaching practices, some teachers described incidents when they designed and implemented innovative instructional practices to motivate their learners, to accommodate their needs and preferences, and to address problems that their learners often face in understanding certain lessons. Abdou [T, C, Ref], for instance, referred to an incident when he realised that his learners face difficulties in understanding the rules for the use of different conditional types, specifically when delivering the lesson in the traditional way. He, therefore, decided to search for a more effective and innovative method to deliver that lesson. Based on his search, he eventually decided to opt for relevant movie scenes that would enable the learners to derive the rule and use of each conditional type. He explained that this innovative teaching strategy not only made his learners 'more motivated and interactive and increased their understanding of the lesson' [Abdou, T, C, Ref 14-15], but also enabled him as a teacher to deliver that lesson in fewer sessions. Having noticed the effectiveness of this

innovative instructional practice, Abdou shared the teaching materials with his peers and explained how to effectively implement this strategy. His peers, he explains, not only implemented this strategy for the teaching of the conditional types lesson, but ‘started designing and delivering all their lessons using more innovative strategies’ [Abdou, T, C, Ref 18-19].

Also, in relation to teaching practices, both Nour [T, C, Ref] and Sarah [T, B, Ref] described a similar experience as they both expressed their emphasis on using differentiated and innovative teaching strategies and materials that would meet the different learning preferences of their learners. Sarah explained that such emphasis was mainly inspired by the psycho-pedagogy module that she used to have at university while Nour stressed that it was inspired by her own experience as a pupil. As such, their classrooms were overall more inclusive as they demonstrated a sense of responsibility and devoted the necessary time and resources to meet the needs of different learners. While in her written reflection, Nour focused particularly on the ways in which such an approach influenced her learners both in terms of their academic achievements and their levels of motivation and engagement; Sarah stressed similar outcomes, yet she went further to explain how her colleagues, both EFL teachers and teachers of other subjects, were influenced after attending some of her sessions or as she herself initiated discussions with fellow peers about the usefulness of this approach. She maintained that as a result, many of her fellow teachers began implementing the same strategies within their classrooms. The following extracts highlight the impact of these self-initiated practices as reported by the two teachers:

It enhanced their understanding and their scores. I also noticed that they were more motivated and more engaged in the class than before. This was my aim from the start. [Nour, T, C, Ref 11-13]

When my colleagues attended some of my sessions, they noticed this and asked me to share my teaching materials with them if I can. Of course, I did and after that all of them applied them in their classrooms. Even teachers of other subjects, when I discussed this with them, they said that they realized the importance of this strategy and decided to use it too. So, our lessons were enjoyable, and our learners become even more motivated. [Sarah, T, B, Ref 13-18]

In her reflective essay, Melina [PT, B, Ref 7-9] explained that as a teacher she has always been firmly convinced of the great impact that rewards can have on the learners and on the classroom atmosphere as a whole. Therefore, to implement this in her classrooms, she decided to reward her learners for multiple reasons. To exemplify, she stated that she always rewards ‘the high achieving pupils in [her] subject’ and ‘the learner who has the most organised copybook’. Furthermore, in an attempt to maintain discipline within her classrooms, she also rewards the most disciplined pupil in each of the classes she teaches. Melina [PT, B, Ref 12] emphasised that this made her learners ‘more motivated, better disciplined and competitive’, which in turn enabled her to ‘establish and maintain a

positive learning environment' for her learners. As she shared her strategy at one of the school's meetings that she attended, she was praised by the school principal for her efforts. She also stated that some of her colleagues 'started doing that too and they also noticed similar improvements' [Melina, PT, B, Ref 16-17].

Ibtissem [TM, D, Ref] referred particularly to the relationship that she has with her learners as her defining characteristic as a teacher. She emphasised that her relationship with her learners is something that she has always been recognised and praised for within her school. Throughout her twenty-two years working as a teacher, her primary aim has always been to establish and maintain a good relationship with her learners, based on understanding, tolerance, and mutual respect. Due to this relationship, her learners loved her and loved her subject. The good rapport that she always maintained with her learners was also effective in preventing disruptive behaviour within her classrooms, which benefited her too as it made her 'daily work more enjoyable' and she 'always felt at ease' [Ibtissem, TM, D, Ref 20-21]. As in the case of the practices reported previously by other teachers, Ibtissem also seems to indirectly exert influence on her peers, particularly on her trainees. She wrote: 'My colleagues and the teachers who I supervise always say that I am a good example and model for them because of this. This is something that they try to learn and adopt from me' [Ibtissem, TM, D, Ref 24-26].

Prioritising learners and caring for them was also highlighted by Halima [PT, A, Ref] as she reflected on her experience with one of her learners, named Dalal. Halima explained that when she first taught Dalal, she was a first-year middle school pupil and was one of her most motivated, interactive, and high achieving pupils. Two years later, Halima taught Dalal again at third year middle school level when she noticed that the pupil no longer participates within the classroom, and her scores noticeably decreased. She explained: 'in her third year, I saw a different student, almost the opposite. She does not participate a lot. I noticed how she was often inattentive, wandering. Her scores decreased' [Halima, PT, A, Ref 9-11]. Being concerned for this situation, Halima discussed this issue with other teachers who teach Dalal, and they stressed noticing the same. Having realised this negative change, Halima took it as her own responsibility to solve this issue. She first talked to the pupil herself, and then reached out to her father and as such she realised that the main reason for that change was that Dalal's mother was diagnosed with breast cancer. Halima explained the situation to all of Dalal's teachers and suggested that they help her 'by providing follow-up sessions outside the school' [Halima, PT, A, Ref 20-21]. She also requested the school psychologist to meet Dalal and talk to her. Having done all this, Halima explained that there was a noticeable increase in the pupil's scores and that she became as motivated and involved as she used to be.

All of the above experiences reported by the participants exemplify the ways in which they were very attentive and caring to detect any problems within their classrooms and took it as their own responsibility to solve them. Notably, all of the practices that those teachers reported as teacher leadership were self-initiated. Those teachers took initiative to search for and apply more effective and innovative ways to solve the issues they or their learners encountered. It was evident through these practices that the initiatives that they undertook eventually led to improvements in their learners' achievements and behaviour. Apart from that, most of their reported practices revealed that although these practices were classroom-based, their influence was not restricted to their learners and the classroom environment but was indirectly extended to their fellow teachers. As those teachers noticed the effectiveness of their innovative practices, they negotiated, and made these innovative practices visible to their peers. They often led by example by inspiring their peers and motivating them to be more creative within their classrooms and enhancing overall instructional practices and classroom management strategies, which would in turn result in improved students' learning and discipline.

5.3.2. Reported Practices beyond the Classroom

Participants referred to various aspects related to their teacher leadership practices outside their classrooms. Marwa [T, E, Ref], for example, stressed that her dedication to independently work on her own continuous professional learning is the main element that she believes might characterise her as a teacher leader. Inspired by her university teacher of didactics, who always stressed that 'a teacher is also a learner' [Marwa, T, E, Ref 1], Marwa assumed the responsibility of her own professional learning. Therefore, instead of solely depending on formal training sessions and programmes organized by the MoNE, which she readily described as 'very limited and not very useful for [their] actual classroom practices and improvements' [Marwa, T, E, Ref 7-8], she constantly searches for various ways to develop both her English language and her teaching skills. She explained, 'My development and my learning is my responsibility in the first place. That is why I started to look for ways to improve my subject knowledge and also to improve my teaching capacities' [Marwa, T, E, Ref 8-10]. As a result, whenever she attends training sessions, she shares her own ideas instead of 'passively receiving information', which is something the inspector really appreciated and other teachers could benefit from [Marwa, T, E, Ref 16].

Reflecting on her short teaching experience, Maria [T, B, Ref] referred to an incident when she took initiative in supporting her colleagues, drawing on her ICT (Information and Communication Technology) knowledge as an incident that made her feel as a teacher leader. Maria explained that, as Covid-19 cases begun to increase by the beginning of 2020, she noticed that many schools worldwide started shifting to virtual teaching due to lockdown and expected that the same was likely to happen in Algeria. Being aware of this potential situation and of the fact that not all her fellow teachers

‘possess the necessary knowledge and experience using software for online teaching’, she decided to take initiative to support her colleagues with this matter. She wrote: ‘I decided to step up mainly because I have a diplomat in computer science. Also, my sister is a lecturer at university, and she knows very well how to use Moodle as a platform to teach’ [Maria, T, B, Ref 5-7]. Maria, accordingly, prepared Power-Point slides explaining the use of Moodle, presented the slides to her colleagues in three sessions, and shared these slides with all her peers while equally urging them to reach out to her if they required further assistance. She explained that the school principal and her peers appreciated her initiative and that she felt that she made a valuable contribution for her peers, for the learners and for the school, especially given that schools did indeed shift to virtual teaching during lockdown. She reported: ‘I really felt that I contributed with something for my colleagues and for my school and our students, especially at this challenging time’ [Maria, T, B, Ref 13-15].

Nawel [PT, B, Ref], on the other hand, described a situation when she nominated a novice teacher to prepare learners for an interschool competition. Nawel was responsible of supervising that teacher as she began teaching, and during the period of her training, she noticed that although that teacher ‘was very motivated and passionate about her job, she was also very shy and lacked self-confidence’ [Nawel, B, Ref 10-12]. When choosing that teacher to prepare the learners, Nawel’s aim was particularly to provide that teacher with an opportunity to show her potentials and increase her self-esteem. Nawel explained: ‘I chose her to push her out of her comfort zone...I trusted her abilities, her skills, her capacities maybe so much more than she trusted herself’ [Nawel, B, Ref 12-13]. She explained that from that experience, the novice teacher became more interactive with her peers, and more involved in various school activities by confidently sharing her own ideas and viewpoints.

As a teacher mentor, one of Heba’s crucial roles is to support and guide novice teachers. She explained that she constantly tries ‘to come up with more innovative ways’ to fulfil her role as she believes that supervising novice teachers is not merely about providing them with guidelines related to teaching and classroom management, but it also involves enhancing their self-confidence [Heba, TM, A, Ref 19]. To do so, Heba decided to share with her trainees a copy of a reflective diary from the time she was a novice teacher herself. In that diary, she reflected on the difficulties she used to face as a novice teacher including stage fright and ways in which she managed to overcome those difficulties; her own relationship with different members within her school community, mainly colleagues, her school principal and her pupils as well as tips about how she prepared for her examination to be tenured, how it went, and the feedback she received from the school inspector. She believed that this ‘innovative way’ for mentoring novice teachers was very effective as it extended her role from providing teaching-related and pedagogical guidelines to inspiring her trainees and enhancing their self-confidence. Indeed, Heba maintained that her trainees often stressed the

usefulness of this strategy for enhancing their self-confidence as they get to realise through her diary that the early stages of the teaching career has also been challenging for Heba herself who they consider a role model. Heba reported:

My diary can be an inspiration to them. It can give them ideas about how to deal with issues with their pupils, how to deal with others in the school, how to overcome teaching challenges. But, what is more important is that it can boost their self-confidence because when they read it they will know that it was difficult for me too when I was a new teacher, not them only [Heba, TM, A, Ref 14-18].

The examples provided by the participants in relation to their teacher leadership practices beyond their classrooms revealed their emphasis on empowering themselves and others. In Marwa's case, for instance, as she independently sought opportunities to enhance her own professional learning, her focus was not only on her own professional growth, but also the professional learning of other teachers, either within her school or beyond it. This was evident as she stated that she has always been interested in contributing to the formal professional training by sharing her own ideas with the inspectors and with teachers who attend from different schools. Taking initiative to provide professional support was also highlighted by Maria as a practice that made her feel that she was a teacher leader, given the praise and recognition that she received from her peers and school principal. Apart from the professional teaching-related support, the two promoted teachers, Nawel and Heba, provided examples that reflected the ways in which they empowered other teachers, mainly novice teachers, by enhancing their self-esteem and confidence in their skills and capacities. It is important to note that as in the case of teachers' reported practices within the classroom, teachers' reported practices beyond the classroom were also self-initiated and not delegated by school principals or schools' senior management.

5.4. Supports and hindrances of teacher leadership in the Algerian middle school context

One of the key aims of this study was exploring participants' perspectives regarding the current supports or hindrances of teacher leadership within their context. The collected data revealed that while participant teachers across the five schools spoke at length about hindrances that exist within their context, they briefly referred to some desired supports, which they believe would have a crucial role in enhancing teacher leadership within their schools. Overall, the interviewees' responses indicated that the factors, which they believe could empower or disempower teacher leadership in their context, related broadly to *teacher-related factors*, *school-based factors*, *system-based factors*, and *sociocultural factors*.

5.4.1. Teacher-related factors

Teachers' personal characteristics have been identified by some participants as having a great influence on their engagement in teacher leadership. Participants, in this sense, referred to some of the

traits outlined in section 5.2.4, as traits that would enhance teachers' participation in leadership work, particularly within their schools. These involved: teachers' sense of confidence and intrinsic motivation. The following quotes corroborate these views:

Confidence is important...the more confidence the teacher has, he will do more leadership work [Sarah, T, B, Int 222-224]

When teachers are motivated to improve the current situation, they can do so much to bring improvements to the teaching and learning process [Amine, T, A, Int 93-95]

Participants equally highlighted the importance of teachers' willingness and desire to engage in leadership work and to drive change. On a positive note, data indicates that all interviewees, regardless of their positions, held a positive outlook of teacher leadership and recognised its value. Some of them utterly expressed their willingness and desire to be involved in more leadership work that could positively impact their students' learning and their schools as a whole. Interestingly, some teachers provided concrete examples that demonstrated their desire to engage in leadership work by introducing certain innovative practices to their schools.

I taught an online course in an Omani middle school...I was impressed by the various clubs established within the school as part of extra-curricular activities and I really want to implement such an initiative in my school [Rokia, T, D, Int 252-254]

We always assess our learners' outcomes using tests...they just learn things by heart and answer and we give them marks...this does not make critical learners, so I always wanted to use more innovative assessment strategies [Nawel, PT, B, Int 156-160]

I created a Facebook group for middle school EFL teachers where we can exchange ideas and collaborate to improve the learning process. We choose together the topics that we want to discuss and we prepare for this...this is very effective and I hope I can do this in my school too [Sandra, T, D, FG3 163-166]

The examples in the above extracts are suggestive of teachers' willingness and desire to introduce new initiatives into their schools, which they believe to likely influence learners, peers, and schools as a whole. Those teachers, however, did not manage to take the first steps to implement these initiatives given the limited support and professional autonomy.

While Rokia [T, D, Int 142] stressed the importance of teachers' willingness to initiate change, she equally commented that teachers should also maintain consistency in their efforts to drive change. For her, teachers should not give up their change initiatives just because their first attempt did not succeed. However, she explained that some teachers might lack this sense of consistency:

I think the problem is that we try once, and then when it doesn't work, we just step back, but no, leadership needs consistency and we kind of lack that sort of mentality [Rokia, T, D, Int 144-146]

As teacher leaders initiate and lead change within their schools, Nour [T, C, Int 129-131] stated that they must be ready to assume responsibility for any possible risks or outcomes that accompany their leadership practice.

5.4.2. School-based Factors

Data from individual interviews and focus group discussions highlighted various factors that were particularly related to the school contexts in which participant teachers worked as amongst the major conditions that either support or hinder their engagement in teacher leadership work. These conditions related essentially to peers' and principals' support and work conditions within schools.

5.4.2.1. (Un)supportive Peers

A recurrent factor stressed by all interviewees was the amount of support that they receive from their colleagues and the nature of their relationships with their peers. Most participants pointed out that the relationship that teachers establish with their peers is an important condition that contributes to teacher leadership practice. Sarah [T, B, Int 215] maintained that teacher leadership practice flourishes 'when teachers support each other' and stand with each other. Nawel [PT, B, Int 136-137] supported Sarah's view as she pointed out that collaborative peers empower teacher leadership. Teachers would be more motivated and confident and more willing to assume leadership responsibilities when they obtain collegial support from their colleagues. This is particularly because collegiality provides an opportunity for teachers to develop professionally by sharing and exchanging knowledge with peers within their professional community. To exemplify, Chahine [T, C, Int 97-98] stated that empowering peers could be for instance through providing 'peer observation for some particular teaching skills' as this would help them improve their teaching practices and enhance their confidence at the same time.

In describing their relationships with their peers, most teachers maintained that these relationships were generally positive and mostly limited to professional aspects, and that their peers were often supportive. Sarah [T, B, Int 217-219], Keltoum [T, E, FG3 84-86] and Rokia [T, D, FG1 102-104], in particular, explained that as they first joined their schools, they received great support from more experienced teachers within their schools. Those teachers were often available and approachable to answer their queries and provide the needed professional guidance. The reciprocal dimension of the relationship was also highlighted as some teachers stressed mutual respect as a defining criterion of their relationships with their peers:

We are all respecting each other. It's based on mutual respect [Chahine, T, C, FG3 90]

I have the right to be respected and I must respect others' points of view [Nawel, PT, B, FG2 106]

All teachers must respect each other and tolerate each other's circumstances. We all treat each other with respect [Abdou, T, C, Int 152-153]

Praise and affirmation were also highlighted as an essential part of such positive relationships. It was evident from the participants' responses that this kind of encouragement strengthened the relationship between teachers and increased their motivation and willingness to engage in leadership work. This was highly valued by the interviewees as they stated:

I often got compliments from some of them that made me feel that I'm on top of everything and super confident. These compliments really motivate you to do even more [Rokia, T, D, FG1 521-523]

We like to be praised. As teachers, we like compliments. When you do something and your peers praise you, you will definitely be motivated to keep doing it [Chahine, T, C, FG3 97-98]

Such positive relationships between teachers were perceived as essential for supporting teacher leadership practice. However, while most teachers stressed that their relationships with their peers were often positive and were primarily based on mutual respect, they equally highlighted cases in which relationships between novice and experienced teachers were rather not so supportive. In this sense, some novice teachers across different schools reported incidents of control exerted by more experienced peers. Those more experienced teachers were mostly teachers who hold positional teacher leadership roles, based on which they exerted control over novice teachers. Both Keltoum [T, E, FG1 261-263] and Chahine [T, C, FG3 234-237] explained that when teachers join the profession for the first time, they are often underestimated by their colleagues simply for being novice teachers. As a result, those teachers often have less freedom to express their viewpoints or to take decisions related to their teaching practices.

Rokia [T, D, FG1] echoed this sentiment as she described an incident when all teachers attended an annual meeting at the level of her school to discuss pupils' achievements and behaviour. She stated that while other teachers held a negative view about a particular pupil, she held a rather positive view about him because he was 'very good in English'. When Rokia expressed her viewpoint, some of the more experienced teachers gave her 'looks of judgement'. Rokia, thus, felt that she was out of her 'comfort zone' and that she was not free to express her opinion, mainly because she was a novice teacher.

So, in one of our meetings, we needed to talk about some particular students...I felt a little bit out of my comfort zone when speaking about a certain pupil because some of the more experienced teachers held negative views about him, while I had

very positive comments because he is very good in English. When I attempted to say something that's positive about him, the more experienced teachers gave me looks of judgement. So, I did not really feel free to give my opinion and I think that was mainly because I am a novice teacher [Rokia, T, D, FG1 275-283].

Elaborating on this, Marwa [T, E, FG3 241] suggested that it may not always be 'very easy' for novice teachers to freely express their views because they are perceived to lack sufficient knowledge. She further stressed that novice teachers, in some cases, may not even be asked to share their viewpoints, and whenever they do, their views may not be taken into consideration unless they were validated by a more experienced teacher. She stated:

They even don't ask about your opinion and if you say something, it's not taken into consideration unless someone else who has better experience say the same thing [Marwa, T, E, FG3 242-243]

Although Marwa [T, FG3 223-227] explained that some of her colleagues were supportive and willing to listen to her viewpoints, the conflicting situation with some experienced teachers made her more reluctant to work with them and less willing to express her viewpoints, which contradicts the collaborative nature of teacher leadership practice:

In this situation, I think that I would never tell my opinion to them again. I may isolate myself from working with them [Marwa, T, E, FG3 229-230]

Most participants emphasised that it is crucial that both experienced and novice teachers recognise that they can mutually support each other. For them, based on their experience, promoted teachers can provide early-career teachers with the necessary professional guidance in terms of teaching practices and classroom management. In return, novice teachers can help experienced colleagues with 'digital literacy' matters. The following extracts by Rokia [T, D, FG1 393-394], Nawel [PT, B, FG2 187] and Maria [T, B, FG1 405-408], respectively, support this view:

Many older teachers are not much digitally educated. In my school, they usually come to you for guidance, like 'she's young, so she must know it'.

I am an experienced teacher so I think I have teaching knowledge that I can share with new teachers but also, I try to always learn from them new teaching strategies. They use creative strategies.

As a novice teacher could take from a much older or more experienced teacher the way to make the information simple for the pupils. The older teacher could take from me what Rokia said digital literacy.

5.4.2.2. (Un)supportive school principals

Apart from peers, school principals were viewed by some interviewees as having a fundamental role in empowering or limiting teacher leadership within their schools. Some participants stressed that it is the principals' responsibility to ensure that appropriate circumstances are made

available for teachers to encourage them to be more involved in leadership work within their schools. Abdou [T, C, Int 147-148], for instance, stressed that principals are required to ensure that ‘teachers benefit from all needed teaching materials and classroom resources’ and should equally ‘value teachers’ efforts and their viewpoints’. In doing so, principals would create a suitable school environment within which teacher leadership is more likely to flourish. Teachers’ appreciation for principals’ recognition and praise was evident in some of their written reflections. Melina [PT, B, Ref 19], Maria [T, B, Ref 16] and Sarah [T, B, Ref 18-19], for instance, stressed their appreciation for the recognition and praise that they received from their school principals for the initiatives that they undertook.

Rokia [T, D, Int 245-250], however, made it clear in her interview that while teachers may often receive recognition from their peers, encouragement and praise from principals remains an essential enabler of teacher leadership. For her, this kind of encouragement from school principals seems to be minimal in most public-school as she maintained:

Teacher effort should be recognised by the headmaster, because most of the time if you’re doing a good job, probably you are going to hear it from a couple of teachers, but the headmaster is not really going to give you any sort of encouragement. So, I think this is one of the things that would really motivate teachers to give more and to be able to demonstrate that sort of leader inside of them.

Rokia’s view was echoed by Nour [T, C, Int 137-139] who explained that principals who do not value teachers’ efforts or do not respect their viewpoints can ‘demotivate teachers’ and limit their participation in leadership work within their schools. She further added that some principals would prefer not to give teachers a chance to be involved in school leadership because they believe that a school should have ‘only one leader’, and that teachers’ participation in leadership would threaten school principals’ position.

I think the problem is that headteachers here believe that schools have only one leader, that is them. So, they will not allow teachers to practise leadership.

Unsupportive school principals, thus, may constrain teacher leadership as they do not provide teachers with the necessary resources, encouragement, and recognition, and as they adopt an authoritarian rather than a shared or distributed leadership style. This latter aspect was extensively discussed by teachers across the three FGs.

Both promoted and non-promoted teachers shared the view that the extent of control exerted by school principals often resulted in conflicting relationships as principals underestimate teachers’ capacities and limited their professional autonomy. To exemplify, Serine [PT, E, FG1 246-250] reflected on an incident with the headmaster, when Serine felt that she was not capable of doing what she believes ‘was appropriate for those learners’ and that her views were not respected. Rather, the

headmaster imposed his own viewpoints on her. Serine was required to teach an additional class whose teacher went on maternity leave. The headmaster required her to finish teaching almost half the textbook in no more than 24 hours, which she believed was ‘impossible’. Although she tried to explain the situation, the principal insisted on his opinion, stressing that she has ‘to finish no matter what’. She maintained:

My problem was with the headmaster. It was not with other teachers, because I could not do what I knew was best for this class. He did not take my opinion into consideration...he did not even listen to me or let me explain my idea and I just had to do as he said [Serine, PT, E, FG1 246-250]

In another scenario, Amira [T, A, FG2 209-214] reported a negative experience with her former principal. By the end of the exams’ period and after the pupils were given their grades, the headmaster requested to discuss pupils’ grades with Amira, as all pupils in one class ‘got above the average while most of them usually get low grades’. Although she explained that she employed an effective teaching strategy and that she carefully designed an exam that meets their potential, the headmaster was not convinced and even ‘refused to listen’ to her. Amira felt that the principal, instead of praising her efforts for enhancing students’ academic achievements, questioned her decision mainly because she was a novice teacher. She stated:

It was my first year of teaching. So, he didn’t trust me because he thought that I will not be good enough. I’m not experienced. So, I was not enough [Amira, T, A, FG2 213-214]

The views shared by Serine [PT, E, FG1 246-250] and Amira [T, A, FG2 209-214] illustrate negative incidents they encountered with their current or former school principals. They suggest that the kind of control that some principals exert on teachers limited their freedom to express their viewpoints and largely restricted their professional autonomy, thus creating a culture that seemed to be less conducive for teacher leadership enactment. These incidents seem to equally indicate a lack of trust and effective communication between teachers and their principals. As those teachers perceived autonomy as a prerequisite for the enactment of teacher leadership, their responses indicate that principals can play an important role in brokering opportunities for teacher leadership by granting teachers appropriate levels of autonomy, particularly in terms of their teaching practices and by recognising their efforts and valuing their views.

Notably, Amira [T, A, FG2 217] was one of those teachers who changed their schools due to the lack of support and trust from their former principals. Compared to the conflicting relationship that she had with the headmaster of her former school, her relationship with her current principal was ‘more positive’. She reported that the latter was more supportive, showing more recognition and appreciation for her efforts, but more importantly trusting her capacities and allowing her more

autonomy in her work. Similar views were held by Nawel [PT, B, FG2 220] and Sarah [T, B, FG2 223] regarding their current school principal, who they described as more supportive as compared to their former principal.

5.4.2.3. Working conditions

Most participants stressed that certain work conditions should be made available within schools to encourage teacher leadership practice. These were primarily related to availability of materials, time, and provision of rewards.

Most participants (eg. Abdou [T, C, Int 168], Heba [TM, A, Int 125-126] and Amine [T, A, Int 148-150], Melina [PT, B, Int 121-125], Nour [T, C, Int 146-147]) emphasised the importance of providing teachers with the necessary up-to-date resources and teaching materials as these would support teachers' innovative and differentiated instructional practices and would enable them to prove themselves as effective teachers. However, participants unanimously stressed that despite their importance, such materials are remarkably scarce within Algerian public middle schools. As per this issue, some of them commented:

Unfortunately, we miss materials. We do not have a lot of technological materials that support our creative teaching and help us innovate and improve our pupils' learning [Maria, T, B, Int 143-145]

There are limited materials, for example, data-shows. This can hinder your innovation in teaching and your leadership because it does not let you show your capacities [Sarah, T, B, Int 207-208]

Lack of materials in our schools is a serious issue...often as teachers, we wish to innovate and to be creative in our teaching practices and even when we are given some margins of freedom to do so, lack of materials comes as a serious barrier [Rokia, T, D, Int 233-235]

Nour [T, C, Int] and Kenza [PT, C, Int] voiced the same concern while equally acknowledging the ministry's continuous efforts to equip schools with the necessary resources:

It is true that the ministry recognises the importance of providing materials and is working to equip schools with the needed resources, but currently our schools still lack the necessary materials that support our work [Nour, T, C, Int 148-150]

There are limited materials across all schools, I believe. This hinders teachers' potential to innovate. But, we can see that the ministry is putting efforts to address this problem. So, this may improve in the coming years [Kenza, PT, C, Int 95-97]

Apart from scarcity of materials, shortage of time coupled with work overload were highlighted by most interviewees across the five schools as factors that limit teachers' potential to participate in leadership work. Most participants explained that they have very limited time within a school day to engage in additional activities that are part of teacher leadership work given their daily

fixed and heavy teaching schedules. Participants explained that overwhelming timetables and the work overload may tire teachers and decrease their willingness to be involved in any further roles beyond their classrooms. In this sense, they stressed the importance of a suitable and lighter timetable that would enable teachers to devote some of their time to take part in leadership practices. Interestingly, although promoted teachers have relatively lighter teaching loads compared to their non-promoted peers, they shared similar concerns as per the issue of time and work overload. The following extracts from participants across the five schools corroborate this view:

I think the timetable is important...we have heavy timetables for teaching. So, we have short time to do other activities [Ibtissem, TM, D, Int 94-96]

When teachers have some spare time throughout the week, they would be able to plan and deliver more innovative lessons. They will also be able to collaborate and interact with their colleagues. If the timetable is overwhelming as in our case, this would be difficult. Teachers would feel tired [Nour, T, C, Int 126-130]

I think the number of teaching hours or time allotment...teachers get tired and exhausted by the number of hours they have to teach every day. Most teachers here suffer from this...teachers should have some free time to do other activities [Nawel, PT, B, Int 146-151]

We also have to teach many classes. So, we rarely have time to fulfil roles beyond our teaching responsibilities [Kenza, PT, C, Int 111-112]

Recognising and rewarding teachers' initiatives was also viewed as crucial for enhancing teacher leadership. While many participants stressed the importance of recognition from peers and school principals as discussed in sections 5.4.2.1 and 5.4.2.2, Rokia [T, D, Int 258-260] highlighted the importance of an increased salary or provision of monetary rewards for encouraging teachers' participation in teacher leadership work:

Providing extra salary and so on...would really motivate teachers to innovate, to be change initiators and go beyond the boundaries of their basic day-to-day teaching responsibilities.

Her view was reiterated by Chahine [T, C, Int 109-111] and Keltoum [T, E, FG1 702-705], who respectively maintained:

I believe when a teacher is paid for the extra effort that he makes, I think this will make him even more motivated to keep doing more and more for the benefit of their learners and the school.

I just want to comment about something. So, I think if any teacher does something creative and puts his time and efforts to do it and then gets some kind of let's say extra payment or some rewards, he will feel it was worth his time and his effort and will motivate him to keep doing this. So, I think this is important.

Agreeing with Keltoum and elaborating on her response, Maria [T, B, FG1 706-710]

commented:

I really agree with that...when this is done, it will motivate not just the teacher who gets that...that extra money, it will motivate all other teachers to do like him too.

The above extracts demonstrate the usefulness of providing monetary rewards as a recognition for teacher's leadership initiatives, being perceived by some teachers as both a gesture to value and recognise initiatives undertaken by those teachers as well as a means to motivate other teachers to be more engaged in different practices within their schools. Notably, this aspect was particularly highlighted by non-promoted teachers.

Data presented in sections 5.4.2.1, 5.4.2.2 and 5.4.2.3 indicate that overall, the five middle schools in which participant teachers work seem to be less conducive to teacher leadership enactment. While teachers across the five schools unanimously stressed structural deficiencies within their schools as a deterring factor to teacher leadership practice, findings related to school members' support, however, seem to be mixed and inconsistent across these settings. What could be noted from these findings, supported with findings in sections 5.2 and 5.3, for instance, is that school B in which Melina [PT], Nawel [PT], Sarah [T] and Maria [T] work seems to represent a school culture that is more ideal for teacher leadership enactment compared to the other four schools. Teachers within this school maintained that attending each other's classes and engaging in professional discussions and collaborative work is an essential part of their work routine. Regardless of their length of teaching experience, those teachers stressed that they continuously learn from each other. Similarly, the four teachers described their school principal as a supportive principal who often provides teachers with more margins of freedom in terms of their teaching practices and encourages and praises the initiatives that they undertake. This was evident in the examples provided by Sarah [T, Int and Ref], Melina [PT, Ref] and Maria [T, Ref] in sections 5.2 and 5.3, in which they explained that their school principal praised and encouraged their innovative practices.

5.4.3. System-based Factors

Interviewees also referred to certain systemic factors that seemed to hinder teacher leadership enactment in their context. They stressed the important role that the MoNE could play in actively promoting teacher leadership practice while stressing that the current policies of the MoNE represent a deterring factor to teachers' participation in leadership work. Hindrances that relate to the broader educational system in Algeria were particularly centred on the centralised decision-making processes and directives, and the scarcity of relevant professional development programmes for teacher leaders.

5.4.3.1. Impact of the centralised educational system

Concerns were raised by many teachers as to the centralised nature of the educational system that was perceived to highly minimise teachers' potential to contribute to decision-making processes

and to notably restrict their professional autonomy. For them, teachers in Algerian public schools are required to strictly adhere to ministerial policies and directives that strictly govern their work and marginalise them from decision-making processes at different levels. Melina [PT, B, Int 24-26], for instance, stressed the importance of participating in decision-making processes as a core aspect of teacher leadership, yet maintained that in Algeria, teachers' roles often remain restricted and that they have no opportunities to engage in decision-making:

So, you are just like a slave to books, to administration, and to inspectors and mainly to the ministry of education. You have to do exactly as they decide.

The above quote by Melina demonstrates how several variables may interfere and restrict teachers' freedom to take decisions or to have voice in decision-making processes in their work context. Teachers have to follow curricula, syllabi and textbooks ascribed to them and are required to fully comply with guidelines of the MoNE. She explains that it is the role of subject inspectors to ensure that teachers strictly follow these guidelines, and this in itself puts further pressure on teachers and further limits their professional autonomy and agency. She, accordingly, stressed that teachers should be given more room to be involved and share their viewpoints, concerns, and feedback mainly in terms of designing the 'schoolbook' because she believes that as teachers, they know their learners better than headmasters, school inspectors and policymakers at the level of the MoNE.

Amine [T, A, Int 39-43] spoke about the same issue:

New teachers like me or young teachers have the motivation to innovate. They have the desire to keep making their classes better, to try new things, but since we have to completely follow the ministry's curriculum and syllabus, and we have other people who are always restricting our work, it is difficult...we are like we are chained.

In the above excerpt, Amine [T, Int] described teachers as being 'chained', which further stresses the negative impact of a highly centralised system that seems to marginalise teachers' voice and restrict their professional autonomy. This view was equally highlighted by other participants who commented that their 'voice is not listened to' [Kenza, PT, C, Int 112], that they 'are marginalised' [Sarah, T, B, Int 235] and that their 'opinions are not at all considered' [Nour, T, C, Int 147].

Interestingly, Rokia [T, D, Int 124-126] further explained that this is 'ironically' more common among more experienced teachers who are 'supposed to be the leaders of change' within their schools, but rather prefer to 'remain obedient to the system'. She, thus, stressed that Algerian teachers must be given more 'margins of freedom', and that some measures should be introduced by policymakers to extend teachers' roles and to enable teachers 'to stand out'.

5.4.3.2. Scarcity of relevant professional development programmes

Another desired support from the MoNE as highlighted by some participants is the provision

of adequate and relevant professional training for in-service teachers to enhance their confidence and readiness to participate in school leadership. As per the status quo in relation to teachers' professional training, some participants accentuated their dissatisfaction with the current professional development programmes directed to middle school teachers in Algeria. Marwa [T, E, Ref 4-5], for instance, stressed the scarcity of professional development opportunities provided by the MoNE for middle school teachers. In her case, such scarcity was one of the factors that led her to engage in more self-directed professional learning.

In a similar way and as a novice teacher who recently completed her formal professional training, Rokia [T, D, Int 212-218] spoke at length about this issue, referring to the inadequacy and ineffectiveness of both the content she received at teachers' college and the initial professional training she received as a novice teacher. She further shared her viewpoint as to the ways in which such teacher education and professional training programmes may become more effective for preparing teachers for leadership roles:

To be honest, from what I witnessed, the sort of training that I received was purely theoretical...leadership was definitely not an element of our training. The training mainly focused on subject knowledge and some pedagogical aspects...I mean teaching methods, assessment and so on...we were already exposed to this at university. It was a little bit what to say, dissociated from the reality of the classroom... I think that this is something that we really don't need, currently. We need workshops. We don't need lectures. But as far as I'm concerned, these are rare here.

It could be inferred from the above extract that the training that teachers received was mostly theoretical and largely focused on aspects related to subject matter and pedagogy with the absence of any input related to teacher leadership or educational leadership. Similarly, Maria [T, B, Int 153-155] and Nour [T, C, Int 158-160] respectively stressed that 'the training did not include leadership...inspectors never speak about it' and that 'when I studied at university, we did not have leadership module or preparation for leadership'. As per her perceptions of ways to improve the quality of teachers' professional training, Rokia [T, D, Int 218-219] stressed that the professional training must be continuous and should not be exclusively provided for early-career teachers. This aspect of continuity of professional training was echoed by many participants like Kenza [PT, C, Int 107-111], Melina [PT, B, Int 128-129] Sarah [T, B, Int 221-222] who all emphasised the importance of providing more professional development opportunities for teachers at all stages of their careers.

Indeed, as explained earlier in section 5.2.5, teachers who possess positional teacher leadership roles also need training that would enable them to adequately fulfil their role. Such training should clarify and clearly define teachers' roles as teacher leaders and provide guidelines as to the ways in which teachers can fulfil those roles. Rokia [T, D, Int 222- 224] equally insisted that teachers' training

must be up-to-date and must target issues and concerns related to educational leadership and the roles that teachers can assume as leaders within their schools. Apart from this, she pointed out that it is highly important that more research is conducted in the field of teacher leadership that would serve as a reference to plan future workshops and training sessions, as there are not sufficient insights into educational leadership and teacher leadership within the Algerian context.

5.4.4. Socio-cultural Factors

The Algerian socio-cultural context emerged as an important variable that may shape and affect teacher leadership practice within Algerian middle schools. Certain socio-cultural norms, according to participants, resulted in less sense of empowerment for female teachers as well as restricted opportunities for collaborative practices between male and female teachers.

Two participants brought up how the broader sociocultural context might result in less empowerment for female teachers. Rokia [T, D, Int 120-122] stated that due to certain socio-cultural barriers, married female teachers do not usually stand for their opinions or rights simply in order not to be involved in an argument with male headmasters. As she perceived teachers' potential to stand up for their rights as an important aspect of teacher leadership, Rokia stressed that gender differences may, in some cases, represent a barrier to participation in school leadership.

Women have that sort of acceptance to these behaviours of headmasters. Specifically, if they were married. Some female teachers would not engage in an argument with their male school principals because they fear what others would think of them.

Reflecting on her own experience, Nour [T, C, Int 141-146] supported the view that female teachers might often feel underestimated or marginalised by their male headmasters. She explained that the headmaster of her former school had a 'patriarchal mentality' as he often did not listen to or appreciate female teachers' views. At first, she only 'thought he was one of those school principals who prefer to be the centre of the school and the only leader'. However, she later realised that while he treats female teachers in that way, he seemed to value male teachers' contribution. She explained:

In my previous school, the school principal I would say had a patriarchal mentality. He often ignores female teachers' views. At the beginning, I thought he was one of those school principals who prefer to be the centre of the school and the only leader. However, I later realised that he treats male teachers differently. He discusses matters with them and appreciates their ideas and contributions.

Nour's example indicates that some male principals, affected by certain cultural norms and traditions, might undervalue, or exclude female teachers. In explaining that, she highlighted that it is mainly a cultural issue rather than a religious one. This might imply that in such situations, female teachers might feel less empowered and valued and more marginalised compared to their male counterparts.

Another aspect of the influence of the sociocultural context is related to the limited interactions between male and female teachers. Although most participants stressed that collaboration is a fundamental aspect of teacher leadership, certain Algerian socio-cultural factors were reported to limit collaboration within the school. Focus group participants emphasised that collaboration with peers from the opposing gender is minimal and occasional. There appeared to be a consensus among all focus group participants from the five schools (all were female teachers) that they felt more comfortable collaborating and interacting with other female teachers than with male teachers. Nawel [PT, B, FG2 112], Sarah [T, B, FG2 116] and Marwa [T, E, FG3 127], for instance, admitted that they favoured working with female peers, respectively stressing that for them, working with female peers was ‘more productive and acceptable’, ‘more appropriate’ and felt ‘more comfortable’. Similar views were shared by other participants:

When I want to collaborate, I would feel more at ease with females rather than males, because of the community and the culture [Chahine, T, C, FG3 131-132]

I noticed this with female teachers of different subjects. They did not collaborate too much with male teachers. There is a distance between them. They both distance themselves from each other...I do the same to be honest [Keltoum, T, E, FG1 173-175]

Participants’ accounts indicated that by virtue of the Algerian cultural norms and traditions, teachers often tend to minimise their interactions with peers from the opposite gender. According to Marwa [T, E, FG3 139-140], a school represents ‘a small community or a small society’ that adheres to the broader Algerian sociocultural norms, which makes collaboration and interactions between the two genders ‘a little bit difficult’. Being essentially conservative, the Algerian society sets limits that individuals in general, and teachers in this case, should not exceed when dealing with the other gender. The following quotes support this view:

Living in a conservative society, no matter what good relationship you want to establish with your co-workers, there are some limits. [Maria, T, B, FG1 178-180]

We live in a pretty conservative society and no matter how strong the bonds we want to create with the other gender, we always know that there are certain limits. I think the cultural and societal limits put us in this situation, especially for married female teachers [Rokia, T, D, FG1 163-166]

While Rokia [T, D, FG1 163-166] stressed that all teachers adhere to these ‘cultural and societal’ limits, she also emphasised that this might also relate to female teachers’ marital status. Her view was echoed by Keltoum [T, E, FG1 195-196], who noted that married female teachers often tend to distance themselves from their male colleagues. Elaborating on this, Sarah [T, B, FG2 121] explained that while male teachers choose to distance themselves from their female peers because

they perceive interactions with females as ‘a sensitive matter’, female teachers do the same to avoid potential ‘misunderstandings from others’.

To sum up, data presented in sections 5.4.1 to 5.4.4 revealed that overall, the kind of support required to empower the practice of teacher leadership is, to a great extent, missing in the Algerian middle school context. As explained earlier, when referring to their school contexts, most participants focussed on the hindrances that prevent teachers from assuming teacher leadership roles and while they described some desired supports, they stressed the need to nurture these within their workplace. It is worth highlighting that while certain factors can be subject to immediate attempts for amendment to meet teachers’ professional requirements, others may be more challenging to address as they seem to be deeply rooted within the broader Algerian socio-cultural context.

5.5. Professional growth as teacher leaders through informal collaboration within Teachers’ Communities

This section considers participants’ perceptions of the role of engaging and collaborating with other teachers in enhancing their professional learning as teacher leaders. Data presented in this section is primarily generated from the three focus groups and is organised into three broad themes, which aim to facilitate an understanding of participants’ perceptions of the ways in which informal collaboration with other teachers within the immediate school context and beyond is perceived to enable teachers to grow professionally and to acquire certain professional traits and skills required for teacher leaders.

5.5.1. Engaging in Collaborative practices within School-based Teachers’ Communities

This section considers participants’ perceptions of and experiences with collaboration with peers within their schools, and how these affect their sense of belonging to their school community. Data also revealed that teachers sometimes face issues that hinder collaboration, leading to feelings of isolation and a lack of sense of belonging.

Most participants stressed the importance of collaborating with peers within their schools and maintained that collaborative practices often take place in the staffroom, mainly during lunch breaks. This indicates that communal spaces, such as the staffroom, play an important role in cultivating a collaborative culture as they represent a physical space, where teachers could meet and engage in professional discussions. Participants reported various reasons for which they believe informal collaboration often takes place. Broadly, most teachers reported engaging in informal collaboration with peers for the sake of advancing their own practices, and more importantly for enhancing their students’ learning.

I think it's mainly due to shared knowledge and more importantly shared goals. They might know something that I don't know, I might know something that they

don't know, we sort of experience the same thing less or more, and we all want to do our best to enhance our pupils' learning [Rokia, T, D, FG1 204-207]

What is important for all teachers is that our pupils succeed, so it is important that we work together to help the learners [Nawel, PT, B, FG2 233-234]

we are all there doing our best and try to give the pupils the best teaching to develop their understanding and like, I don't know, to improve their scores and so on. So, we collaborate to do this [Serine, PT, E, FG1 214-216]

In pursuit of enhancing their own practices and thereof their learners' learning, participants reported engaging in various activities as part of informal collaboration with peers within their schools. Many participants, for instance, reported engaging in collaborative problem-solving with fellow teachers. In this sense, they maintained that whenever they encounter job-related problems, the first thing that they consider is consulting their colleagues and seeking their support:

Whenever I face a problem, I contact other teachers and consult them [Serine, PT, E, FG1 213]

The first thing that I usually do when I encounter a problem in the classroom is to share it and discuss it with other teachers in the teachers' room [Rokia, T, D, FG1 6-7]

We always discuss and work together to solve the problems we face. Together, we try to find the best solution to solve those problems [Sarah, T, B, FG2 245-246]

Apart from engaging in collaborative problem-solving, some participants informally collaborated with their peers through initiating and engaging in professional discussions; attending and observing each other's classes; and jointly planning lessons. Both novice and experienced teachers maintained that these practices allowed them to learn from each other through sharing more innovative and creative ideas related to lesson planning and delivery, engaging learners, and implementing technology and provided them with a space to reflect on their own instructional practices. The following quotes support these views:

It is very important when we discuss issues with each other...this gives you the chance to think about your teaching approaches and the ways you can improve it [Chahine, T, C, FG3 34-36]

It was through the collaborative work that I learnt how to design effective lesson plans [Keltoum, T, E, FG1 603-604]

Data equally indicated that both experienced and novice have the potential to make their own contributions within teachers' communities. Maria [T, B, FG1 601-604], Sarah [T, B, FG2 261-265] and Nawel [PT, B, FG2 268-271] particularly stressed the usefulness of regularly attending each other's classes and engaging in follow-up professional discussions as they respectively maintained:

When we attend each other's lessons, we observe how our colleague starts the lesson, engage the pupils and so on...As a beginning teacher, I face problems with classroom management...I, for example, observed how the principal teacher manages her classroom, how she gets learners' attention and compare it to my way.

Every time when I attend with them, I see how they bring new strategies in different lessons...they innovate always and I think like 'this is the missing part in my lessons.

Then when you discuss teaching practices with your colleagues, you start thinking like 'It will be good if I do this too'. So, you decide to do the same...and they also learn from you when you are creative in your teaching.

The above extracts indicate that for those teachers, attending each other's classes and engaging in follow-up discussions, they not only exchange feedback and ideas, but also engage in critical reflection of their own practices. These responses equally hint at the ways in which both novice and experienced teachers could learn from each other. While the innovative practices introduced by Sarah and Maria seem to be highly valued by their promoted peer, Nawel, who, through peer observation and critical reflection on her own practice, decided to implement more innovative instructional practices, other novice teachers spoke about their attempts to introduce more innovative practices within their school-based teachers' communities, yet maintained that these initiatives were resisted by their more experienced peers, who preferred to stick to the traditional teaching approaches and even tried to impose these approaches on them, which resulted in feelings of isolation among those novice teachers. This was particularly the case for Sandra [T, D, FG3 104] and Nour [T, C, FG2 167], who both reported that although they value collaboration with their peers, they often felt more 'isolated' and 'marginalised' because whenever they try to introduce more innovative teaching practices within their schools, the more experienced teachers as Sandra maintained often 'directly refuse' and insist that they 'must follow the traditional methods because new methods take more time'.

Overall, data presented in section 5.5.1 suggests that participants perceived informal collaboration within teachers' communities within their schools as a fundamental aspect of their daily work. As it has been shown earlier in section 5.2.2, collaboration was equally stressed by most participants as important aspect of teacher leadership. While in most cases, participants reported receiving collegial support and engaging in informal collaborative practices with their colleagues, they reported, in fewer cases, problematic relationships and lack of a 'collaborative spirit'. Data also revealed that power relations at the school level as well as specific Algerian sociocultural norms discussed in sections 5.4.2.1, 5.4.2.2 and 5.4.4 seem to further reinforce such feelings as they hinder teachers' autonomy, interactions, and collaborative work. Teachers in such situations would, therefore, try to establish professional connections and engage in collaborative practices with teachers beyond their immediate school contexts.

5.5.2. Establishing Connections with Broader Teachers' Communities

In cases when teachers did not feel a sense of belonging to teachers' communities within their schools, they tried to establish connections with other teachers beyond their immediate school context. Data indicated that these connections were particularly established within virtual communities, mainly Facebook groups of Algerian middle school teachers.

For some teachers, establishing networks within broader teacher communities beyond their immediate school contexts was fundamental even if they received professional support from peers within their workplace. Keltoum [T, E, FG1 42-45] and Sarah [T, B, FG2 172] maintained that although they often received professional support from peers within their schools, they equally appreciated participation and contribution in teachers' communities beyond their workplace. Similarly, Nawel [PT, B, FG2 177] stressed that 'it is important to interact and discuss issues with other teachers outside of the school'. For other participants, however, the need to establish such broader connections resulted from the limited professional support and collaboration within their schools, which seemed to result in feelings of isolation and lack of a sense of belonging to their school-based teachers' communities. This was the case for Nour [T, C, FG2 169-170] and Sandra [T, D, FG3 112-114], for instance, who stated:

I collaborate with teachers in Facebook more than in my school because teachers in my school are not always willing to collaborate.

I opt for social media collaboration, rather than the collaboration in the same school because I don't feel I find people who really have the spirit of collaboration in my school.

Accordingly, virtual communities, mainly in the form of Facebook groups of Algerian middle school teachers, provided an alternative avenue for teachers to debrief about work-related issues and to regularly engage in collaborative practices and professional discussions with other teachers. In this regard, both Sarah [T, B, FG2 58] and Keltoum [T, E, FG1 44] reported that whenever they failed to find effective solutions for any work-related problem, they resorted to similar groups where they initiate discussions to inquire about effective ways to approach them. They both stressed that as teachers post in these groups, they initiate a discussion that permits all members to share their viewpoints; discuss different ideas and perspectives and provide constructive feedback. While Sarah and Keltoum joined already existing Facebook groups for teachers, other participants took the initiative themselves to create such groups. This was the case for Halima [PT, A, FG3 328] and Nour [T, C, FG2 192] who created virtual groups with EFL or non EFL teachers who were their former university colleagues, friends or relatives and invited other teachers to join. Within these groups, teachers 'discuss issues about teaching and classroom management' [Keltoum, T, E, FG1 337-338] and 'collaboratively produced innovative teaching materials' [Halima, PT, A, FG3 328-329].

Based on some teachers' perspectives, the usefulness of engaging in these broader teacher communities lies in that they enable teachers to collaborate with 'like-minded' fellows. In this sense, both Sandra [T, D, FG3 332-334] and Nour [T, C, FG2 194-195] specifically described how their innovative practices, which were often resisted by experienced teachers within their schools, were more valued and were adopted by other teachers within these Facebook groups:

I always share creative strategies with like-minded teachers in this group...they praise my practices and some of them apply them too in their classrooms.

They also welcome creative teaching...we always support each other and share with each other to develop more creative teaching approaches to improve our learners' achievements.

These virtual spaces not only promoted interaction and collaboration between teachers, but also seemed to reduce -to some extent- the sociocultural barriers between male and female teachers. Sandra's [T, D, FG3 336-338] statement that she felt more comfortable interacting and collaborating with male teachers within these groups than within her school context supports this view:

I think that when I interact with male teachers on Facebook for example, I have no problem with that. We discuss and exchange ideas and materials and it is totally fine unlike inside the school.

The examples provided in this section indicate teachers' willingness to join broader teachers' communities beyond their school context. Engaging in those communities provided teachers with opportunities to seek and provide professional support and gave them more margins of freedom to express their viewpoints. Furthermore, it enhanced their teaching practices as well as their sense of belonging to the profession as they aligned their practices with those of other teachers within these broad communities. More details on the perceived impact of engaging in informal collaboration within teachers' communities at the school level and beyond are presented in the following section.

5.5.3. Perceived Impact of Collaboration on Enhancing Teachers' Professional Learning as Teacher Leaders

Overall, all participants held a positive outlook of informal collaboration, perceiving it as fundamental for both novice and experienced teachers' professional learning. For them, collaboration represents an opportunity for ongoing professional learning through which teachers could develop qualities and skills that they deemed crucial for teacher. Developing such qualities and skills was perceived to be facilitated by informal collaboration which allows for sharing experiences and providing feedback, encouragement, and professional support.

5.5.3.1. Developing Qualities of Teacher Leaders

Most participants related collaboration to enhancing certain qualities, which they, in turn, perceived as a prerequisite for teacher leadership practice. These qualities particularly involved: *competence and self-confidence*.

According to Nour [T, C, FG2 471], it is through collaboration with peers that teachers ‘attain efficiency and effectiveness in their teaching and enhance creativity in their work’. For her, teachers who work collaboratively are more likely to reach higher levels of competency in their profession than teachers who isolate themselves from their peers.

As an example of collaborative practices that teachers believed to enhance their teaching competence were the opportunities, which they had to attend and observe each other’s sessions, and subsequently engage in follow-up discussions. Attending these sessions enabled teachers to observe their peers’ best practices and ‘take notes’ [Nour, T, C, FG2 467]. Furthermore, discussions initiated between teachers by the end of such sessions provide a space for knowledge sharing through which teachers continuously learn, acquire new information, adapt their teaching practices, and eventually become more competent and effective teachers. These were perceived as ideal spaces for ‘providing constructive feedback’ [Keltoum, T, E, FG1 150-151], and for reflecting ‘on [their] practice and the practice of others’ [Amira, T, A, FG2 458]. In this regard, Keltoum [T, E, FG1 541-542] maintained that as teachers engage in discussions as part of their collaborative practices, they often share their lived experiences, which she perceived as more effective for enhancing teachers’ instructional capacities and competence than ‘searching and reading theoretically’. Sarah [T, B, FG2 474] equally stressed that the feedback and advice provided by her peers helped her to recognise and thus avoid some mistakes that she used to make in terms of lesson delivery and classroom management, and thus become a more competent teacher.

For Nour [T, C, FG2 469] as teachers work in a team, they can ‘brainstorm new ideas’, which facilitated development and implementation of new teaching techniques and instruments within their classrooms. This, in turn, increased their skills and potentials as teachers. In most cases, the sharing of different ideas and perspectives could enable teachers to ‘find the most suitable methods’ that they can employ with their learners [Nawel, PT, B, FG2 481].

Data indicated that collaboration was perceived by most participants to be beneficial to all teachers, regardless of their seniority or position. To illustrate, Nawel [PT, B, FG2 183-184], with an experience of 14 years in teaching stressed that she learns through reflecting on her experiences and experiences of others as they share them as part of their collaborative practices. Similarly, Halima [PT, A, FG3 412] maintained that senior teachers often lack effectiveness in the use of technology, which they can develop through collaborating with ‘younger teachers’. Alternatively, Rokia [T, D,

FG1 585-586], a novice teacher, reported that it was through collaboration that she learnt the basics of teaching and ‘survived [her] first year’ as a teacher. Likewise, speaking from a novice teacher’s perspective, Marwa [T, E, FG3 417] specified that as novice teachers work collaboratively and engage in discussions with more experienced colleagues, they can give them ‘the core of the experience that [they] may take ages to acquire on [their] own’ and can accordingly develop pedagogical competence and become ‘more effective in dealing with their learners’.

Apart from its impact on enhancing teachers’ competence and effectiveness, collaboration within a positive and supportive environment was reported by most participants as having a great impact on their confidence and self-esteem, a trait that they associated with teacher leaders. On the one hand, collaborative work that they engaged in increased their confidence in their teaching practices and competencies. This was, in Halima [PT, A, FG3 424-425] and Sandra’s [T, D, FG3 427-428] case mostly evident when they jointly plan lessons with other teachers. They, respectively, stated:

When I present something, it’s not only my work, but the fruit of collaboration, between different teachers. This will make me more confident about how I’m doing it.

You present to the pupils the fruits of the work of all teachers or a group of teachers. So, it makes me more confident.

Collaborative peers were perceived by some participants as capable of empowering their colleagues and strengthening their personalities. Nour [T, C, FG2 518] and Serine [PT, E, FG1 628] explained that in cases when teachers felt ‘timid’ to talk in public or ‘anxious’ about the effectiveness of their teaching practices, it was the guidance and support that they received from their peers that helped them to overcome these negative feelings and to develop a stronger and more confident personality. In a similar sense, Nawel [PT, B, FG2 523] reported having a stronger personality as a result of her interactions and informal collaboration with peers.

On the other hand, teachers reported a positive impact of collaboration on their confidence in sharing their viewpoints within their immediate and broader teacher communities. Working in an environment where positive interactions and collegial support are the norm would enhance teachers’ confidence ‘to express and defend [their] viewpoints’ in an environment in which this ‘is not risky’ [Serine, PT, E, FG1 637-638]. Reiterating the same viewpoint, Nawel [PT, B, FG2 524-525] and Sarah [T, B, FG2 531-535], respectively, stated:

When the environment is supportive and collaborative, I can express my opinions freely concerning not only teaching, even about any matter concerning the school. At the beginning when I started teaching, I used to be shy. I used to hide. I always keep silent and just listen. Now, I interact, I give my opinion with confidence. I got that self-confidence from those meetings and interactions with teachers, not just in the domain of teaching, but to give my opinion inside the school.

In Sarah's [T, B, FG2 531-535] case, she gradually developed a sense of belonging to her school community and became more confident in sharing her viewpoints due to the collaborative nature of her relationship with other teachers. In this sense, informal collaboration seems to serve as a means to empower teachers. Some novice teachers, particularly, reported feeling even more confident when their innovative practices, which they share within teachers' communities, gained them recognition, and were adopted by their peers.

5.5.3.2. Enhanced Skills Required for Teacher Leaders

In addition to enhancing their teachers' effectiveness and competence and increasing their self-confidence and sense of empowerment, participants highlighted the role of informal collaboration in enhancing certain professional skills, which they deemed essential for the practice of teacher leadership.

To begin with, four participants stressed that collaborative practices enhanced their decision-making skills. Sarah [T, B, FG2 566-567] and Nawel [PT, B, FG2 573-575] explained that it was through the collaborative practices that they often engaged in that they learnt how to make informed and appropriate decisions both within and beyond their classrooms. When teachers work in an environment where they interact and discuss various issues, they seem to acquire and adopt the teams' method of approaching problems. In this sense, Nour [T, C, FG2 592-594] stated:

When I talk about a problem with teachers, they give their opinions, different solutions to solve the problem. I listen to them. What are their advantages? What are their disadvantages? And I decide what solution is better.

The above quote indicates that through collaboration and interactions with fellow teachers, Nour became more capable of taking informed decisions by evaluating all possible choices and finally choosing what they believe was the most appropriate and effective option. Halima [PT, A, FG3 487-492] shared a similar view, yet she referred to it as critical thinking skills, stating that through collaborative work, teachers learn to approach issues in a more rational way by analysing and weighing up different ideas and perspectives.

Through collaboration, I learned that as a teacher, I should not just take anything or accept everything as it is. I notice how some other teachers analyse the situation and evaluate the different options which we have. This is critical thinking. So, I also developed this critical thinking in my work. I adopted this approach from collaborating and interacting with other teachers.

Not only was collaboration perceived to enhance decision-making skills and critical thinking capacities, but it was also perceived by many participants to enhance teachers' reflective skills. To exemplify, Amira [T, A, FG2 600-601], Rokia [T, D, FG1 611-614] and Nawel [PT, B, FG2 578-582] explained that through collaboration and interactions between teachers within their schools and

beyond, they became more aware of the importance of reflection and more capable to reflect on their own practices as well as the experiences of others.

As I discuss issues with other teachers on Facebook groups and I hear their views, I always think about my teaching and my work like how I can improve it.

I think that the gains of such collaborative practices are beyond mere exchange of ideas. These practices make us as teachers reflect on our own teaching practices, our relationships with learners, with peers and so on. Developing such a reflective stance is really important for our growth as teachers and as leaders.

It happens with me that every time when I attend a class with my colleagues and I observe the way they deliver the lesson, they use technology and innovative methods, I reflect more on my teaching and decide how to adopt similar methods to develop my teaching too.

Five focus group participants equally stressed that the more teachers engage in informal collaborative practices, the more likely they are to develop collaborative and communicative skills. In this sense, Sarah [T, B, FG2 569-572] and Rokia [T, D, FG1 621-624], for instance, maintained:

It is logical when you work with others in a regular way, you will surely enhance your communication. You become better in explaining your opinions and also a better listener to others.

You become part of a team and you value this team. That sort of teamwork becomes an indispensable part of your day-to-day work...It involves being a better, more efficient communicator who listens to others, respects their views, and clearly explains his own.

In summary, sections 5.5.1 to 5.5.3 provided an overall understanding of the perceived role of informal collaboration within teachers' communities at the school level and beyond in enhancing teachers' leadership learning. Data revealed that while engaging in collaborative work enhanced teachers' sense of belonging to teachers' communities within their schools, non-collaborative environments resulted in feelings of isolation and lack of sense of belonging. Such feelings particularly resulted from control exerted by school principals or by promoted teachers and the boundaries established by the overall Algerian sociocultural context. Teachers, in this case, established connections with broader teacher communities beyond their immediate school contexts. For those teachers, virtual communities provided an alternative for teacher collaboration within their schools. Informal collaboration and interactions with other teachers within their immediate workplace and beyond represented a learning experience that was perceived by teachers in this study to have a potential to enhance certain qualities and professional skills, which they believed were essential for teacher leaders' work.

5.6. Chapter Summary

This chapter has provided a detailed presentation of the findings generated from individual interviews, written reflections, and focus group discussions. Overall, the presented data provided a detailed overview of teacher leadership in the Algerian middle school context, from the perspective of middle school EFL teachers. First, in terms of teachers' perceptions of teacher leadership, it was revealed that despite their unfamiliarity with the term, teachers perceived the concept mainly in terms of influence through non-positional practices rather than designated position or authority. Participant teachers defined the concept with reference to practices within the classroom, practices beyond the classroom, teacher leaders' traits and participation in decision-making. Furthermore, while participants were aware of the available positional teacher leadership roles within their context and the process through which teachers were assigned these roles, their awareness of the additional responsibilities that come with these roles was to some extent limited. Second, teachers' reported practices of teacher leadership were in line with their perceptions in that they were mainly non-positional in nature and were not restricted to the classroom context. Their reported practices were mainly self-initiated and overall, reflected their innovative and differentiated teaching practices, individualised support for their learners, continuous professional learning, and the direct or indirect influence that they exerted on their peers. Third, several factors were highlighted by the participants as supporting or hindering the enactment of teacher leadership within their school contexts. These related broadly to teacher-related factors including their confidence, intrinsic motivation and willingness and desire to initiate change; school-based factors including peers and principals' support and work conditions; and system-based factors including the top-down system and professional training opportunities. Interestingly, findings indicated that the broader Algerian sociocultural context could equally influence teacher leadership enactment, particularly resulting in some female teachers feeling less recognised and empowered by their school principals compared to their male counterparts; and in relatively limiting interactions and collaborative practices between male and female teachers. Finally, in relation to the fourth research question, findings indicated that participant teachers believe deeply in the power of informal collaboration within teachers' communities at the school level and beyond for enhancing their potential for teacher leadership work. For them, engagement within these communities represented a learning opportunity for teachers that reportedly enabled them to become more effective, competent and confident in their work and to develop skills that they perceived to be fundamental for teacher leaders' work. The following chapter sets to discuss these findings in relation with relevant literature on teacher leadership.

Chapter Six: Discussion of the Findings

6.1. Introduction

This chapter discusses the research findings with reference to the existing literature on teacher leadership as well as features of the educational context in Algeria. The main foci of this study were related, first, to the investigation of Algerian middle school EFL teachers' perceptions of teacher leadership. Second, this study investigated participants' reported practices of and experiences with teacher leadership. Third, as the review of the literature proved that effective enactment of teacher leadership is subject to various variables, it was deemed important to investigate factors that either supported or hindered teacher leadership practice within the Algerian context from the perspective of Algerian middle school EFL teachers. Finally, the study investigated participants' perceptions of the role of collaboration with other teachers in enhancing their professional learning and growth as teacher leaders. This chapter is structured into five sections. The first section broadly discusses the findings in light of the study's conceptual framework. The remaining four sections discuss the findings in more details in relation to each of the four research questions that guided this study.

6.2. A snapshot of major findings in light of the conceptual framework

This section discusses findings with reference to the conceptual framework that underpins this study. As discussed in section 3.7, the present study is underpinned by Wenger's (1998) CoP and specifically draws on concepts from Campbell and colleagues' (2019) Communities of Practice Teacher Leadership Model (CoPTLM hereafter) and Wenger's (1998) modes of belonging: engagement, imagination, and alignment.

The current study sets as its overarching aim the investigation of teacher leadership within the Algerian context. Broadly, both teachers' perceptions and their reported practices in this study were centred on non-positional teacher leadership, which Murphy (2005) described as community based. Participant teachers related teacher leadership particularly to teachers' self-initiated practices, through which those teachers could exert influence at many levels and within multiple settings. Looking at the emerging findings from the lens of Campbell and colleagues' (2019) CoPTLM facilitates not only a broader understanding of the communities or social settings that teacher leaders engage in and contribute to, but more specifically an understanding of the competences that enable teacher leaders to contribute to these communities; their performances within these communities; the kind of internal and/ or external recognition that teacher leaders receive as a result of these practices as well as the role of existing structures within the research context that either supported or constrained teacher leadership enactment across different communities.

The study equally draws on Wenger's (1998) modes of belonging to better understand teachers' professional learning and growth as teacher leaders through their engagement in informal collaborative practices within teachers' communities. To recap, Wenger (1998) describes three

specific modes of belonging to a CoP, which are not linear or mutually exclusive but rather occur through inter-processes (Huggins, 2017). These three modes of belonging are: engagement, imagination, and alignment. *Engagement* entails ‘doing things together’ (Wenger, 2000) and sharing experiences with co-practitioners. *Imagination* goes beyond engagement in practice within a community as it is based on individuals’ ability to re-create the images of themselves and of the world through different perspectives (Huggins, Lesseig and Rhodes, 2017). In that sense, imagination is largely dependent on individuals’ self-awareness and active reflection on their engagement to explore new ways of doing things and to incorporate other perspectives into one’s identity and practice. Finally, *alignment* entails sharing objectives or principles with other members within a CoP, which enables community members to position their own practices within broader communities. It, therefore, implies establishing a broad common vision and coordinating and directing energies and efforts to achieve shared goals (Goodnough, 2010).

That being said, it could be inferred from findings presented in the preceding chapter that teachers’ self-initiated leadership practices and teacher leaders’ influence, as perceived by participant teachers, seem to span four main communities or social settings. These were: learners’ community (sections 5.2.1), teachers’ community (sections 5.2.2), school management community (sections 5.2.2), and the broader policymakers’ community (section 5.2.3). Findings presented in section 5.3, however, indicate that teachers’ reported practices were notably restricted to only two communities (the learners’ and teachers’ communities).

First, teachers in this study perceived the classroom as the primary space within which teachers could practise leadership and, directly or indirectly, exert influence on learners’ communities at multiple levels. As shown in sections 5.2.1 and 5.3.1, based on their content and subject knowledge, knowledge of their learners and their relationship-building skills (*competences*), teacher leaders provide their learners with high quality, innovative and differentiated instruction; establish and maintain a suitable learning environment; and lead by example as they model ethical behaviour (*performances*). Those practices, as stressed by most participants, would result in enhanced students’ learning and motivation; improved discipline; and enhanced ethical behaviour.

Beyond their classrooms, teacher leaders are perceived in this study to influence other teachers, thus engaging in, and contributing to school-based teachers’ communities. Particularly, findings in sections 5.2.2, 5.3.1 and 5.3.2 indicate that the content and subject knowledge as well as the collaborative skills that teacher leaders possess (*competences*) enable them to professionally support, motivate and empower their peers and to lead by example through modelling effective instructional practices (*performances*). These practices often gained teachers praise and respect among their peers and to a lesser extent among their school principals.

A third community that teacher leaders could contribute to, as perceived by participant teachers in this study, is the school management community. In this sense, findings presented in section 5.2.2 indicate that teachers' extended knowledge of their classrooms' realities and their learners' needs and peers' requirements (*competence*) place them in the best position to advocate for their needs. Teacher leaders in this sense were perceived to play a mediating role between their learners and peers on the one hand and the school senior management on the other hand and could equally contribute to problem-solving, thus relieving the burden of school management of overworked school principals (*performances*).

A fourth and final community that teacher leaders can contribute to, as perceived by teachers in this study, is the broader policymakers' community as discussed in section 5.2.3. As in the case of the third community, the main competences that enable teachers to contribute to the broader policymakers' community is their extended knowledge of their learners and of classroom realities. Such knowledge places teacher leaders in the best position to inform policymaking reforms as well as the design of textbooks and curricula (*performances*).

Campbell and colleagues (2019) maintain that teacher leaders often engage in practices across different communities drawing on common competences across these communities. This argument highlights the potential of boundary crossing (Wenger, 1998) as an essential aspect of teacher leaders' work. As could be noted from the above, findings of this study indicate that teachers' pedagogical and subject knowledge as well as knowledge of their learners seem to be particularly relevant and valuable for their leadership practices across multiple communities. These types of knowledge were perceived to enable teacher leaders to exert influence at multiple levels through a range of *performances*. At the level of learners' community, these types of knowledge enabled teachers to enhance their students' learning through designing and implementing innovative and differentiated instructional practices to accommodate their learners' needs and provide individualised assistance for specific learners. Within teachers' communities, teacher leaders draw on these competences to lead by example through modelling effective instructional practices. Likewise, these same competences were perceived by many participants to uniquely position teachers to function as mediators between their classrooms and the school management teams; and to inform and contribute to the design and development of relevant textbook and curricula. Looking more specifically at findings presented in sections 5.3.1 and 5.3.2 of the preceding chapter, it could be noted that the same competences and performances reported by teachers in relation to their classroom-based practices enabled them to exert influence on their learners through enhancing their academic outcomes, their motivation and their engagement, while at the same time influencing their peers as they made these practices visible to their peers or as they engaged in professional discussions to share the positive outcomes of their practices with their fellow teachers.

Recognition was an important aspect highlighted by teachers in this study. In their CoPTLM, Campbell and colleagues (2019) specifically stressed two types of recognition that support teacher leaders' work. These are internal recognition, which relates to teachers' sense of self as teacher leaders; and external recognition, which delineates recognition that teacher leaders receive from other school members. The importance of external recognitions lies in that it strengthens teachers' sense of self as teacher leaders and of their *performances* as teacher leadership practices. In the present study, when teachers spoke of external recognition, they often referred to it as desired or expected recognition. This was particularly the case when they referred to teacher leaders' potential to contribute to the school management community and the broader stakeholders' community, in which some teachers stressed the importance of praising and valuing teachers' contributions to these communities. Equally in terms of desired external recognition, teachers in this study stressed that beyond praise and verbal recognition, they desire remuneration for the initiatives that they undertake across the four communities. As noted earlier in this section, participant teachers' reported practices of teacher leadership were particularly restricted to the learners' community and the teachers' community. Findings presented in sections 5.3.1 and 5.3.2 indicate that while participant teachers themselves referred to certain initiatives that they undertook as teacher leadership practices given their perceptions of positive impact that these practices had on their learners or their peers, which is consistent with Campbell and colleagues (2019) description of *internal recognition*, most of them equally highlighted the ways in which these practices gained them praise from their peers and to a lesser extent from school principals or subject inspectors. Such *external recognition* seems to have further reinforced participants' perceptions of their practices as teacher leadership practices.

As teachers engage in multiple communities, teachers' lens, dispositions, and existing structures could either support or challenge teacher leadership work (ibid). Findings of the present study similarly provided insights into multiple factors that either support or hinder teacher leadership practice within the Algerian context. Particularly, findings in sections 5.4.2 and 5.4.3 indicate that within the study context, time constraints, work overload, scarcity of resources as well as prevalent hierarchical structures represented major hindrances for teacher leadership enactment.

Interestingly, findings indicated that while these factors largely hindered teachers' participation in and contribution to the school management communities and broader policymakers' community, teachers seem to challenge these hindrances to exert influence -at some level- within learners' and teachers' communities as discussed above. As teachers in this study engage in leadership work, their primary aim is to enhance their students' learning and to a lesser extent to support and empower their peers.

In the present study, the teachers' community was specifically put under the spotlight with the aim of examining teachers' perceptions of the impact of engaging in informal collaboration within this community in enhancing their professional learning and growth as teacher leaders. Lieberman and Friedrich (2010) and Trabona and colleagues (2019) maintain that teachers' learning according to Wenger (1998) is deeply rooted in individuals' need to feel a sense of belonging and to contribute to a community. Interestingly, teachers in this study often explicitly stressed that engaging in informal collaboration enhanced their sense of belonging to teachers' communities at the school level and beyond. In this sense, these communities were perceived by participant teachers not only as one of the primary spaces in which teachers could practise leadership and exert influence as discussed above, but also as a social setting in which teachers, both novice and experienced, can grow professionally as teacher leaders. Indeed, both novice and experienced teachers in this study valued informal collaboration within teachers' communities and perceived it as the most effective professional learning opportunity. These views support Hara's (2009) observation that CoPs provide an informal learning environment for both novice and experienced members of the community given the opportunities that all members have to interact with each other, share their experiences and learn from each other. The examples shared by participants in this study provided evidence that as part of informal collaboration with other teachers within both school-based and virtual teachers' communities, teachers *engaged* in practices with peers; *imagined* new possibilities and alternative ways of doing things; and *aligned/ critically aligned* their practices with the broader goals, principles, and practices of their community.

Both experienced and novice teachers in this study reported engaging in informal collaborative practices within a teachers' community both at the level of their schools and beyond, particularly within virtual communities of teachers on Facebook. Teachers in this study *engaged* in both subject-related and interdisciplinary informal collaborative practices as they participated in collaborative problem-solving; joint lesson planning; and some of them regularly attended, observed each other's classes and engaged in professional discussions. Engaging in these practices provided those teachers with a space within which they shared best practices; provided constructive feedback; and exchanged innovative ideas and teaching materials. For them, the positive and supportive relationships that teachers established and maintained with their colleagues were an important enabler of such collaborative work particularly within their school contexts. An essential part of these positive relationships was experienced teachers' sustained availability and approachability to support early-career teachers. Likewise, findings stressed that these professional relationships were further strengthened and supported by maintaining mutual respect and providing affirmation, praise, and encouragement. Working in a collaborative environment characterised by positive and supportive

professional relationships enhanced teachers' sense of belonging to teachers' communities and to the profession. Notably, engagement and collaboration with peers at the school level was perceived by most participant teachers as a key aspect of teacher leadership practice and an essential means through which teacher leaders could influence their peers.

Teachers' learning within teachers' communities at the school level and beyond, however, seems to transcend the benefits of their immediate joint practices. That is, engaging in informal collaborative practices enabled teachers to consider new possibilities and new ways of doing things. Findings presented in sections 5.5.1 to 5.5.3 revealed that as some teachers in this study engaged in joint practices and professional discussions within school-based and virtual teachers' communities, they constantly reflected on their own practices and envisioned ways to refine and improve these practices. Examples included some experienced teachers considering more innovative and creative instructional strategies as well as some novice teachers considering different ways of interacting with learners and maintaining discipline within their classrooms as a result of their engagement with fellow teachers and particularly through peer observation and professional discussions. These examples are reflective of Wenger's (1998) description of *imagination* as a mode of belonging. Interestingly, such reflective practices were perceived by many teachers in this study not only as fundamental for teachers' professional learning and growth, but also as essential for teacher leadership practice.

As participant teachers engaged in informal collaboration with other teachers both at the school level and virtually, they come together and engage in joint practices to achieve common goals. These goals particularly revolved around enhancing students' learning by addressing common problems and seeking ways to enhance their own instructional practices. Arguably, the shared overarching goal of improving students' learning aligns well with York-Barr and Duke's (2004) and Fairman and Mackenzie's (2012) conceptualisations of teacher leadership practice, which similarly stress improvements in students' learning as the ultimate goal of teacher leaders' work. While teachers in this study seem to *align* themselves with this common goal, they appear, sometimes, to consider different ways to arrive at this goal. This was specifically the case for novice teachers, who often sought to challenge the status quo by attempting to introduce more innovative instructional practices as opposed to the traditional teaching methods commonly employed within teachers' communities in their schools. These attempts by novice teachers are reflective of Biza, Jaworski and Hemmi's (2014) *critical alignment*. Evidence from the present study, however, indicates that the outcomes of these initiatives significantly differed. While for some novice teachers, their innovative practices were welcomed, recognised, and embraced by other teachers within their schools, including the more experienced teachers, which further enhanced their sense of belonging and contribution to the teachers' community within their schools, other novice teachers faced resistance as a response to their

innovative practices within their immediate school contexts. For teachers in the latter case, such resistance seemed to result in feelings of isolation and a lack of sense of belonging to the teachers' community in their schools. This led them to seek connections with virtual communities within which their innovative practices were valued and embraced. Participant teachers perceived such innovative practices as an important aspect of teacher leadership and stressed that school contexts that do not value and promote teachers' innovative practices as restrictive to teacher leadership enactment.

While this section broadly looked at findings of the present study and discussed them in light of Campbell and colleagues' (2019) CoPTLM and Wenger's (1998) modes of belonging, sections 6.3 to 6.6 provide a more thorough and detailed discussion of the research findings with reference to previous empirical research in the field as well as features of the Algerian educational system.

6.3. What perceptions do middle school EFL teachers hold regarding teacher leadership?

The purpose of this research question was to gain a collective understanding of how Algerian middle school EFL teachers perceive teacher leadership. This question was addressed in the preceding chapter, in sections 5.2.1 to 5.2.5. Findings revealed that although the term 'teacher leadership', itself, may not have been a term that teachers in this study were familiar with, most of their responses indicated that they had some understanding of what constitutes teacher leadership and recognised its value for individuals, institutions, and policy. Teachers' unfamiliarity with the term 'teacher leadership' might be attributed to the fact that this term is not commonly used in the Algerian school context. As discussed in chapter two (section 2.4.3), the use of the terms 'teacher leadership' or 'teacher leader' is not visible in educational policy discourse in Algeria. Similarly, Algerian middle school EFL teachers receive no input on educational leadership or teacher leadership as part of their pre-service or in-service training.

In this study, teachers' perceptions supported the complexity and multi-dimensionality of teacher leadership, as they perceived it as covering a wide range of activities that teacher leaders could engage in and multiple traits that characterise teacher leaders. This is aligned with what the literature reveals about authors' various interpretations of teacher leadership, stressing that the existing literature provides multiple competing and overlapping definitions of the concept (Nguyen, Harris and Ng, 2019; Schott, van Roekel and Tummers, 2020; Wenner and Campbell, 2017). Overall, participants' perceptions of teacher leadership share important characteristics with the definitions proposed by York-Barr and Duke (2004) and Katzenmeyer and Moller (2001) in that teacher leadership is understood as a process of influence and that teachers can practise leadership both within and beyond their classrooms.

First, one of the study's key findings is that teacher leadership is mainly perceived by the participants in relation with non-positional practices rather than designated positional roles. Irrespective of their length of teaching experience or position, all teachers in this study defined teacher leadership with reference to teachers' self-initiated practices and to their attributes and traits, which gain them credibility and recognition, and enable them to exert influence through collaboration, providing professional support for peers, and modelling effective instructional practices and ethical behaviour. This view is consistent with an extensive body of research that views teachers as capable of practising teacher leadership regardless of their designated position or authority (Harris, 2003; Nguyen, Harris and Ng, 2019; Schott et al., 2020; Supovitz, 2018; York-Barr and Duke, 2004). Second, findings revealed that participant teachers recognised the practice of teacher leadership as not restricted to the classroom context, but as a practice that could also be extended beyond classrooms. This idea is a core aspect of Katzenmeyer and Moller's (2001) definition of teacher leaders, as they emphasised that teacher leaders 'lead within and beyond the classroom' (p. 17). Findings similarly support Cooper and colleague's (2016) argument that in spite of the varied conceptualisations of teacher leadership, it is commonly agreed that teacher leadership can take place both within and outside the classrooms.

Supporting Hunzicker's (2017) argument, teachers in this study perceived the classrooms as the primary space within which all teachers can lead and as an important springboard from which teacher leadership attributes could emerge. In terms of teacher leadership within the classroom, it was interesting to note that some participants in this study particularly referred to the Competency Based Approach, perceiving teacher leadership as tightly related to knowledge and effective implementation of the CBA approach. This view seems to be somewhat narrow, reflecting an aspect that could well be relevant to general teachers' role rather than to teacher leaders. Focus on the CBA approach by some teachers in this study might be very much reflective of the MoNE's focus on this latter. As discussed in chapter two (section 2.3), implementation of the CBA is at the core of most recent educational reforms in Algeria. This might have led some teachers in this study to perceive teacher leaders as teachers who possess extended knowledge of and are capable of effectively implementing the CBA within their classrooms.

Beyond this arguably narrow perspective, participants in this study understood that teachers could be non-positional leaders within their classrooms particularly as they prioritise their students' learning and strive to provide them with the best teaching quality, which in turn implies understanding and attending to their learners' needs and learning preferences, and accordingly designing and implementing effective and innovative teaching strategies that would eventually lead their learners to academic success. For the participants, this also requires teachers to be competent and to manifest extended knowledge of their subject matter and pedagogy. Moreover, they stressed that teachers could practise non-positional teacher leadership within the classroom by being effective in terms of

classroom management, and as a result establishing and maintaining an optimal learning environment for their learners. These views support findings from previous research that stress the focus on student learning as the primary foundation of teachers' leadership actions (Alsalahi, 2016; Muijs and Harris, 2006; Wenner and Campbell, 2017). In line with Öqvist and Malmström's (2018), teachers in this study also stressed that teacher leaders inspire and motivate their learners. Findings indicated that teacher leaders' practices within their classrooms were perceived to particularly influence students' achievements, behaviour, and motivation. This impact was mostly indirect, as teacher leadership was perceived to have an impact on teachers' instructional practices and classroom management skills, which could in turn improve learners' achievements, enhance their motivation and reduce misbehaviour within classrooms.

Notably, for teachers in this study, teacher leaders' role within their classrooms transcends the efforts that target enhancing learners' academic outcomes to involve instilling values and ethics in their learners who perceive them as role models. They maintained that through modelling ethical behaviour and establishing and maintaining a good relationship with the learners, teacher leaders could play a central role in instilling values in their learners. This aspect of teacher leaders' role within their classrooms was unanimously stressed by participant teachers regardless of their positions. The views shared by participant teachers in this regard are largely consistent with the views shared by Qatari teachers in Sawalhi's (2019) study, who constantly referred to a teacher leader as a *Murabbi*, an Arabic term used to describe a teacher, who is 'not simply a teacher...but rather an exemplary human being and ideal Muslim' (Kazmi, 1999, p. 222 cited in Sawalhi, 2019). Sawalhi (2019) attributed such emphasis on the role of a *Murabbi* to religious influence, maintaining that in Muslim countries, teachers are expected to model ethical behaviours and promote values to prepare good citizens, rather than exclusively focus on developing their teaching and pedagogical expertise.

Findings also concur with a number of previous studies in which teacher leadership roles were perceived as extended beyond the classroom (Alsalahi, 2016; Chien, 2020; Emira, 2010; Oppi, Eisenschmidt and Stingu, 2023). In this study, a particular reference in this regard was made to teachers' collaboration with their colleagues, which was stressed by both positional teacher leaders and teachers who do not hold a positional leadership role as an essential aspect of non-positional teacher leadership practice beyond their classrooms. Participant teachers stressed that as teachers engage in informal professional conversations and attend each other's classes, they exchange constructive feedback and innovative ideas and materials and motivate each other towards improved instructional practices. It was important to note from the findings that it is through such activities that teacher leaders could influence their peers, particularly through providing professional support and modelling effective and innovative instructional practices. In this sense, these findings resonate with

Katzenmeyer and Moller (2011) who maintained that teacher leaders can influence other teachers informally by having casual conversations, sharing materials, facilitating professional development, or simply extending an invitation for other teachers to visit their classrooms. Findings also echoed many other empirical studies (Alsalahi, 2016; Chien, 2020; Fairman and Mackenzie, 2015; Hunzicker, 2012) in stressing the importance of ‘supporting others’ as an effective way for teacher leaders to influence their colleagues. All of these examples of teacher leaders’ influence as perceived by participant teachers correspond to what Supovitz (2018) referred to as ‘soft strategies’ that non-positional teacher leaders employ to influence their peers’ instructional practices. These strategies, as suggested by participants in this study, enable teachers to indirectly impact instruction without necessarily having any positional role, which aligns with Munroe and Driskill (2014) who stress teacher leaders’ potential to influence instruction without necessarily possessing any positional authority based on the positive relationships that they establish and maintain with their peers. For teachers in this study, as teacher leaders contribute to improving their peers’ instructional practices and to enhancing their professional learning through collaboration, role modelling and providing professional support, they equally increase their self-esteem and confidence in their potential, which in turn enhances their sense of empowerment.

Another manifestation of teachers’ participation in non-positional teacher leadership practice beyond the classroom context occurred when the participant teachers played a mediating role between classrooms and the school senior management team. According to Harris and Muijs (2002), there is some divergence in teacher leadership literature between those who perceive teacher leaders as collaborators with senior management and a minority who sees them as performing some of the senior management functions and partly replacing them. Findings of this study support the former view. As mediators, teacher leaders in this study communicated and advocated for their learners and peers’ needs and expectations, thus representing a link between the classrooms and the school administrative team. Somewhat aligned with Margolis’ (2012) notion of ‘hybrid teacher leaders’, teacher leaders in this study are, therefore, perceived as an important human resource within their work environment as they serve as a bridge linking multiple subgroups within the school context. The mediating role of teacher leaders as perceived by participants in this study, however, seems to be narrower than that in Margolis’ study as it is limited to the school level and does not extend to cover other subgroups at other levels of the educational system. Findings of this study indicate that through such mediating role, teacher leaders can support school principals’ work as they represent a valuable and reliable resource for data on classrooms, teachers and learners. Participant teachers in this study maintained that as mediators between classrooms and senior management, teacher leaders not only communicate problems and concerns, but can also participate in problem solving within the school and in so doing,

they can facilitate school principals' role and ease the burden of school leadership on school principals. This is consistent with Muijs and Harris (2006) and Barth (2001) who maintained that teacher leadership extends school principals' capacity by devolving responsibility from them and reducing their workloads.

Interestingly, these findings, despite highlighting examples of teacher leadership practices beyond classrooms, point at a relatively narrow and restricted form of teacher leadership in relation with broader school-wide, cross-schools and community issues. For instance, although engaging with wider communities represents one of the core roles of teacher leaders beyond their classrooms and schools as a whole (Oracion, 2014; York-Barr and Duke, 2004), this aspect was highlighted by only one participant who stressed teacher leaders' role in engaging learners' parents and keeping them informed of their children's achievements and behaviour. Such relatively narrow perspective of teacher leadership might be the result of the top-down policies and guidelines set by the MoNE, which seem to restrict teachers' roles to their classrooms and to a noticeably lesser extent to their immediate school context (as discussed in section 2.4.3).

Another key finding relates to the perception of teachers' participation in decision-making as an essential aspect of teacher leadership. Participants in this study perceived decision-making at the classroom, school, and broader system level as being at the core of teacher leaders' work. For them, participation in taking decisions that particularly relate to their teaching and their students' learning both at the school level and more broadly at the system level is particularly crucial as among the different educational stakeholders, teachers are better positioned to inform such decisions given their proximity to the classroom contexts and intimate knowledge of learners' needs and potentials. These findings echo findings from Emira (2010), which indicated that Egyptian teachers of English perceived decision-making as tightly related to teacher leadership. Findings of this study, accordingly, stressed that through participation in decision making, teacher leaders have a great potential to contribute to informing educational reforms and designing more relevant and effective curricula and textbooks, an area of teacher leaders' influence that has been recurrent in most empirical research in both Arab and non-Arab contexts (Katzenmeyer and Moller, 2001; Lai and Cheung, 2015). It is worth noting that while teachers in the present study stressed the importance of teachers' participation in decision-making processes and their potential to contribute to educational reforms through being actively involved in decision-making, this does not necessarily reflect reality within their context as teachers in this study had limited voices in relation with reforms and policy within their work context. This was stressed by most of them as a hindrance to teacher leadership enactment in the Algerian context as will be subsequently discussed in section 6.5.

The views shared by teachers in this study equally demonstrated their remarkable tendency to define teacher leadership with reference to the personal traits that characterise teacher leaders. Previous research outlined a list of teacher leaders' traits including, among others: competence, motivation, confidence, life-long learning, and collaboration (van der Heijden and colleagues, 2016; Oppi, Eisenschmidt and Stingu, 2023; Oracion, 2014). Teacher leaders' qualities as perceived by participant teachers confirm and expand findings of these studies. Within the present research, a profile of teacher leaders was developed based on participants' accounts, maintaining that teacher leaders are perceived by participants as competent and confident teachers who engage in life-long learning; are both motivated and motivating; and who value collaboration with their peers. Teachers' competence in this study came on top of these traits, almost unanimously stressed by all participant teachers. Findings revealed that for teachers in this study, teacher leaders are competent and effective classroom teachers, who possess extended subject and pedagogical knowledge. These findings indicate that teachers' competence is a fundamental requirement for teacher leadership work and that teacher leaders are teachers with highly effective and comprehensive knowledge and understanding of subject matter and teaching-related issues. It was interesting to note from the findings, however, that although effectiveness as a classroom teacher represented a prerequisite and an essential trait of teacher leaders, gaining them respect and recognition from their peers, it was equally important for teachers in this study that those effective classroom teachers collaborate with their peers beyond their classrooms. For them, while teachers' effectiveness within their classrooms gains them respect and recognition, it is through collaborative work that those competent teachers could influence their peers. These findings resonate to a great extent with the three qualities of teacher leaders highlighted by Katzenmeyer and Moller (2011); competence, credibility, and approachability. The latter of which is consistent with participant teachers' emphasis on teacher leaders possessing a collaborative spirit.

Apart from their competence and effectiveness as classroom teachers, teachers' self-confidence was equally highlighted by some participants in this study as a quality that earns them respect and recognition both among their learners and among their peers. Additionally, teachers in this study perceived teacher leaders are both motivated and motivating. That is, they possess intrinsic motivation to give their best within and beyond their classrooms with the ultimate aim of improving the teaching and learning process, and they equally represent an important source of motivation for both their learners and their peers, which resonates well with Tomal et al. (2014). Notably, teacher leaders in this study were also perceived as independent, life-long learners who are driven by a sense of intellectual curiosity that in turn encourages them to continuously reflect on their own practices and experiences as well as those of their peers. As one participant commented, life-long learning is what

enables teacher leaders to ‘reach terrains in their classrooms that they would not be able to reach otherwise’.

Interestingly, although seniority or length of teaching experience is the primary criteria for the promotion of teachers to positional teacher leadership roles in the Algerian public-school context as discussed in section 2.4.3.1, being an experienced teacher was highlighted by only one participant as an essential trait of teacher leaders. Most participants in this study did not relate teacher leadership to teachers’ length of teaching experience, but rather stressed that the influence that teacher leaders could exert is independent of their years of experience as for them, even novice teachers can be teacher leaders. As noted in chapter three (section 3.4.1), research findings in relation to differences in perceptions and enactment of teacher leadership in relation to teachers’ demographic characteristics, including their length of experience, remain inconsistent. While, for instance, findings of this study are to some extent consistent with Van der Heijden and colleagues (2015) who concluded that teachers could function as agents of change regardless of their age or years of experience, they seem somewhat contrary to Lukacs (2012) who found that both age and years of experience matter.

As all participants perceived teacher leadership with a particular reference to its non-positional nature, it was deemed important to get insights into their awareness of the available positional teacher leadership roles within their context. Findings indicated that participant teachers possessed some level of awareness, though simplistic and incomplete, of available positional teacher leadership roles within their context. In this regard, positional teacher leadership was linked to the selection and promotion process that Algerian middle school teachers have to undergo, which aligns with the definition of positional teacher leadership proposed by Frost (2012). As per the exact promotion procedures, differences were noted between promoted and non-promoted teachers in this study. Findings indicated that positional teacher leaders (teacher mentors and principal teachers) were more knowledgeable of the promotion procedures compared to their non-promoted peers. Nonetheless, findings of this study indicated that both promoted and non-promoted teachers possessed limited awareness of the additional responsibilities that teacher leaders are supposed to assume as part of those positional teacher leadership roles. This may raise questions on issues related to role clarity and positional teacher leaders’ preparation for these roles in the study context. That is, teachers’ limited awareness of additional responsibilities of teacher leaders might be attributed either to the lack of clear definitions of these positional roles and relevant additional responsibilities or to the lack of teachers’ preparation and training programmes for these roles in the study context. Alternatively, this might suggest a gap between policy discourse and policy implementation regarding promoted teachers’ roles. That is, while the publicly available policy documents clearly outline various roles of principal teachers and

teacher mentors, including mentoring novice teachers, in reality it seems that their roles, as suggested by findings of the present study, are largely restricted to the mentoring role.

Given the preceding discussion in relation to participant teachers' perceptions of teacher leadership, it was evident that those teachers possess some understanding of what constitutes teacher leadership, which seems to be particularly aligned with emerging trends of non-positional teacher leadership. This is particularly interesting given that the term itself is not commonly used within their context and that they have not previously received any teacher leadership input as part of their pre-service preparation or in-service training (as discussed in section 2.4.3). As noted earlier, their perceptions of teacher leadership support its multi-dimensionality with a clear reference to non-positional teacher leadership. For the research participants, teacher leadership practices can take place both within and beyond the classroom. Nevertheless, forms of teacher leadership enactment beyond the classroom seem to be restricted to some extent in the study context. Thus, findings of this study revealed some degree of discrepancy between teachers' conceptualisations of teacher leadership practice and the reality of teacher leadership enactment within their work context. While participant teachers, for instance, stressed participating in decision-making and contributing to reforms and policy-making as essential aspects of teacher leadership, these perceptions as noted earlier in this section and as shall be further discussed in section 6.5 do not necessarily reflect the reality as teachers' participation in decision-making processes and their contribution to shaping educational reforms are currently beyond the scope of teachers' roles in Algeria and are restricted to those at the apex of the hierarchical structure of the educational system in the country. This gap was further noted in teachers' reported practices of teacher leadership as discussed in the following section.

6.4. What are middle school EFL teachers' reported practices of and experiences with teacher leadership?

This research question was addressed in sections 5.3.1 and 5.3.2 of the previous chapter. It was interesting that participant teachers reported various teacher leadership practices given the centralised nature of the educational system in Algeria (Gherzouli, 2019; Messekher and Miliani, 2017) that is mostly not conducive to effective teacher leadership enactment. Although findings of this study indicate that participant teachers possessed some understanding of what constitutes teacher leadership, their reported practices as described in their written reflections indicated that most of them still hesitate to openly refer to their practices as teacher leadership practices. These findings resonate with Idelcadi, Rguibi and Bouziane (2023) who similarly found that Moroccan EFL teachers still hesitate to acknowledge their leadership. Helterbran (2010, p. 363) provided a possible explanation for such hesitation among teachers by relating such attitudes to what he referred to as 'I am just a teacher syndrome'. The author explains that teachers might have no problem envisioning themselves

as teacher leaders; however, they often ‘tend to have great difficulty identifying themselves as leaders within their schools’ (p. 366). This explanation seems to be relevant to most teachers in the present study.

Despite such hesitation, almost all teachers in this study described their leadership practices, stressing that it was through these practices that they gained recognition and praise within their schools, and exerted influence on both their learners’ and their peers. All of their reported practices of teacher leadership were self-initiated and not delegated, confirming Fairman and Mackenzie’s (2012) argument that teacher leadership is mostly initiated by teachers themselves. Interestingly, participant teachers’ reported practices of teacher leadership were largely consistent with their perceptions of the construct in the sense that they reported practices that took place both within and beyond their classroom contexts, and that were essentially non-positional in nature, with only one exception of a participant who reflected on her positional teacher leadership role as a teacher mentor. Even in this case, the teacher mentor did not merely refer to her role in supervising novice teachers, but to the innovative approach that she undertook on her own initiative to inspire and motivate her trainees.

The fact that most participants reported teacher leadership practices within their classrooms further confirms the view that the classroom represents the foundation and the primary space from which teacher leadership emerges for those teachers, as discussed in section 6.2. Previous studies by Greenier and Whitehead (2016), Nguyen, Huynh and Tran (2022) and Achach-Sonda and Cisneros-Cohernour (2023) outlined the different practices that teacher leaders engage in within their classrooms including: creating and maintaining a suitable learning environment; designing and implementing innovative and attractive teaching strategies; adopting differentiated instructional approaches; and providing personalised assistance for learners. Teachers’ reported practices of teacher leadership in this study are largely consistent with aspects highlighted in these studies. Teachers in this study enacted teacher leadership within classrooms essentially through designing and implementing innovative and differentiated instructional practices and adopting innovative classroom management strategies to establish a suitable learning environment for their learners and to attend to their needs and learning preferences. Another manifestation of teacher leadership inside the classroom was demonstrated in the personalised academic and emotional support provided for one learner by her teacher, in collaboration with other fellow teachers, the school psychologist and the learners’ parent. These findings indicate that as teacher leaders care deeply for their learners’ learning and wellbeing, they attentively notice any problems that their learners, individually or collectively, face and take initiative to search for effective solutions for these problems or to provide specific learners with personalised assistance. Teachers in this sense invested more effort, devoted more time, and demonstrated a sense of responsibility to produce meaningful learning experiences and to establish a supportive and inclusive learning

environment for their learners to succeed and achieve planned learning objectives.

Similar findings were reported by Baecher (2012, p 323) who explained that for the case of some teachers in his study, an ‘informal’ pathway to teacher leadership was ‘initiated by teachers themselves to address a perceived void in meeting students’ needs in which case teachers identified a need based on their own observations and voluntarily addressed it. Such self-initiated practices, the author explains, gained teachers recognition from the school principal, and were then followed by a request to continue this work in a more formal manner with the provision of a title, creation of a specialised position in the school community and provision of remuneration. As for the case of the present study, although most of the teachers’ self-initiated practices gained them recognition, praise, and credibility primarily among their peers, and to a lesser extent among school principals, or subject inspectors, creation of positional teacher leadership roles and provision of a title or remuneration based on these initiatives within individual schools might not be possible. This is particularly because, as discussed in section 2.4.2, these processes are strictly regulated by the MoNE, and school principals have limited power to take such decisions at the school level.

Participant teachers equally practised teacher leadership beyond the boundaries of their classrooms in a variety of ways. One way was by assuming responsibility for one’s own professional learning and informally contributing to the professional learning of other teachers. Another participant teacher identified the professional support that she provided for her peers on her own initiative as a practice of teacher leadership. Engaging in independent life-long learning, providing professional support, and contributing to the professional learning of peers were similarly reported in previous research as essential aspects of teacher leadership (van Der Heijden et al., 2015; York-Barr and Duke, 2004). Two positional teacher leaders, in this study, reported practising leadership through empowering novice teachers, enhancing their self-esteem and increasing their confidence in their professional skills and potentials. Such empowerment was through assigning them responsibilities that could push them beyond their comfort zone, or through adopting innovative ways for teacher training that target developing both instructional capacity and a strong sense of self-esteem within novice teachers.

It was interesting to note from the findings of this research that even reported teacher leadership practices within classrooms had an extended impact beyond the classroom context. Relevant evidence from the literature suggests that an important aspect of teacher leaders’ work is enhancing instructional practices of their peers (Supovitz, 2018). This, in the context of this study, was achieved more or less indirectly. Teachers who reported teacher leadership practices within their classrooms as discussed above similarly reported that their practices had an impact on their peers. In this sense, those teachers modelled a professional stance and served as an exemplar of effective and

innovative instructional practices and classroom management skills for their colleagues, inspiring their peers and pushing them to advance their instructional practices.

What could be concluded from teachers' reported practices of teacher leadership is that Algerian middle schools, despite the top-down structure in which they operate, seem to allow for some kind of non-positional teacher leadership practices, to varying degrees. However, practices at a broader school-wide or community scale were missing. Reported practices in this study particularly related to designing and implementing innovative instruction to accommodate learners' needs and to the indirect influence that teachers exert on their peers regardless of their positional role through modelling effective and innovative practices and providing professional support. An important point to highlight here is that although participants in this study perceived teacher leadership as independent of teachers' positional role and that in terms of their reported practices only one participant reported her ability to influence teachers through her designated position, existing literature stresses the crucial role that both positional teacher leaders and school principals could play in brokering teacher leadership success. Within the context of this study, the scarcity or lack of such support, in addition to other school-based, system-based and sociocultural factors seem to result in a rather restricted form of teacher leadership enactment. All of these factors constitute the discussion of the following section.

6.5. What factors reportedly hinder/ foster Algerian middle school EFL teachers' practice of leadership?

This question was addressed in sections 5.4.1 to 5.4.4 of the preceding chapter. While various factors were identified in the findings, it was noted that teachers generally focussed more on existing hindrances while also referring to desired supports of teacher leadership, which may indicate that Algerian middle schools currently seem to be less conducive for successful teacher leadership enactment. Previous research suggests that factors that either support or hinder teacher leadership practice generally relate to teachers' characteristics and beliefs, school structures, school principals and fellow teachers (Frost and Harris, 2003; Muijs and Harris, 2006; 2007; Nguyen, Harris and Ng 2019; Wenner and Campbell, 2017; York-Barr and Duke, 2004). Findings of this research support and expand these results as discussed below.

6.5.1. (Un)supportive School Members

Participants in this study stressed that success or failure of teacher leadership practice largely depends on the extent of support that teacher leaders receive from other members within their school community, particularly from peers and school principals.

Findings indicated that teachers could motivate their peers and enhance their self-confidence and their willingness to be involved in teacher leadership work through maintaining positive relationships based on trust and respect, providing collegial support and exchanging knowledge and

innovative ideas. In a similar way, Margolis (2012) found that teachers feel more motivated and willing to take on leadership roles when they obtain collegial support from their peers. In the current study, although most teachers maintained that their relationships with their peers were generally positive and were particularly based on mutual respect and that they often receive praise and encouragement from their peers for the initiatives that they undertake, some participants equally highlighted instances in which promoted teachers could hinder novice teachers' potential to exercise leadership. This was particularly perceived by some participant novice teachers in terms of limiting their autonomy to innovate as well as their freedom to express their viewpoints regarding important instructional and students' issues. These findings suggest that positional teacher leaders, in particular, can play an essential role in brokering the success of teacher leadership work and particularly in supporting novice teachers and providing them with more opportunities and appropriate levels of autonomy to engage in teacher leadership practice. Woodhouse and Pedder (2017) similarly concluded that senior and middle leaders can play an important role in providing early-career teachers with both formal and informal opportunities to engage in leadership practices and allowing them flexibility and space to take the initiative and try out new ideas. The authors further argue that experienced teachers responsible for early-career teachers' induction and professional development, particularly teacher mentors and principal teachers in the case of this study, should balance between providing early-career teachers with appropriate levels of autonomy while at the same time being available to provide them with guidance, support, and reassurance.

An extensive body of empirical research equally suggests that school principals play a central role in supporting teacher leadership enactment by adopting a more distributed leadership style; recognising and valuing teachers' initiatives and contributions; and ensuring the availability of the required resources that facilitate teacher leaders' work (Cheng and Szeto, 2016; Szeto and Cheng, 2018). Findings of this study support these views as participant teachers stressed that enactment of teacher leadership is more likely to succeed when teachers receive sufficient support and encouragement from their school principals and when school principals provide teachers with more opportunities to initiate and lead change. These views often reflected desired supports whereas participants responses as per the status quo within their schools seemed to be somewhat mixed and inconsistent as participant teachers shared both positive and negative views regarding their current or former school principals. While notably few participants described their current school principals as supportive principals, who value their initiatives and provide them with some margins of freedom, many others stressed that encouragement and recognition from school principals was minimal, and that teachers' contributions and initiatives often go unnoticed. Moreover, many participants maintained that school principals often adopt an authoritarian rather than a shared or distributed

approach to school leadership as they seem unwilling to relinquish control and tend to impose their own viewpoints in even matters related to classroom practices with little consideration given to teachers' viewpoints. Such an approach was perceived by most participant teachers to limit their professional autonomy; prevent them from practising their agency; and harm professional relationships and interactions within the school and to ultimately minimise their participation in leadership work within their schools.

Professional autonomy, particularly in relation with classroom practices including teaching methods, classroom management and students' assessment was highlighted by teachers in this study as an essential aspect of teacher leadership enactment. Participant teachers emphasised that school principals should provide them with appropriate levels of autonomy in these specific areas if they were to be effective as teacher leaders. These views are consistent with Wenner and Campbell (2017) who stress that in order to support teacher leadership within schools, school principals should provide teachers with appropriate levels of autonomy. The importance of teacher autonomy for teacher leadership practice was further stressed in a quantitative study conducted by Kara and Bozkurt (2022), investigating the relationship between teacher leadership and other variables including teacher autonomy. Those researchers found that autonomy was one of the factors explaining teacher leadership in the sense that teacher leadership behaviours tend to increase with the increase in teachers' professional autonomy. Teacher autonomy for Kara and Bozkurt's (2022) participants, as in the case of participants in this research, related particularly to teachers' practices within their classroom in relation with teaching methods and practices, classroom management and students' assessment.

One issue that is worth considering at this point is the challenge that Algerian school principals themselves might face when adopting a distributed leadership approach. In this sense, Harris (2013) and Torrance (2013) maintained that implementing a distributed leadership style might be challenging for principals who have to balance between their own control and staff autonomy. This might be even more challenging for principals within the Algerian context who are themselves held accountable for ensuring completion of the mandated programme within their institutions in due course, having to report to school inspectors and to the regional directorates of education. This might have put those school principals under pressure, resulting in their tendency to prioritise the end product (completion of the programme in due course) over the process (allowing teachers' more margins of freedom and professional autonomy to innovate and collaborate) and adopting a rather authoritarian approach to ensure completion of the programme. Similarly, the top-down school regulations implemented by the MoNE, as discussed in section 2.4.2, explicitly state that all staff within public educational institutions, including teachers, are subject to school principals' authority and that school principals are at the apex

of the pyramidal management structure within their schools. These guidelines are likely to be interpreted in a way that would result in some principals' adoption of an authoritarian rather than distributed approach to leadership.

6.5.2. Working conditions as a Hindrance to Teacher Leadership

Findings of this study highlighted structural deficiencies within Algerian public middle schools as an essential barrier to teacher leadership enactment. With regard to this issue, evidence from previous research stressed the importance of allocating time and space for teachers; ensuring the availability of necessary resources; and rewarding teachers for their initiatives as important supports of teacher leadership practice (Galland, 2008; Oppi, Eisenschmidt and Stingu, 2023). In the present study, participants similarly stressed the importance of providing teachers with the necessary teaching materials and resources as that would support their innovative instructional practices and their ability to accommodate students' learning needs and preferences. These aspects, as discussed earlier in this chapter, were perceived and reported by most participants as an essential aspects of teacher leadership. Teachers in this study unanimously stressed the scarcity of such resources and materials in Algerian middle schools. Apart from the scarcity of resources and materials within these schools, findings revealed that shortage of time coupled with work overload represented another major hindrance that could limit teachers' active participation in leadership work. Overwhelming timetables in Algerian middle schools may, thus, tire teachers and decrease their willingness to take part in further activities that go beyond their classrooms or teaching schedules. Margolis (2012) and Al-Teneiji and Ibrahim (2017) similarly concluded that shortage of time was an important deterring factor that prevented teachers in his study from collaborating with their peers as part of teacher leadership work. Likewise, and in line with much of the existing literature (e.g., Harris, 2003; Gigante and Firestone, 2008), recognising and rewarding teachers' initiatives and efforts have a significant impact on teacher leaders' effectiveness. Findings of this study indicate that while teachers might receive recognition and praise from their peers, they desire to receive more recognition from their school principals too. Beyond verbal recognition, some participants stressed that rewards in the form of remuneration are likely to encourage Algerian middle school teachers to engage in leadership work. Within the Algerian context, although teachers promoted to positions of a principal teacher or a teacher mentor receive remuneration for the additional responsibilities that come with these roles, currently there seems to be no certification or pay-scales that promote non-positional teacher leadership practice or acknowledge, and reward initiatives undertaken by non-positional teacher leaders.

6.5.3. System-based Factors

Policymakers and officials at the level of the MoNE were also perceived as crucial for either supporting or hindering teacher leadership enactment in the Algerian middle school context. The

current situation indicates teachers' limited participation in decision-making processes both at the school level and broadly beyond the school context as some participants perceived themselves as 'slaves' who are 'chained' by and must abide to the top-down decisions imposed on them by school principals, school inspectors and other officials at the level of the MoNE, with little consideration to teachers' views regarding those decisions. While findings of this study indicate a relatively greater opportunity for some participant teachers to practise decision-making within their classrooms, specifically in terms of teaching methods, classroom management and students' assessment, opportunities for participation in decision-making processes beyond their classrooms were remarkably minimal. In fact, as discussed in section 6.5.1, some teachers even reported not having an appropriate level of autonomy to take decisions that relate to their classroom-based practices mainly in terms of their teaching methods, classroom management or students' assessment, as their authoritarian school principals or their promoted peers tend to impose their own viewpoints in relation to these matters. Findings similarly suggested that teachers are excluded from broader decision-making processes, and are merely regarded as decision implementors. Interestingly, although different councils are established across all public schools in Algeria following the MoNE's guidelines with the aim of providing different stakeholders, including teachers, with opportunities to share their views regarding important school matters, none of the participants referred to these councils as a space to participate in decision-making.

In accordance with these findings, previous empirical research in other Arab countries have reported similar results. In the Moroccan context, for instance, findings from Idelcadi, Rguibi and Bouziane (2023) indicated that Moroccan teachers of English reported having limited opportunities to engage in decision making both within their schools and at the national level. Similar to the situation in Algerian public schools, councils are established in Moroccan schools following ministerial guidelines to provide teachers with some space to engage in decision-making processes at the school level. The authors, however, noted that even within these councils, Moroccan teachers' role in decision-making processes remains notably limited. This might well be the case for teachers in the Algerian context, where teachers' participation in these councils might be tangential and does not imply decision-making power in courses of action for the school. This is evidently one of the core features of centralised educational systems as in the case of the Algerian system (as discussed in section 2.4.2). Such centralised structures enforce top-down decision-making processes in which decision-making is confined to individuals at the apex (the MoNE in the case of this study), while teachers' role is restricted to mere implementation of these policies and reforms. Findings of this study reinforce Gherzouli's (2019) findings from a study of Algerian secondary school EFL teachers' perceptions of curriculum development, as she stressed the 'imbalanced power relation between the

government and teachers with the former controlling and dictating curriculum and excluding teachers from the whole developmental process' (p. 01).

Clearly, participant teachers desire more opportunities to participate in decision-making at some level, particularly in terms of decisions that have a direct impact on their learners and classroom practices. Participant teachers, in this sense, stressed that the Algerian MoNE can support teacher leadership and empower teachers by providing them with more opportunities to be involved in decision-making processes both within and beyond their schools as they have first-hand exposure to problems in classrooms and they are better positioned to know how their learners' needs and preferences can be accommodated. This aligns with Emira (2010) who reported that Egyptian teachers of English language demonstrated a strong willingness to participate in decision-making within their schools, regardless of their teaching experience or position.

Apart from teachers' marginalisation from decision-making processes, some participant teachers stressed the inadequacy and scarcity of relevant teacher training programmes as another factor hindering their development as teacher leaders. Almost two decades ago, and particularly in the context of the USA, Dozier (2007), Katzenmeyer and Moller (2001) and Murphy (2005) cautioned that teachers are often expected to assume teacher leadership roles without receiving any relevant training or preparation. While this might not be currently the case in contexts like the USA, UK, Canada, Australia, or Hong Kong where professional training programmes for teacher leaders at both pre-service and in-service levels are receiving more attention, findings of this study suggest that the issue of lack of relevant training still persists in Algeria.

Many participants in this study expressed their dissatisfaction with the current professional training programmes. Findings suggest that these programmes are merely theoretical; are centred on pedagogical and subject-related aspects that teachers were already exposed to as part of their pre-service teacher education programmes; and are exclusively provided for teachers at the early stages of their careers. Participants, accordingly, accentuated that Algerian middle school EFL teachers could greatly benefit from more updated, relevant and continuous professional training that would be accessible for teachers at all stages of their careers rather than being exclusive for early-career teachers. Professional training programmes, as suggested by one participant, should be designed and planned to go beyond training in subject matter or pedagogy and to include input related to educational leadership and more specifically to teacher leadership. This would increase teachers' awareness of both positional and non-positional teacher leadership roles and practices and enhance their confidence to engage in teacher leadership work. The views shared by participant teachers in relation to the above issues are unsurprising. Given the discussion in section 2.4.3, pre-service and in-service EFL teachers in Algeria receive no input related to teacher leadership and are under-prepared in this field. Similarly,

previous research conducted in the Algerian context with a focus on EFL teachers equally stressed their frustration with the limited in-service and continuous professional development opportunities in their context (Abdat, 2023). These findings are largely consistent with Alsalahi (2016) who found that Saudi English language teachers similarly stressed the inadequacy of teachers' pre-service and in-service training programs and reported that they received no teacher leadership training.

6.5.4. Teachers' Traits

Certain teacher traits have also been recognised in this study as having a noticeable impact on teacher leadership practice. Apart from the personal traits that defined teacher leaders, from the participants' perspective, teachers' willingness, desire, and readiness to initiate and drive change within their schools was perceived in this study as an essential enabler for teacher leadership. Teachers who are willing to drive change must also maintain consistency in their efforts and are ready to take risks and assume responsibility for their actions. Brosky (2011) similarly stressed the importance of teachers' willingness to initiate and drive change, explaining that teacher leaders are likely to face difficulties fulfilling their roles when they are not willing to challenge traditional hierarchical structures within their work environment.

On a positive note, all teachers in this study demonstrated willingness and desire to engage in leadership work, particularly in practices that are directly related to enhancing students' learning and improving circumstances for the teaching and learning process in the country. Many participant teachers provided examples of initiatives that they desire to implement within their schools. The lack of support, however, prevented them from putting their ideas into practice. The examples that those teachers provided evidenced their willingness and desire to initiate and lead change within their schools. It seems that the willingness, desire, and intrinsic motivation that those teachers possess is what enabled them to challenge the various constraints and to navigate ways to initiate change and exercise teacher leadership at some level within their schools as suggested in the examples in sections 5.2 and 5.3 of the preceding chapter.

6.5.5. Algerian Sociocultural Norms and Teacher Leadership Enactment

Somewhat less evident in previous research, the impact of the sociocultural context emerged as an important factor that could limit teacher leadership enactment within Algerian middle schools. Findings of this study stress that teacher leadership should not be perceived independently from the broader sociocultural context within which it is to be practised. More specifically, findings confirm and elaborate on Boyce and Bowers' (2018) view that teacher leadership must always be thought of as a culturally sensitive concept by providing evidence of two ways in which norms within the broader Algerian sociocultural context may have an impact on teacher leadership enactment.

First, influenced by traditions within their sociocultural context, some male school principals within Algerian middle schools may develop a patriarchal mentality that leads them to underestimate female teachers' efforts, ignore their viewpoints or ability to influence and marginalise them. Similarly, in fear of judgement from their surrounding context, Algerian female teachers who face such a situation, as suggested by one participant in this study, would prefer not to stand up for their rights if this could result in conflicting or problematic relationships with male principals. Although this may not be the case for all male school principals in Algeria, it is deemed important to attend to such variables when considering a model for successful and equal teacher leadership enactment within the Algerian context as these findings point at certain scenarios in which female teachers might feel less empowered and encouraged to engage in leadership work compared to their male counterparts.

The existing literature provides little evidence as to the relationship between gender and teacher leadership enactment both in Western and Arab contexts (Nguyen et al., 2020). Some quantitative studies that examined the relationship between teacher leadership perceptions and different demographic characteristics of teachers, including gender, yielded mixed results and given the quantitative design of the research, these studies did not provide deep insights as to how teacher leadership practice could be dependent on teachers' gender. Findings from a quantitative study by Hammad et al. (2023), for instance, highlighted teachers' gender as a significant variable affecting teachers' perceptions of teacher leadership practice in the contexts of Oman, Qatar and Egypt. The authors reported that although female teachers seemed to be more willing to share expertise and knowledge with peers, male teachers in their study were more willing to perform extra tasks and duties than female teachers. This, according to the authors, might be attributed to the fact that within Arab societies, there are strong societal and cultural expectations for women to prioritise their roles as caregivers and mothers over extra work duties (James-Hawkins, Qutteina and Yount, 2017). While stressing the need for further investigations on the relationship between gender and teacher leadership, Hammad et al. (2023) point to the importance of carefully considering the social, cultural and political contexts in which such research is being conducted.

Second, by virtue of the Algerian sociocultural norms and traditions, teachers may often tend to distance themselves from peers from the other gender. It was clearly noted in the present study that the broader sociocultural context affected the mutual engagement and professional interactions between male and female teachers. Viewing the school as 'a small society' or 'a small community', teachers necessarily adhere to the broader sociocultural norms that imply limited interactions between individuals from different genders. This is likely to limit collaboration, which was perceived by most participants in this study as an essential aspect of teacher leadership practice beyond classrooms as well as an important means for teachers to grow professionally as teacher leaders. Participant female

teachers stressed that they feel more comfortable interacting and collaborating with other female teachers while they tend to distance themselves from their male peers. This was reported by some participants to be mainly influenced by female teachers' marital status.

Teacher leadership research highlighting the impact of the broader sociocultural context as in the current study seems to be remarkably limited in the existing literature. One of the few studies that stressed the impact of the broader contextual variables, though from a different lens, is Van der Vyver, Fuller and Khumalo's (2020) study that evidenced the impact of the broader South African context on conceptualisation and manifestation of leadership and teacher leadership. Findings of their study revealed that as a result of the socioeconomic, political and historical context of South Africa, almost half of the analysed official documents directed for teachers and educational institutions focussed on issues of equality, democracy, non-discrimination and the protection of human rights for everyone. In Pakistan, Ali (2014) stressed the need to problematise teacher leadership within the Pakistani context in which becoming a leader in schools or broadly in society might be highly dependent on individuals' race, gender, kinship and so forth rather than their qualifications.

Viewing teacher leadership as a context-specific phenomenon implies that teacher leaders' roles could be perceived and more importantly manifested differently in different contexts, and that teachers' access to leadership roles is likely to be influenced by various social, cultural or political factors. Due to sociocultural dissimilarities, thus, the Western understandings of teacher leadership that tend to dominate the literature in this field may not currently be fully applicable to the Algerian context or to other contexts similar to it. Other perceptions of teacher leadership should instead be more sensitive to certain sociocultural norms that characterise certain societies and differentiate them from others.

The above discussion, thus, reveals that although participant teachers have a positive outlook on teacher leadership and its merits and aspire to engage in more leadership activities within their context, certain school-based, system-based as well as sociocultural barriers seem to restrict their participation in leadership. Interestingly, however, despite all the afore-mentioned constraints, teacher leadership still occurred at some level based on teachers' initiative as evidenced by teachers' examples in sections 5.2 and 5.3 of the preceding chapter. Teachers in this study utterly expressed their willingness and desire to be engaged in more leadership work. These findings suggest that given the necessary support and margins of freedom, Algerian middle school EFL teachers are likely to engage in more leadership practices within and beyond their school contexts to initiate and lead change and to contribute to improved instructional practices and student learning as well as to overall school improvements. One possible way to enhance such potential for teachers' engagement in leadership work within and beyond their school, as stressed by participants in this study, was teachers'

collaboration with their peers. The following section discusses the perceived role of teachers' collaboration in enhancing their professional learning and growth as teacher leaders in more details.

6.6. How do Algerian middle school EFL teachers view collaboration with each other as contributing to their professional learning and growth as teacher leaders?

This question was addressed in sections 5.5.1 to 5.5.3 of the research findings chapter. A bulk of relevant research, particularly from Western contexts such as the USA, UK, Australia and Canada, stresses the importance of teachers' leadership preparation and training programmes both at pre-service and in-service levels (Acquaro and Gurr, 2022b; Campbell et al., 2018; King, McMahon, Nguyen and Roulston, 2019; Webber, 2021a; Webber and Nickel, 2021). Given the lack of such preparation and training programmes in Algeria as discussed in section 2.4.3 and as suggested by participants in this study, this study examined teachers' perceptions of the role of more job-embedded professional learning opportunities, particularly in the form of informal collaboration with peers, in enhancing their professional learning and growth as teacher leaders. Findings in this regard highlight the importance of teacher collaboration for both teachers' professional growth and their wellbeing. In this sense, teachers' communities both at the school level and beyond were perceived as learning communities within which teachers could develop certain qualities and professional skills which participants deemed as essential for teacher leaders' work as they engaged in professional interactions, discussions and collaborative practices and established positive relationships with peers. As discussed in section 6.2, engaging in informal collaborative practices within teachers' communities provided participant teachers with a space in which they did things together and considered alternative ways to refine their own practices. Such emphasis on the crucial role of teachers' collaboration resonates with the views shared by many authors (e.g., Geijsel et al., 2009; Thoonen et al., 2011) that collaboration is key to promoting teachers' professional learning and initiating educational change at the classroom and school level.

It was, however, noted that while in most cases, collegial support and positive relationships were the norm, examples of conflicting relationships and lack of collegial support were also highlighted. Findings of this study revealed that power dynamics within schools as well as certain aspects of the Algerian sociocultural context were likely to hinder teachers' collaboration and minimise their sense of belonging to their school community as well as their engagement in teacher leadership work. As discussed in detail in sections 6.5.1. and 6.5.5 of this chapter, power dynamics in the form of control exerted by school principals and promoted teachers together with the boundaries set by the Algerian sociocultural context seemed to minimise some teachers' sense of belonging to their school community as well as their engagement in teacher leadership work within their schools, leading them to work independently and to isolate themselves from their peers, which contradicts the

collaborative nature of teacher leadership practice. In an attempt to maintain their sense of belonging to the profession, those teachers try to establish professional connections beyond their immediate school context. As detailed in the preceding chapter, these connections were particularly established within virtual communities like Facebook groups of Algerian middle school teachers. Such broader communities represented an alternative space for teachers to seek and provide professional support; to practise their autonomy and agency; and to freely express their viewpoints regardless of the length of their teaching experience or positions. Interestingly, these virtual communities were also viewed by some participant teachers as a more comfortable space for interaction between male and female teachers.

It is important, however, to point out that despite the perceived value of such virtual communities as stressed by teachers in this study, they are not without downsides. One issue to consider in relation with virtual communities as a space of professional learning, for instance, is that of teachers' mutual engagement given the possibility that some teachers may become passive members who learn from the community but do not contribute to it. Bedford (2019), for instance, found that some participants in his research felt that their learning within virtual communities notably exceeded their contributions. Although continuous learning is well established both in the current study and in relevant teacher leadership literature as an essential aspect of teacher leadership, it is equally important that teachers actively participate within such communities to have their voices heard and to contribute to improved instructional practices. Another issue worth noting relates to teachers' potential to transfer their learning that occurs within these virtual communities to their actual working environments. While participant teachers in this study perceived these communities as a space where they could freely express their viewpoints, share knowledge, and provide and receive the necessary professional support, it may be more challenging to transfer their learning from these spaces to influence instruction within their actual work setting. This is particularly relevant for some participants in this study as it was the unsupportive school environment that limited their freedom to express their viewpoints and their professional autonomy as well as their potential to contribute to improvements in instructional practices that led them to join these virtual communities in the first place. A supportive school culture is thus necessary for those teachers to successfully transfer their learning from broader virtual communities to their actual school setting and to ultimately influence instruction there.

Overall, engaging and collaborating with other teachers' communities at the school level and beyond was reported in this study to enable both novice and experienced teachers to learn from each other and to grow professionally. Participant teachers, both promoted and non-promoted, stressed that through informal collaborative practices, experienced and novice teachers can mutually support and

learn from each other. In this sense, novice teachers can benefit from the experience of promoted teachers in terms of pedagogical knowledge and classroom management while they could in turn support experienced teachers with matters related to digital literacy and pedagogical innovation and creativity. These findings are largely consistent with findings from Geeraerts et al. (2018) in the Netherlands context, which stressed that learning among novice and experienced teachers was notably reciprocal, taking the form of informal discussions in the context of teachers' daily practice. The authors reported that, as in the case of the present study, beginning teachers influenced their more experienced peers in areas related to the use of technology and innovative teaching practices, while at the same time older teachers were a source from which younger teachers developed knowledge and skills related to classroom management, community-building and self-regulation. These findings equally support Lieberman and Friedrich (2007) who point out that participation in collaborative practices provides teachers with an opportunity to practise small-scale leadership in addition to recognising peers' areas of expertise, establishing trust, and collectively engaging in solving problems and completing tasks. Indeed, teachers in the present study could be seen to practise 'small-scale' leadership through the opportunities that the informal collaborative practices provided for them to work towards common goals, to support their peers and engage in collaborative problem-solving and joint lesson planning and to influence peers' instructional practices and classroom management strategies. Notably, for most participant teachers, collaboration with peers was in itself perceived as an essential aspect of teacher leadership enactment beyond the classroom context as discussed in section 6.3.

For all participants, professional learning as teacher leaders through informal collaboration was particularly perceived in terms of developing skills, competencies and traits that were, for them, required for teacher leaders' work. Such professional growth was the result of sharing experiences, and providing feedback, encouragement, and professional support. Similarly, findings from Fairman and Mackenzie's (2015) study in the USA context indicate that teacher leaders perceived informal collaboration and professional relationships based on trust and collegiality as essential for supporting teacher leadership development as well as school improvement. Collinson (2012) described the progression from a teacher to a teacher leader as 'a continuously evolving process of learning and refining ideals' (p. 264), in which the initial stage involves developing deep pedagogical and content knowledge. Teachers, accordingly, initially seek improvements in their own teaching practice then gradually progress to contribute to and influence their schools, districts, and the teaching profession (Collinson, 2012; Nicolaidou, 2010). In the present study, informal collaboration with peers was primarily perceived by all participant teachers as an impetus for improved teaching skills and practices, which they, in turn, stressed as a prerequisite for teacher leadership practice. Both promoted

and non-promoted teachers in this study stressed that as teachers regularly and actively engage in informal collaborative practices within teachers' communities, they constantly learn new teaching and classroom management strategies and ideas, which they use to refine their own practices and become more competent and effective teachers.

Herterbran (2010), who described non-positional teacher leadership as emergent and self-initiated, stressed that 'This emergence cannot and will not occur unless and until teachers recognize their own leadership potential and develop the confidence and skills to be effective teacher leaders' (p. 365). Muijs and Harris (2003) similarly maintained that one of the most important aspects of teacher leadership capacity building is boosting teachers' self-confidence to assume leadership responsibilities within their schools. Within the present study, collaboration within a positive and supportive school culture was perceived to enhance teachers' self-confidence, a trait that participants in this research associated with teacher leaders. As teachers work collaboratively with their peers, establish positive professional relationships and exchange innovative ideas and resources, their confidence in their potentials and their teaching capacities enhances. Similarly, teachers in this study felt more confident and empowered to share and stand for their viewpoints within such collaborative and supportive cultures. Such enhanced sense of confidence is likely to support teachers to take the lead and to initiate changes within their schools.

Apart from advancing teachers' competence and effectiveness and enhancing their sense of confidence and empowerment, collaboration with other teachers within the school community and beyond was perceived by participant teachers as a means through which teachers could develop certain professional skills, which they believed were crucial to teacher leaders' work. These involved decision-making, problem-solving, critical and reflective thinking as well as collaborative and communicative skills, all of which were equally stressed within relevant teacher leadership research as important for teacher leadership practice (Alsalahi, 2016; Danielson, 2006; 2007; Tomal et al., 2014). Snell and Swanson (2000) maintained that teachers are likely to emerge as leaders if they develop high-level skills in areas of expertise, reflection on their practices, collaboration and empowerment of themselves and others. Findings of this study, as explained in detail in chapter 5, indicated that teachers' informal collaboration with peers both within and beyond their schools reportedly lead to developments in these specific areas.

Although findings of the present study support the perceived effectiveness of engaging in collaborative practices within teachers' communities for enhancing teachers' professional growth as teacher leaders, it is important to caution that progression from a teacher to a teacher leader is not a one-shot phenomenon. Such progression is a rather recursive and gradual process that likely requires a longer time scale (Poekert, Alexandrou and Shannon, 2016). This would, therefore, require such

informal collaborative practices to be more sustained to provide teachers with more opportunities to practise leadership and to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills to grow professionally as teacher leaders. Teachers would, however, necessarily need further support in the form of formal professional preparation and training programmes, as well as a supportive working environment in which they can engage in ‘small-scale’ teacher leadership practices to gradually grow as teacher leaders.

6.7. Chapter Summary

This chapter provided a discussion of the research findings in light of the study’s underpinning conceptual framework and in relation with the existing literature on teacher leadership and features of the Algerian educational context. Overall, teachers’ perceptions of teacher leadership were largely consistent with existing conceptualisations of teacher leadership as per its multi-faceted nature; the view of teacher leadership as influence, particularly through collaboration, professional support and role modelling; and the view of teacher leaders’ work as involving activities both within and beyond the classroom. Consistent with their perceptions, participants’ reported practices of teacher leadership were essentially non-positional in nature and covered different aspects both within and beyond the classroom context. Some discrepancies were, however, noted between participant teachers’ perceptions of teacher leadership and the realities of teacher leadership enactment in the research context. This gap was particularly noted in terms of teacher leadership practices and teacher leaders’ influence beyond the classroom and school context. The environment within which those teachers work seemed to be less conducive to successful teacher leadership enactment. Although teachers’ relationships with their colleagues were mostly positive, thus creating a more or less supportive school culture, scarcity of resources, time constraints and workloads, lack of incentives, school principals’ authoritarian leadership styles, centralised decision-making processes, lack of relevant teacher training as well as the impact of the broader Algerian sociocultural context represented essential hindrances to effective teacher leadership enactment within the Algerian middle school context. The impact of the broader sociocultural context was particularly accentuated, as it is likely to result in less empowerment and support for female teachers to engage in leadership practices and to limit professional interactions and collaborative practices within the school context. Not only is collaboration stressed by both the research participants and relevant research as an essential aspect of teacher leadership work, but it is also reported in this study to have a great potential in fostering teachers’ professional growth as teacher leaders within a community of practice. The results of this research have a significant contribution to existing teacher leadership literature as well as important implications for policy and practice. These will be presented in detail in the following chapter in addition to highlighting the study’s limitations and suggestions for future research.

Chapter 7: Conclusion

7.1. Introduction

This final chapter provides a general conclusion for the thesis. It begins by providing a summary of the research findings and highlighting the study's contribution to the existing body of research on teacher leadership. It, then, provides implications for practitioners and policymakers based on the study's findings. Subsequently, it acknowledges limitations of the study and presents suggestions for future research. The chapter ends with my own reflections on the journey of conducting this research.

7.2. Substantive findings of the Study

This qualitative exploratory study examined Algerian middle school EFL teachers' perceptions and reported practices of teacher leadership, supports and hindrances of teacher leadership within the study context as well as the perceived impact of peer collaboration on teachers' professional growth as teacher leaders. To meet these aims, data was collected from 18 teachers using individual semi-structured interviews, written reflections and focus group discussions and was then analysed thematically. Findings that explore each of the four research questions are summarised below.

Research question 1: What perceptions do middle school EFL teachers hold regarding teacher leadership?

Despite teachers' unfamiliarity with the term 'teacher leadership', findings revealed that participant teachers possess some awareness and understanding of what constitutes teacher leadership. Their definitions of the concept and the various examples that they provided were particularly centred on non-positional teacher leadership. Regardless of their positions, teachers in this study perceived teacher leadership as influence rather than a designated position or authority. They described ways in which teacher leaders could exert influence at different levels and on multiple individuals through their practices within their classrooms; practices beyond their classrooms; their participation in decision-making processes as well as the set of traits that teacher leaders demonstrate. For them, teacher leadership practice and teacher leaders' influence stem from the classroom in which it is manifested in implementing innovative instructional practices; establishing and maintaining a suitable learning environment through effective classroom management as well as modelling and instilling ethics and values based on their relationships with their learners. Extending beyond the confines of classrooms, teacher leadership was perceived by participants to involve activities such as collaborating with peers; providing professional support and modelling effective instructional practices; playing a mediating role between teachers and students and the school senior management; and encouraging parental engagement. Participation in decision-making both at the school level and beyond was equally perceived as an essential aspect of teacher leadership. Participant teachers stressed that as through participation in

decision-making processes, teacher leaders could inform the design of more relevant curricula, syllabi and textbooks that would accommodate learners' needs and match their levels. Some teachers defined teacher leadership by referring to certain traits which they believe characterise teacher leaders. These involved traits related to their teaching practices, as well as their relationships with their learners and peers. For those teachers, these traits are what earn teacher leaders recognition and respect from their peers. Findings equally suggest that participant teachers possessed limited awareness of the available positional teacher leadership roles within their work context. That is, despite their awareness of the available positions and the procedures that teachers must undergo to be promoted to these positions, most of them, including some positional teacher leaders, were not fully aware of the additional responsibilities that come with these positions.

Research question 2: What are middle school EFL teachers' reported practices of and experiences with teacher leadership?

Teachers' reported practices of teacher leadership were largely consistent with their perceptions of the concept in their focus on non-positional roles both within and beyond classrooms. While their reported practices within the classroom related particularly to the implementation of innovative teaching practices and differentiated instruction; classroom management and their relationship with their learners, and providing personalised assistance for their learners, practices beyond the classroom revealed their emphasis on empowering themselves and their peers through engaging in professional learning and professionally supporting their peers, and motivating novice teachers and enhancing their self-esteem. It was, however, noted that even teachers who reported leadership practices within the classroom context explained that their influence was not restricted to their learners and the classroom environment, but was rather indirectly extended to their fellow teachers beyond the classroom context. Teachers' reported practices indicate that Algerian middle schools seem to allow for some kind of non-positional teacher leadership practices, to varying degrees. However, practices at a broader school-wide or community scale were missing.

Research question 3: What factors reportedly hinder/ foster their practice of leadership?

Participant teachers focussed more on hindrances to teacher leadership practice than on its supports, which indicates that Algerian middle schools are currently less conducive for successful teacher leadership enactment. In this sense, teachers reported various school-based, system-based as well as socio-cultural barriers to the work of teacher leaders. While structural deficiencies within schools were almost unanimously reported as the main hindrances at the school level, findings related to the school culture particularly in terms of school members support were mixed and inconsistent. In this sense, while most participants stressed that their potential to practise teacher leadership was often constrained by unsupportive and authoritarian school principals, teachers from one school described

their school principal as supportive and encouraging. Similarly, while participants stressed that collaboration and positive relationships between teachers were often the norm, they pointed at some aspects that were likely to hinder collaboration between teachers. This was particularly the case when promoted teachers exerted control over novice teachers, limiting their professional autonomy and potential to practise their agency. Beyond the school context, the system itself, according to most participant teachers, does not promote the idea of teacher leadership and teacher empowerment and involvement in decision-making processes, nor does it provide relevant professional preparation or development programmes that target the leadership potential within teachers. Moreover, and despite teachers' great emphasis on collaboration as an essential aspect of teacher leadership both in the current research and in an extensive body of previous research, certain sociocultural norms and power relations within the Algerian context seemed to hinder collaboration between teachers from the two genders or between teachers, positional teacher leaders and school principals. Likewise, some female teachers in this study reported feeling less empowered by their school principals compared to their male peers. On a positive note, teachers in this study expressed their willingness and desire to engage in more leadership work and to initiate and lead change in pursuit of improved teaching and learning.

Research question 4: How do teachers view collaboration with each other as contributing to their professional development as teacher leaders?

Engaging in informal collaborative practices within teachers' communities was perceived by all teachers in this study as a valuable learning experience that could positively impact their wellbeing and professional growth. However, the sociocultural boundaries and power relations that exist within their schools hindered teachers' collaboration with peers from the opposite gender or with positional teacher leaders and school principals, sometimes leading to feelings of marginalisation and lack of sense of belonging to the school community. As a response, teachers facing these conditions reported establishing professional relationships with other teachers beyond their immediate school contexts particularly through joining virtual communities of EFL teachers and middle school teachers. Overall, collaboration with other teachers within the school context and beyond was reported to have a positive impact on teachers' professional growth as teacher leaders. Such collaborative practices were reported to result in enhanced instructional effectiveness, increased self-confidence and sense of empowerment and enhanced professional skills which the participants believed were crucial for teacher leaders.

7.3. Contribution to Knowledge

This study contributes to the existing knowledge base on teacher leadership in different ways, particularly in terms of the research context, the research methodology, theoretical grounding as well as its findings.

First, the unexplored context within which this study has been conducted represents an important contribution to the existing teacher leadership research. The review of existing literature revealed that teacher leadership research is predominantly Western as most empirical studies have been conducted in the USA, UK, Australia and Canada (Webber et al., 2023). While teacher leadership research recently began to noticeably emerge in other non-western contexts including the Middle East and North Africa region, particularly in the KSA, UAE, Qatar, Egypt and Morocco, no research of this kind has been conducted in the Algerian context, to the best of my knowledge. Thus, being the first research to investigate teacher leadership in the Algerian context, this study contributes to existing teacher leadership research by adding the Algerian perspective, and as such it contributes to enriching and diversifying the existing knowledge base on teacher leadership. This corroborates with emerging calls from prominent figures in the field (Hallinger, 2018; Nguyen, Harris and Ng, 2019; Schott, van Roekel and Tummars, 2020; Webber et al., 2023) to examine teacher leadership across cultures and contexts, accounting for the potential impact that the contextual variables might have on both perceptions and enactment of teacher leadership.

Second and in relation to the research methodology, this research addresses one of the limitations of previous empirical research on teacher leadership as highlighted by three influential review articles. In their seminal work, York-Barr and Duke (2004) noted that most studies that they reviewed were either purely descriptive or relied on non-triangulated data. Similarly, and in more recent reviews, Wenner and Campbell (2017) and Nguyen, Harris and Ng (2019) further stressed that conclusion. This research, thus, employs triangulated data obtained from teachers with different positions, working across five different middle schools, using three different methods to fully address the study's main research questions and meet its aims, thus providing a more detailed and trustworthy account of teacher leadership in the study context. It is important to note, however, that given the interpretivist nature of this study, triangulating teachers' accounts from different data sets specifically aimed to provide a richer and more comprehensive insight into the phenomenon under investigation and not to validate findings as might be the case in studies adopting a positivist paradigm. As suggested by Jick (1979), 'triangulation [of perspectives] may be used not only to examine the same phenomenon from multiple perspectives but also to enrich our understanding by allowing for new or deeper dimensions to emerge' (pp. 603-604). Elaborating further on this, Vogl, Schmidt and Zartler (2019) specifically explain that participants accounts could converge, diverge, or complement one another. This is relevant for this study in which participant teachers' accounts, for instance, converged in terms of their perceptions of collaboration as an essential aspect of teacher leadership practice beyond their classrooms; diverged in terms of their perceptions of and experiences with the school principals' support; and complemented each other when data from the three online focus group

discussions provided more detailed insights into the impact of the sociocultural context on teacher leadership enactment. Thus, within the present research, triangulating perspectives obtained from teachers holding different positions, working in different settings through data obtained using three data sets provided more richness to the research and enabled me as a researcher to provide a more complete image of the phenomenon of teacher leadership within the Algerian context.

Third, the study provides a theoretical contribution to the existing teacher leadership knowledge base. Wenner and Campbell (2017) concluded that the existing body of research on teacher leadership remains partially theoretical, calling for researchers to draw on existing theoretical and conceptual groundings to inform their studies. In a response to these calls, the current study draws on notions and concepts from Communities of Practice, and particularly on Campbell and colleagues' (2019) Communities of Practice for Teacher Leadership Model and Wenger's (1998) modes of belonging to better understand and interpret the emerging findings. These theoretical perspectives proved to provide a solid grounding for understanding teacher leaders' work across multiple communities and their professional learning and growth as teacher leaders within different teachers' communities.

The final contribution of this study relates to its findings, which confirm and expand on the existing knowledge base on teacher leadership from different perspectives. Findings of this study provide evidence that supports early-career teachers' potential to practise teacher leadership as teacher leadership in this study was perceived as influence that is independent from teachers' length of teaching experience. In this sense, findings equally stress the important role that school principals and positional teacher leaders could play in brokering teacher leadership success and particularly in supporting and encouraging novice teachers to engage in leadership work within their schools. Moreover, the study's findings stress the importance of teachers' collaboration within teachers' communities at the level of their schools and beyond as an important means for supporting teachers' professional growth as teacher leaders, particularly in contexts where formal professional development and training programmes for teacher leaders are currently missing, as in the case of Algeria. More importantly, findings of this research provide evidence that supports Boyce and Bowers' (2018) view that teacher leadership must always be thought of as a culturally sensitive concept. Such a view implies that teacher leadership research should carefully consider the broader sociocultural context within which the research is conducted as different contextual variables might result in different conceptualisations and enactment of teacher leadership. According to Webber, Pineda-Baez, Gratacos Wachira and Nickel (2023, p. 11), 'Insufficient consideration of context can result in inappropriate cross-cultural borrowing of educational constructs and lead to the failure of teacher leadership to enhance localized educational practices'. This, similarly, highlights the

importance of developing more culturally sensitive and relevant models that could be effectively applicable to these contexts.

7.4. Research Implications and Recommendations

In light of the findings of the present research, one of the major impediments of teacher leadership enactment in Algeria is the hierarchical structure of the educational system. As explained by Hammad et al. (2023), the authoritative leadership approach in Arab countries, including Algeria, is reflective of collectivist cultures' that value group cohesion and loyalty and consider seniority and rank as critical organisational values, resulting in centralised leadership approaches and decision-making processes. This might imply that such an approach to leadership is deeply rooted within these contexts. Therefore, suggesting an immediate shift from a highly centralised to a fully decentralised approach to leadership within the Algerian educational system might not currently be realistic or feasible. This research, thus, recommends a shift towards a partially decentralised system in which teachers are empowered, encouraged, and provided with more opportunities and margins of freedom to be more involved in leadership and decision-making processes. This is consistent with Gherzouli's (2019, p. 01) recommendation based on her research with Algerian EFL teachers at secondary school level to combine 'top-down government directives with bottom-up teachers-based creativities'. To facilitate and inform such a shift, this study, based on its findings, provides valuable practical recommendations for teachers and positional teacher leaders, school principals and policymakers. It is worth noting that despite the current study's focus on EFL teachers, the research findings seemed to be rather generic and not specifically restricted to the EFL teaching context. Therefore, the recommendations provided in the following sections might well be applicable for teachers of other subjects within Algerian public schools. These recommendations would serve in informing efforts to encourage, facilitate, and cultivate teacher leadership enactment within Algerian public-school contexts.

7.4.1. For Teachers and Positional Teacher Leaders

As findings of this study highlighted teachers' willingness to engage in leadership work as an important enabler of successful teacher leadership enactment, it is important that all teachers recognise their own potential in both initiating and leading positive change within their schools regardless of the length of their teaching experience or their designated position. Teachers could, accordingly, consider the various ways through which they can engage in and support teacher leadership work and change the status quo within their work contexts. This can be achieved, for instance, through constantly working to improve their own instructional practices and making these improvement initiatives visible for their colleagues through professional collaboration, which is likely to lead in turn to overall improved instructional practices as suggested by some of the examples shared by some participant

teachers. Teachers should similarly seize opportunities to enhance their professional learning through joint work with their peers or through attending relevant professional workshops and seminars. Opportunities for collaborative practices with peers are particularly important as they provide teachers with a space to engage in professional discussions, leading to improved instructional practices, increased awareness of different professional matters and enhanced levels of teacher empowerment. Such collaborative work could take place not only physically at the level of individual schools, but also virtually via online platforms that are likely to enable teachers from different school settings to meet and engage in meaningful discussions. Findings of this study indeed demonstrate the usefulness of such online platforms given that some participant teachers perceived them as a space within which they could support other teachers and equally seek their support and could maintain a sense of belonging to the profession overall. Equally important, all participant teachers who took part in the online focus group discussions in the present research not only stressed that they benefited from the perspectives shared by other peers in the focus groups but also expressed their willingness and desire to engage in any future focus group discussions. Such social media and online platforms, if used appropriately, could represent an important forum for evolving virtual CoPs. Beyond this, it is also crucial that positional teacher leaders within the Algerian school context recognise the importance of their role both in initiating and driving change and in empowering novice teachers and providing them with the necessary support as well as appropriate levels of autonomy and opportunities to engage in leadership work.

7.4.2. For School Principals

As this study indicated that Algerian middle schools are currently less conducive for successful teacher leadership enactment, it is recommended that principals seek to ensure availability of the necessary conditions and supports for teacher leaders' work. Moreover, principals could consider ways to embrace a more distributed and shared approach to leadership, relinquishing control and providing teachers with appropriate levels of professional autonomy. It is equally important that school principals recognise the value of teacher leadership and consider it as a support rather than a threat to their work and should thus value rather than suppress teachers' innovative practices, support their change initiatives, and encourage their engagement in more actions of influence and decision-making processes. Participants in this study reported cases of both supportive and unsupportive school principals based on which it is suggested that school principals should ensure that teachers obtain the necessary support and encouragement as well as more margins of professional autonomy and equal opportunities to tap into their leadership potentials regardless of their gender, position, or career stage. Similarly, principals should consider ways to eliminate barriers to effective communication between them and teachers within their schools.

7.4.3. For Educational Policymakers

Considering the findings of this research and given the highly centralised nature of the Algerian educational system, it is argued that it is primarily the system's and policymakers' responsibility to set the tone for change in the status quo as per school leadership overall and teacher leadership in particular. The system, embodied in policymakers at the level of the MoNE and MHESR, should, accordingly, introduce relevant policies that embrace, advocate and actively promote teacher leadership in schools, in terms of both discourse and implementation, and provide the professional support and training required for teachers' growth as teacher leaders.

7.4.3.1. Policy Discourse

Findings of this study stressed Algerian middle school EFL teachers' positive outlook of teacher leadership and their desire to engage in more leadership activities within their work context and as such these findings can serve as a resource, providing policymakers in the Algerian context with the necessary information regarding teachers' perceptions of teacher leadership practice in Algerian middle schools and more importantly the factors that seem to currently hinder effective teacher leadership enactment within the study context. These findings could thus serve as the basis for planning future actions and guiding future school improvement reforms to nurture teacher leadership in Algeria through directing efforts to minimise obstacles facing Algerian public-school teachers.

First and foremost, as findings of this study indicate teachers' willingness and desire to engage in more leadership practices and decision-making processes and their dissatisfaction with how limited their roles are due to restrictive ministerial directives, it is recommended that as an essential part of future educational reforms, the MoNE considers redefining and expanding teachers' role, mainly beyond their classrooms to involve roles that extend beyond their instructional practices in a way that they are perceived as decision-makers and important change agents rather than mere implementers of centralised policies and reforms. In a similar way, teacher leaders' qualities, skills and their roles and practices as highlighted in this study could constitute an important aspect of educational policy in Algeria, representing the core of teachers' professionalism and teachers' standards.

Some non-promoted teachers in this study stressed the importance of providing teachers with monetary rewards for their initiatives to encourage them to engage in more leadership work. Policy makers should, therefore, consider the provision of incentives for non-positional teacher leaders as well as reconsider the current parameters and procedures for the promotion of teachers to positional teacher leadership roles in a way that enhances teachers' willingness to initiate and drive positive change within their schools regardless of their position. In this sense, promotion to positional teacher leadership roles should be more based on teachers' professionalism, initiatives, contributions, and

qualifications, rather than being exclusively based on their seniority in teaching. In this study, effective teacher leadership practice was not necessarily perceived to be related to teachers' length of experience but rather to their willingness to initiate change, to innovate and to exert influence in a way that would eventually lead to improved instructional practices and enhanced student learning. Moreover, non-promoted teachers in this study expressed their desire to engage in teacher leadership work and provided many examples of incidents in which they influenced or wish to influence their learners, peers and to contribute to overall school improvement. It could equally be helpful if the MoNE extends school principals' role to allow them to reward teachers' initiatives at the level of their schools.

Similarly, as most participant teachers stress the importance of collaboration both as an aspect of teacher leadership and as a useful means to grow professionally as teacher leaders, it is crucial that the MoNE invest the necessary efforts to establish and promote a collaborative culture within and beyond schools. This would facilitate cooperation at different levels and would enable teachers to establish professional networks to discuss and exchange views related to their roles within and beyond their classrooms and schools. It would equally be useful if such collaborative work could be more formalised, taking the form of formal professional learning communities, so that teachers from both genders could freely interact and discuss relevant matters. Similarly, the MoNE should consider adapting teachers' overwhelming timetables and ensuring availability of appropriate communal spaces across public schools for teachers to meet and collaborate or to engage in professional development activities both within and beyond their schools.

7.4.3.2. Professional Preparation and Training Programmes

This study highlights some important shortcomings as per teachers' pre-service preparation programmes as well as in-service training that explicitly train, prepare and empower teachers to take on leadership roles. Considering teachers' pre-service preparation, Algerian universities, unfortunately, do not currently provide EFL student teachers with any courses or input related to educational leadership or teacher leadership (as discussed in section 2.4.3), which explains teachers' unfamiliarity with the term teacher leadership itself in this study. Based on these findings as well as the importance of introducing leadership studies in teacher education programmes (Campbell et al., 2018; King et al., 2019; Webber, 2021b), it is recommended that the MHESR ensures that both universities and teacher colleges introduce teacher leadership theory to student teachers, which would help them develop a leadership stance prior to starting their careers to be well prepared and positioned to benefit from the leadership opportunities available to them once they begin their careers. Judd Pucella (2014, p.16) argues that student teachers could greatly benefit from relevant university coursework that is likely to help them 'find their voice' and understand 'the language of leadership'.

Universities and teacher colleges in Algeria could benefit from emerging efforts and initiatives in the field of programmes for teacher leaders' preparation in other countries like Canada, the United States, Scotland, England, and Australia. However, as teacher leadership is considered to be a context-specific phenomenon (Boyce and Bowers, 2018), and in cases where borrowing and fully adopting these programmes would not be feasible, then characteristics of the local context should be taken into consideration for adapting relevant training materials.

As for the in-service professional training programmes, one key finding that emerged from this study is that the current professional training is limited both in scope as it only targets the development of teachers' subject and pedagogical knowledge, and in length as it is only provided for early career and novice teachers. It is thus recommended that more training programmes are designed and implemented in a way that clarifies the roles of positional teacher leaders and at the same time targets the development of teacher leadership capacity beyond these roles to tap into teachers' capacity to initiate and engage in leadership activities. In this sense, these programmes should recognise teachers' potential to practise teacher leadership without a positional role and as such they should focus on building teachers' capacity and empowering them to serve as leaders from their existing positions in their classrooms. It is equally important that this training is considered as a continuous and ongoing process and should thus be provided to all teachers regardless of their career stages. Such training should particularly target the development of specific skills of teacher leadership as well as their self-confidence to engage in leadership activities.

Following Hunzicker's (2017) argument that success of teacher leadership initiatives is largely dependent on the professional development of both teachers and school principals and the current study's findings that non-supportive and authoritarian school principals represent a major hindrance to teacher leadership enactment in the study context, it is recommended that school principals too receive the necessary training that would enable them to adopt leadership approaches that are more supportive for effective teacher leadership enactment. As suggested by Mangin and Stoelinga (2010), educating both school leaders and prospective teachers in the merit and value of teacher leadership as an instructional support is key for enhancing receptivity to the idea of teachers as instructional leaders.

It is important to highlight at this point that the implications provided in sections 7.4.1, 7.4.2 and 7.4.3 are not to be taken separately but are rather interrelated in the sense that there should be a collective effort from teachers, positional teacher leaders, school principals and senior management teams as well as policymakers at the level of the MoNE and MHESR to stress the importance and value of teacher leadership practices for overall school improvement and educational reforms and to actively promote teacher leadership enactment within Algerian schools.

7.5. Limitations of the Study

Although the aims of this research have been achieved overall, this study, like all research, has some limitations that need to be acknowledged. First, recruiting participants for this study was both challenging and time-consuming. During the initial stage of recruiting participants and although I tried to ensure them of confidentiality and anonymity, some teachers were reluctant to take part and one teacher decided to withdraw her participation particularly because she was not comfortable with being recorded. Those teachers were not familiar with the ethical procedures of research in the UK, which required me to keep reassuring them anonymity and confidentiality to eventually gain their trust. Likewise, although I initially approached participants with the aim of obtaining their consent to contribute to the three data sets, most of them expressed their willingness and interest in taking part in this research but were concerned that due to their overwhelming workloads and personal commitments, they might not participate in all data sets. Therefore, as I was aware that insisting on their participation in the three data sets is likely to lead to their reluctance to take part in this research, I had to be more flexible and to provide them with the freedom to contribute to the data sets based on their convenience. Additionally, focus group discussions in this study were intended to be conducted face-to-face with six teachers per group. However, as it was not possible to agree on a time and space that suited all participant teachers and due to Covid-19 restrictions, I took the decision to shift to online focus groups with four teachers per group to facilitate managing the online group discussion.

A second limitation relates to the research sample. Although the present study provided a detailed picture of teacher leadership within the Algerian middle school context, it might be limited as it only focused on the perspectives of Algerian EFL teachers at middle school level. As discussed in section 1.3 of the introductory chapter, the decision to focus on the views of EFL teachers was specifically influenced by practical considerations that primarily relate to the plan under which the present research is funded by the Algerian government. Involving perspectives of teachers of other subjects, teaching at other school levels might have provided more detailed insights. Involving school principals could have also deepened some specific aspects that emerged from this research, particularly with reference to their role in supporting or hindering teacher leadership enactment.

Moreover, although the study obtained rich data through the three qualitative methods employed, it focusses particularly on teachers' self-reported practices of teacher leadership and did not observe their actual ones. Therefore, it was not possible to determine whether teachers' self-reported practices matched their actual practices. Although this might be considered as a limitation of this study, the decision to address teachers' reported practices of teacher leadership is arguably consistent with the interpretive nature of the current research and its focus on participant teachers' perceptions and understanding of their own leadership practices as discussed in section 4.5.2.

Finally, the research design and the small size of the research sample limit statistical generalisation of the findings to the wider population. While this study yielded detailed descriptions on teacher leadership in the Algerian middle school context and is thus rich in terms of depth of findings, it could be limited in terms of breadth. However, the thick descriptions provided throughout the study would enable readers and researchers to make judgements about the likely transferability of the findings to other situations, cases or contexts (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). The fact that EFL teachers across the five schools often shared similar views as regards the perceived hindrances of teacher leadership, and given the highly centralised nature of the Algerian educational system, might further enhance transferability of the present research findings to other public schools in Algeria.

7.6. Suggestions for Future Research

The limitations addressed above as well as some of the study's main findings could provide valuable insights for informing and framing future research, mainly in terms of research design and focus. Overall, while forms of teacher leadership clearly exist in Algeria, though often in a restricted form as this study suggests, until recently they have not been the focus or the source of a great deal of research activity. This study, thus, highlights the need for some substantial research into school leadership in general and teacher leadership in particular and is hoped to serve as impetus for future research that would both advance the knowledge base in these fields and inform emerging policy and practice in Algeria. Such research could consider aspects including but not restricted to the foci outlined below.

First, more quantitative large-scale studies could be conducted that would broaden the knowledge base of teacher leadership in Algeria and in other contexts and allow for more generalisability of the findings. The association of results obtained from both qualitative research, as in this study, and further quantitative studies would likely provide an even clearer and deeper image of teacher leadership that is then more likely to be generalised.

Second, as this study focused exclusively on EFL teachers' perspectives, it is suggested that future research explores teacher leadership from the perspectives of teachers from other disciplines as well as other school levels. It is worth noting at this point, however, that despite the study's focus on perspectives of middle school EFL teachers, the responses provided by participant teachers seemed to be rather generic and not subject-specific. That is, teachers' comments and responses in this study did not highlight aspects of teacher leadership that seemed to be specific to EFL teachers. In responding to the questions in the three data sets, none of the teachers in this study used the expression 'EFL teacher leaders', for instance, which might imply that in their responses, they referred to teacher leadership as a general rather than a subject-specific concept. Within the study context, research that goes beyond the scope of middle school EFL teachers is particularly important for providing teachers

of other subjects and in other school levels with an opportunity to openly express their views on the one hand and for familiarising them with the term ‘teacher leadership’ and enhancing teachers’ awareness of it across different subject areas and school levels on the other hand.

Third, apart from teachers, examining perceptions and attitudes of other members at the level of the educational system is equally important. Views of school principals, school inspectors, curriculum designers as well as professional development specialists would provide valuable insights and further clarify the broader picture as to any potential barriers for successful teacher leadership enactment that need to be addressed. Particularly, as this study stressed the importance of school principals’ support, trust and encouragement as an important enabler of teacher leadership and reported on both supportive and unsupportive school principals, it is recommended that further case studies are conducted with the focus on supportive school principals and their leadership styles and behaviours. Findings obtained from such research could provide educational policy makers with valuable insights as to the preparation of school principals to embrace and support teacher leadership within their schools.

Finally, as findings of the current study highlighted the impact of the sociocultural norms particularly from the perspective of Algerian female teachers, future research within the Algerian context and in other contexts globally is also recommended to further explore teacher leadership experiences of both male and female teachers. More broadly, more research focusing on the interplay between the broader social, cultural, political, religious, and economic contexts and teacher leadership perceptions and enactment as well as issues of equity is required. Likewise, more comparative cross-cultural studies need to be conducted to highlight any potential aspects of teacher leadership that may not be similar across contexts or may not necessarily be consistent with the Western scholarship that currently dominates the field.

7.7. Ending the PhD Journey: Personal Reflection and Future Aspirations

The process of conducting this research has significantly shaped my identity as a researcher as I became more aware of important concepts related to research and more capable to take informed decisions when conducting research. When I first began this journey, for instance, understanding concepts such as epistemology, ontology and positionality and their relevance to research was in itself a challenging task. Now, however, I not only understand these concepts, but I can effectively articulate them in my research. Moreover, being a novice researcher conducting research abroad during the challenging Covid-19 lockdown period, I was able to overcome multiple unanticipated challenges and feelings of frustration, fear, and homesickness as I learnt how to cope with the ‘new normal’. Throughout this journey, I have always been eager to establish connections with other PhD researchers and seize opportunities to discuss my work and engage in broader academic discussions with fellow

PhD students, my supervisors, and other academics. These discussions played an essential role in polishing my researcher identity. As for my future research endeavour and because I am fully aware of the scarcity of research in the fields of educational leadership and teacher leadership in Algeria, I do consider this study as a steppingstone along the path to more upcoming research that delves deeper into the field of teacher leadership and educational leadership, which remain -to date- unexplored in the Algerian context -to the best of my knowledge. Findings of my research equally motivate me to consider future action research aimed at enhancing teacher leadership professional learning and enactment within Algerian middle schools.

I do not consider drafting and submitting this thesis as necessarily the end of this four-years journey, but rather as a beginning of another journey as this research has greatly shaped my identity as a prospective practitioner. It has provided me with valuable insights as to the current situation of teacher leadership within Algerian schools and as such it provided me as a future university lecturer in the field of TEFL with a solid background to advocate for extending teachers' roles and empowering teachers within the Algerian context. This research journey that was at its early stages inspired by my passion to examine issues related to teacher empowerment and engagement in decision-making processes resulted in a strong desire to advocate for teachers' potential as leaders and to promote teacher leadership within a context where it seems to be notably restricted. For this, I am keen to put the knowledge gained from this research into practice, and to collaborate with academic members both within and beyond the TEFL field, at the level of my home university and teacher colleges to introduce teacher leadership studies to university students and prospective teachers.

Appendices

Appendix A: Structure of the Algerian Educational System

Appendix B: Semi-Structured Interview Schedule

General introductory questions:

Could you tell me about your career as a middle school EFL teacher?

How many years have you been a teacher?

What responsibilities or roles do you have in your school?

Main Interview Questions

1. How would you define teacher leadership?
2. What types of teacher leadership roles and practices are available in your context?
3. How are teachers who do not possess formal leadership positions involved in leadership in your school?
4. How do you think teachers can lead inside the classroom/ outside the classroom? Illustrate with examples.
5. How would you define a teacher leader?
6. What personal characteristics should teacher leaders have?
7. What professional skills enable teacher leaders to fulfil their leadership responsibilities?
8. In your opinion, what is the impact of teacher leadership?
9. What conditions, you believe, support teacher leadership practice within your school?
10. What conditions limit teacher leadership practice in your school?
11. Is there anything you wish to add to the information you had already provided?

Appendix C: Instruction for Teachers' Written Reflections

Could you please write a reflective essay (no more than 400 words) about your experience(s) with or practice(s) of teacher leadership. Recall, for instance, situations in which you participated in decision making or initiated change either within or outside the classroom.

Appendix D: Focus Group Guide

1. How do you usually solve issues related to your profession and daily work?
2. Why does collaboration with other EFL teachers usually take place?
3. Do you consider collaboration as a learning experience? Can you explain or illustrate with examples?
4. Do you think collaboration with colleagues has contributed to your professional development as a teacher leader overall? If it does, then in what way(s)?
5. Do you think participation in your school community increases your confidence and sense of empowerment?

Appendix E: Sample Interview Transcript

Participant: Rokia

A teacher, 1 year experience

[...]

So, to begin with, could you please tell me about your career as an EFL teacher, as middle school EFL teacher, when did you start teaching, etc.

So, I am a higher College of Teachers graduate. I graduated in 2020, with a five-year bachelor's degree. And I was supposed to be teaching at the level of high school, secondary school, but because there were no job vacancies, they found some positions for us at the level of middle school, which was something that I really liked, because I wanted to start from the very scratch. If you know what I mean. I wanted to be able to teach the ABCs before being able to teach any other advanced level. I think that that actually gave me some solid ground to advance my career and to teach other levels. I started in September 2021. So, this was basically my first teaching year at the level of middle school. But I did have other experiences when it comes to teaching, so if you want me to tell you about that.

Yeah, please do.

All right, cool. So, I do have like a two-year experience, being an online instructor. I taught with a school that is based in the Middle East, but like it was remote specifically in Oman. So, I also taught young learners, but like online, remotely, and that was a challenge on its own. I also taught at some private schools, in Algiers and here in Setif, where I'm from. So basically, I was hustling through teaching since like or for four years and a half.

That's very impressive.

Thank you!

Now, as you know, for my research, I'm investigating the concept of teacher leadership in the Algerian middle school context. So, for my first question, I would like to know, how would you define the concept of teacher leadership?

All right. I see. So, I think before being able to define what is teacher leadership, I think I will need some time to fixate on what leadership presents for me generally. So, can I do that?

Yeah, sure!

So, I think that leadership is being able to have some sort of a vision, to be to be part of a vision, to be part of a higher objective while having the expertise to drive that sort of change. So to make my words more simple, now, if I wanted to say, what is the difference between a manager and a leader, I'm going to say that the manager although successful and responsible, and has problem solving skills, and has to drive some sort of change and success, which is also part of leadership, but the manager

only sees that sort of change as some sort of personal gain. They lack the sort of, you know, objective, vision, being part of something that is larger than their own selves. This is what a manager is. They are only fixated on their personal gain or the company's personal gain, but there is no larger objective to that, there is no sort of vision. You are willing to go there and to drive some sort of unprecedented change, and this is what a leader can do. Leaders could be managers, but they are fixated on much more than just, you know, the immediate gain of that sort of company, or that sort of school or that sort of class.

Yeah.

Yeah, I think this is what leadership is for me to be, again, part of something that is larger than your own self. Now, as for teacher, a teacher leader, I think that a teacher leader is somebody who is willing to give their learners more than just the sort of knowledge that they have to receive in the classroom. Their job, it isn't just, you know, to give them information. Their job is to lead, to guide, to help, to be a friend, to be sometimes a psychologist, to be sometimes a parent, to be sometimes the caring friend, and so on. Their goal is not really to just meet the immediate objective of the lessons. Their goal is to instil values in their learners, to instil some sort of life-lasting appreciation for knowledge, for transcendence, and for curiosity, for knowledge. So, I think this is what a teacher leader is. I don't know if it makes sense to you.

Yeah, it absolutely does!

Like a teacher leader, is someone who just would, you know, guide you, like their focus is to make you love that thing. Now, to draw on my own experience, one of my goals, to be honest, was to enter the classroom, and try to make my learners lives less miserable. This is like this is my goal. I wanted to make their lives less miserable. And so, I think this was like, my higher objective, my higher goal or something like that. And this time that allowed me to show some sort of probably leadership traits inside the classroom. I don't know, I have to be honest. But yeah, this is what I actually strive to do.

I noted that your responses are mainly centred on teachers' role in relation to their learners and classrooms. Do you then think that teachers can only practise leadership within the boundaries of their classrooms?

Absolutely not. I mean not necessarily. I do not think that teacher leadership should be restricted to the classroom context.

Could you please elaborate on this? Can you provide more examples?

Alright, the most important thing is that a teacher leader has to really master his subject matter. I think, this is obvious. You cannot really transcend to any other role if the teacher does not really have a good, at least, a somewhat good command of the subject. So, expertise is the first requirement of being a leader in the classroom. This ensures that you'd provide your learners with quality teaching. The

second, the second element, the second requirement, I think, is empathy, and a good understanding of psychology because what I noticed is that, you know, some of the newbie teachers, and I, myself, am guilty of this, sometimes I put my head at the same level of my students. Especially when, you know, like, you know, some like comment or circle in the classroom, and that kinda makes me frustrated, why aren't they, you know, focusing, like, what is wrong with them, they are careless, but these are really wrong. If the student is doing that sort of thing, there must be something else. There must be another way to deal with that sort of problem, other than just, you know, like, being frustrated with them, and, and taking it personally. So, like, a good command on developmental psychology would also be good. You really need to understand your learners' developmental stages in a practical way. I really do not mean you know, go open the psychology books and try to read. No! Just being able to understand that they are teenagers, and you can expect everything and beating them and humiliating them will never work. This is not the right way. Another third requirement might be responsibility. I think this is like umm this is obvious, but like knowing that they need your guidance, you are the model of the class. Although sometimes we have to listen to what they have to say, we have to follow their guidelines, but we are still the commander of the class.

Alright!

Outside the classroom, I think it can be mainly through collaboration, to communicate and to collaborate with other teachers to stand up for your rights, which is something that does not really exist in our systems specifically if you happen to be a woman. So yeah. I think as a teacher leader, anywhere where you can make your voice heard, anywhere that you as a teacher could drive some sort of positive change, this is like some sort of role for you to, you know, be a leader. Leadership is about driving change. It's the core of it. So, whenever you are given that space to take part in decision-making to drive positive change, this is a role for you to be a teacher leader. So, by communicating and collaborating with your colleagues and others and also being part of decision making and positive change in your school.

When you talked about teacher leaders you referred to certain traits that you believe they should possess, do you think that these traits support them in their role?

Sure, and there are more characteristics that make the teacher a teacher leader. I think good communication, motivation, motivating the students, trying to make them see the world in a different way. For example, like When I went to the place where I currently work, I noticed that most of the learners are not really aware that a world exists beyond their village. Most of the girls were like, this is it, I'm studying, maybe I'm going to quit halfway, and I'm just getting married because why would I really bother doing anything else? The guys, when you ask them, what is your dream? They

all want to be soldiers. So, one of the things that I really thought I needed to do before focusing on anything else was to try to erase this view from their minds. I always try to broaden their visions and to motivate them to think beyond their immediate restrictive environment. So, I tried to really communicate that often with them. And so I think that one of the characteristics of a leader is you know, to try to broaden their horizons, the learners' horizons outside of the curriculum, and outside of everything they are taking at school.

That's really interesting. What about the professional skills that you think enable teacher leaders to fulfil their leadership responsibilities and roles?

Yeah, professional skills. Yeah, other than a good command of teaching. I think that the most important professional role is a willingness to keep being a learner. Really, like the willingness to keep updating, you know, oneself about current research data on what is happening in the EFL field, what are the new insights that like how can you, you know, really deal with young learners as opposed to adults and what are the strategies that you know, you should follow and stuff. I think updating oneself is like one of the most important professional roles because a teacher once told me that if we stopped learning, we are just going to be umm the top student of the class, and that's it. You are going to be just like your learner's, but like, you know, like a very good one [shifts to Arabic] a diligent learner between quotation marks, but like if we kept learning and updating oneself, I think that is going to give teacher leaders the ability to reach terrains in their classrooms and profession that otherwise they cannot reach.

Interesting! Now, in terms of impact, how do you think teacher leadership can contribute or can have an influence on the schools or school members?

I think, again, leadership is about collaboration. So, one leader is not really going to do much. If you are willing to change, and if you are willing to give enough reasons, to your colleagues about why we need to change a certain situation, I think teachers could have been a power that everybody fears. But unfortunately, not everyone is willing to drive that sort of change. Especially for women! Women have that sort of acceptance to these behaviours of headmasters. Specifically, if they were married. Some female teachers would not engage in an argument with their male school principals because they fear what others would think of them. Also, some teachers whether women or men often accept everything set by the system with no questions or you know I mean no concerns, ironically speaking. Normally, old, experienced teachers are the ones who should drive change, but like, I think experience conditioned them to just, you know, remain obedient to the system and not drive any sort of change.

And do you think that teacher leadership or being a teacher leader can have an influence on the teacher leader himself or herself, either positively or negatively?

Of course, being able to drive something, having the motivation to drive change is a risk, and, if it was not done wisely enough, if it was just some sort of a rebellion, like I have to do this, but like, there aren't really higher, like higher objectives. Like as leaders, a leader in the educational system should really respect and love and is willing to risk everything for the sake of these learners, for the sake of the quality education, but I think we still have hope on getting it. If we really did the right steps of change. But then things are really bad at the same time that change needs a network of change makers, a lot of them. People who are willing to risk their careers for this. People who are willing to listen, and to learn in order to risk their careers, you don't just want to go there and act like you are the master of change. No, that is not going to work. I think building a network of connection is also an important thing when it comes to umm driving that sort of, you know, that sort of change. Can you repeat the question? Because I kind of lost myself.

What I wanted to know is how do you think the practice of teacher leadership could influence teacher leaders?

Yeah. Okay. So, to wrap up, it should be done wisely because it could have a lot of negative umm a lot of negative influences. One of them being despair. You know, like, I think the problem is that we try once, and then when it doesn't work, we just, you know, step back and, okay, didn't work, the system sucks and stuff. But no, like, leadership needs consistency. And we kind of like that sort of mentality, to be honest.

And how do you think such teacher leadership practice could have an impact on other teachers?

All right, like I think I do have an example. Well, when I first started out, I was like, I'm just going to do my job, and I'm not really willing to stay here in this country and whatever. I just need to be a good teacher and that's all about it, but then there was another teacher who really influenced me positively. She was just filling in a vacancy. She wasn't like [shifts to Arabic] a permanent teacher.

Yeah, she wasn't permanent.

Yeah, she wasn't. She wasn't like a permanent teacher. But then I figured out that she really is motivated to do a lot of things. She's motivated to speak up. She's motivated to drive that sort of change. I had the idea of having a class outside of the classroom, like having one of my lessons outside of the classroom, but I was like, okay, when it's sun and when the weather is warm enough and when it's nice and stuff. I had that idea back in November, but then this teacher came. She did not receive support to take her students outside, but then there was a small hall inside the school that was really deserted and needed to be cleaned. So, this is a very small trait of leadership. She went there, despite the fact that she was not granted access to other areas. She brought a wheelbarrow, and she had two students with her, she cleaned it and it became a perfect area for having classes outside

the classroom. So, this is like a very small trait of leadership. So, that was like really something that affected me in a positive way, given the fact that I really did not have enough motivation to do what she did. She really isn't being paid. This is the most baffling thing. She's not being paid on whatever she's doing, but she's doing it despite all of that. That's why teacher leaders really should be part of a goal that transcends their immediate gains, see? Like, she's not being paid. She's literally going there and doing her job for free, but she was like, 'Okay, I'm going to do it in the best way possible', and I think this marked me, and it will mark me for the rest of my teaching career.

[...]

Appendix F: Teachers' Written Reflection Sample

Participant: Maria A teacher, 1 year experience

Some of the most challenging time for teachers just like for all the world is when Covid-19 was spread very much in the world. With this spread, teachers faced many challenges specially that it was possible that schools may close and we will have to teach online. So, we had to prepared for that. But you know how limited it is access to technology in our country. So, I decided to step up mainly because I have a diploma in computer science. Also my sister is a lecturer at university and she knows very well how to use Moodle as a platform to teach.

Thus I relied on my knowledge of ICT and on information that my sister gave me about how to use Moodle and then I prepared some Powerpoint slides explaining how to use Moodle and also Zoom. I presented the slide 2 times for my colleagues and also shared them with them. Some of my colleagues also downloaded the software on their personal computer and bring them to the school so that I show them more practically how to

Use them. So this was the one time when I really felt that I contributed with something for my colleagues and for my school and our students especially at this challenging time. I used the knowledge that I have to help them all.

Appendix G: Focus Group Transcript Sample

Focus Group 1

[...]

Researcher: One of the aims of my research is to investigate the role of informal collaboration between teachers in enhancing their leadership capacities or in enabling them to develop professionally as teacher leaders. So, to begin with, I would like to know, how do you usually solve issues related to your daily work as teachers?

Rokia: I think for me the first thing that I usually do when I encounter a problem in the classroom is to share it and discuss it with other teachers in the teachers' room. It doesn't really matter if the teacher is an English teacher, or you know, like a teacher of Arabic language. The most important thing for me is that sort of discussion that we have because I know that these teachers have dealt with similar situations or with even more intense situations, like the one I faced, and I'm sure that I'm going to find, you know, guidance from them. For example, there was this umm this incident when there was this pupil in my classroom, who had competitive like, serious competitive issues with other learners in the classroom. And because it is my first year, I literally did not know how to deal with that sort of, you know, competitive urge that she had, because that competition was like, wasn't just like the good one, that always motivated her to do her best, but it was it was that sort of competition that was about 'do not answer that question, I am going to answer it and if you answer that question, you are in trouble, you are getting yourself into some trouble'. So like, the problem was beyond, you know, encouragement, was beyond motivating her, was beyond explaining that you all have to participate, and you all should participate equally, and that your friends have the right to raise their voice, if I might call that. So, I mentioned this recurring problem, because it was recurring, it was like I faced that problem whenever I was in that in that in that classroom. So, I raised this issue with other teachers. And, like, a lot of them gave me different approaches on how to deal with this issue. And I think this was like one of the best techniques on how to deal with problems in the classroom. So, yeah, I think this is it.

Keltoum: Well, for my case, I think it depends on the issue or the problem itself. For example, if it has to do with the English language issue, I have to contact English language teachers. When it comes to for example, classroom management, I have to contact maybe the other experienced teachers even from other modules I mean. I can contact the headmaster, why not? It depends on the problem. For the English language, per se, for my case, I used to contact my mentor. She is more experienced than me. She's an English teacher. I contact also my, my colleagues in my school. When I don't find the solutions, for example, what I do for my case, I make a post on Facebook groups of teachers, and I have a feedback, I get feedback from many teachers and we discuss the solutions that they give, you know. This is for my experience.

Researcher: Interesting! What about you, Serine?

Serine: Okay, so in my case, I don't feel like I faced that much problems, but whenever I face a problem, I contact other teachers and consult them and they give me feedback and so on. So, the main solution for me is asking others. I also try to do my best to solve the things by my own, to search and read maybe but I feel discussing it with other teachers is more useful.

Researcher: Do you agree with what the other teachers said, Maria or do you have something else to add to what they have already mentioned?

Maria: Yes, actually, I agree with all what the ladies have said. I mean most of the time when we are sitting in the teachers' room, you find that most of the teachers are sharing the same problems and looking for the same solution so often.

Researcher: Great! Thank you all for sharing! Now, could you please describe your relationship with other teachers in your school, Keltoum? Let's start with you.

Keltoum: In my school?

Researcher: Yeah, your relationship with your fellow teachers.

Keltoum: It's good. Generally it's good.

Researcher: What about you, Serine?

Serine: Okay, the case of mine is I have a good relationship with them. It is a positive relationship as we respect each other. Maybe we don't always interact so much and everything but like I said before when someone of us needs help, the others will help and assist as they can. So, it's generally good.

Rokia: For me, this was my first year. And at the very beginning, everybody, I mean mainly the other teachers who were pretty experienced, they offer their guidance, they met my questions with ease and they guided me whenever I asked about certain things. And we also used to collaborate for instance. So like we used to have like these conversations. So, I had this one teacher mainly whom I really had a lot of collaboration with me even sometimes we would share lesson plans. We would also like, just try to build the exams together, knowing my learner's levels and knowing her learner's levels. I think it was such a relief. I am also going to say like something. I don't know, it might be funny. So, on the day of my, what do we say? How do we say [shifts to Arabic]? (The day when she was supposed to be tenured), they all came to me, and they were like, 'Hey, do not even bother preparing the coffee and stuff because all of that is on us'. The sweets and the coffee, and everything. It was like it was really good and friendly especially with female teachers. Also, I often got compliments from some of them that made me feel that I'm on top of everything and super confident. These compliments really motivate you to do even more. But like I understand that, that some other schools can be very different and even some teachers in my school may not be the same as those maybe. So, yeah!

Maria: Yeah, especially, sorry to interrupt you!

Rokia: Yeah, yeah, it's okay.

Maria: Thank you. I mean, yes, in some schools, the relationship between the teachers is very nice and I happy I work in such a safe and like positive environment.

Researcher: So, when it comes to the relationship between teachers, I can see that one of let's say the variables that you insisted on is the gender. Is it the case that gender plays a role in your professional relationships with peers?

Rokia: Definitely!

Keltoum: Okay, before moving to this point, please, they remind me of something. I mean in my case, I also try to always keep in contact and work with other teachers who do not teach in my school. I am a member in some Facebook groups of middle school teachers. So, when sometimes I want to discuss something or I cannot find a solution or yeah a solution to some problem after I discuss it with my colleagues, I share this in the Facebook groups and discuss with other teachers. So, we discuss issues about teaching and classroom management and we even sometimes share new ideas and strategies with each other.

Researcher: Interesting!

Rokia: Imene, I just I think I want to, I want to add something about, you know, gender, the gender issue and whether it really affects the general atmosphere of the relationship between the teachers. Now, let's not forget that we live in a pretty conservative society and no matter how strong the bonds we want to create with the other gender, we always know that there are certain limits. I think the cultural and societal limits put us in this situation, especially for, you know, married female teachers. So, I'm not trying to generalize but the societal factors definitely play a role. Of course, collaboration between the two genders and collaboration between all humans is a good thing, but I think the limits that the cultural and the societal limits hinder that. For me, probably for a married woman, that could kind of, I don't know, be a problem or something like that.

Maria: I totally agree with that. I believe they are important limits. I mean living in a conservative society, no matter what good relationship you want to establish with your co-workers, there are some limits.

Serine: I totally agree with you in that!

Rokia: So, I think it does have some importance here.

Keltoum: Yeah, I was, I was coming back to Rokia's idea about male and female teachers, I want to say it is not just for EFL teachers. In my school, I noticed this with all teachers of any of the other modules. I saw such a thing that married women, I mean, married teachers, they didn't collaborate too much with male teachers.

Researcher: Now, could you please tell me why does collaboration with other teachers usually take place? For what reasons do you usually collaborate with your fellow teachers?

Maria: I didn't get the question. Could anyone please explain it?

Keltoum: Why we do collaboration, for what reason?

Researcher: Yeah, why do you usually collaborate with your fellow teachers?

Rokia: Okay. I think I think it's mainly because, due to shared knowledge and more importantly shared goals. They have something they might know something that I don't know, I might know something that they don't know, we sort of experience the same thing less or more, and we all want to do our best to enhance our pupils' learning. So, this is why we tend to, you know, like, ask each other and try to learn from each other. Only if we put, you know, our ego aside and that sort of, I do not need anyone, I'm just only going to rely on myself sort of, you know, mentality and attitude.

Researcher: Yeah. Do you agree with this Serine?

Serine: Yes, I do. I mean we are all there doing our best and try to give the pupils the best teaching to develop their understanding and like, I don't know, to improve their scores and so on. So, we collaborate to do this. And like we said before sometimes when we face problems, we need to work together to solve them. Like, I don't know, disruptive behaviours, or I don't know something about the material, maybe anything like that, whenever I face a problem is the main reason why I contact others and consult them.

Maria: Yeah, I do agree with this. Because I think collaboration takes place whenever a teacher raise questions or interrogatives. I mean, when you have this sense of curiosity to know the unknown or to find solutions to problems about student learning, here comes the collaboration, like here you initiate the collaboration.

Researcher: Yeah, yeah, I got you. And what about you, Keltoum?

Keltoum: Actually, I have to think about this. But the first idea that comes to my mind is yes, I agree with the girls. And I feel that, for instance, what came to my mind is collaborating while doing exams. In my case, I was not the one who decides which text I should give my students or which exam I should give my students. It was the more let's not say privileged because they are privileged, I feel, the more experienced teachers have a say in that. So, I'm not really free to put any exam. And sometimes I feel that yes, when we collaborate together and put the same exam to the different classes that we teach, that we teach differently, it gives credibility to you as a teacher.

Researcher: Yeah, and I could notice in your response Maria that you mentioned something which I believe is important in relation to the freedom. Do you think that you have freedom to express your viewpoints openly within your school? In relation to exams, in relation to students'

discipline, in relation to various matters related to your teaching and to your students and classrooms?

Serine: Can I start?

Researcher: Yeah, Serine, please go ahead.

Serine: So, in my case, the thing umm I have to talk with the head of the school. I once..I mean I first I thought I am free to decide, as a teacher because I am I'm more knowledgeable than the headmaster. So, I had another colleague was in maternity leave. So, I was requested by the headteacher to teach her pupils in one class and they were already late in their programme..like in their lessons. Then, I was forced to finish half of the book that I was using in 24 hours only. And it was like, impossible to do that. So, I told him that I can't, it is not possible! He said like 'I don't care, you have to finish no matter what'. So, I thought I could decide what was appropriate for those learners, but I ended up like, just like rushing everything up, and the students did not get anything. I mean like my problem was with the headmaster. It was not with other teachers, because I could not do what I knew was best for this class. He did not take my opinion into consideration...he did not even listen to me or let me explain my idea and I just had to do as he said. This is my problem. I didn't face it with other teachers, but with the headmaster of the school.

Researcher: Yeah. Keltoum or Rokia, do you have anything to raise?

Keltoum: Would you please repeat the question? To answer right to the point, please?

Researcher: The question was based on Maria's response when she mentioned the idea of freedom. And the question was whether or not you have freedom to express your viewpoints openly within your school or to do whatever you think is best for your students. Do you have freedom to do that?

Keltoum: Yeah, I got you. Yes, I do have freedom because of many reasons. For my case, I'm six years' experience teacher. For my whole six years, I umm from my first year, I used to plan the test and the exam for each term for what...why? Sometimes, sometimes the old teachers I'm not talking at that at their back, but sometimes they are less responsible, they said just do it, just do whatever you want. And the other times they do lack the digital literacy. Before, they used to umm to write tests, you know. For the English language, it needs pictures it needs umm it needs, you know, when preparing tests and exams, it's not it's not like umm it's not like the other modules you need to make some your touch on the test. Yeah. So for the technological knowledge they do not possess so they give me the responsibility to prepare a test or an exam.

Researcher: That's really interesting. Yeah.

Rokia: Can I add something?

Researcher: Yes, Rokia, go ahead, please.

Rokia: Based on Keltoum's response, I remember something I felt as a novice teacher, I remember this incident when we had that sort of mid-term meeting. So, in one of our meetings, we needed to talk about some particular students. I mean we were all discussing the scores and you know the behaviours of some learners and so on and I felt a little bit out of my comfort zone when speaking about a certain pupil because some of the more experienced teachers held negative views about him, while I had very positive comments because he is very good in English. When I attempted to say something that's positive about him, the more experienced teachers gave me looks of judgement. So, I did not really feel free to give my opinion and I think that was mainly because I am a novice teacher.

Keltoum: At your first year, you are novice, so they underestimate your opinion. That's what you want to say?

Rokia: Yes, yes, exactly. Yeah. Thank you.
[...]

Appendix H: Manual Coding
a/ Example of manual coding:

Participant: Ibtissem A principal teacher, 22 years experience

To be honest, I do not remember a specific incident where I practiced teacher leadership. But, there is one thing that I am very known of and the other teachers always envy me about. It is my relationship with my pupils during all the period of my career as a middle school EFL teacher which is now 22 years. When I started teaching in 2000, the most important thing that was crucial for me is that I develop a good relationship with my pupils that it is based on mutual respect and based on my understanding of the situations, conditions that my pupils go through. That good relation with my learners made them respect me very much and love my subject and give me a good reputation in my school, with other teachers, with administration, with parents and all. Also, because of how I treat my learners they also would not do any disruptive behaviour. Even very rarely when disruptive behaviours happen, I never treated my pupils in a harsh way or insult them in front of their colleagues. However, I talk to them at the end of the session in a nice manner and explained why the behaviour that they have practiced is not good and is not appropriate and respectful for me and how their parents maybe feel disappointed if they know it. So, my relationship with them was always more like a sister or a mother than just a sever and strict teacher. I deal with them in the way that I always hoped that my teachers deal with me when I was a pupil. I always wanted that my pupils love me and respect me

recognised the relationship with Ls
 establishing & maintaining a positive relationship with Ls

positive outcomes

Ibtissem Ref
 * Establishing & maintaining a positive relationship with Ls
 * Recognition & good reputation among peers, admin, & Ls' parents.
 * Respect from Ls / Ls more disciplined.
 * "She's not a 'sue'"

instead of just be afraid of me. This good relationship benefited me as well. It
make my daily work more enjoyable and I always felt at ease. So, I do not really *unsure if it's TL!*
know if this is part of teacher leadership or it is just me satisfied and proud of my
teaching style and also the way in which I deal with my learners. But what I know
without any doubt is that this is for me my greatest accomplishment through my
whole teaching career. My colleagues and the teachers who I supervise always
say that I am a good example and model for them because of this. This is
something that they try to learn and adopt from me. *impact/influence on peers too!*

b/ From extracts to codes and themes

Extracts	Codes	Themes/ Subthemes	Clustered under RQ
<p>In the classroom, he can decide how he arranges his students' seating. He can also decide about his lessons; how he will present them, through technology, using realia and so on. Outside the classroom, he can make decisions concerning the time of the tests and he decides with his colleagues on the content of the exams and tests [Maria, T, Int]</p> <p>So, in here, decision-making is not limited to one teacher who is, for instance, the principal teacher... We sit together, we negotiate, we share our ideas, then we choose the best idea that supports our pupils' levels [Sarah, T, Int]</p> <p>We know the pupils better than the inspectors, the headmasters and even the ministry of education. So, we have to share our ideas and viewpoints and participate in decisions [Melina, PT, Int]</p>	<p>Decision-making inside and outside the CR/ mainly decisions related to teaching and learning</p> <p>Collective decision-making among teachers within the school</p> <p>Importance of teachers' participation in decision-making within and beyond the school</p>	<p>Decision-making as an aspect of teacher leadership</p>	<p>RQ1</p>
<p>They become more motivated and interactive and increased their understanding of the lesson [Abdou, T, Ref]</p> <p>I saw a different student, almost the opposite. She does not participate a lot. I noticed how she was often inattentive, wandering. Her scores decreased [Halima, PT, Ref]</p> <p>My colleagues and the teachers who I supervise always say that I am a good example and model for them because of this. This is something</p>	<p>Impact of the innovative practice on Ls</p> <p>Care for the learner</p> <p>Recognised by peers for her relationship with Ls</p>	<p>Practices within the classroom</p>	<p>RQ2</p>

<p>that they try to learn and adopt from me</p>			
<p>I think the problem is that headteachers here believe that schools have only one leader, that is them. So, they will not allow teachers to practise leadership [Nour, T, Int]</p> <p>I was happy because the headmaster thank me for my effort [Melina, PT, Ref]</p> <p>It was my first year of teaching. So, he didn't trust me because he thought that I will not be good enough. I'm not experienced. So, I was not enough [Amira, T, FG2]</p>	<p>Authoritarian principals</p> <p>Recognition by the principal for her work</p> <p>Lack of trust from the principal/ underestimating novice teachers</p>	<p>(Un)supportive principals</p>	<p>RQ3</p>

<p>Through collaboration, I learned that as a teacher, I should not just take anything or accept everything as it is. I notice how some other teachers analyse the situation and evaluate the different options which we have. This is critical thinking. So, I also developed this critical thinking in my work. I adopted this approach from collaborating and interacting with other teachers [Halima, PT, FG3]</p> <p>...every time when I attend a class with my colleagues and I observe the way they deliver the lesson, they use technology and innovative methods, I reflect more on my teaching and decide how to adopt similar methods to develop my teaching too [Nawel, PT, FG2]</p> <p>...when you work with others in a regular way, you will surely enhance your communication. You become better in explaining your opinions and also a better listener to others [Sarah, T, FG2]</p>	<p>Developing critical thinking skills</p> <p>Developing reflective skills</p> <p>Improved communication and collaboration skills</p>	<p>Enhanced Skills Required for Teacher Leaders</p>	<p>RQ4</p>
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Appendix I: Formal Letter to Facilitate Access to schools

School of Education & Social Sciences

24th September 2021

To Whom it may Concern

This is to confirm that **Imene MESSALEM** is a PhD student within the School of Education & Social Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland. She enrolled in November 2019 and is currently at the data collection stage of her research project.

Ceci est pour confirmer que **Imene MESSALEM** est doctorante au sein de la School of Education & Social Sciences de l'Université de l'Ouest de l'Écosse. Elle s'est inscrite en novembre 2019 et est actuellement au stade de la collecte de données de son projet de recherche.

[Redacted]
Professor Donald Gillies
Dean of the School of Education & Social Sciences
University of the West of Scotland
Paisley PA1 2BE
Scotland, UK.

SCHOOL OF EDUCATION
& SOCIAL SCIENCES

Appendix J: Participants' Information Sheet

School of Education & Social Sciences
Paisley Campus

Participant Information Sheet

Study Title: Exploring Teacher Leadership in the Algerian Context: Middle School English as a Foreign Language (EFL) Teachers' Perspectives

Researcher: Imene MESSALEM

Introduction

This research is conducted by Imene MESSALEM, a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland, School of Education and Social Sciences.

Why have you been chosen?

This research focuses on Algerian middle school EFL teachers. Therefore, you are approached because you are an EFL teacher at middle school level. You may or may not have an official leadership position.

What is the purpose of this research?

This research aims to investigate teacher leadership within Algerian middle schools, with a particular focus on the case of EFL teachers. Specifically, it entails an exploration of middle school EFL teachers' perceptions of and experiences with teacher leadership as well as the factors that they believe may hinder or foster their professional development as teacher leaders. Furthermore, it aims to examine teachers' perceptions on the role of collaboration within their school community in developing their leadership practice.

Do you have to take part?

Your participation in this research is completely voluntary, and even if you initially accept to be involved and then decide to withdraw at any stage of the field work, you can do so with no penalty and without having to provide any justification or explanation. In such a case, the information you already provided (if any) will be removed.

What will happen to you if you take part?

If you agree to take part in this study, a consent form will be sent to you so that you sign it as a proof of agreement to participate. Then, you will be contacted to schedule an interview session at a time that you find suitable. Interviews will take 30-45 minutes. Focus group sessions will also be scheduled in the same way. Focus groups will involve six participants who will choose a time that is suitable for all of them. Group interviews will also last from 30 to 45 minutes. By the end of each interview session, each participant will be requested to write a reflective essay of no more than 400 words regarding their experience(s) with teacher leadership and those who accept to do this would be asked to return it to me later. Throughout the entire research process, participants' identities will be kept anonymous. Interviews and focus group discussions will be recorded in order to not lose any important responses and to facilitate data analysis.

Are there any potential risks to you in taking part?

There will be no foreseeable risks to you in taking part in this research project, except taking some of your time to be interviewed and to write a reflective essay. To ensure that your participation in this research would not interrupt your working hours, you will choose suitable time for interview and focus group sessions.

Will my participation be confidential?

Confidentiality of participants and their responses is of paramount importance within this research. You can remain assured that your identities will not be revealed and no identifying information will be disclosed throughout the entire research process. To assure anonymity, you will be asked to choose a pseudonym that will be used instead of your real name. As for the data you provide, it will be only

accessed by myself and exclusively used for the current research purpose. All data will be saved in my personal computer that requires a password to be accessed.

Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

If you have any further questions or comments concerning this research, please do not hesitate to contact me via email:

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Supervisor details:

Professor Donald Gillies

Dean of the School of Education & Social Sciences

University of the West of Scotland,

Paisley PA1 2BE

Scotland, UK.

[REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Appendix K: Informed Consent Form

School of Education & Social Sciences
Paisley Campus

Consent Form

Title of the research project: Exploring Teacher Leadership in the Algerian Context: Middle School English as a Foreign Language (EFL) Teachers' Perspectives

Name of the researcher: Imene MESSALEM

- 1- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any queries to my satisfaction.
- 2- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.
- 3- I understand that I am going to:
 - a- Participate in an interview and a focus group discussion (approx. 30-45 minutes each).
 - b- Write a reflective essay (no more than 400 words).
 - c- Be audio-recorded during the interview and focus group sessions (approx. 60 minutes).
- 4- I understand that any information recorded in the investigation will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.
- 5- I consent to being a participant in the project

Name of the participant: _____

Date: _____ **Signature:** _____

Name of the Researcher: _____

Date: _____

Signature:

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